

Preconceptions, Perceptions and
Preparation for Practice:
A Longitudinal Study Exploring Self-Efficacy
in Undergraduate Student Nurses Caring
for Persons with Dementia

Hazel Margaret McWhinnie

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Personal details withheld.

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Abbreviations

AAPPQ	Alcohol and Alcohol Problems Perceptions Questionnaire
DDCPQ	Dementia and Dementia Care Perceptions Questionnaire
DoH	Department of Health
MAPP	Maudsley Alcohol Pilot Project
MWD	Motivation to Work with Dementia
NES	NHS Education for Scotland
NICE	National Institute for Care Excellence
NMC	Nursing and Midwifery Council
QAA	Quality Assurance Agency
RA	Role Adequacy
RCN	Royal College of Nursing
RL	Role Legitimacy
RS	Role Support
SCQF	Scottish Credit and Qualifications Framework
SIGN	Scottish Intercollegiate Guidelines Network
SWD	Satisfaction in Working with Dementia
TSSE	Task Specific Self Esteem
UKCC	United Kingdom Central Council

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Abstract

Title of the research

Preconceptions, Perceptions and Preparation for Practice: A Longitudinal Study Exploring Self Efficacy in Undergraduate Student Nurses Caring for Persons with Dementia.

Background

In terms of epidemiological impact, dementia has been cited as one of the most significant modern challenges to international public health (Scottish Government, 2013, Alzheimer's Disease International, 2014, World Health Organisation, 2015, Scottish Government, 2017). Demographic ageing and reduced disease related mortality through healthcare and medical innovation, strategic health promotion and public health improvements have contributed to a globally ageing population, living longer with multiple comorbidities (World Health Organisation, 2012). One of such co-morbidities directly linked to older adulthood is dementia.

There is a plethora of research examining dementia care from nursing and social care perspectives but a dearth of research examining ability to deliver dementia care exclusively from the student nurse perspective (Suhonen, Gustafsson, Katajiso et al, 2010, Clissett, Porock, Harwood et al, 2013). There is a need to explore student nurses perceptions of delivering dementia care, their role in care giving and importantly, their ability to deliver such care, as they are soon to be accountable, autonomous practitioners (Koh, 2012, Spector, Orrell and Schepers et al, 2012, Koskinen, Salminen, Stolt et al, 2015).

Study Aims

- To explore undergraduate student nurse perceptions of dementia care and their role in care delivery.
- To examine the influence of theory, skills training and clinical experience on approach to dementia care delivery amongst undergraduate student nurses.
- To appraise how dementia training policy directives for pre-registration nurse education is reflected in undergraduate student nurse's knowledge, skills and readiness for nursing practice.

- To evaluate the psychometric properties of a self-efficacy tool designed to measure attitudes, experiences and perceptions of dementia care in undergraduate student nurses.

Design

The research study is a prospective, longitudinal, mixed methods case study exploring self-efficacy in undergraduate student nurses caring for people with dementia. The 'case' under study is the Sept 2014 cohort of undergraduate student nurses at the University of the West of Scotland.

Methods

The psychometric properties of an adapted version of the Alcohol and Alcohol Problems Perception Questionnaire (AAPPQ) devised by Cartwright (1980), was adapted, validated and used to measure attitudes, experiences and perceptions of dementia care in undergraduate student nurses. The Dementia and Dementia Care Perceptions Questionnaire (DDCPQ) was used to facilitate understanding of undergraduate student nurses' self-perceptions of dementia care and their role in care delivery, examining and analysing the influence of theory, skills training and clinical experience on their approach to dementia care delivery and the changes in these perceptions over time. Method triangulation was used in concurrent qualitative data collection and analysis. Utilising the DDCPQ's original key themes of Role Adequacy, Role Legitimacy and Role Support, focus groups were carried out to further explore the student nurses' perceptions.

Results and Unique Contribution of Study

- Conclusions drawn and new insight gained from measurement of the students 'role adequacy', 'role legitimacy' and the need for 'role support' in dementia care and the changes in these over the duration of an undergraduate nursing programme.
- Training, experience and knowledge gain has a positive effect on role adequacy and role legitimacy.

- Although attitude scores reduced over the duration of the undergraduate nursing programme, students overall remained positive towards dementia and demonstrated commitment to deliver the best nursing care possible.
- Reduced scores of Role Adequacy and Role Legitimacy over the duration of the undergraduate nursing programme were reflective of novice student's unrealistic expectations of the reality of complex care needs in dementia care.
- Adaptation and psychometric testing of the Alcohol and Alcohol Perceptions Questionnaire to measure Dementia and Dementia Care Perceptions.
- Validation of a new tool; "The Dementia and Dementia Care Perceptions Questionnaire" – (DDCPQ).
- In depth understanding of 'the case'; student nurses' self-perceptions of their role in dementia care delivery using a self-efficacy approach, underpinned by social learning theory, in a longitudinal, mixed methods context.

Chapter One: Setting the Scene: Thesis Structure

This thesis is presented in a series of chapters which detail the processes undertaken to explore self-efficacy in undergraduate student nurses caring for persons with dementia using a longitudinal, mixed methods, case study approach;

Chapter One: Thesis Structure

This section provides a chapter by chapter overview of the thesis, to help assist the reader to navigate their way through the research study.

Chapter Two: Introduction, Background and Rationale for Study

The research study is introduced and dementia defined, examining the presentation and common manifestations of the main subtypes. The impact of dementia epidemiologically is explored, considering risk stratification and impact on morbidity, mortality and quality of life indicators. National and international healthcare policy in relation to dementia and the complexities of dementia care is critiqued and directly related to the significance, justification and unique knowledge contribution of this research study.

Chapter Three: Literature Review – Students Perceptions of Dementia Care and an Exploration of Dementia Education in the Undergraduate Pre-Registration Nursing Curriculum

The systematic literature review is an in-depth exploration of student nurses' perceptions of dementia care and their ability to deliver such care, considering how student nurses learn in University and how they implement that learning in clinical practice. This requires analysis of undergraduate pre-registration nursing education in the United Kingdom, considering both the professional and educational standards of requirement. This chapter also critiques the learning theories applicable to the nursing profession and justifies social learning theory as the

underpinning theoretical framework for this study. Furthermore, the concept of self-efficacy and its use for undergraduate pre-registration nursing students is validated.

Chapter Four: Methodology

The ontological and epistemological perspective of the research study is justified and rationale provided for the use of a concurrent triangulation mixed methods approach. Case study as a research design is critiqued and the longitudinal nature of the study appraised. Ethical considerations are detailed and justification provided for the sampling strategy and data collection timings.

Chapter Five: Research Methods

Data collection methods for both the quantitative and qualitative aspects of the research study are examined. The use of a survey questionnaire as a quantitative data collection tool is critiqued and the origins of the Dementia and Dementia Care Perceptions Questionnaire (DDCPQ), with its central themes of Role Adequacy, Role Legitimacy and Role Support explored and related to self-efficacy. The validity and reliability assessments of the quantitative tool are also detailed. The use of concurrent qualitative data collection through the use of focus groups is critiqued, with justification for use of nominal group technique and use of the 'Ketso Kit' for assistance in data collection. Furthermore, the consideration of reflexivity, rigour and trustworthiness within qualitative data collection is explained.

Chapter Six: Quantitative Results

The quantitative data collected is presented. Data collection timings, response rates and descriptive statistics are detailed to provide an overview of the population under study. Thereafter, statistical testing measures (ANOVA) are detailed and inferential statistics are used to consider the students' changes over time according to the themes of the questionnaire (Role Adequacy, Role Legitimacy and Role Support).

Chapter Seven: Qualitative Results

The qualitative data collected is presented. Data collection timings, response rates and group demographics are detailed to provide an overview of the population under study from a qualitative perspective. Changes to group dynamics, researcher observations and ability of participants to use nominal group technique and the Ketso kit are critiqued and well as the rankings from the focus groups and the changes tracked over time in relation to the key study themes of Therapeutic Commitment, Role Security and Role Support. Conceptual analysis of the findings is detailed.

Chapter Eight: Triangulation of Quantitative and Qualitative Results

This penultimate chapter triangulates the quantitative and qualitative results. There is critique of student's perceptions of their role and the changes in these over time. The quantitative scores for Therapeutic Commitment, Role Security, Role Support and Overall Attitude are presented, with context and meaning provided to these scores by triangulating the findings with the concurrent qualitative narrative from the focus groups.

Chapter Nine: Discussion, Recommendations and Overall Conclusion

The final chapter provides an iterative discussion on the justification for the study and the insight gained. Study findings are aggregated and the resultant implications for nursing education and dementia policy and practice critiqued. Achievement of the aims is acknowledged, study limitations are recognised and recommendations for both nursing practice and future research are suggested. Finally, the thesis is concluded. The originality of the research study is asserted and the study's contributions to both nursing practice and nurse education are confirmed.

Chapter Two: Background

It is essential that nursing students have a critical understanding of the epidemiology, aetiology and pathophysiology of the most prevalent acute and enduring long-term health conditions, nationally and internationally (McKinney and Page, 2009, Levitt-Jones, Hoffman, Dempsey et al 2010, Logan and Angel, 2011). Furthermore, it is vital that nursing students can conceptualise the care management of these conditions from a person-centred perspective and within a variety of healthcare environments (Coyne and Needham, 2012, Murphy, Rosser, Bevan et al, 2012, Morrell and Ridgeway, 2014).

In nursing education, curricular design should always takes cognisance of current health policy to ensure that nurses are fully prepared for clinical practice. Despite cancer and cardiovascular disease retaining the highest mortality rates overall in Scotland (National Records of Scotland, 2013) and amongst the highest figures in the developed world (World Health Organisation, 2015), it is widely recognised that many older adults are living longer with multiple healthcare needs and thus require complex care from nurses (World Health Organisation, 2009, Ellis, Whitehead, Robinson et al 2011, Roland and Paddison, 2013). National and international healthcare policy reflects these complexities and dementia care in particular has been a leading focus of Scottish Governmental healthcare policy over recent years as well as an identified international public health priority (Scottish Government, 2013, World Health Organisation, 2015).

Whilst pre-registration nursing curricula has content of professional requirement, common to all Nursing and Midwifery approved programmes, certainly in Scotland, dementia care is included in both professional and political context. The Scottish Government publication; Setting The Direction For Nursing And Midwifery Education: Delivery Plan 2015-16 (Scottish Government, 2015), aspired that the key dementia national policy document, 'The Promoting Excellence Framework' (Scottish Government, 2011b) was inherent throughout all pre-registration nursing curricular development and design in Scotland, with all nursing graduates achieving at least the 'dementia skilled practice level' of the framework. Dementia care should be intrinsic in all undergraduate nursing programmes, focusing on important components such as communication and person-centred care and thus providing the student with an opportunity

to consider the impact of dementia on patients, their family carers and the wider health and social care environment (Scottish Government, 2015).

The University of the West of Scotland (UWS), where this research study took place, has a recognised reputation for excellence in dementia education and dementia research through the Alzheimer Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice who are a partner of the University and work collaboratively with the University, people with dementia and their carers to enhance dementia care through education, policy and practice. The Alzheimer Scotland Centre contributes to and supports applied research for policy and practice in dementia, as well as providing dementia education. The centre has won numerous awards including the prestigious Scottish Dementia Awards in 2016 and 2019. Indeed, with such partners, it is no surprise that, dementia and dementia care is inherent throughout all 3 years of the undergraduate pre-registration nursing programme at UWS on 4 campuses (Paisley, Ayr, Lanarkshire and Dumfries). Student nurses learn about dementia care from year one of their undergraduate programme. The foundations of health, nursing, life and social science modules all incorporate indicative dementia content and students also practice skills and strategies for dementia care in simulated care environments within the University. As the students move into the second and third years of their programme, the theoretical and practical content revisits dementia (in a spiral approach) and considers knowledge acquisition, problem solving and skill level with increasing complexity as knowledge, understanding and intuitive practice develops. This provides the student with the opportunity to consider in depth, the impact of dementia to patients, their family carers and the wider health and social care environment.

The Promoting Excellence Framework (Scottish Government, 2011) provided the basis for curricular development and sought to ensure that all graduates achieve at least the 'dementia skilled practice level' of the framework as per policy direction (Scottish Government, 2011b). Such spiralling of content is exemplified in (Appendix 1) and it can also be seen that UWS further aspired to enable students to achieve the 'dementia enhanced level' of the Promoting Excellence Framework (Scottish Government, 2011) at the point of registration. Nonetheless, whilst UWS is in the fortunate position to work in partnership with the Alzheimer Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice, the centre is based within one campus location (Lanarkshire). Lanarkshire campus was not sampled as part of this study (this will be further explained later) and at the time of carrying out this research study, Alzheimer Scotland colleagues had no

direct input at all into pre-registration nursing education. Thus, it can be noted that the Alzheimers Scotland/UWS partnership offered no expert input or influence to the pre-registration students taking part in this study and would not have been impactful on the student nurses perceptions or experiences.

Indeed, when considering student nurse perspectives, it is essential that learning needs are being met to enable pre-registration nursing students to be ready to deliver safe, effective dementia care. A comprehensive, systematic literature review has identified that there is a need to explore student nurses' perceptions of dementia and their role in dementia care, as well as factors that influence their ability to deliver such care and their 'readiness' for contemporary nursing practice (Koh, 2012, Spector et al, 2012, Koskinen et al, 2015). This exploratory approach will be the focus of this research study and specific research aims will be explicitly stated, once the background and justification for the study are considered.

This chapter will define dementia, examining the presentation and common manifestations of the main subtypes. The impact of dementia epidemiologically will be explored, considering risk stratification and impact on morbidity, mortality and quality of life indicators. National and international healthcare policy in relation to dementia and the complexities of dementia care will be critiqued and directly related to the significance, justification and unique knowledge contribution of this research study.

2.0: Dementia: Presentation of Disease and Risk

In terms of epidemiological impact, dementia has been cited as one of the most significant modern challenges to international public health (Scottish Government, 2013, Alzheimer's Disease International, 2014, World Health Organisation, 2015). Demographic ageing and reduced disease related mortality through healthcare and medical innovation, strategic health promotion and public health improvements have contributed to a globally ageing population, living longer with multiple comorbidities (World Health Organisation, 2012).

One of such co-morbidities directly linked to older adulthood is dementia. Dementia is a chronic incurable neurological condition (Scottish Government, 2010a) characterised by a progressive decline in cognitive function and physical deterioration affecting daily life (NHS Education Scotland, 2012, Department of Health, 2013a). Dementia is not a part of normal ageing but is normality for many who are both directly and indirectly affected. Dementia is a collective term for a group of degenerative brain disorders that commonly affect memory, cognition and reasoning. Consequently, dementia can also cause neuropsychiatric problems (such as agitation, aggression and hallucinations) that can make perceptual and behavioural aspects of the disease extremely difficult to manage (Rockwood, Zeng, Leibman et al, 2012, Selbaek, Engedal and Bergh, 2013). Dementia has a profound effect not only on the person living with it but also on families, carers and the wider society (Scottish Government, 2010a, Department of Health, 2013a). Whilst the collective term 'dementia' is often used interchangeably with Alzheimer's Disease, it is important to acknowledge the heterogeneity of the common dementia subtypes as this can effect presentation, diagnosis, disease progression and thus potential specific patient care needs.

Alzheimer's Disease is the most prevalent form of dementia, characteristically recognised by Ballard, Gauthier, Corbett et al (2011) as the presence of amyloid plaques and neurofibrillary tangles that cause neurogenic dysfunction and eventually brain cell death. Such neurogenic dysfunction and progressive atrophy of brain cells cause the memory impairment and cognitive reasoning problems associated with Alzheimer's Disease. However, if diagnosed at an early stage, treatment with cholinesterase inhibitors have proven to provide some alleviation of symptoms and slow symptomatic disease progression (Mangialasche, Soloman, Winblad et al, 2012, Selbeck et al, 2013). Nonetheless, as acknowledged by Norton, Matthews and Barnes et al (2014), although the disease remains incurable, effectually treating Alzheimer's Disease could actually increase incidence and morbidity rates with a resultant negative effect on disease related mortality rates (in the short term).

Vascular dementia is the second most prevalent dementia subtype and similar to Alzheimer's Disease, can be characterised with cognitive decline and memory impairment. Indeed, as it shares many risk factors (including advancing age) with Alzheimer's Disease, it is recognised by Jiwa, Garrard and Hainsworth (2010), that both often co-exist making exacting differential diagnosis troublesome. This view is shared by Korczyn, Vakhapova and Grinberg (2012) who note

that whilst occasionally an underlying vascular incident (such as stroke with resultant clinical manifestations) can make vascular dementia easier to diagnose, more often, lack of exclusive epidemiological data on vascular dementia makes it difficult to distinguish it from other dementias. It is suggested that certainly in the older adult, multiple heterogeneous pathology of dementia is common, despite symptoms often being homogeneous in nature (Korczyn et al 2012, James, Bennett, Boyle et al 2012).

Another dementia of overlapping pathology is Dementia with Lewy Bodies. Dementia with Lewy Bodies has clinical features of both Parkinson's Disease and Parkinson's Disease Dementia and thus as acknowledged by Goldman, Williams-Gray and Barker et al (2014), differentiation between the diseases can be problematic. Parkinson's Disease is a progressive neurological condition of relatively unknown cause that presents with motor symptoms (tremor, bradykinesia and rigidity) as well as non-motor symptoms such as depression, anxiety, hallucinations and sleep disturbances (all of which can be present in dementia) (Cook, McNamee, McFetridge et al, 2010). However, in Dementia with Lewy Bodies, whilst dementia type cognitive impairment as well as hallucinations are early symptoms of the disease, these are often quickly accompanied by Parkinsonian motor type symptoms such as impaired visuospatial acuity and kinetic mobility problems. Thus, it is often difficult to distinguish and diagnose and indeed both can quickly affect quality of life and the ability to live independently (Galvin, Duda, Kaufer et al, 2010, Morra and Donovick, 2013). Due to these worsening cognitive and motor symptoms and the resultant care implications, whilst being progressive and incurable like Alzheimer's Disease, Dementia with Lewy Bodies often has a poorer prognosis with more aggressive disease progression than other dementias (Morra and Donovick, 2013, Goldman et al, 2014).

Finally, frontotemporal dementia (also known as Picks Disease) affects the frontal and temporal lobes of the brain. Neural atrophy in the frontotemporal regions mean that language and behavioural symptoms are amongst the most common initial signs and unlike Alzheimer's Disease, according to Piguet, Hornberger, Mioshi et al (2011), memory can initially remain preserved. Epidemiologically, frontotemporal dementia is a rarer form of dementia, however, statistics suggest that it can account for up to 50% of dementia presentations in those under 65 years of age (Cardarelli, Kertesz and Knebl, 2010). Genetic associations with Motor Neurone

Disease have also been established but as per other dementias there is a notion of heterogeneity in terms of potential for mixed pathological diagnosis (Piguet et al, 2011).

It must also be acknowledged that there are also other conditions that can cause neurological damage and thus dementia type symptoms such as impaired cognition and memory loss (Alzheimer Europe, 2013). These conditions are usually directly related to an underlying pathological disease or condition. For example, Aids Dementia Complex (dementia in advanced AIDS), Creutzfeldt-Jakob Disease (causes a very aggressive dementia causing brain cell death), Huntington's Disease (a genetic condition causing brain nerve damage and resultant behavioural, psychiatric and mobility problems) and Korsakoff's Syndrome (caused by thiamine deficiency, most commonly in chronic alcoholism). Like the more common forms of dementias, exacting diagnosis is often challenging and prognosis remains poor. Although treatment can slow progression, the resultant outcome remains terminal, thus, in terms of primary health promotion for public health, there is a need to consider whether some types of dementia can be prevented by risk factor modification.

Non modifiable risk factors such as increasing age and familial history are well documented risk factors for dementia (Scottish Government, 2010a, Alzheimer's Disease International, 2012). However, as recognised by Scriven (2010), addressing modifiable risk factors through primary health promotion can be a key factor in reducing the likelihood of disease development. Indeed, such primary health promotion has already been successfully used when considering modifiable risk factors for other public health priorities such as cardiovascular health (World Health Organisation 2014, World Health Organisation, 2015). However, in terms of dementia, the evidence base on risk factor stratification (likelihood of diagnosis) is fairly limited and certainly, there is no singular factor that can reduce dementia risk (Scottish Government, 2010a). Whilst there is evidence that overall health measures (such as avoiding smoking, eating healthily, exercising, maintaining a healthy weight and remaining cognitively stimulated) can help reduce overall risk (Barnes and Yaffe, 2011, Mangialasche et al, 2012), the complexities of conducting research trials for so many variables are both ethically and practically challenging (Alzheimer's Disease International, 2012). Nonetheless, it is acknowledged that any risk factor modification that reduces the risk of hypertension and atherosclerosis will somewhat reduce the overall likelihood of developing vascular dementia as hypertension in itself is a recognised significant risk factor for the development of vascular dementia (Sharp, Aarsland, Sonnesyn et al, 2010).

Nonetheless, despite the risk of the dementia epidemic globally, international health Millennium goals as set by the World Health Organisation (World Health Organisation, 2015) remain focused on assisting developing countries to meet basic healthcare needs. Global mortality indicators remain consistent in demonstrating the main causes of death worldwide as ischaemic heart disease, stroke, chronic lung disease and lower respiratory tract infections (World Health Organisation, 2014), with common chronic diseases such as diabetes impacting significantly on both mortality and morbidity rates globally. However, the potential burden of dementia is still significant. Collectively, dementia in heterogeneous form as one disease pathology, whether existing independently or co-existing with another heterogeneous dementia pathology in an older adult, is a challenge to global health. Risk factor stratification and health promotional intervention need to be considered on an international scale to reduce the overall epidemiological disease burden.

2.1: Epidemiology and the Burden of Dementia

Statistically, one of the first comprehensive reports on the projected global prevalence of dementia was The World Alzheimer Report (Alzheimer's Disease International, 2009). Systematic review on an international scale examined studies on dementia (n=154), providing evidence to allow for predicted numbers of people living with dementia from present day to the year 2050. The estimation of people living with the condition were n=35 million (2010), n=66 million (2030) and n=115 million (2050) (Alzheimer's Disease International, 2009). These escalating figures are similar to predictions from the World Health Organisation (2012), estimating over seven million people being diagnosed with dementia annually and an overall prediction of the total population of people living with dementia more than trebling in the next three decades. However, The Global Impact of Dementia 2013-2050 report (Alzheimer's Disease international, 2013) suggests that these figures are an underestimation and further projects dementia statistics for those living with dementia are n=44 million (2013), n=76 million (2030) and n=135 million (2050). This is an expected increase from previous epidemiological projections of 15% and 17% in 2030 and 2050 respectively.

Parallel to international statistics, United Kingdom statistics for demographic ageing and dementia are also increasing. Alzheimer's Society (2014a) estimates 850,000 people are living with dementia in the United Kingdom. Population wise, this is equivalent to 1.3% of the total population and 7.1% of those over 65 years of age. Current epidemiological projections based on demographic ageing, suggest that these figures will significantly increase; n=1 million (2025) and n=2 million (2050) (Alzheimer's Society, 2014b).

Nationally, whilst the population of Scotland is projected to increase by 8% over the next two decades, the population of those over 65 years is predicted to rise by 49% as life expectancy reaches its highest level to date; n=76.1 years (males) and n=80.6 years (females) (Scottish Public Health Network, 2013). There are currently 90,000 people with dementia in Scotland (Alzheimer's Scotland, 2015b) and in direct correspondence with the ageing society, the projected numbers of dementia diagnoses will increase accordingly.

Nonetheless, as dementia is a progressive condition, causing ongoing mental and physical decline, measuring diagnostic or even mortality rates will not always show the true impact of living with dementia. Indeed, the use of metrics to show the impact of disease in comparison to living free from disease can be a useful way to measure the overall disease burden (World Health Organisation, 2013). Years of Life Lost (YLL) and Years Living in Disability (YLD) can help quantify such burden and when both are combined to measure Disability Adjusted Life Years (DALYs), they can give an indicator of the overall loss of years of living in good health. When considering dementia, the latest statistics measuring the years 2000 to 2012 show an increase overall of the impact of dementia, however, the quantifiable data for dementia is still much less significant than that of the leading causes of disability, such as ischaemic heart disease, stroke, HIV and respiratory conditions (World Health Organisation, 2014). Nevertheless, the potential impact of the disabling nature of the dementia epidemic is not yet fully apparent. Most recent global figures show that Alzheimer's Disease and other dementias accounted for 8329 YLL in 2012 (0.4% of total YLL and an increase from 0.2% in 2000). The figures for YLD were 9878 (1.3% of total YLD and an increase of 1.1% from 2000). Overall DALYs were 18,207 (0.7% of total DALYs and an increase from 11,045 from 2000) (World Health Organisation, 2014).

Whilst these figures are only beginning to show the increasing prevalence of dementia and its life changing effects, there is no doubt that the overall impact of dementia will undoubtedly be a significant challenge to public health.

2.2: Dementia as a Public Health Priority

The World Health Organisation recognised dementia as an international public health priority in 2012 and urged all countries to consider the impact of dementia, not only in terms of increased mortality but in terms of life changing comorbidity and overall impact on society (World Health Organisation, 2012). Progressive demographics mean that lower income countries will see the greatest increasing prevalence of dementia (Alzheimer's Disease International, 2012) however, as acknowledged by George-Carey, Adeloje and Chan et al (2012), dementia is often overlooked as a health priority in favour of focusing on communicable diseases, publicly perceived to be the most significant immediate health risk. Indeed, cognitive decline is often dismissed as an inevitable aspect of advancing age with dementia under diagnosed (World Health Organisation, 2012, George-Carey et al, 2012).

The United Kingdom has identified dementia as a significant societal burden and recognises the increasing implications of a demographically ageing population. Such recognition has resulted in a plethora of policy documents aiming to provide guidance on dementia care, including Living Well with Dementia: A National Dementia Strategy (Department of Health, 2009) and Quality Outcomes for People with Dementia: Building on the Work of the National Dementia Strategy (Department of Health, 2010). Following the development of the UK National Dementia Strategy, the Prime Minister launched a nationwide challenge to tackle dementia (Department of Health, 2012). The UK government as part of the Global Action against Dementia campaign and in collaboration with G8 countries (Department of Health, 2013b), released a declaration of commitment to the dementia challenge. The G8 health ministers pledged to improve quality of life for those living with dementia and to commit to internationally collaborative research to aid diagnosis, treatment and dignified care. Since such declaration, there has been a significant drive for improvement in dementia care, research and awareness in the UK (Department of Health, 2013c, Department of Health, 2013d). However, as recognised by the updated Prime Ministers Challenge on Dementia 2020 (Department of Health, 2015) there are still many objectives to be

met to aid understanding of dementia and to provide equality of opportunity to receive an excellent standard of post diagnostic support and care.

Indeed, post diagnostic support after a prompt diagnosis is one of the key outcome measures of Scotland's national dementia targets. Dementia has been a recognised national priority for the Scottish Government since 2007 (Scottish Government, 2013) and is also a designated HEAT (Health improvement, Efficiency, Access and Treatment) target for NHS Scotland. Scotland was one of the first nations to develop a National Dementia Strategy (Scottish Government, 2010a) and the strategy supported the implementation of national standards for dementia care and a framework to guide health and social care workers to deliver such care. The Standards of Care for Dementia in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2011a) demand that a person with dementia has a right to a timely diagnosis, to access support and education about dementia and to receive dignified care, respectful of individual rights. To help deliver such care, the Promoting Excellence Framework (Scottish Government, 2011b) defines the knowledge and skills that all health and social care workers should have to provide care to the person with dementia. This framework aspires that all health and social care workers regardless of designation will be informed about dementia with a baseline standard set of skills and knowledge to enable them to deliver safe and effective care. However, despite such aspirational policy and public health prioritising, there is still a lack of awareness and understanding of dementia, not only from the general population, but also from healthcare professionals (Scottish Government, 2010a, Spector et al, 2012). Thus, there remains a required commitment to increase awareness of dementia, invest in dementia research and education and ultimately improve dementia care and support (Scottish Government, 2013, Scottish Government, 2017).

2.3: Caring for a Person with Dementia

Since the implementation of the first National Dementia Strategy (Scottish Government, 2010a) diagnostic targets have been achieved with an estimated 64% of individuals with dementia diagnosed in Scotland, the highest diagnostic target achievement rates in the United Kingdom (Scottish Government, 2013, ISD Scotland, 2014). Potential screening opportunities for recognition of cognitive decline in the older adult are now routine in UK healthcare settings with early identification and treatment of dementia a continuing aspiration of health policy (Scottish

Government, 2013, Scottish Government, 2017). However, despite national achievement of the set diagnostic target, it is recognised that increased social perception of dementia (public awareness) may mean that many people do not seek support for fear of diagnosis either as a single condition, or more likely, as an additional comorbidity (Fox, Lafortune, Boustani et al, 2013, LeCouteur, Doust, Creasey et al, 2013). In older adults with multiple comorbidities, even for trained healthcare professionals, the complexities of identifying cognitive decline and thus specifically diagnosing dementia (especially in the early stages) are problematic (Piguet et al, 2011). Such troublesome differentiation of disease has meant that the notion of dementia as a terminal condition that will ultimately need palliative care is not always considered at the point of diagnosis (Alzheimer's Scotland, 2015a). Indeed, Marie Curie (2015) acknowledges that dementia is often overlooked as a cause of death and statistics show very few referrals for palliative or hospice care for people with end stage dementia in comparison to other terminal conditions. Such lack of insight into the palliative care needs of advanced dementia has implications for funding, opportunity of access to post diagnostic support and ultimately, opportunities for advance planning and choice for end of life care. Thus, the need for the introduction of the Alzheimer's Scotland Advanced Care Dementia Palliative and End of Life Care Model (Scottish Government, 2017). A diagnosis of dementia is a life changing, significant aspect of the dementia journey and post diagnostic support is an essential component of the evolving dementia care requirements for both patient and family (NHS Education Scotland, 2014). Despite healthcare policy advocating early diagnosis and thus early availability of support (Scottish Government, 2013, Department of Health, 2015) the emotional implications of an unpredictable life journey with an ultimately terminal diagnosis should not be overlooked (Bunn, Goodman and Sworn et al, 2012). Nonetheless, whilst an early diagnosis effectively lengthens the dementia journey (or could be perceived as such), with good post diagnostic support, an early diagnosis gives both patient and family time to emotionally adapt to changing roles, anticipate potential care needs and make advanced decisions whilst cognitively able (De Vugt and Verhey, 2013, NHS Education Scotland, 2014).

In Scotland, post diagnostic support was a key assertion set by the first dementia strategy (Scottish Government, 2010a) and the updated strategies (Scottish Government, 2013, Scottish Government, 2017) have made the ongoing commitment to ensure at least 1 year guaranteed post diagnostic support from a named person, working at the 'enhanced level' of the Promoting Excellence Framework (Scottish Government, 2011b). The post diagnostic support follows the '5 Pillars' of Post Diagnostic Support as set out by Alzheimer's Scotland (2011), namely focusing

on education on dementia and symptom management, anticipatory care planning, advance decision making, peer support and facilitating social support networks. Post Diagnostic Support, whilst guaranteed for 1 year following diagnosis, should ultimately aim to help the person and their family through the stages of the dementia journey, which are; keeping and living well post diagnosis, needing extra care to live well and finally dying well at the end of life (Scottish Government, 2011a).

Most dementia care takes place in the home by informal family carers with help from social care services (Scottish Government, 2010a, Scottish Public Health Network, 2013, Rokstad, Halse, Tretteteig et al, 2014). It is well recognised that the majority of people with dementia want to stay at home and indeed a plethora of recent evidence identifies hospital admission as having a negative impact on the person with dementia (Toot, Devine, Akporobaro et al 2013, Scottish Government, 2013). However, with inevitable cognitive and physical deterioration and considering most people with dementia have other comorbidities, acute hospital admission can be unavoidable. A systematic review by Toot, Devine, Akporobaro et al (2013) reported that people with dementia are at an increased risk of hospital admission due to orthopaedic trauma (falls and fractures), infection (respiratory, urological) and worsening behavioural or psychological symptoms. The difficulty of distinguishing whether behavioural and psychological symptoms are a direct effect of the dementia or as a result of a causal physiological problem can be complex for acute nursing staff who are not familiar with a person's normal cognitive ability and behaviour patterns (Toot et al, 2013). Indeed, managing the complex care needs of the person with dementia in an acute hospital environment is persistently challenging and as there is no panacea in terms of total care management, the person's physical and cognitive problems can often be misdiagnosed or even exacerbated during such admissions (NHS Education Scotland, 2012, Jurgens, Clissett, Gladman et al, 2012).

In Scotland, there has been an ongoing improvement programme, especially in acute care, led by newly appointed Dementia Nurse Consultants and local "Dementia Champions" (Scottish Government, 2013) who act as advocates for the person with dementia and share best practice dementia education advice and problem solving strategies. Furthermore, NHS Education Scotland (2012) published the Acute Care Dementia resource to aid all staff working in acute care to help understand and care for the person with dementia from admission to discharge, however the complexities of delivering effective dementia care in reality are well documented

(Clissett, Porock, Harwood et al, 2013, Selbaek et al, 2013). The second dementia strategy (Scottish Government, 2013) detailed a 10 point action plan for acute care, focusing on leadership and staff development, planning for safe, person centred evidence based care and ensuring equality and partnership working for the person with dementia and their family, aspirations echoed in the third and latest dementia strategy (Scottish Government, 2017). Such aspirations capture the fundamental ethos of the Healthcare Quality Strategy (Scottish Government, 2010b), whereby all that access healthcare have the right to safe, effective, person centred care.

Person centred care embraces the concept of personhood, notably conceptualised by Tom Kitwood and used widely to underpin person centred healthcare. According to Kitwood (1997), personhood is focused around three discourses which form the basis of his theory; transcendence, ethics and social psychology. Transcendence is conceptualised as a sense of self, who we are and what makes us a unique person, whilst ethics considers the principles of justice and respect for self and others and social psychology reflects the notion of individuality whilst having an interrelated role in the wider society (Kitwood, 1997, Baldwin and Capstick, 2007). Person centred care embraces the notion of holistic care, in that healthcare should encompass not only physical care but should consider the emotional, psychological, social and spiritual care needs that any person may have (Alzheimer Scotland, 2012, Brooker and Waugh, 2013).

However, person centred care is a challenging concept to fully meet for the person with dementia in the medically orientated acute care setting (Clissett et al 2013). Indeed, the medical model of dementia only considers the pathophysiological changes that cause symptomatic cognitive and behavioural decline, yet doesn't fully consider the associated emotional and psychosocial factors (Alzheimer's Scotland, 2012). There should however be greater opportunity to deliver more effective person centred care in the community environment, especially when care is being delivered in a person's own home (Scottish Government, 2010a, Scottish Government, 2013, Scottish Government, 2017). Nonetheless, the complexities of coordinating health and social care services in the community have also presented a continuing challenge. To successfully meet a person with dementia's complex physical, cognitive and emotional needs and wellbeing, a range of both health and social care interventions are required and often complex care packages are necessary (Alzheimer's Scotland, 2012, Scottish Government, 2017)

2.4: Complexities of Care

The complexities of coordinating health and social care, particularly for older people with multiple comorbidities and with cognitive impairment such as dementia has been an ongoing challenge, both in terms of communication between differing multidisciplinary teams and also in allocation of resources between competing budgets. In Scotland, such challenging situations have led to the introduction of the Public Bodies (Joint Working) (Scotland) Act (2014). This legislative act provides a framework for integrated health and social care services working together in partnership and within a joint budget to plan and deliver preventative and anticipatory care to patients, carers and families in need (Scottish Government, 2014).

Such integrated care in dementia follows the 8 Pillars Model of Community Support as set by Alzheimer's Scotland (2012). The 8 Pillars of Support are; having a named, skilled, support coordinator, support for carers, personalised support for the person with dementia, community support to help maintain social networks, environmental adaptive support, mental and general health support and therapeutic support for symptom management. Furthermore, in keeping with the Charter of Rights for People with Dementia and their Carers in Scotland (Alzheimer's Scotland, 2009) the person with dementia and their family carers have the right to be empowered to be an active participant in all decisions regarding care assessment, planning and care delivery, including advanced decision making regarding potential future care needs (Scottish Government, 2013, Scottish Government, 2017). Such full and effective participation in care must be applied without prejudice or discrimination. Moreover, when the person with dementia becomes unable to fulfil their full partnership role, by being unable to communicate or understand decisions, they are safeguarded by the Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) Act 2000, whereby a family carer or designated 'proxy' can participate in decision making on the persons behalf (Scottish Government, 2008).

Participative decision making and person centred care planning and delivery is a key role of the nurse when caring for a person with dementia (Clissett et al, 2013, Royal College of Nursing, 2013). Whether in a hospital, community or care home setting, the nurse has a strategic role as both care provider and the person with dementia's professional advocate. Despite this, many nurses feel unprepared for the role and feel lacking in both the knowledge and skills required to

deliver safe, effective, person centred dementia care (Livingston, Pitfield, Morris et al, 2012, Gandesha, Souza, Chaplin et al, 2012, Dewing and Dijk, 2014). Furthermore, a study by Robinson, Dickinson and Bamford et al (2013) found that many nurses were unsure of their own role and responsibilities when delivering dementia care and felt significant challenges impacted on their ability to deliver the expected standard of care.

In Scotland, such lack of knowledge, experience and confidence in ability to provide effective dementia care is one of the ongoing challenges being tackled by aspirational health policy such as Scotland's National Dementia Strategy (Scottish Government, 2010a) and the updated Dementia Strategies 2013-2016 (Scottish Government, 2013) and 2017-2020 (Scottish Government, 2017). The Standards of Care for Dementia in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2011a) and Promoting Excellence Framework (Scottish Government, 2011b) aim to provide a standardised acceptable knowledge and skill level for all healthcare staff which is especially important for nurses who are at the centre of care giving as the largest group of healthcare professionals (Gandesha et al, 2013).

One of the most important ways to ensure that nurses have the essential knowledge and skills to care for patients with dementia, is to ensure that pre-registration nurse training facilitates the start of such a knowledge and skill base and that dementia knowledge and skills training is inherent in all pre-registration nursing programmes (Collier, Knifton and Surr, 2015, Scottish Government, 2015).

2.5: Significance of Research and Unique Knowledge Contribution

Whilst there is a plethora of research examining dementia care from nursing and social care professionals (Suhonen et al, 2010), there is a dearth of research exploring dementia care delivery from student nurses (Clissett et al, 2013). Considering that nursing students experience dementia in clinical placements from the beginning of their training and are active participants in care delivery (Scerri and Scerri, 2013), there is a need to ensure that they can deliver research based, effective and inclusive dementia care even as a student. Moreover, there is a lack of quality research exploring student nurses' perceptions of dementia and their role in dementia

care, as well as their readiness for delivering such care and factors that influence their care delivery. From the student nurse perspective, it is essential that specific learning needs are being met to prepare them to deliver safe, effective dementia care and also to enable evaluation of the effectiveness of the educational dementia knowledge and skills training they have undertaken. It is acknowledged that many nursing students' receive inadequate dementia training (Alushi, Hammond and Wood 2015), with current curricular content not always adequately preparing the students to deliver the expected level of care (Eccleston, Lea, McInerney et al, 2015). It is suggested by Spector et al (2012) that this lack of requisite knowledge and skill may lead to inconsistency in knowledge and skill levels as qualified practitioners. Thus, it is essential to consider not only student nurses' perceptions of dementia but also how the student perceives their own abilities in terms of knowledge, skills development and readiness to fulfil their role in dementia care.

To facilitate such an understanding of student perceptions of dementia and their ability to provide dementia care and also to provide a research study that offers a unique and original knowledge contribution, a critical review of the literature was required.

The following chapter will provide clarity and focus for this research study by carrying out an in-depth literature review.

Chapter Three: Literature Review: Students Perceptions Of Dementia Care and an Exploration of Dementia Training in the Undergraduate Pre-Registration Nursing Curriculum

Now that the impact of dementia on nursing has been established, it is essential to explore how student nurses are prepared to deliver dementia care as part of learning to be a nurse. Accordingly, this chapter will provide an overview of the literature review process that informed this study.

Firstly, there will be a critique of the available literature exploring student nurses' perceptions of dementia care and dementia care delivery. To set these perceptions in context, it is essential to understand how student nurses learn. Therefore, there will also be a critique of undergraduate pre-registration nursing curricula in the United Kingdom, considering both the professional and educational standards of requirement. In relation to the dementia context, an overview of the integration of the Promoting Excellence Framework (Scottish Government, 2011b) into the undergraduate nursing curriculum in Scotland will be detailed and dementia care in nursing practice explored. Lastly, the learning theories applicable to the nursing profession will be critically appraised, introducing social learning theory as the underpinning theoretical framework for this study and the concept of self-efficacy as a measure of student perception of success.

3.0: Literature Review Process

A systematic literature review is one of the first and most essential components of a doctoral thesis (Murray, 2011, Walshaw, 2012) and assists in the identification of research questions by identifying areas of limited knowledge or understanding (Gray, 2014, Bazely, 2018, Yin, 2018). A comprehensive literature search was commenced in 2013 and provided the initial impetus for commencing this research study. To ensure currency, the literature review has been updated several times to date (2019) and electronic alerts set on the saved search history to inform the researcher of any recently published research that meets the search criteria.

As this study encompasses both nursing practice and theoretical education, it required extensive review of published research as well as critique of professional resources and policy documents;

Searched Databases	Dementia and Older Adult Specific Resources	Nursing Resources
Cinahl	Alzheimer's Disease International	NMC
Medline	Alzheimer Europe	RCN
PMC/Pubmed	Alzheimer Scotland	DoH
Proquest	Alzheimer's Association	NES
ERIC	Alzheimer's Society	WHO
Ovid	British Gerontological Society	QAA
Ingenta Connect	Age UK	NICE
Cochrane Library	Help the Aged	SIGN
EthOS	Dementia Specific Journals (such as	
Health Reference Academic Centre	Dementia and Journal of Dementia	
Science Citation Index	Care)	
RCNi		
Onfile Gale		
Science Direct Journals		
Elsevier		
Taylor and Francis Online		
Sage Journals/Publications		
Informa Taylor Francis		
Springerlink		
Oxford Journals		

Wiley Online Library		
Lippincott Williams/Wilkins		
Journals/Wolters Kluwer Health		
Cambridge Journals		

Table 3.0: Literature Review Search Detail

For the databases, keywords were searched, using truncation, including demen*, nurs*, student, undergrad*, nurse education and the Boolean operators ‘and’ and ‘or’. To ensure currency, the search was limited to articles published in the last 10 years (2009-2019 at last literature review update). Specification was set to ensure articles were peer reviewed, available in full text and written in English. Initial search found (n=1334) articles however, the majority of these were deemed unsuitable after screening by title and abstract. Reasons for unsuitability included irrelevancy, duplications or not being specific to student nurses. Following initial screening, (n=95) articles were selected for full text evaluation. Thereafter, full text evaluation facilitated exclusion of articles that were non-nursing focused, only involved the evaluation of a specific learning intervention or related to specific aspects of older adult care, such as; medication adherence, loneliness and communication. Whilst it was desirable to only include articles that were student nurse specific and related to dementia care, there were very few that fulfilled this requirement and thus articles that were explicitly student nurse related but older adult focused were also included for review. This resulted in (n=25) articles that presented 3 dominant themes; Perceptions and Attitudes towards Dementia, Dementia Knowledge and Dementia Education.

3.1: Perceptions and Attitudes towards Dementia

As previously stated, there were more articles exploring student nurses attitudes towards older adults but few specifically dementia related. Whilst this study is not exclusively about attitudes or measuring attitudes, it is widely recognised that attitudes can influence perceptions (Bandura, 1997a, Bandura, 1997b, Banks, Waugh, Henderson et al, 2014, Ridgeway, 2018).

A study by McKenzie and Brown (2014) focused on student nurses' work intentions, specifically focusing on intentions to work in dementia care. Evaluation of (n=135) undergraduate nursing students demonstrated significantly increased levels of positive ageism ($p < 0.001$) as they progressed through their nursing programme. However, similar to the findings of an earlier study by Cherry and Palmore (2008), students perceived barriers to working in older adult environments. Whilst there was some inconsistency in stereotypes of age and recognised factors associated with ageing, a view concurred by Lambrinov, Sourtzi, Kalokerinou et al (2009), young students cited emotional barriers to working in older adult environments (such as being unable to cope with palliative care). In contrast, older students perceived professional barriers such as challenging work environments and multidisciplinary team dynamics. Indeed, some students desire for curative nursing and medical care is exemplified by the desire to work in acute areas which are seen by some as more dynamic. Moreover, McKenzie and Brown (2014) suggest that if students had a better understanding of the complexity and diversity of older adult care, they would be more likely to choose to work in such an environment.

Conversely, a systematic literature review by Koh (2012) reported that older people's nursing becomes less popular as student nurses progress through undergraduate training programs. In other words, the more clinical experience that the students get, the less that they value nursing the older adult. Furthermore, there was also a relationship between students working part time (as a care assistant) in older adult environments and a more negative attitude towards older people's nursing. Koh (2012) acknowledges aspirational health policy for dementia care and the health service and governmental goals to provide high quality elder care, however, recognises that in the reality of delivering complex nursing care to elderly people, there remains constant challenges with staff attitude, lack of resources and less opportunity for career advancement within older adult care environments.

Indeed, such challenges and in particular those related to negative attitudes, are recognised by Dingwall, Fenton, Kelly et al (2017), to have a negative impact on care environments, contributing to nursing care that does not always meet patient's fundamental needs. In a mixed method exploratory study involving nursing and social work students (n=63), attitudes towards people with dementia were measured using the 21-item attitudes towards older people scale devised by Kogan (1961). Although Kogan's scale was recognised as perhaps dated, its use was verified by the fact that it had previously been tested in student populations. Certainly, although

this study was small scale, its findings drew comparisons to the study by Koh (2012), in that, as the nursing students neared course completion, they demonstrated more negative attitudes towards older adult nursing and were less likely to seek employment in an older adult environment. When specifically considering dementia, there were striking differences between the nursing and social work students. The social work students were found to have a more holistic attitude towards dementia care, focusing on the home environment and home based therapeutic interventions. Conversely, the nursing students were found to be more safety focused and had a clinical and symptom relieving approach to care aspirations. Interestingly, the social work students perceived the nursing students to have negative attitudes towards people with dementia and in turn, the nursing students perceived the social work students to have little insight into the multifaceted needs of the person with dementia. Such difference in perception was sought to be related to training differences and hence it was postulated that interprofessional learning could help multidisciplinary teamwork and thus ultimately patient care, a view concurred by Baillie (2015). Furthermore, Baillie (2015) additionally recognises the role of nurse lecturers in shaping attitudes towards older adults and recognises that even when learning about more medicalised 'acute care' nursing, it should be acknowledged by lecturers, that the majority of people that students will be caring for are over 65 and indeed dementia is a commonly seen condition in all care environments, thus, should be inherent in all pre-registration nursing programmes from an early stage.

Certainly, the importance of education was also apparent in a study by Ridgeway et al (2018). A longitudinal mixed method study of (n=307) undergraduate nurses saw the students asked to complete an attitudinal survey (Kogan, 1961), undertake drawing opportunities and take part in interviews. Whilst this research study was related to older adults and not dementia specific, it demonstrated interesting comparisons to other published literature. Similar to the findings of Koh (2012), Baillie (2015) and Dingwall et al (2017), the resource specific and attitudinal challenges of working in older adult environments were recognised and furthermore, it was acknowledged that educational and practical experiences in pre-registration nursing programmes undoubtedly contribute to the student's attitudes and perceptions. However, the key difference in the study by Ridgeway et al (2018) was the fact that student nurses in this study developed more positive attitudes towards older adults as they progressed through their nursing programme. This difference may be reflective of the fact that all fields of nursing were included (adult, mental health, child and learning disabilities) or may be skewed by the 38%

attrition rate. Nonetheless, interesting findings and also an astute recognition of the need to gain students perceptions, as future practitioners that must be prepared for practice.

In terms of seeking perceptions, a study by Baillie, Merritt, Cox et al (2015), sought to gain understanding on student nurses confidence and expectations about delivering dementia care. Using a bespoke cross sectional survey questionnaire (developed by the research team), the views of (n=328) student nurses were gained. Whilst little detail on the validity or reliability of the survey questionnaire was included, the scarcity of dementia specific literature including student nurses, warranted further critique. Results showed that confidence in caring for people with dementia was higher in third year students than it was in first or second year but confidence was reported to be low overall amongst all students. The observations of caring practices in clinical learning environments were recognised to be impacting on confidence and attitudes, with older students more realistic in expectations of ability to provide care, particularly if they had experience of working in older adult environments as a care assistant. Nonetheless, whilst these results were interesting, it was recognised that the cross sectional design was a limitation of the study and it was suggested that longitudinal studies were required to show when and how students were influenced by both theoretical and practical learning environments. Hence, gaining understanding on the significance of changing perceptions and the requirement for timely and focused dementia education to facilitate knowledge and skill gain.

3.1.1: Dementia Knowledge

Although measurement of dementia specific knowledge indicators are not the purpose of this study and are measured by modular learning outcomes specific to the undergraduate nursing programme, perceptions of knowledge and ability are inherent components of nursing care delivery and are impactful on undergraduate nursing education.

A study by Scerri and Scerri (2013) used the Alzheimer Disease Knowledge Scale and the Dementia Attitudes Scale to gain insight into dementia knowledge amongst (n=305) undergraduate student nurses. Overall, the study found an adequate knowledge level amongst the students and positive attitudes towards dementia in all years of the 3 year undergraduate

nursing programme, though interestingly, second and third year students cited specific learning needs. They particularly professed the need for better preparation to deliver person centred care. Indeed, once they had gained insight into the complex needs of the person with dementia in first year, they recognised the requirement for such person centred care and specifically cited a lack of support in practical environments to help them achieve this. Therefore, they felt there was a need for more detailed theoretical and simulated skill preparation to ensure they were prepared for practice. To ensure such preparation for contemporary practice, Scerri and Scerri (2013) recommend that all dementia education should be focused on learning need as perceived by the student. Thus, the need to extract students' perceptions is essential to tailor learning interventions appropriately.

A small scale qualitative study by Watts and Davis (2014) further exemplified the requirement to consider students' perceptions of learning need. Their exploratory study involved (n=11) third year student nurses who were providing complex nursing care to people with advanced dementia. Although the students felt positive about the knowledge gained from educational opportunities within the undergraduate curriculum, they felt unprepared to deliver the complexity of care required at the latter stages of their patient's dementia journey's. The students found the transfer of idealised theory to the reality of practice challenging due to time constraints and practical difficulties in the clinical area. Furthermore, the students felt unempowered to insight positive change or to challenge practice due to their relative inexperience.

Certainly, the influence of clinical practice on dementia knowledge is variable in terms of positivity. In a study by Kimzey, Mastel-Smith and Alfred (2016), (n=94) senior student nurses were tested for dementia knowledge using the Alzheimer's Disease Knowledge Scale and the Dementia Attitudes Scale, drawing parallels to the work of Scerri and Scerri (2013). Overall, knowledge indicators were good, with clinical placements proven to increase dementia knowledge, but only if there was adequate support for the students. Similarly, a study by Eccleston et al (2015) also highlighted knowledge improvement post clinical placement experience. However, again this was only increased when students were well supported in practice placement environments. In their study involving (n=99) second year student nurses, assessed using the Dementia Knowledge Toolkit, despite the potentially positive impact of clinical experience, dementia knowledge was actually deemed poor. In particular, the students

had a lack of understanding of the progressive and ultimately terminal nature of dementia. Furthermore, this disparity of knowledge and skill was also reflected by Wood, Alushi and Hammond (2017) whereby students were noted to provide conflicting opinion on preparation for clinical practice as well as perceptions of dementia knowledge and skill. Overwhelmingly, there was a recommendation for the need to examine factors influencing student's knowledge and skills in dementia care to ensure dementia education is timely, meaningful and prepares students effectively for professional nursing practice (Watts and Davis, 2014, Shin, Seo, Kim et al, 2015, Eccleston et al, 2015, Wood et al, 2017).

3.1.2: Dementia Education

Dementia education is essential for all health, medical and social care professionals (Banerjee, Farina, Daley et al, 2016) and it is recognised that it needs to be relevant and orientated to the reality in which dementia care takes place (Surr, Gates, Irving et al, 2017). However, it is well recognised that there is great variation in dementia education provision (Pulsford, Hope and Thompson 2007, Traynor, Inove and Crookes, 2011). An exploratory study by Hvalic-Touzery, Savic, Macrae et al (2018) investigated the prevalence of dementia specific content in nursing, medicine, allied health professional and social care education programmes in (n=6) European countries. Mapping of dementia curricular and course content found dementia content in all countries and all courses at undergraduate level but not above. However, this content was extremely variable, was delivered by academic staff with limited expertise in dementia and in particular, had little content on advanced dementia.

This variability echoes the content of the Higher Education for Dementia Network Position Paper (Surr, Baillie, Waugh et al, 2017) which recognises that despite health policy consistently advocating for appropriate dementia education for all health and social care professionals, regulatory bodies do not explicitly state what content or how much content should be included. For nursing, as the largest professional group, there is a distinct and essential role for dementia education as part of preparing the future nursing workforce.

3.2: Dementia in Pre-Registration Nursing Programmes

Student nurses care for patients across the lifespan and at all stages of the health, ill-health continuum (Quality Assurance Agency, 2009). However, it is well recognised that many patients who require nursing care are at the latter end of the lifespan and indeed, the number of older adults requiring nursing care is increasing in direct correspondence with the ageing population (WHO, 2009, Ellis et al, 2011). People are living longer, with multiple co-morbidities and as such can require complex nursing care (Robinson et al 2011, Roland and Paddison, 2013). As discussed in Chapter Two, the burgeoning co-morbidity nationally and internationally that is dementia, has become an international public health priority (Scottish Government, 2013, Alzheimer's Disease International, 2014, World Health Organisation, 2015). Although care of the older adult and dementia care in particular has long been part of the undergraduate pre-registration nursing curriculum within the UK, it is well acknowledged that this has not always been at an acceptable level and has not consistently provided student nurses with the required knowledge and skills to deliver effective dementia care in practice (Alushi et al, 2015 Eccleston et al, 2015, Surr et al, 2017). NMC educational directives specify the overall programme wide particulars for pre-registration nurse education (NMC 2010a), however do not advise on exacting curricular content, thus individual programme providers must look to healthcare legislation and policy to inform course content and modular learning outcomes. Current healthcare legislation demands nurses to be competent practitioners who are well equipped to serve patient need (Scottish Government, 2010b, WHO, 2014) and indeed the complexity of modern healthcare means there has never been a greater requirement for equity in healthcare provision through recognised standards of care and health policy which must be reflected in education (Crinson, 2009, RCN, 2012, NES, 2012, WHO, 2014).

The NMC Strategy 2015-2020 (NMC, 2015b) recognises such requirement and advocates that nursing must always be responsive to demographic changes, as advised by the 2020 Workforce Vision (NHS Scotland, 2013). The challenges of an ageing population bring increased demands to healthcare knowledge and resources (NHS Scotland, 2013) through increased complex patient need as patients live longer at home with progressive and long term conditions (such as dementia) (NMC, 2015b). NES (2013) recognise the need for career planning to reflect service need and changing populations, such as the frail older adult with dementia, and also acknowledge that nursing career planning starts at pre-registration level. Indeed, the Setting the

Direction Delivery Plan 2015-16 (Scottish Government, 2015) clearly states the need for pre-registration nurse education to be aligned with such service need. It asserts that pre-registration nurse education must reflect the complexity of care needs that the older adult with dementia brings and sets the ambitious goal that all pre-registration adult, mental health and learning disability nursing students in Scotland, registering in 2016 or thereafter should at least be at the ‘skilled practice’ level of the Promoting Excellence Framework (Scottish Government, 2011b).

As discussed in chapter two, the Promoting Excellence Framework (Scottish Government, 2011b, p7.) defines the knowledge and skills that all health and social care workers should have to provide care to the person with dementia;

Dementia Informed Practice Level	Baseline knowledge and skills required by all staff working in health and social care settings including a person’s own home.
Dementia Skilled Practice Level	Knowledge and skills required by all staff that have direct and/or substantial contact with people with dementia and their families and carers.
Enhanced Dementia Practice Level	Knowledge and skills required by health and social services staff that have more regular and intense contact with people with dementia, provide specific interventions, and/or direct/manage care and services.
Expertise in Dementia Practice Level	Knowledge and skills required for health and social care staff who by virtue of their role and practice setting, play an expert specialist role in the care, treatment and support of people with dementia.

Table 3.2: Promoting Excellence Framework

As can be seen from table above, the ‘skilled’ level of the Promoting Excellence Framework (Scottish Government, 2011b) demands a knowledge of dementia and skills in dementia care, gained from direct and/or substantial contact with people with dementia, therefore should be easily achievable in all pre-registration nursing courses. However, with the drive for care excellence through quality assurance and the utmost need to embed values, professionalism

and research into nursing through measurable values based standards (Scottish Government, 2015, NES, 2016), the Promoting Excellence Framework (Scottish Government, 2011b) and other dementia legislation provide a useful benchmark for curricular content (Scottish Government, 2010a, Scottish Government, 2013). Nonetheless, as well as the theoretical underpinning of dementia and dementia care, the students also experience dementia in clinical practice.

3.3: Dementia Care in Practice

Student nurses care for people with dementia from the beginning of their undergraduate programme, in a variety of health and social care settings, yet many studies have shown that even more experienced students feel unprepared for this role (Spector et al, 2012, Alushi et al, 2015, Eccleston et al, 2015). From the student perspective, it is essential that learning needs are being met to enable them to be ready to deliver safe, effective dementia care and thus also to enable evaluation of the effectiveness of the educational knowledge and skills training they have undertaken (Collier et al, 2015, Banerjee, 2016, Surr et al, 2017, Hvalic-Touzery et al, 2018).

As a self-regulating profession, nursing students (under supervision) and staff nurses, are accountable for the care they deliver and they must ensure that research based, effective and inclusive dementia care meets policy directives and aspirations (Scottish Government, 2010a, Scottish Government, 2013, Scottish Government, 2017). Therefore, it is important to explore self-perceptions of ability to deliver such care. With dementia a recognised public health priority, this has led to an abundance of research examining dementia care from nursing and social care professionals. However, there is a scarcity of research exploring the student perspective of dementia care. Considering that current students deliver much of the 'hands on' care in clinical areas, there is a need to explore their perceptions of dementia and their role in dementia care, as well as their perceived readiness for dementia care practice and factors that influence their ability to deliver such care.

Thus, to gain an understanding of such perceptions, the literature review thus far, has prompted the generation of the following research aims;

- To explore undergraduate student nurse perceptions of dementia care and their role in care delivery.
- To examine the influence of theory, skills training and clinical experience on approach to dementia care delivery amongst undergraduate student nurses.
- To appraise how dementia training policy directives for pre-registration nurse education are reflected in undergraduate student nurse's knowledge, skills and readiness for nursing practice.

To facilitate achievement of these aims, it is essential to further the literature review to have a critical understanding of nursing education and to fully comprehend the preparation of student nurses for professional practice.

3.4: Nursing Education

As the aforementioned research aims seek to explore perceptions of dementia care by undergraduate pre-registration student nurses in full time University education, it is essential to put such educational training in perspective. To grasp the significance and educational relevance for this specific research study, it is essential to understand the nuances of pre-registration nursing education in the UK and the context in which learning takes place.

Pre-registration nursing education is the requisite programme for all nursing students in the United Kingdom, to allow them to meet the competency based requirements for professional registration with the Nursing and Midwifery Council (NMC) (Nursing and Midwifery Council, 2010a). The NMC are the governing body and regulator for all nurses, midwives and specialist practice nurses in the United Kingdom. As the regulating body, the NMC sets professional standards for training and education of student nurses. At present, most educational providers are still using pre-2018 Standards of Competence for Registered Nurses (NMC, 2010b), Standards for Pre-Registration Education (NMC, 2010a) and Standards to Support Learning in Practice (NMC, 2008). However, the NMC has developed new professional standards to reflect healthcare and societal changes. These are; Standards of Proficiency for Registered Nurses

(NMC, 2018a), Standards Framework for Nursing and Midwifery Education (NMC, 2018b), Standards for Student Supervision and Assessment (NMC, 2018c) and Standards for Pre-Registration Nursing Programmes (2018d). As these standards were not yet currently in use by all higher educational establishments providing nursing education at the time of writing this literature review and considering the fact that the NMC core professional values are fundamentally unchanged, this thesis has used the pre-2018 standards as a point of reference. However, the implications of the introduction of the new professional standards are critically discussed in Chapter Eight.

To fully appreciate the uniqueness of studying nursing, in terms of both theoretical and practical learning, as well as educational and professional regulatory requirements, it is useful to have an understanding of how nurse education has evolved.

3.4.1: Background: Pre-Registration Nursing Education

Nursing was traditionally learned by a hierarchical apprenticeship model of learning, whereby, nurses were employed by hospitals or health boards and most of their learning took place in the wards, working alongside and learning from other more experienced nurses (Lauder, Watson, Topping et al, 2008, O'Driscoll, Allan and Smith, 2010, Gardner, 2013, Andrew, Lopes, Pereira et al, 2013). This apprenticeship model was called to change by the NMC's predecessor, the United Kingdom Central Council for Nursing, Midwifery and Health Visiting (UKCC) in the drive to give nursing a professional status through its integration into higher education (UKCC, 1986, UKCC, 1999). The Project 2000 model of nurse training (established in 1986) saw the affiliation of nursing schools with Universities and the notion of the student nurse being a 'learner' rather than a paid employee (UKCC, 1999, UKCC, 2001). For the first time, student nurses had supernumerary status as their training was educationally focused in classroom environments, rather than task based 'learning by doing' in the clinical ward area (O'Driscoll et al, 2010, RCN, 2012). However, despite the increased theoretical focus, Project 2000 was widely criticised and the notion of whether newly qualified nurses were actually fit to practice, required further examination (UKCC, 1999, UKCC, 2001, NHS Education Scotland, 2008a). Such requirement for fitness to practice and increased professional and public demands, as well as the lessons learned from Project 2000, led to the implementation of a competency based pre-registration nursing

curriculum, components of which are still used in contemporary nurse education (Lauder et al, 2008, , NMC 2010a, RCN, 2012).

In addition to a competency based curriculum, current pre-registration nursing programme specifics are also directly influenced by the aspirational aims of the Nursing and Midwifery Council as set out at its inception in 2002. The Nursing and Midwifery Council took over as the new governing body and sought further review of nursing education, in its drive for enhanced professional status for nursing. The move to an all graduate profession was key to meeting such aspirational professional demands (Andrews et al, 2013) and current NMC approved pre-registration nurse education programmes must meet exacting educational and professional requirements;

3.4.2: Pre-Registration Programme Requirements

In the United Kingdom, the NMC has an overarching responsibility for public protection as set by the Nursing and Midwifery Order 2001 (NMC, 2010a). The Order sets out a legislative framework to ensure quality assurance in nursing by enforcing the establishment of standards of training, education, conduct and performance (NMC, 2010a, NMC, 2015a). These standards correlate with the aspiration of the 'Global Standards for the Initial Education of Nurses and Midwives', which reinforce the need for equity in provision of a high standard of evidence based nursing care, delivered by competent practitioners who are well equipped for professional registration (WHO, 2009). NMC standards are also aligned with EU directive 2005/36/EC in terms of recognition of level of professional qualification, minimum pre-registration programme length and nursing theory to practice ratio (NMC, 2010a).

The Nursing and Midwifery Council accredits 77 educational institutions across the UK who deliver 951 NMC approved nursing education programmes (most of which are pre-registration) (NMC, 2015a). The NMC Standards for Pre-Registration Nursing Education (NMC, 2010a) assert that nursing must be an all graduate profession, commensurate with all other allied health professionals and from 2013, all pre-registration accredited courses became ordinary degree level or above. Student nurses must complete a programme of at least 3 years/4600 hours in

length, with a 50/50 theory practice ratio (2300 hours theory and 2300 hours practice) in line with EU Directive 2005/36/EC to qualify to register in a specific field of nursing practice; adult, mental health, learning disabilities or children's nursing (NMC, 2010a). Student nurses must also meet specific NMC educational standards and fulfil the standards set by Higher Education legislation.

3.4.3: Educational Standards

NMC standards for nurse education (NMC, 2010a) set very specific criteria that aim to ensure that public protection is paramount at all times and that student nurses are fit for practice and ultimately fit for award and registration. Specific standards regarding equality and diversity, recruitment and retention, student support, programme structure and delivery, as well as theoretical and practical learning and assessment, ensure quality assurance through transparent and clear objectives that must be met (NMC, 2010a, NMC, 2015a). The Quality Assurance Code for Higher Education (QAA, 2018) recognises that such accessible, open and honest goal setting is essential in ensuring academic standards are maintained and imparts the need for continual quality improvement in learning opportunity in all higher education courses. However, the Scottish Subject Benchmark Statement for Nursing (QAA, 2009) recognises that nursing is not only an academic programme but also that as a professional discipline, learning takes place in many different settings and indeed, students are accredited for practice based learning as well as theoretical learning.

Nursing education encompasses not only scientific learning of anatomy, physiology, pathophysiology and social science but also the learning of humanities and the arts such as the process of communication and the art of caring (which is often best learned and experienced in a practical setting) (QAA, 2009). Therefore, student nurses spend time both learning in University and also delivering patient care within practice learning environments (QAA, 2009). Assessment of learning is undertaken theoretically by academics but also practically by clinicians, using a competency based framework (Lauder et al, 2008, NMC, 2010a). Thus, the National Health Service (NHS), other health and social care providers and higher educational establishments that deliver pre-registration nursing programmes must work in partnership to promote and support learning in practice (NES, 2008, NMC 2010a, NMC, 2015a, NES, 2016).

Student nurses should be afforded the opportunity to learn and be assessed in a practical environment that is conducive to learning, whereby their learning is facilitated by a 'mentor' who provides leadership and guidance to enable learning and reflection on learning (NMC, 2008, NES, 2008). The NMC Standards to Support Learning and Assessment in Practice (NMC, 2008) stipulate that a mentor is a registered nurse, whom following completion of a mentorship preparation programme has achieved the knowledge and skills to effectively take responsibility for facilitating student learning in practice, through supervision, assessment and the provision of constructive feedback on performance. Mentors have a significant influence on the student learning experience (NMC, 2015a) and help students achieve the standards of competence that will be required of them upon registration (NMC, 2008, NMC, 2010b).

Such standards of clinical competence are met in part by the student's achievement of the 'Essential Skills Clusters' (NMC, 2010b). The essential skills clusters are a set of clinical skills, deemed integral to nursing care and students must achieve competence in the skills of "care, compassion and communication, organisational aspects of care, infection prevention and control, nutrition and fluid management and medicines management" (NMC, 2010b, p20). The assessment and evaluation of achievement of these skills through evidence based practice is carried out throughout the educational programme by mentors, with achievement of overall standards of competence accredited by the 'sign off mentor' (NMC, 2008). The 'sign off mentor' deems the student competent (or not) for entry to the professional register at the end of the pre-registration programme and after 2300 hours of clinical practice are complete (NMC, 2010). This pivotal role ensures clinicians remain a key component in both the education and implementation of professional standards for nurses (Lauder et al, 2008, NMC, 2010, NMC, 2015a, NES, 2014).

3.4.4: Professional Standards

As a professional discipline, the Nursing and Midwifery Council is responsible for the registration and guidance of 685,000 nurses and midwives (NMC, 2015c). Whilst nursing students are not fully accountable to the NMC, both the educational requirements of the student nurse and the practice based requirements are inherently related to the role specific professional standards

(NMC, 2010b, QAA, 2011). The underpinning professional standards for all nurses and midwives are detailed in The Code (NMC, 2015c, NMC, 2018f). The Code specifies not only the professional standards that all nurses and midwives must adhere to but also the standards expected by patients and the public (NMC, 2015c). According to The Code (NMC, 2015c, NMC, 2018f), nurses and midwives must ultimately uphold the principle of patient priority. They must respect a patient's rights and dignity whilst acting in the patient's best interest at all times. Furthermore, nurses and midwives must also ensure that clinical practice is safe and research based, working effectively within a team in an open, honest and collaborative manner, within both personal and professional limitations. Nurses are accountable for their clinical decision making and their actions, therefore, like medical staff, they are bound by the professional duty of candour (NMC, 2015d). The duty of candour demands that openness and honesty must be applied to patients even when things go wrong or mistakes are made. Such public openness and transparency in all standards (including The Code) are fundamental philosophies for the NMC, with the underpinning values of fairness, accountability, collaboration and continuous improvement key concepts in all standards and published guidance for practice. Nurses are in a position of trust and they must uphold that position and indeed uphold the reputation of the profession at all times (NMC, 2015c, NMC, 2015d). All nurses must ensure that they meet, not only the requirements of The Code, but also the required standards of clinical competence.

The Standards for Competence for Registered Nurses (NMC, 2010b, p4) demand that all qualified nurses must meet specific standards for clinical competence in relation to "professional values, communication and interpersonal skills, nursing practice and decision making, leadership, management and team working". They must also understand their specific roles and responsibilities, and be able to practice independently whilst recognising their limits of proficiency and understanding (NMC, 2010b, NMC 2010c). Thus, nurses need not know every aspect of every condition or treatment plan that they encounter, but they must be able to recognise any knowledge deficit and confidently practice (NMC, 2010b), meeting multifaceted patient need within their own field of nursing practice, in any care environment (NMC, 2010b, NMC, 2010c).

Whilst the move to a degree only profession reflects such multifaceted complexity of modern nursing care (NMC, 2015a), learning in nursing must be lifelong and as such, nurses are required to prove that they continually engage in learning to ensure their professional practice remains

current and research based (NMC, 2015c, NMC, 2015e). New revalidation guidelines implemented in April 2016, build upon the underpinning ethos of safe and effective nursing practice and demand that nurses not only complete continuing professional development educational requirements but also that they reflect on learned knowledge and experiences, sharing knowledge in a collaborative manner and facilitating feedback on practice to ensure continual improvement in knowledge and capability to deliver quality nursing care (NHS Scotland, 2012, NMC, 2015e, NMC, 2017). Such personal and professional development through learning, and quality improvement through the use of reflective practice, is integral to meeting aspirational healthcare demands (Scottish Government, 2010b) and the process of this learning can be understood in part by critical examination of the learning theories applicable to nursing.

3.5: Learning Theories

Whilst learning can be very broadly defined as the gaining of knowledge through theory, research or experience that impacts on behaviour (Johnson and Webber, 2005), the theoretical conceptualisation of approaches to learning vary (Merriam, Caffarella and Baumgartner, 2007, Bryman, 2016). There is much discourse and debate on learning theories and the understanding of human behaviour and knowledge acquisition, however, while learning theories can seem to be disparate in nature, there are often many overlapping concepts (Illeris, 2007, Jarvis, 2010). Certainly, in nursing, where learning takes place in a variety of ways (for example lectures, tutorial groups and online e-learning) and in differing settings (such as university classrooms, skills labs and practice placement areas), learning and teaching styles require to be flexible. It could even be argued that such diversity of learning experience for student nurses has meant that there are inherent characteristics of some seemingly opposing learning theories imbedded in nurse education curricular design (Twomey, 2004). Indeed, to understand the common learning theories, it is useful to group them according to ideological stance. Although Hayden (2014) suggests that learning theories are either intrapersonal, interpersonal or at a community level, the more common perspective is that of behaviourist theories, cognitive theories and humanistic theories (Jarvis, 2010).

For the purposes of selecting the most appropriate underpinning learning theory for this research study, it is useful to acknowledge that theory is being used in the sense of a concept or

framework of ideas that can contribute to the understanding of or predication of explained behaviours, patterns or behaviour changes (Johnson and Weber, 2005, Glanz, Rimer and Viswanath, 2008, Hayden, 2014).

3.5.1: Behaviourism

Behaviourism is quite simply the stimulus and response theory that focuses on observable behaviour or observable events (Quinn, 2006, Kala et al, 2010, Jarvis, 2010). Behaviourism considers someone or somethings' learned response to an external stimuli. The fundamental significance of behaviourism considers not only how the response to the stimulus is made but also how the response is maintained or replicated. One of the most seminal works of behaviourism is that of Pavlov (1927). Pavlov 'conditioned' his dogs to salivate at the sound of a bell as the bell indicated feeding time. This learned or conditioned response (salivating) was caused by previous exposure to the external stimuli (the bell ringing) and was known as 'classical conditioning'. Although the reactive nature of behaviourism can be applicable to many aspects of learning, Skinner (1969) recognised that positive or negative reinforcement could also affect the conditioned behaviour. According to Skinner, the consequence or outcome of the conditioned response (in the shape of a reward) could affect whether or how the response was replicated in the future, he called this 'operant conditioning'. Operant conditioning makes use of positive reinforcement to encourage the replication of a desirable behaviour.

In education, behaviourism is often used for measurable, task specific behaviours and indeed in nursing education, could be applicable to both theoretical or practice based learning as exemplified in the table below;

External Stimuli	Learned Behaviour in Relation to Nursing	Student Reward
Students are asked to complete a written assignment	Student submits assignment prior to deadline	Student gets a good grade and positive feedback from marker
Person with dementia in an acute hospital ward is refusing to eat.	As taught in simulation in University, student attempts to problem solve the potential cause of persons refusal to eat and implements risk assessment tools and communicates with the person and their family to involve them in care decisions	Prompt action identifies the issue and stops any unnecessary weight loss. The student receives positive feedback from their mentor.

Table 3.5.1: Behaviourism in Context

According to operant conditioning, as the student receives positive reinforcement from their learned behaviour, they would repeat such behaviour should the same situation arise again. However, whilst behavioural changes following learning are certainly observable, it is recognised that adult learning is not such a simplistic process and whereas fundamental behaviourist research mainly focused on children and animals, the iterative process of adult learning and level of knowledge acquisition and critical thinking required in nursing, cannot be explained in full by a behaviourist stance.

3.5.2: Cognitivism

Cognitivism seeks to explain the complex, cognitive changes that occur during learning. Cognitivism considers the conceptualisation of how information is stored, organised by coding and processed (Kala et al, 2010). Unlike the simplistic behaviour change due to a learned response in behaviourism, cognitivism involves higher level reasoning, memory and problem solving to make sense of information (Jarvis, 2010, Kala et al, 2010). Although, like behaviourism, the impact of the environment on learning is acknowledged in cognitivism, the learner actively seeks to understand the phenomena, rather than just learning an expected response. The most

influential cognitive theorists can be grouped by developmental theorists, data processing theorists and transformational theorists.

Piaget is one of the most well-known psychologists in terms of child development. Piaget purported that children move through developmental learning stages and he sought to relate biological stages of child development to learning and cognition (Piaget and Inhelder, 1969). According to Piaget, children move through 5 stages of development; Sensorimotor – children differentiate themselves to external objects, Preoperational – external objects are categorised by differentiating features, Intuitive – thinking by categorising and classifying, Concrete Operational – the commencement of logic and reason and lastly, Formal Operational – the commencement of abstract conceptual thoughts (Jarvis, 2010). Although Piaget has been extremely influential in pedagogical aspects of education, as his theory relates mainly to children, the transferability of his theoretical explanation of learning cannot fully be generalised to adult learning, such as nursing. Piaget was also very individualistic in his perception of cognitive processing and such egocentricity of learning (whilst perhaps could be seen as applicable to young children who are not as perceptually aware of their social surroundings), does not fit so well in adult learning where learners are much more socially aware (Ruey, 2010). Indeed, even although Kohlberg further developed Piaget's work in terms of the belief that moral knowledge (developed by advancing age) influences Piaget's conceptual theory (Colby, Kohlberg, Gibbs et al, 1983), this was again in children and thus perhaps the data processing cognitive theorists are more appropriate to nursing education.

Gagne's seminal work on the 8 phase model of learning offered a data processing cognitive approach to learning, whereby learners moved through the following phases; motivation to learn due to expected outcome, attention to and perception of learning, acquisition of learning through coding, storing learning in memory, retrieving learning from memory, transferring learning to new situations, responding or performing according to previous learning and lastly gaining feedback on performance and reinforcement for future performance (Gagne and Driscoll, 1988). Indeed, although Gagne is seen as a theorist whose beliefs sit firmly in cognitivism, the inferences to behaviourism are apparent in his model of data processing, whereby learners respond according to previous learning (classical conditioning) and are influenced by positive reinforcement (operant conditioning) (Skinner, 1969, Kala et al, 2009). However, the main difference between Gagne and the classical behaviourists such as Pavlov is

that Gagne believed the individual learner to be capable of free thought and inherent personal perceptions, and thus perhaps cognitivism can be relevant to adult education and indeed the theoretical or practice based learning in nursing, as exemplified in the table below;

Stage of Cognitive Data Processing According to Gagne (1977)	Student Nurse Example
Motivation/expectancy of learning	Student receives learning outcomes for class on “The Nursing Process”
Attention to/perception of learning	Student attains learning through paying attention in lecture and asking questions to ensure understanding
Acquisition of learning through coding information	Student codes the nursing process using the mnemonic “APIE” – “Assess, Plan, Implement, Evaluate”
Storing learning in memory	Student stores the memory in code format and using simulated learning, applies APIE to a simulated patient situation
Retrieving learning from memory	Student is in clinical practice and must remember the nursing process to deliver actual patient care
Transferring learning to new situation	Student transfers APIE and the simulated learning to the actual practice learning environment
Responding/performing due to learning having taken place	Student Assesses, Plans, Implements and Evaluates effective care for a patient
Gaining feedback/reinforcement	Student gets positive feedback from mentor which reinforces knowledge acquisition and the likelihood of the same performance in future patient care

Table 3.5.2: Cognitivism in Context

While the logical, progressive nature of cognitivism as exemplified above and applied to nursing education, can seem to simplify learning, the notion that learning should be more than a simple

process and actually be a meaningful exercise (certainly in a profession such as nursing and certainly in holistic dementia care delivery) cannot be overlooked.

Ausabel (1978) as cited in Quinn (2000), professed that learning can and should be transformational. Ausabel, differentiated between learning simply for recall of facts (such as rote learning) and meaningful learning, which involves the integration of new knowledge with previously learned material. Moreover, the way that learning materials are presented by teachers are seen by Ausabel to be inherently important to facilitate this assimilation and 'transformation' of learning through meaningful understanding. Indeed, the benefit of progressive introduction of new knowledge in a logical format and in manageable amounts is characteristic of the work of Gagne (as detailed above) but also of Bruner (Quinn, 2000). Bruner argues that the way new learning material is presented is intrinsically related to the amount of knowledge that can be recalled at a later date. Bruner's original work, although like Piaget focused primarily on children, was based upon the concept of continual reinforcement. In other words, new learning is introduced in small amounts and then built upon and revisited in greater detail as learning and understanding progresses and has greater meaning and complexity. This type of learning structure is commonly evident within nursing education in the use of a spiral curriculum, whereby common themes (such as dementia care) are revisited and considered with increasing complexity, both theoretically and practically to provide meaning and relevance to learning. Meaningful learning, although characterised by Ausabel, is also evident in the constructivist approach.

3.5.3: Constructivism

Constructivism is often used interchangeably with cognitivism (Hayden, 2014, Bryman, 2016) and indeed like many of the other learning theories, there are elements of overlap between the theoretical stances. However, constructivism is unique in its belief that learning also comes from experience and that learning is individual and unique to the person experiencing it. Constructivism also infers that learning can only take place following knowledge gain and practice in the correct learning environment or culture (Brown, Collins and Duguid, 1989, Ruey, 2010), thus both learner and environment are crucial components if meaningful learning is to

be achieved. Such constructivist ideologies, led to the development of a model of learning, commonly referred to in nursing literature; the cognitive apprenticeship model.

The cognitive apprenticeship model maintains that skills and knowledge acquisition are gained from working through 3 stages; cognitive, associative and autonomous stages. In the true sense of the term 'apprentice', the learner starts as an unknown novice and works to become an autonomous practitioner (thus the relevance to nursing becomes apparent). Brown et al (1989) explained the cognitive apprenticeship model in 6 stages which were modelling, coaching, scaffolding, articulation, reflection and exploration. In relation to nursing, again it can be useful to explore how the cognitive apprenticeship model may apply in nursing education;

Stage of Cognitive Apprenticeship Model	Learner (Student Nurse) Activity
Modelling	Nurse lecturer demonstrates step by step process of calming a distressed person with dementia (de-escalation) in a simulated ward skills lab environment (real world simulation).
Coaching	Students practice the technique they have observed and the lecturer 'coaches' them through their performance using prompts and continual feedback and encouragement.
Scaffolding	The lecturer uses mnemonics to assist in the recall process of what has caused the distressed behaviour (ABC) (A- antecedent, B- behaviour, C-consequences) and uses mannequins to allow the student to practice.
Articulation	Lecturer asks students to talk through the process of de-escalation to check knowledge acquisition.
Reflection	Students are asked to reflect on their learning experience and through peer review, reflect on the performance of others in their peer group.

Exploration	Students can access the skills lab for independent practice with their peers and are encouraged to take the initiative to participate in similar situations in clinical practice (in real world environment, under the supervision of their mentor).
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Table 3.5.3: The Cognitive Apprenticeship Model

While the cognitive apprenticeship model sits within the constructivist paradigm, the notion of modelling, coaching and scaffolding learning in a real world situation, draws parallels with the humanistic side of learning and thus imparts the need for a humanistic approach to nurse education.

3.5.4: Humanist Learning Theories

Humanistic learning theories have the student at the centre of learning and focus on the social and experiential aspects of learning. One of the most influential learning theorists who recognised the social nature of learning was Vygotsky (Jarvis, 2010, Berragan, 2011). Vygotsky (whose research also focused on child development), considered not only progressive development, but also potential development. Vygotsky (1978) posited that whilst learners have an actual developmental level (achieved by progressive development through cycles or phases) and perhaps comparable to Piaget’s (1929) stages of development, they also have a ‘Zone of Proximal Development’ (Illeris, 2007). Actual development is the level of knowledge or skill that the learner has already achieved, whereas the Zone of Proximal Development is the level of potential development that could be achieved by support or guidance from more experienced others or ‘experts’. Such learning support is recognised by Spouse (1998) as essential to gain higher levels of development through cognitive problem solving, a view shared by Carlisle and Jordan (2005). As the learner is supported to progress and develop in terms of both knowledge and problem solving, the new knowledge is subject to an internalisation process, whereby it becomes such an inherent part of their own understanding so that they now ‘know’ it. This is known by Vygotsky as the process of knowing (Vygotsky, 1978, Spouse, 1998, Jarvis, 2010) and the use of Vygotskian theory can in some essence still be applied to modern nurse education;

Actual Developmental Level	Zone of Proximal Development	Assistance to Achieve Zone of Proximal Development	Process of Knowing
Learner (student nurse) has independently reviewed the NHS Education Scotland learning packages on dementia as preparation for learning in University.	Learner can independently de-escalate situation when a person with dementia is distressed.	Learner is taught by experienced lecturer the step by step process of de-escalation.	Learner can perform independently – like qualified nurses, the student has internalised the process and now innately ‘knows’ how to perform in the situation.

Table 3.5.4: Vygotskian Theory in Context

Getting to the point of independent ‘knowing’ can be useful in nursing as much learning is competency based and students must achieve complete competence (such as those skills in the essential skills clusters; communication, infection control and basic life support amongst others) (Tilley, Allen, Collins et al, 2007, NMC, 2010). Certainly, scaffolded instruction based on Vygotskian theory has been usefully applied to practical learning and simulation in nursing as well as web based courses, particularly at post graduate level (Twomey, 2004, Tilley et al, 2007, Ruey, 2010). However, as can be seen in the tabulated example, the learner cannot progress to the Zone of Proximal Development according to Vygotsky (1978) without ‘expert’ assistance. Thus, as acknowledged by Illeris (2007) the ‘expert’ is in control of the learning situation and therefore the learning experience is teacher centred, rather than student centred. Indeed, the concept of student centred learning is not only desirable but essential in contemporary higher education and in nurse education (NMC, 2010, NHS Scotland, 2012, Bryman, 2016). Thus, a more student-centred learning theory was sought to underpin this research study and the student learning experience had to be considered.

3.5.5: The Student Learning Experience

Carl Rogers is well known in adult education for his theorising of student centred learning (Jarvis, 2010, Hayden, 2014). Rodgers theory reflects the emotional dimension of learning as well as the intellectual component. According to Rogers (1983), teachers are merely facilitators of learning and students actively initiate their own learning by 'doing' and 'experiencing'. Learning instigates organisational and perceptive changes in individuals and such change is part of the learning process (Illeris, 2007, Jarvis, 2010). This ethos of learning correlates well with the student nurse population. As adult learners, many are mature students who have made the conscious decision to study nursing. Such internalised enthusiasm to learn is a key component in the move from pedagogical learning to andragogic learning, according to Knowles (1980). Adult learners are self-directed and initiate their own learning opportunities by choice, seeking the humanistic desire to learn and be a valuable partner in the learning process (Knowles, 1980, Jarvis, 2010).

Other instrumental learning theorists similarly noted the need for learning partnerships. Lave and Wenger (1991) perceived that students must be 'legitimate peripheral partners' in learning to allow learning to take place. Whilst they acknowledge that the early learner may have less of an active or influential role in learning than the more experienced learner (Lave and Wenger, 1999), the notion that all learners have a role in their learning community is a fundamental component in what they consider 'situated learning'. Situated learning according to Lave and Wenger (1991) is the connection between learning and the unique situation the learning arises in. Rather than considering learning as an abstract act with an unintentional transfer of knowledge, new knowledge is understood in the environment in which it is learned and related to a specific concept or situation. Lave and Wenger (1991) consider learning to be an interactive process whereby the learner gains knowledge from those in the surrounding community and, indeed, can learn as much from those around them as they can in participation in a specific task. Actively engaging with the learning experience, in the learning environment and within the social community of practice, should, according to Lave and Wenger (1999), see learning become a more meaningful exercise. Collins et al (1991) implies that such meaningful learning, gained in the right context, can help link theory to practice which is essential in nursing. However, Lave and Wenger (1999) acknowledge that although increased knowledge leads to increased participation in the social community and thus increased motivation to learn and gain

satisfaction from learning, the opposite could also be true. Therefore, although social learning from others can take place for all, novice learners who cannot perhaps offer full participation in the social learning context may feel demotivated as they are unable to fulfil a partnership role, especially in hierarchical social communities (as exists even in modern healthcare environments).

To help understand hierarchical perceptions in healthcare, it is useful to mention the seminal work of the nurse educationalist Benner and her perception of novice to expert practitioners (Benner, 1984). Benner recognises that novice student nurses are very task oriented and though capable of effectively completing designated 'tasks', they often struggle with prioritising nursing care and providing rationale for clinical care decisions or 'clinical reasoning' (Benner, 1984, Benner et al, 2010). Benner (1984) purported that all nursing theory should recognise that knowledge and skill acquisition in nursing was related to a progressive experiential journey. Benner's conceptual framework details the nurse moving through the stages of novice (little or no experience, such as the student nurse), advanced beginner (limited clinical experience), competent (ability to manage but still rather inflexible to change), proficient (flexible performance, using experience to guide care decisions) and lastly expert (intuitive performance with a deep understanding of field of practice). Whilst Benner (2010) acknowledges that experience can be gleaned in part from simulated skills lab based learning in nursing, the framework clearly shows that even at registration stage as a newly qualified nurse, the new nurse is unlikely to have moved past the novice stage and thus Gardner (2013) suggests that Benner's theory may be more appropriate for post registration nurse education. Indeed, such 'novice' status and lack of independent performance seems in complete disparity with graduate attributes and degree level learning outcomes, which would be fully achieved at pre-registration level to allow for conferment of award graduate status as well as professional registration (NMC, 2010a, NMC, 2015a). Such graduate attributes and degree level performance indicators according to the Scottish Credit Qualification Framework (SCQF Level 9) (SCQF, 2012) can easily be exemplified and applied to nursing, demonstrating a level of competence that seems to surpass the 'little or no experience' demonstrated by a novice according to Benner (1984);

SCQF LEVEL 9 DESCRIPTOR CHARACTERISTIC	EXAMPLE DESCRIPTION OF REQUIRED LEVEL OF COMPETENCE FROM STUDENT NURSE
Knowledge and understanding	A critical understanding of the principles, principle theories, concepts and terminology associated with nursing.
Practice; applied knowledge, skills and understanding	Uses a range of the principal, professional skills, techniques and practices associated with nursing
Generic cognitive skills	Undertakes critical analysis, evaluation and synthesis of concepts relevant to nursing
Communication, ICT and numeracy skills	Uses a range of ICT to enhance and support nursing
Autonomy, accountability and working with others	Exercises autonomy and initiative in activities at a professional level

Table 3.5.5: Scottish Credit and Qualifications Framework Applied to Nursing

Therefore, although student nurses may be arguably considered novices in some aspects of their nursing journey, the value of their experience, albeit limited, should not be overlooked. The importance of experiential learning is well documented and perhaps one of the most influential theorists on experiential learning is Kolb. Kolb's (1984) experiential learning cycle is commonly used in andragogy and in nurse education in particular, due to nursing's significant emphasis on practical experience. According to Kolb (1984), learners move through a cycle of experience; have the experience, make observations on it and reflect upon it, formulate concepts and attempt to generalise from the experience and then test the implications of the learning on new experiences. Whilst elements of other learning theories are implicit within the ethos of the cycle, it has been criticised for somewhat simplifying the learning process (Jarvis, 2010). Even though the active nature of experiential learning is clear, the humanistic element of the adult students' ability to self-evaluate is not apparent and the emotional dimension of learning (as popularised by Rogers) is not obviously considered within Kolb's cyclical approach to learning.

Such humanistic and emotional aspects of learning are very relevant to an emotive profession like nursing. Indeed, traditional empirical research such as that of Pavlov, Piaget and Vygotsky, whilst instrumental in recognising the complex process of cognition and learning, are perhaps not as relevant to the nuances of modern nursing than the more experiential learning theorists such as Rogers, Benner and Kolb (Twomey, 2004, Tilley et al, 2007). However, the complexities of differentiating between learning theories and the lack of exacting evidence on learning and cognition cast doubt upon basing nursing curricula on one specific theoretical stance. Spouse (1998) suggests that curricula and educational research should be based around specific, individual student-centred learning need.

Self-evaluation and self-assessment of learning needs and performance are key components of all higher educational curricula (Lew, Alwis and Schmidt, 2010) and certainly within nursing, the ability to self-evaluate is a crucial aspect of professional self-regulation (Boud, 2007). The recognition of independent learning needs as well as acknowledging limitations of personal and professional ability are key components of self-regulation in nursing (NMC, 2010b, NMC, 2015c, NMC, 2015d). As a self-regulating profession, nurses (including student nurses) must declare themselves of good character and of good health to do the job but must also take responsibility that their requisite knowledge and skills base is up to date and research based to fulfil patient need within their scope of practice. Thus, a learning theory that advocates self-assessment and self-regulation fits well with nursing. Bandura's Social Learning Theory (1991) recognises the importance of self-assessment and self-regulation, has been widely used in andragogy and also recognises the influence of the social environment and personal experience on learning, therefore it seemed an appropriate learning theory for nursing and for this research study.

3.6: Social Learning Theory

Initial exploration of Bandura's early work on social cognitive theory displays similarities to components of other learning theories and ideological stances. Bandura asserted that many behavioural patterns were acquired through 'modelling' which was observing others in the immediate environment and then copying their behaviours in a modified manner and transferring it to new experiences (Bandura, 1997a, Bandura, 1997b). Such learned behaviour can be seen to have roots in behaviourism (Jarvis, 2010), with the transferability of learning

similar to that of cognitivism (Kala et al, 2010), the ‘modelling’ parallel to a cognitive apprenticeship concept and the influential social learning environment recognised as per Vygotsky, Rogers and Lave and Wenger. However, Bandura’s theory is more holistic in its interpretation of learning. According to Bandura (1977), learning is also affected by personal factors. Personal factors that contribute to behaviour such as “self-reward, self-regulation, self-efficacy, self-directedness and self-reflection” are all considered to impact on learned behaviour (Hayden, 2014, p4). Indeed, this relationship was conceptualised by Bandura as ‘reciprocal determinism’ and he noted that all aspects of reciprocal determinism could have a profound effect on the other aspects if subject to change (as exemplified in the diagram below;

Figure 3.6: Health Behaviour Theory

Adapted From: Hayden (2014)

Indeed, this unique association between learning influences, differentiates Bandura’s theoretical concept from other social learning theories yet gives acknowledgement to its positionality in terms of theoretical construct;

Figure 3.6.0: Positionality of Social Learning Theory

Whilst Bandura acknowledges that external and social influences can impact on the ‘locus of control’ of a learning environment, the various factors of reciprocal determinism have a direct effect on the learning experience according to Social Learning Theory; the expectations of the learning experience and/or of the outcome of the learning experience as well as belief about personal ability can affect the motivation to learn. The attention paid to the learning experience is the observational learning or ‘modelling’ and can be influenced by the perceived value of the experience and the arousal associated with the experience, in terms of its emotional connection or distinctiveness. The ability to retain the information has its roots firmly in cognitivism and lastly the ability to reproduce the learning is influenced by behavioural capability or perceived capability and also even reinforcement (as per operant conditioning in behaviourism). The diagram below provides a visual aid to show such reciprocal determinism in Social Learning Theory;

Figure 3.6.0a: Social Learning Theory

When then applied to an example from nurse education; teaching communication in advanced dementia, within a pre-registration nursing curriculum, social learning theory can be seen to be logical and relevant to nursing in its philosophical stance and underpinning learning beliefs;

Figure 3.6.0b: Social Learning Theory Applied to Nurse Education

As can be seen from the diagrammatic representations above, the concept of self-perception is apparent within all aspects of reciprocal determinism. Such self-perception is commonly known as self-efficacy and the awareness of one's self and one's abilities is an essential concept in a self-regulating profession such as nursing (NMC, 2010a, NMC, 2010b).

3.6.1: Self-Efficacy

The measurement of perceptions of ability to deliver, succeed at or attain something is known as self-efficacy (Bandura, 1997a, Zimmerman, 2000). Such awareness of one's knowledge, skills and/or proficiency is inherent in social learning theory as discussed by Bandura (2006) and indeed the concept of self-efficacy has been deemed so influential some view it as a theory in its own right (Hayden, 2014). Whilst self-efficacy is a fundamental construct of social learning theory, it essentially centres upon the learner having enough belief in their own ability to allow themselves to attempt and successfully perform a set task (Bandura, 1997b, Hayden, 2014). Self-efficacy as a concept, is also influenced by the social environment as well as perceived locus of control and self-perception;

Figure 3.6.1: Self Efficacy

Figure 3.6.2: Self Efficacy in Context

Such concept of self-efficacy as well as awareness of personal and professional expectations link well to self-regulation in nursing (as exemplified above). Nurses are expected to have the ability to self-regulate at the point of registration (NMC, 2010c, QAA, 2011) and thereafter throughout their career to meet revalidation criteria (NMC, 2017), thus the notion of self-efficacy as a student nurse is not an obtuse concept. Nurses are often asked to use aspects of self-efficacy for meeting key performance indicators at personal development reviews or as part of their own personal development planning whilst students are rarely (if ever) asked if they have the skills and/or abilities to do the job asked of them. Such self-assessment is an important component of quality assurance in nursing (NMC, 2010c) and as recognised by NMC (2014), students can have a unique and valuable contribution to quality assurance. Therefore, this research study will take the unique approach of asking students about their perceived abilities using a self-efficacy tool. Bandura (2006) suggests that as self-efficacy is multidimensional, any self-efficacy assessment tools should be bespoke to the area of interest or subject matter. This study will therefore seek to answer the research questions by exploring self-efficacy in undergraduate student nurses caring for people with dementia.

3.6.2: Self Efficacy Tools to Measure Dementia Perceptions

There are several tools that measure perceptions towards dementia, however, from review of the literature, there were six tools identified, specific to dementia care that warranted further review to check applicability for use in this research study.

One of the most commonly cited self-efficacy tools in dementia care is the Approaches to Dementia Questionnaire (ADQ) (Lintern and Woods, 1996). The ADQ has been used in a number of research studies and using a 19-item scale, seeks answers on the concepts of hope and personhood. Whilst the tool itself has been rigorously tested for validity and reliability and has been used in a number of research studies, the questions only provide insight into the respondents' perceptions towards dementia and understanding of dementia related issues. The ADQ offers no scope to gain understanding of perceptions of ability or confidence in own care giving practice, which is sought from the previously cited research aims.

A questionnaire that does measure sense of competence though, is the Sense of Competence in Dementia Care Staff (SCIDS) Scale (Spector, Orrell, Schepers et al, 2012). Hypothesising that sense of competence should increase with training and knowledge gain, the SCIDS is a 17-item questionnaire focusing on the subscales of professionalism, relationships, challenges to care and personhood. As it measures sense of competence, it initially seemed applicable to student nurses, however, some aspects of the questions are out-with the learning remit of students, such as changing work patterns and risk management and there are no indicators of perceptions of knowledge and ability.

A tool to measure such knowledge was developed by Annear, Eccleston, McInerney et al (2016), in the Dementia Knowledge Assessment Scale (DKAS). The 27-item DKAS was proven to be a valid and reliable measure of dementia knowledge, in a large study (n=3649) which used the scale to measure knowledge pre and post learning intervention. Despite the participants being a diverse group of health professionals and thus applicability of the scale to student nurses apparent, the scale only sought measurement of knowledge gain in dementia specifics such as pathophysiology as opposed to perceived care giving ability.

Similar in terms of knowledge is the Alzheimer's Disease Knowledge Scale (Carpenter, Balsis, Otilingam et al (2009). Whilst specifically recognised as appropriate for students, the 30-item questionnaire makes statements about dementia and respondents are invited to answer the questions by indicating whether the responses are true or false. As the responses mostly relate to patient assessment and symptom specific problems, this again would not give any insight into personal perceptions of ability.

Personal perceptions were however sought by the Staff Experience of Working with Demented Residents Questionnaire (Astrom, Nilsson, Norberg et al, 1991). Although the 21-item questionnaire is perception related, the questions relate to job satisfaction and not to perceptions of ability. The questionnaire was used effectively in a study by Surr, Smith, Crossland et al (2016) to measure the impact of dementia training and thus could have applicability to this study but this previous use was in conjunction with the Approaches to Dementia Questionnaire, hence further highlighting the limitations of the staff experience questionnaire to measure knowledge impact on its own merit.

Another tool considered that has a broader scope, considering both attitudes and knowledge is the Dementia Attitudes Scale (O'Connor and McFadden, 2010). Tested with a cohort of students and healthcare professionals, psychometric testing resulted in a 20-item validated questionnaire seeking answers to questions across cognitive, affective and behavioural domains. Although this would have provided some valuable insight, the tool offers no ability to gain any insight into perceptions of ability to apply knowledge and skills and thus does not fully meet with the desire to underpin the study with the self-efficacy concept of perceived ability to deliver dementia care.

Lastly, a tool that did specifically seek to measure self-efficacy is the Inventory of Geriatric Nursing Self-Efficacy (MacKenzie and Peragine, 2003). In a study examining (n=41) nurses perceptions of care giving to residents of dementia, the importance of self-efficacy was recognised as well as the dearth of research using self-efficacy approaches to measure perceptions of care delivery. Nonetheless, the study was specifically aimed at trained staff at risk of burnout and as such, some aspects of the inventory were not applicable to student nurses.

Thus, in the absence of specific self-efficacy tools to measure dementia perceptions that are appropriate to student nurses and meet the aims of this research, it was logical to consider other measures of self-efficacy that could be applied to dementia care and this study.

3.6.3: Other Measures of Self Efficacy

Many studies purport to use the concept of self-efficacy but are often testing an intervention or specific educational training session (Banks, Waugh, Henderson et al, 2014). An example of this is a study specifically measuring self-efficacy in meeting the needs of clients with dementia which was carried out by Jordan and Church (2013). A cohort of (n=39) undergraduate student nurses took part in a study which sought to measure self-efficacy in meeting the needs of people with dementia in a nursing home. Students took part in a psychosocial activity with the residents and were asked to complete a self-efficacy questionnaire upon completion of the activity. However, this was a locally generated questionnaire and thus not fully subject to psychometric testing for validity and reliability.

In contrast, the Nursing Student Self-Efficacy Scale (Stump, Husman and Brem, 2012) was tested with (n=421) nursing students to gain understanding of their perceived ability to deliver care to critically ill patients and thus to guide curricular content to ensure safety in clinical practice. Initial tests for validity and reliability were proven, however, it was recognised by the authors that further testing of the sub themes of the tool was required prior to widespread use.

Thus, a tool that had been used widely and developed to be used in different contexts was sought. The Alcohol and Alcohol Problems Perceptions Questionnaire (AAPPQ) (Shaw et al, 1978, Cartwright, 1980a, Gorman and Cartwright, 1991, Cartwright and Gorman, 1993) is a self-efficacy tool that has been extensively used to measure perceptions towards alcohol and ability to deliver care to people with alcohol problems. Furthermore, it has also been successfully validated for use in other areas of nursing and social care practice such as drugs, mental health and medication concordance amongst others (Lauder, Reynolds, Reilly et al, 2000, Watson, McLaren and Kerr, 2006, Byrne, Willis, Deane et al, 2010).

The AAPPQ focuses on the central themes of Role Adequacy (having the correct knowledge and skills to deliver care), Role Legitimacy (being legitimately placed to deliver the care) and Role Support (support required to deliver care) and thus fits extremely well with care delivery in nursing. As initially developed as part of the Maudsley Alcohol Pilot Project (MAPP) which will be further discussed in Chapter Five, the AAPPQ, works upon the hypothesis that training, experience and knowledge gain should have a positive effect on Role Adequacy and Role Legitimacy, Role Support is influenced by Role Security and Role Security influences Therapeutic Commitment (Cartwright, 1980b).

Indeed, such influence of experience fits well with Social Learning Theory as the underpinning theoretical concept of this study and also with dementia care in practice. Hence, the Alcohol and Alcohol Problems Perceptions Questionnaire will be adapted, psychometrically tested and revalidated to become the Dementia and Dementia Care Perceptions Questionnaire (DDCPQ) and accordingly forms the final aim of this research study;

- To evaluate the psychometric properties of a self-efficacy tool designed to measure attitudes, experiences and perceptions of dementia care in undergraduate student nurses.

3.7: Summary

This chapter provided a critical review of student nurses' perceptions of dementia care and dementia care delivery. Providing context, there was critique of undergraduate pre-registration nursing curricula in the United Kingdom, reflecting on the professional and educational standards of requirement as well as key policy drivers for nursing education and dementia care delivery. Thereafter, the learning theories applicable to the nursing profession were critically appraised, introducing social learning theory as the underpinning theoretical framework for this study and the concept of self-efficacy as a measure of student perception of success. Finally and most importantly, this literature review assisted in the generation of the following research questions;

- What are student nurses' perceptions of dementia care and their role in care delivery?
- Does theory, skills training and clinical experience influence undergraduate student nurse's approach to dementia care delivery?
- In what manner are dementia training policy directives reflected in undergraduate student nurses knowledge, skills and readiness for nursing practice?
- Can a self-efficacy tool be used to measure attitudes, experiences and perceptions of dementia care in undergraduate student nurses?

Thus, to answer these questions, this study aims;

- To explore undergraduate student nurse perceptions of dementia care and their role in care delivery.

- To examine the influence of theory, skills training and clinical experience on approach to dementia care delivery amongst undergraduate student nurses.
- To appraise how dementia training policy directives for pre-registration nurse education are reflected in undergraduate student nurse's knowledge, skills and readiness for nursing practice.
- To evaluate the psychometric properties of a self-efficacy tool designed to measure attitudes, experiences and perceptions of dementia care in undergraduate student nurses.

To achieve such aims, the research will be carried out at the largest undergraduate nursing educational provider in Scotland; The University of the West of Scotland (UWS) and will seek to follow the September 2014 cohort of nursing students through their undergraduate programme.

Following identification of these clear research aims and a research study location, it is essential to select an appropriate research methodology that will facilitate achievement of these aims. Therefore, the following chapter will focus on research methodology, detailing the explicit decision making process to ensure a suitable and rigorous methodological research design.

Chapter Four: Methodology

The systematic literature review assisted in the generation of the aforementioned research questions and it is now imperative that the research questions inform the research design, to facilitate the generation of new knowledge (Bryman, 2016, Murray, 2011, Walshaw, 2012). The complex integration of a conceptualised research project and the need to demonstrate rigorous application in research design, commences with the selection of an appropriate methodology to underpin the research (Griffiths, 2009, Thomas, 2009, Strudsholm et al, 2016). Indeed, the choice of an appropriate research methodology is recognised as one of the most critical components of any successful research project (Parahoo, 2014) and successful integration of relevant research questions with a complementary methodological underpinning, enhance the validity and reliability of research and facilitate achievement of the overall research aims (Bryman, 2016, Sturudsholm et al 2016).

To ensure transparency and facilitate replicability in research, it is advocated that the research design provides a framework to substantiate the decisions made throughout the research journey (Thomas, 2009, Swanbourne, 2010). Therefore, this chapter will justify the ontological and epistemological perspective of this research study and provide rationale for the use of a concurrent triangulation mixed methods approach. Case study as a research design will be critiqued and the longitudinal nature of the study appraised. Ethical considerations will be detailed and justification provided for the sampling strategy and data collection techniques.

4.0: Ontological and Epistemological Perspective

Ontology is the nature of social inquiry or an individual's position in reality (Grix, 2010, Flick, 2018); put simply it could be looked upon as how one views the world around oneself. Indeed, many have prior assumptions or 'ontological perspectives' that are implicitly part of their own, personal consciousness, reality and understanding of life (Walshaw, 2012). However, as suggested by Grix (2010) for true scholarly engagement, one must recognise and understand the dichotomy of differing ontological perspectives and their relevance to research and learning. If a researcher understands this significance of different world views or ontological perceptions,

it can help not only the construction of the research study but also the researcher's ability to encapsulate original findings in the most appropriate manner. Whilst individuals undoubtedly espouse their own philosophical ideals and this may indeed impact on initial epistemological choice (Cresswell, 2016), it is essential that epistemological approach is appropriate to investigate the reality of the subject under study (Oliver, 2010, Walshaw, 2012). Therefore, to ensure that the epistemological orientation of this study was appropriate to the choice of research area (dementia care) and to facilitate answers to the already defined research questions, it was essential to consider whether the ontological orientation was objectivist or constructivist in nature (Cresswell, 2016, Oliver, 2010). According to Bryman (2016), objectivism takes the position that social occurrences are independent, organised and uninfluenced by external factors. Objectivist research is deductive and logical and is primarily concerned with the testing of theory. In direct contrast, constructivism takes the position that social occurrences are fluid and change according to the social phenomena they are experienced within (Cresswell, 2016, Bryman, 2016). Constructivist research is inductive and seeks to generate new knowledge or theories, rather than testing existing theories. Epistemologically, objectivism is associated with a positivist orientation and constructivism associated with an interpretivist orientation.

4.1: Positivism

Positivism lends itself to the quantitative side of scientific enquiry (Topping, 2006, Macnee and McCabe, 2008, Thomas 2009). Positivist research takes an ordered approach to data collection and analysis and using an empirical, logical and deductive process, seeks to test theory and hypotheses through experimental examination of the relationship between defined variables. This data can then be statistically analysed and ultimately seeks to ensure standardisation in design so that results can be objective, replicable and generalizable. Such verifiable research design as well as the establishment of scientific fact is a key advantage of the quantitative approach and provides the quality assurance that many scientists seek (Flick, 2018, Walshaw, 2012). Furthermore, quantitative experiments allow for the sampling of large numbers of participants in a short space of time.

Given the large number of nursing students at the University of the West of Scotland and the notion that study results could be generalizable and thus applicable to the wider student nursing

population, it was recognised that a quantitative approach to this research study could generate not only new knowledge within nursing education but ultimately result in the improvement of nursing care and thus patient care. Such desire to improve patient care, a fundamental reason that most people enter the nursing profession, certainly appealed, and indeed, the process of accurate measuring and deduction of fact fits well within nursing research as nursing practice exists within very defined parameters and calls for measurement and numerical calculation on a daily basis (Griffiths, 2009).

Although quantitative research design can seem simplistic due to its formal and logical process of deducing findings, there are many types of quantitative design (Bell, 2005, Topping, 2006). Macnee and McCabe (2008) suggest that when considering quantitative methodology; asking questions of timing, control and function can help assist the researcher to the most appropriate study design. Thus, for this study, firstly, the factor of timing was considered. Data was sought as the students progressed through their undergraduate nursing programme, therefore, a cross-sectional design was immediately ruled out as it only collects data at one specific point in time. Secondly, it was clear that data was not to be collected retrospectively (after the learning experience) but instead as the learning occurred throughout the programme, therefore the research design would be prospective. As also recognised by Macnee and McCabe (2008), any study that collects data prospectively is also longitudinal in nature. The longitudinal nature of this study will be discussed further later on in this chapter.

Thereafter, the element of control was considered. Control in data collection is ensured by the reliability and validity of the data collection tool and the consistency of the measurement process. Whilst the data collection tool was proven to be valid and reliable (as will be discussed in Chapter Five), it must be acknowledged that any external factors can negatively affect measured variables, skewing results. Therefore, exerting maximal levels of control in a study seeks to minimise the risk of error of measurement, thus maximising validity and reliability. Control in this research study was an important factor of the study design and as suggested by Macnee and McCabe (2008), greater control over extraneous factors can also be achieved by exacting inclusion and exclusion criteria (see appendix 2), as well as random sampling. Whilst every UWS nursing student in the September 2014 cohort at Dumfries, Paisley and Ayr campuses, were given the chance to participate (random sampling), it could be argued that because Hamilton students were not asked to participate (to avoid bias as researcher's base

campus) this therefore is not true random sampling as Hamilton students were purposively excluded. However, the main aspect of this study that was not in keeping with true experimental design was the lack of a control group; empirical, experimental research always has a control group (Topping, 2006). Indeed, whilst experimental designs have little problem with internal validity and accuracy due to such control measures, it is recognised that such exacting control may yield little generalisability to nursing research due to the nature of the variability of experience in nursing (Macnee and McCabe, 2008). Therefore, the notion of the study as a quasi-experimental study (recognised to be more applicable to 'real world situations') was then considered. A quasi experimental study lacks either a control group or random assignment (Thomas, 2009) and for this reason its validity as a research design is viewed by some as inferior to true experimental design (Topping, 2006, Nelson, Dumville and Torgerson, 2006). As this study had no control group and the sampling was not truly random, the quasi experimental design was also decided as inappropriate. Thus, lastly, the notion of the research study as a descriptive correlational study was considered, as relationships between different variables and changes over time will be analysed (which will be further discussed in the next chapter). Furthermore, as recognised by Macnee and McCabe (2008), control measures are not as stringent as in experimental design and correlational studies can be flexible considering timing and function. Also, firmly sitting in the positivist, quantitative realm; one of the aims of this study is to evaluate the psychometric properties of a new self-efficacy tool (DDCPQ). Therefore, to help in categorisation of decisions, the table below helps demonstrate the quantitative decision-making trajectory;

Design Feature	Study Characteristic	Relevance to this Study
Time of Data Collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data collection at points throughout undergraduate programme 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cannot be cross-sectional (one point in time) • Is prospective (as changes occur) • Is longitudinal (from induction of programme to end of year 3 at point of registration)
Measurement and Control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No control group • Purposive sampling • Measurement control • Instrument validity and reliability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cannot be experimental as no control group • Purposeful sampling and no control group rules out quasi experimental also
Function of Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To examine relationship of variables • To explore changes over time • To test a data collection tool (DDCPQ) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Descriptive Correlational Study most appropriate

Table 4.1: Quantitative Decision Making

Indeed, a quantitative methodological underpinning such as a descriptive correlational design, would have been adequate to answer the research questions and evaluate the DDCPQ, however, the notion that a quantitative study could generate facts, figures and hypotheses that could potentially leave unanswered questions was identified. Flick (2018) acknowledges that sometimes in quantitative research, it is difficult to put a deeper context to meaningful data and in this study, with the threat of perhaps a more superficial understanding of the student nurse experience, an interpretivist approach also had to be considered.

4.2: Interpretivism

Interpretivism is in direct contrast to positivism. It sits within the qualitative research paradigm and posits that subjects can be subjectively influenced by other people and their environment in an evolving and developmental manner. Interpretivism is inductive rather than deductive and seeks to generate theory and new knowledge by the in-depth examination of subjects in their own social world (Bryman, 2016, Flick, 2018). Interpretivism is flexible and reactive and seeks to bring meaning to events, behaviours and experiences (Walshaw, 2012). Such fluidity in design is reflected in the less constrained approach to the structure of the qualitative research study. For example, in grounded theory a literature review is not carried out initially as the purpose is to develop a theory or hypothesis from the inductive observations of people's actions and reactions towards a phenomena or stimuli within a certain context. In phenomenology, the researcher reports the 'lived experiences' of a small number of participants as they have lived through 'the phenomena' under study. This is often achieved by carrying out unstructured or semi structured interviews and observations, followed by intensive thematic analysis. Ethnographic qualitative research sees the researcher studying a group of people in their natural setting and combines many data collection methods in an evolving manner. Lastly, case studies are an in-depth research design whereby a 'case' (which can be a very small group of people) are studied in a detailed manner, again using a variety of data collection techniques. Such intensive analysis and detailed complexity of the presentation of data found sets qualitative research apart from its measurable and rigid quantitative counterpart. Indeed, an interpretivist qualitative approach to this study would certainly provide a greater depth of rich data when considering the research study aims surrounding student nurse perceptions, as well as their knowledge, skills and readiness for care delivery. To put these considerations in perspective, it can be useful to similarly tabulate the qualitative methodological decision-making trajectory for this study;

Qualitative Design	Design Characteristics	Relevance to this Study
Grounded Theory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Seeks to generate an abstract or original theory after detailed collection, comparison, coding and categorisation of data. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Theory already exists in relation to how nursing students learn. Grounded theory is more useful when little is known about a phenomenon.
Ethnography	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Studies a culture or group in their natural setting over a long period of time. Data collection involves the researcher becoming immersed in the culture and being able to capture the 'emic' viewpoint. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Whilst the researcher is immersed in the nursing education setting in University, an ethnographic study would also involve immersion in clinical practice due to the 50/50 theory practice split. This would prove impractical to execute.
Phenomenology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Seeks to understand the 'lived experience' of those who have lived through the phenomena under study. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Whilst a phenomenological approach would give a sense of how the students feel as they move through their undergraduate training programme, it relies on the participants being able to articulate such feelings which may be problematic, especially at the beginning of the programme.
Case Study	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> An in-depth examination of a 'case' which can be a group, a programme, an event. Data collection takes various forms and is flexible and holistic. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Insider knowledge of the context of the case is useful to help maximise data collection and also to transfer the knowledge gain beyond the case under study. This approach would be the most appropriate.

Table 4.2: Qualitative Decision Making

As can be seen from the above table, in terms of qualitative research design, the case study approach is aligned most appropriately with this research study. However, the previous alignment of the quantitative descriptive correlational study and the control element of testing the DDCPQ sit firmly within a quantitative paradigm. Such recognition of the benefits of both quantitative and qualitative approaches to research are acknowledged by many (Thomas, 2009,

Walshaw, 2012, Bazeley, 2018). Indeed, Cresswell (2016) suggests that rather than considering positivism and interpretivism as distinct worldviews, viewing them as complementary but differing components of the research continuum exemplifies the distinct benefit of each approach. Taking such a view helps to conceptualise the unique benefit of a mixed methods research design and thus, a mixed method case study design was considered.

4.3: Mixed Methods Research Design

As previously exemplified, quantitative methodology (even in its descriptive sense) imposes control over sampling and measuring and thus is empirically accurate, objective, measurable and generalizable. However, quantitative research can be said to lose the individuality of its participants as well as being unable to capture diverse and rich data (Griffiths, 2009, Flick, 2018). Conversely, the more qualitative approaches, whilst deemed by some researchers as somewhat 'uncontrollable', can capture both the individuality of the participant and the richness of real world understanding (Thomas, 2009, Walshaw, 2012, Strudsholm et al, 2016). Therefore, to gain an in-depth and rich knowledge and understanding of the student nurse experience of dementia care, whilst taking cognisance of the large numbers of student nurses at UWS, a mixed methods design seemed highly appropriate.

Although mixed methods research is a more modern research approach, it is now increasingly used to provide a wider understanding of subjects under study (Tritter, 2007) and is a common design in healthcare research (Griffiths, 2009, Holloway and Wheeler, 2010, Fawcett, 2015). It is also acknowledged that mixed methods research has the greatest congruence with nursing practice due to the multifaceted complexity of health care (Ostlund, Kidd, Wengstrom et al, 2010). Further, as exemplified by Fawcett (2015), the notion of mixed method research as a metaphorical patient whereby the nurse collects quantitative health information (clinical observations), as well as qualitative health information (how the patient reports their feelings) sits well with this study as its focus is on the ability of student nurses to deliver patient care.

Although such integration of diverse data can be deemed as creating a more complex research design, mixed methods can be defined quite simply as the use of both quantitative and

qualitative data within a single study (Johnson, Onwuegbuzie and Turner, 2007, Gray 2014, Bryman, 2016). Mixed methods can be the use of differing research paradigms or the collaboration of differing methods of data collection that normally sit within contrasting ontological positionalities (Strudsholm et al, 2016). Such combination of methodological underpinning provides the researcher with the opportunity to challenge existing epistemological viewpoints and theoretical perceptions through the integration of typically opposing quantitative and qualitative information. As recognised by Ostlund et al (2010), the mixed method researcher should appreciate distinct ontological and epistemological perspectives and use the strengths of both designs to provide a high level of rigour to the mixed method research study.

Such rigour is essential as the complexity of research design and implementation of research has increased greatly in recent years (Murray, 2011, Tight, 2017). Whilst rigour, reliability and validity have always been essential in research (Strudsholm et al, 2016), there has never been such a challenging need to produce credible research that has perceived benefits to diverse audiences with disparate expertise (Bazeley, 2018). Mixed methods can help demonstrate such rigorous quality as long as there is congruence in methodological decision making and research design (Strudsholm et al, 2016). Mixed method designs vary upon the rationale behind choice of underpinning theoretical framework, timing of data collection, priority of methods and point of integration of data and analysis (Creswell, Klassen, Plano Clark et al, 2010, Klassen, Creswell, Plano Clark et al, 2012). Thus, there is an utmost need to provide clear order to integration and analysis, with transparency through an explicit decision-making process (Ostlund et al, 2010). Such congruence of approach, transparency and trustworthiness can be exemplified by tabulating the decision-making trajectory for the use of mixed methods in relation to this research study;

Mixed Methods Design Approach	Approach Characteristics	Relevance for this Study
Sequential Explanatory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quantitative data collected and analysed first. Results used to inform qualitative stage. Qualitative results help understand unexpected results in quantitative data. Primarily favours quantitative data. 	<p>No –</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quantitative data collected just before qualitative and analysis of both thereafter. Quantitative data may inform later qualitative data collections.
Sequential Exploratory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Qualitative data collected and analysed first. Extensive qualitative data used to give insight into phenomenon and to develop a testable hypothesis. Quantitative data then sought to examine the phenomenon in a more generalizable manner. 	<p>No –</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data collection timings as above. No hypothesis.
<p>Concurrent Triangulation</p> <p>✓</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quantitative and qualitative phases conducted at the same time. Equal weight given to both quantitative and qualitative data. Results of both interpreted concurrently to determine comparability in data between approaches. Integration of results can be difficult if contraindications occur – additional data collection may be required. 	<p>Yes –</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Concurrent data collection and analysis. Both aspects of study have potential to yield new learning. Longitudinal nature should help with integration of results.

Table 4.3: Mixed Methods Decision Making

For the purposes of this study, concurrent method triangulation will be used to combine both quantitative and qualitative research paradigms to facilitate a deeper understanding of the case under study. This use of method triangulation is recognised by Parahoo (2006) to facilitate the complementary integration of perhaps conceptually differing research approaches within an individual research study. Triangulation is the combination of findings to support one another and such corroboration can further validate results and provide comprehensive and complete 'knowing' (Thomas, 2009, Bryman, 2016), especially useful in nursing related studies due to the complexity of health care research (Ostlund et al, 2010). Indeed, if triangulation is ineffective, a mixed methods study is just two sets of independent results (as would be achieved by singular quantitative and singular qualitative studies). True triangulation seeks corroboration between findings or describes the use of more than one method to gain a deeper understanding of the phenomena under study (O'Cathain, Murphy and Nicoll, 2008). As also acknowledged by O'Cathain et al (2008) is the valuable and more unique aspect of a mixed method study that collects quantitative and qualitative data from the same cases. This study, as will be described further in this chapter, has the benefit of this unique design and can thus study the case in greater detail. Whilst both the quantitative and qualitative paradigms would have been both relevant and applicable to this study (as exemplified in the previous tables), the use of mixed methods, will not only answer the aforementioned research questions, but will also provide the complex understanding and multiple perceptions of the student nurses in greater depth of detail. Such detail is also further exemplified by the longitudinal nature of this study.

4.4: Longitudinal Study

The complexity of pre-registration nursing education was exemplified in Chapter Three of this thesis, when considering the educational and professional standards of requirement for award graduate as well as nursing registrant status. Indeed, the undergraduate programme of at least 3 years /4600 hours in length with a 50/50 theory practice split (NMC, 2010a) exemplifies the rigorous and multifaceted learning that takes place for student nurses. Thus, a research study that seeks the views of a sample of this population at one point in time would not provide clear data on the research aim 'To examine the influence of theory, skills training and clinical experience on approach to dementia care delivery', as the timing of where learning (or other influence) took place may be ambiguous due to the variability of learning opportunities on the undergraduate programme.

The collection of data over a period of time is a critical element of a longitudinal study according to Bazely (2018). Furthermore, if a longitudinal study is desired, sampling the same research participants over time is essential, otherwise the study is merely a repeated cross-sectional study and will not measure the causal influences of time as a variable (Walshaw, 2012, Bazely, 2018). As acknowledged by Bryman (2016), longitudinal studies can either be panel studies (a random selection of participants) or cohort studies (a selected cohort of people who share the same characteristic). In this case, the September 2014 cohort of undergraduate student nurses provided the same characteristic of commencing an undergraduate pre-registration nursing programme within the University of the West of Scotland. To measure the changes in the student's perceptions of their ability to deliver dementia care over the time of their undergraduate programme, data had to be collected from the commencement of their training programme through to the point of registration at the end of year 3. Undoubtedly, a longitudinal study of 3-year duration will encounter the well documented problem of most longitudinal studies; attrition of participants (Topping, 2010, Bazeley, 2018), thus sampling must seek strategies to minimise such attrition as data can be skewed if sample sizes become too small (Bryman, 2016). Such sampling strategies will be discussed later in in this chapter.

As well as data skewing, longitudinal studies can become quite unmanageable if data collection is not meticulously planned (Thomas, 2009, Cresswell, 2016, Bryman, 2016). If vast amounts of data are collected with no plan for analytical management, the researcher can become overwhelmed and struggle to manage the research study. Bazeley (2018) acknowledges the data management challenge of longitudinal studies and advocates the need for careful planning and transparency of data collection timings and ongoing analysis. Thus, for this study the data collection and analysis timings for both quantitative and qualitative were planned in advance;

Figure 4.4: Longitudinal Design Plan

The longitudinal nature of the study is explicit from the diagram above, however, as acknowledged by Bryman (2016) some studies are open to criticism when they present qualitative components within a cross sectional or longitudinal study more suited to quantitative research. Whilst some studies aim to present this as ‘case evidence’ and cite an underpinning case study methodology, it is advised that to truly justify a case study methodology, the case itself must be the epitome of interest for the study (Swanborn, 2010, Bryman, 2016, Thomas, 2016). In this research study, ‘the case’ (September 2014 cohort of student nurses at the University of the West of Scotland) are at the centre of the study and each study aim (as identified in Chapter Three) is directly student related and thus defines this research study as a “Case Study”.

4.5: Case Study Methodology

Case study research was historically a preliminary research method used mainly for pilot studies and initial investigative stages of larger studies. It was viewed by some as methodologically flawed due to the nature of it examining one singular group at any one particular point in time (albeit in an in-depth, detailed manner). One of the other traditionally negative connotations of case study methodology was the inability to generalise findings on the basis of a single case.

Whilst this lack of generalisability has also been said of other types of qualitative research with small numbers of participants, favoured in methodologies such as ethnography and hermeneutic phenomenology, it is widely recognised that the inherent 'deepness' of such intensive research study is as valuable as statistically relevant and thus generalizable large scale quantitative studies (Swanborn, 2010, Thomas, 2016). Whilst the longitudinal and mixed method approach to this particular research study counters some of these negative associations, overall the study also aims to achieve what Klassen et al (2012) state is 'meta-inference'; triangulation of a complete set of data (whether complementary or contradictory) to gain new knowledge. Indeed, if the methodology is appropriate to the phenomena under study and the environment within which the phenomena exists, then the knowledge gain can be of the utmost value, whether in the hard, scientific sense, in the softer social science sense, or in the case of this study; both.

Case study research can be particularly useful when examining learning and the learning process. Whilst the multifaceted approach of nursing education has already been exemplified (from roots in seemingly disparate behaviourism to the more reflexive social learning context), Flyvbjerg (2006) suggests that expertise in a particular area (in this case dementia care) can only be achieved by making the learner a virtuous practitioner in their own right. In other words, the examination of the learner's experience in the real-world context helps the learner become a skilled, independent practitioner and understanding the nuances of the learner's reality, in turn, helps the researcher articulate the learned knowledge in a meaningful way.

Such meaningful understanding of both the learning process for student nurses as well as the reality of clinical experience in nursing education is essential to ensure nurse educators can assist student nurses to be fully prepared to deliver dementia care and to become autonomous practitioners upon registration as a staff nurse (NMC, 2008, WHO, 2009, NMC, 2010a, Scottish Government, 2011a). To ensure that this research study can provide such meaningful understanding by using an underpinning case study methodology, it is essential to firstly define what exactly a case study is and the decision-making trajectory surrounding the case study approach.

4.5.1: Defining the Case Study

Whilst a case study is epitomised by many as the in-depth study of a particular 'case' (Clarke and Reed, 2006, Walshaw, 2012, Tight, 2017), what constitutes a 'case' and what a case study actually is, is the subject of much debate in the literature (Gibbert et al, 2008, Yazan, 2015, Tight, 2017). 'Case studies' in the medical sense can be dated back to the last century and many well-known psychologists such as Piaget and Freud famously used 'case studies' to exemplify their theories. However, when seeking a definitive definition of a case study in relation to research design, it was apparent that the most well-known activists of case study research were Robert Stake, Sharan Merriam and Robert Yin (Yazan, 2015).

Focusing on the notion that "a case is a noun, a thing, an entity" (Stake, 2006; p1), Stake advocates that a researcher's first priority is to define and understand the case under study. Stake views a case study as the complex multifaceted study of a case, seeking to understand the dynamics of the case within a real-time context (Stake, 2006, Tight, 2017). This desired complexity of understanding is echoed in the definition of a case study according to Merriam (1998; p27) who further classifies that a case must be limited or bound; "if the phenomenon you are interested in studying is not intrinsically bounded, it is not a case". In other words, if there is a limit to those involved and you can categorise them as a unit (eg. in this case, a cohort of student nurses), then they are a case. This view is echoed in Merriam and Tisdall (2016) who define a case as a detailed description and analysis of a delimited system. Conversely, Yin (2018; p16) makes no precedence of the need for a bounded case and in fact states that "boundaries between phenomenon and context may not be clearly evident". Whilst Yin (2018; p16) demonstrates some similarities in perspective, considering case study as investigation of a case "in-depth and within its real world context", Yin (2018) also discusses case study as a method of "empirical inquiry", wording usually more suited to scientific quantitative research. Such ambiguity of definition draws parallels with the diversity of how case studies are applied to real life research (Swanborn, 2010, Tight, 2016, Bryman, 2016). Yazan (2015) recognises that case study is a controversial methodology due to the paucity of explicit, iterative processes on the 'how to' design the study within acceptable parameters. Therefore, to ensure transparency in decision making, it is useful to consider the nuances of the most common case study designs to assist in decision making for this research study.

4.5.2: Case Study Design

According to Walshaw (2012) case studies have no universally defined structure. Whilst the focus is undoubtedly on the case according to Merriam (1998) and Yin (2018), Stake (1995) advises that the focus can be on the case (an intrinsic case study) or on a specific issue (an instrumental case study). Case studies are purported by Swanborn (2010) to be exclusively qualitative methods of enquiry, a view echoed by many more traditional case study theorists (Stake, 2006, Merriam and Tisdell, 2016). This qualitative nature of such enquiry led to the acknowledgement by Stake (2006) that even the most meticulous case study will not fully answer all the research questions, a view contested by the more forward-thinking advocates of case study methodology such as Thomas (2016) who asserts that research enquiry in the case study sense can be contemporary, robust and insightful, without keeping to traditional boundaries of scientific or social enquiry. Indeed, this more contemporary notion of a case study as flexible, evolving and holistic, fits well within healthcare research and perhaps draws parallels with the well-known use of case studies to help clinical decision making in real world situations (Clarke and Reed, 2006). Such context dependent data collection in case study design is exemplified by Gibbert et al (2008) in acknowledging that quantitative data in case studies is ideally placed to complement the more traditional qualitative data. However, whilst the more modern case study approach can be flexible, to ensure rigour, the researcher must ensure the design of the case study is systematic and transparent (Yin, 2018). In keeping with the previously tabulated approach to transparent decision making throughout this chapter, it is useful to consider the decision making behind the underpinning case study design;

Theoretical Underpinning	Design Features	Applicability to this Study
Case Study According to Merriam	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Constructivist in orientation. • Qualitative as doesn't view reality to be objective. • Flexible approach to what is a 'case'. • Case must be bounded by time. 	No - Whilst the September 2014 'case' is bounded by time, this approach doesn't fit with the objective quantitative data sought by the DDCPQ.
Case Study According to Stake	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Constructivist in orientation. • Qualitative. • Holistic and flexible. • Not applicable to advanced planning. 	No – The longitudinal nature of this study requires advanced planning or would potentially become unmanageable.
Case Study According to Yin ✓	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not specific on orientation although has tendencies that are both quantitative and qualitative and advises case studies can be either or both. • Structured approach with clear design strategy from outset. • Clear decision-making trajectory advised. • Uses multiple sources of evidence. • Favours triangulation of data. 	Yes - Fits well with mixed method design of this study and with the specific planned data collection and analysis timings.

Table 4.5.2: Case Study Design

As can be seen from the above table, Robert Yin's approach to case study design sits more appropriately with this research study. Therefore, in keeping with a 'Yinian' approach, the importance of rigour must be explicitly apparent.

4.5.3: Ensuring Rigour in Case Study Design

According to Gibbert (2008) and Yin (2018) certain ‘tactics’ should be employed at the design point of the case study as well as throughout its duration. The researcher must consider construct validity, internal validity, external validity and reliability. Whilst these aspects will be further discussed in subsequent chapters, making a plan to address each ‘tactic’ is advised by Yin (2018) and has been applied to this study;

Test of Rigour	Tactic Employed	Component of Thesis that Addresses Tactic
Construct Validity	Multiple Sources of Evidence (qualitative and qualitative).	Chapter 5 – quantitative data collection tool and qualitative data rigour will be fully critiqued.
	Pilot study.	Pilot study carried out prior to data collection commencement.
	Planned chain of data collection timings.	Chapter 4 - See data collection timings diagram.
	Draft case study report read by subject expert.	As part of PhD supervision, have subject expert on for ongoing advice and reviewing.
Internal Validity	Triangulation of quantitative and qualitative data (whether confirmatory or contradictory).	Chapters 6 and 7 – presentation of results, data analysis and discussion chapters.
	Quantitative and qualitative data collected from the same participants over a period of 3 years.	Chapters 6 and 7 – presentation of results, data analysis and discussion chapters.

External Validity	Longitudinal design rationale for single case study and underpinned by Yin (2018) approach to case study design.	Chapter 4 – see longitudinal data collection timings diagram.
	Generalisability not normally associated with case studies addressed with mixed method nature of study and wording of research questions to reflect mixed method design.	Chapter 3 – see research questions.
Reliability	Case study protocol followed according to Yin (2018).	Explicit design making trajectory throughout study to ensure replicability.

Table 4.5.3: Case Study Rigour

Whilst this formality of case study planning and design as exemplified in the above table are not usually seen in traditional case studies, it is recognised by Yin (2018) that as well as enhancing the case study’s validity and reliability, it can assist in making the case study easier to execute. This is especially important when conducting a longitudinal mixed methods study as both the research questions and thus subsequent data analysis can be more complex. Moreover, Yin (2018) also advocates the benefits of advance planning to ensure research ethics and approved standards are met and maintained throughout the research study. Walshaw (2012) suggests that research ethics should be considered and ethical approval sought after the research design has been planned but prior to the commencement of data collection.

4.6: Ethical Considerations

Research ethics and integrity should be considered at all parts of the research journey (Murray, 2011, Walshaw, 2012). In keeping with the transparent decision-making trajectory exemplified when considering the design of this research study, the ethical implications of each stage were systematically considered. According to Bryman (2016) all research should ensure that research participants are unharmed (physically, emotionally or psychologically), should ensure that consent is informed, privacy is maintained and that there are no means of deception through transparency of information giving. In nursing, the ethical principles of beneficence (to do good),

non-maleficence (to do no harm), autonomy (respect of rights, dignity and choices) and justice (fairness) are epitomised in The Code (NMC, 2015c, NMC, 2018f) to ensure integral standards of professional practice. These ethical standpoints are also essential to ensure integrity in research and thus all research studies are subject to ethical approval.

4.6.1: Ethical Approval

The Integrated Research Application System (IRAS) is the single application electronic system for health and social care research in the United Kingdom. As this research study involved no physically invasive procedures or participation of health/social care professionals, patients, relatives or vulnerable people it did not require ethical approval sought via IRAS. Furthermore, data collection was planned to take place during students' theory time in University and not in clinical practice, therefore site-specific approval (for research taking place on NHS sites) was also not required. The study was however bound by the Research Regulatory Framework (University of the West of Scotland, 2018) and was subject to approval by the University of the West of Scotland School of Health, Nursing and Midwifery Ethics Committee. Following submission of a research protocol and relevant supporting documents, ethical approval was granted in July 2014 prior to data collection commencement (see approval letter, appendix 3).

4.6.2: Participant Information

The potential participants were invited to opt in to the research study during induction week of their undergraduate programme in September 2014. All students were given an introductory letter (see appendix 4) and also a participant information sheet (see appendix 5), informing them what taking part in the research study would mean for them. To ensure no student felt coercion into participation, as advised by Bryman (2016), the participant information was distributed by an independent person (in this case a member of staff on the relevant campus, rather than the researcher). Following perusal of the participant information sheet and the opportunity to ask further questions, the participants were able to make an informed choice about their consent to participate.

4.6.3: Consent

Informed consent from every research participant is an essential component of all research studies (Parahoo, 2006, Walshaw, 2012, Bryman, 2016). In nursing, the concept of consent is an ethical issue and a component of professional practice, as defined by The Code (NMC, 2015c, NMC, 2018f). Patient care may only be carried out after voluntary consent has been given by the patient or client. To ensure that such consent is 'informed' (in other words, the patient knows what they are consenting to), the nurse has an accountability to ensure that the patient is given a sufficient amount of understandable information and time to consider such information before making any decisions about their care. Indeed, exactly the same principles of informed consent apply to research (Macnee and McCabe, 2008, Griffiths, 2009). Therefore, by giving the September 2014 cohort of student nurses information on the research study, time to peruse the information and the opportunity to ask questions, the principles of informed consent were met. For those who decided to take part in the study (as was explained in the participant information sheet), they were free to withdraw at any time, without having to give reason and with no consequence to their withdrawal, as advocated by Bryman (2016).

As the first stage of data collection involved a survey questionnaire (which will be further discussed in the next chapter), consent was implied by choosing to complete said questionnaire. Thereafter, the students were invited to volunteer themselves to opt in to the second stage of data collection (focus groups). As the focus groups involved audio-visual recording, all focus group participants were asked to provide written consent (see appendix 6). The diagram below details the process of consent;

Figure 4.6.3: Process of Consent

As can be seen from the above diagram, the students could opt in or out of any or all stages of the study and they were free to withdraw from the study at any time. Also, as part of the transparency of information giving; in the participant information sheet, in the written consent form and reiterated verbally at the time of data collection, confidentiality of all research participants was ensured.

4.6.4: Confidentiality

One of the most important aspects of research ethics is confidentiality. Although one of the purposes of research is to share findings of new knowledge (Parahoo, 2006, Griffiths, 2009, Bryman, 2016), no research participant should be identifiable from any of the data reported. In keeping with the agreed ethical considerations of confidentiality for this study as approved by the UWS ethics committee, the following were adhered to throughout the study duration;

- The researcher was not informed of the identity of any potential participants until consent for participation was given.
- Student records were not accessed.
- Data collected both through the survey questionnaire and the focus groups were anonymised using pseudonyms as unique identifiers for all participants.
- As the focus groups were recorded (audio-visually), the researcher ensured ground rules re. confidentiality were agreed by all participants prior to the commencement of the group. The students were coded using a simple numerical coding system (Paisley students – P1, P2, Ayr students A1, A2 etc.). The recordings were secured by the researcher and were only accessible by the researcher.
- All research participants at data collection (time 1) were unknown to the researcher due to their campus location.
- All research data was treated as strictly confidential (adhering to University of the West of Scotland Regulations for Research Degrees, 2018 and General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR, 2016).
- Only the chief investigator and supervisors had access to the data collected.
- All data collected was kept in a secure location, accessible only by the researcher and will be destroyed following completion of this study.

As well as adherence to strict confidentiality, transparency of sampling strategies is also an ethical consideration.

4.7: Sampling Strategy

When planning the logistics of a longitudinal study, especially when using mixed methods, as recognised by Tight (2017), a robust sampling strategy is essential.

4.7.1: Quantitative Sampling Strategy

The target population (case) was all September 2014 students at Ayr, Paisley and Dumfries campuses (n=420). Hamilton campus was avoided due to being the researcher's base campus

and could thus hamper confidentiality/freedom of speech of the research participants as they would be known to the researcher. Probability sampling was used for the quantitative data collection (survey questionnaire). Probability sampling is recognised by Flick (2018) as a sampling strategy that gives all potential participants the opportunity to take part in the research, thus in this study, each student had an equal opportunity to be involved in the research, should they wish to take part. To calculate an appropriate sample size, the variables of confidence level and confidence interval had to be considered. The confidence level, according to Proctor and Allan (2006) represents how often the population would pick an answer, regardless of the sample size. If the confidence level is 95%, the researcher can be 95% confident that the wider populations answers would correspond with the results achieved. In health and social care research a 95% confidence level is widely considered adequate (Bryman, 2016). The confidence interval is the plus or minus figure reported in research results. For example, in this study, if a confidence interval of 5 is used and 50% of students perceive that they need more support to deliver effective care to people with dementia, the researcher can be 'sure' that if the question had been asked of the entire student nurse intake between 45% (50-5) and 55% (50+5) would have stated they need more support.

After selecting appropriate parameters, a power calculation was carried out to ensure an acceptable sample size that would be indicative of the wider student population and would also be large enough to evaluate the psychometric properties of the newly developed Dementia and Dementia Care Perceptions Questionnaire (DDCPQ) self-efficacy tool (which will be further discussed in the subsequent chapter). Using the power formula developed by Survey Systems (2012), with a confidence level of 95%, confidence interval of 5% and an overall potential population of 455, the sample size required would be (n=209). This was double checked, using the sample size calculator on Survey Monkey (2018), using the following equation;

$$\text{Sample Size} = \frac{\frac{z^2 \times p(1-p)}{e^2}}{1 + \left(\frac{z^2 \times p(1-p)}{e^2 N}\right)}$$

- The population size = N (in this case N=420)
- The margin of error = e (in this case 5, so e=0.05 as margin of error is expressed as a percentage)
- The z score is the number of standard deviations away from the average or mean, therefore according to Survey Monkey (2018), for a desired confidence level of 95% as discussed, z=1.96.

Figure 4.7.1: Sample Size Equation

Following this subsequent check, the desired sample size for the survey questionnaires was further confirmed at n=209. This sample size was easily achieved and the specifics of response rates and their statistical significance will be explored further in subsequent chapters. In keeping with the suggestion of a robust plan for sampling (Tight, 2017), a sampling strategy for the qualitative component of the study was also considered.

4.7.2: Qualitative Sampling Strategy

According to Bryman (2016), whilst quantitative data is usually sought using probability sampling (as previously discussed), qualitative data usually involves purposive sampling. In correspondence with this notion, purposive sampling for the qualitative data was used in this study. Purposive sampling according to Griffiths (2009) is a form of non-probability sampling, whereby the researcher deliberately samples participants for particular characteristics they possess. In this case, the participants all had to be September 2014 nursing students at Paisley, Ayr or Dumfries campuses and had to have volunteered themselves to participate in focus

groups with their peers. As recognised by Bryman (2016), purposive sampling can also be further defined as sequential, non-sequential, priori and contingent. Following the pattern of transparency of decision making exemplified throughout this chapter, the following table exemplifies the qualitative sampling approaches and the most appropriate methods for this research study;

Purposive Sampling Approach	Features of Approach	Relevance to Study
Sequential sampling	Evolving process where sample is added to according to the research questions.	No – would be more useful in grounded theory when trying to generate a new theory, in this study the research questions are set.
Non-sequential sampling	A fixed approach whereby the sample is set at the commencement of the research and doesn't change.	Yes – the research participants are identified at the study outset as changes over time are sought.
Priori sampling	The criteria for selecting participants is established at the outset of the study and does not change.	Yes – the inclusion/exclusion criteria is set and does not change over the duration of the study.
Contingent sampling	The sampling criteria changes over time as the research questions change or evolve.	No – again more relevant to grounded theory or ethnography where the research is more evolving.

Table 4.7.2: Quantitative Sampling Strategy

As can be seen from the above table, a purposive, non-sequential, priori sampling strategy was identified as the most relevant for this study. In keeping with the norm of qualitative research (quality of data collected rather than quantity) (Miles, Huberman and Saldana, 2014), a power calculation was not required for this aspect of the research study. Furthermore, the sample size is advised to be small for focus groups (6-12 participants) per group as advised by Griffiths

(2009). However, as this study is longitudinal in nature and is thus likely to have higher levels of attrition than a study with a singular data collection (Bryman, 2016, Tight, 2017), it was decided to aim for the upper level of participant numbers at data collection time one, (n=12). The specifics of the students sampled for both the quantitative and qualitative components of this study as well as the detail of data collection timings and critique of the methods used will be discussed in the following chapter.

4.8: Summary

This chapter has justified the ontological and epistemological perspective of this research study and provided transparency of decision making for the use of a concurrent triangulation, mixed methods, longitudinal case study approach. The ethical requirements of the study were detailed and justification provided for the sampling strategy and data collection. The specifics of the data collection and research methods will now be further discussed in the subsequent Methods chapter.

Chapter Five: Research Methods

This chapter will examine the data collection methods for both the quantitative and qualitative aspects of the study. The data collection timings, which were carried out using concurrent triangulation will be detailed. Thereafter, the use of the survey questionnaire as a quantitative data collection tool will be critiqued and the origins of the Dementia and Dementia Care Perceptions Questionnaire (DDCPQ), with its central themes of Role Adequacy, Role Legitimacy and Role Support critically explored and related to the newly formed DDCPQ. The process of ensuring the validity and reliability of the DDCPQ will also be critically examined. Additionally, the qualitative data collection through the use of focus groups will be critiqued, with justification for use of nominal group technique and for use of the 'Ketso Kit' to assist data collection. Lastly, the method of data collection will be critiqued in terms of reflexivity, rigour and trustworthiness.

As previously stated, this study was longitudinal in nature, thus the data was collected over a 3-year period. To gain insight into the complexities of this, the concurrent data collection timings must be clearly justified;

5.0: Data Collection Timings

One of the study aims is;

- To explore undergraduate student nurse perceptions of dementia care and their role in care delivery.

This aim seeks to understand these perceptions at the point of course commencement but also as the undergraduate course progresses, to examine whether perceptions of care and/or role, change throughout the course, and if so, when this change occurs. Thus, the variable of time is important. Furthermore, another aim is;

- To examine the influence of theory, skills training and clinical experience on approach to dementia care delivery amongst undergraduate student nurses.

This aim also specifically seeks to measure these influences as the course progresses and in particular, when theory, skills and experience are gained. As such, measuring the variable of time is thus important to achieve this aim too. The specific measurable changes were in relation to the central themes of the DDCPQ; role adequacy (having the adequate knowledge and skills to care for people with dementia), role legitimacy (being appropriately placed to deliver this care) and role support (the support required to deliver dementia care). These themes reflect the adapted questions from the Alcohol and Alcohol Problems Perceptions Questionnaire AAPPQ (Shaw et al, 1978, Cartwright, 1980a, Gorman and Cartwright 1991, Cartwright and Gorman, 1993) and will be further discussed later in the chapter.

To ensure that the research study followed the student nurses throughout their undergraduate training, it was important that the data collection timings started from the very beginning of the student's undergraduate programme until the very end, at point of registration. Bryman (2016) purports that there is little guidance about timings of data collection in longitudinal studies, suggestive in part that this is due to the costs and resource implications of longitudinal studies, making them a less used type of social research (Bowling 2009, Walshaw, 2012). Nonetheless, according to Gray (2014), when carrying out longitudinal research, data collection timings should be planned in advance and specifically relevant to the subject under study. Thus, it seemed logical to plan data collection at the start and end of the BSc programme but also at each course progression point as the students moved from one academic year to the next.

The diagram below demonstrates the data collection timings;

Figure 5.0: Data Collection Timings

In keeping with the mixed method study design and to give greater depth and breadth to the study, combining methods can be useful at the sampling, collection or analysis component of the data journey (Gray, 2014). In this case, the data collection, as was discussed in Chapter Four, used concurrent triangulation of methods at all of these parts of the journey. To facilitate this, as exemplified above, it was essential that the quantitative and qualitative data was collected at the same time.

5.1: Quantitative Data Collection

The quantitative data collection tool had to allow for the collection of a considerable amount of data from a substantial number of research participants (in this case n=455). As advised by Flick (2018), for quantitative research, the data should be collected in an unambiguous manner that would be easily replicable over the stages of data collection, a view concurred by Thomas (2009), who suggests that a survey questionnaire can facilitate such requirements. Therefore, the quantitative data collection method was the survey questionnaire.

5.1.1: Survey Questionnaire as a Data Collection Tool

Commonly used in health and social science research (Walshaw, 2012), the survey questionnaire is a quantifiable data collection tool that provides numerical and/or descriptive data from all respondents that can then be analysed for the existence of relationships between and amongst variables (Macnee and McCabe, 2008, Thomas, 2009, Walshaw, 2012). As recognised by Bowling (2009) surveys can (with a high level of accuracy), measure demographic differences between populations, as well as knowledge, attitudes and behaviours. The survey questionnaire is a data collection method that facilitates the collection of data from a sample of interest, whereby the unit of analysis is the sampled population, allowing inferential statistical analysis of variance between the population groups (Bowling, 2009, Gray, 2014).

However, as acknowledged by Thomas (2009), the term 'survey' can be ambiguous and is often used interchangeably to describe both a data collection tool and research design method. This view is concurred by Bryman (2016) who suggests that the strong connotations that a 'survey' has with a questionnaire might be the reason for this and recommends that when explaining research design, the term 'survey' should not convey a research design. It is advised that researchers should use the terminology; cross-sectional or in this case; longitudinal design, to describe the research design and 'survey' or 'survey questionnaire' as a component of such design (Bryman, 2016).

In this study, the research design (as identified in the previous chapter) is a prospective, longitudinal, mixed methods case study. A survey questionnaire was one of the chosen data collection methods to gain information from the case under study. The survey questionnaire tool met the overarching aims that a survey questionnaire should (according to Bowling, 2009), namely; gaining relevant statistics from the population of interest and/or testing a hypothesis about a population. As discussed in Chapter Three, the components of the original Maudsley Alcohol Pilot Project (MAPP) hypothesis (Shaw et al, 1978, Cartwright, 1980a, Gorman and Cartwright 1991, Cartwright and Gorman, 1993), were applicable to this survey;

- Training, experience and knowledge gain should have a positive effect on role adequacy and role legitimacy.
- Role support is influenced by role security.
- Role security influences levels of therapeutic commitment.

As well as the testable hypotheses originating from the MAPP study, again, as detailed in Chapter Three, the central themes of role adequacy, role legitimacy and role support provided a robust measurable framework that other dementia perception questionnaires could not offer.

5.1.2: Dementia Perceptions Questionnaires

Flick (2018) purports that the instructive wording of a questionnaire as well as how the questionnaire is designed and the positionality of questions, can all affect how the respondents may answer and thus, the quality of the responses received. Indeed, the complexities of questionnaire design is well recognised (Bowling, 2009, Thomas, 2009, Bryman, 2016), often leading to a timely and overly challenging research study (Flick, 2018). Such complexities of constructing an original survey are exemplified by Gray (2014), who suggests the need for a process driven pathway involving meticulous planning, pre-testing and adaptation, followed by re-testing before data collection can even begin. Thus, many researchers choose to use an existing data collection instrument, acknowledged by Cresswell (2016) as advantageous as it should already have undergone testing to establish validity and reliability.

Whilst this may have been advantageous, particularly in a time constrained educational research study such as this one, it is ultimately important that the data collection tool can meet the research aims (Bowling, 2009, Walshaw, 2012). Following review of the commonly used dementia care questionnaires in Chapter Three, it was apparent that these were not appropriate for use in this study and thus a new tool had to be sought. Indeed, the frequently used dementia knowledge, attitudes and perceptions questionnaires would not be feasible to meet the research aims of this study. Even with adaptation of any of the original previously tested questionnaires, the total component of questions in any one of these tools does not fully address the research aims and thus new questions would need to be generated. Flick (2018) purports that frameworks do exist for the generation of research questions within a survey questionnaire.

Indeed, these frameworks can help consider the types of questions to be asked as well as how and when the questions are asked, which helps ensure clear and unambiguous responses. Nonetheless, as acknowledged by Gray (2014), the testing and merging of new and existing questions to make a unified data collection tool is challenging. Altering the sequencing of the original tool affects its validity and reliability and can also alter how the questions naturally 'flow', leading to potential changes in the quality of answers (Bowling, 2009, Gray, 2014, Cresswell, 2016). Therefore, before considering a major adaptation and extension of one of the existing dementia tools, considering a tool that had the underpinning components that could answer the research questions but was in use in a different subject area was considered. From the literature search and from wider reading of quantitative survey questionnaires that had previously been adapted to a differing subject area, the Alcohol and Alcohol Problems Perceptions Questionnaire AAPPQ (Shaw et al, 1978, Cartwright, 1980a, Gorman and Cartwright 1991, Cartwright and Gorman, 1993) was therefore considered.

5.1.3: Adapting the Alcohol and Alcohol Problems Perceptions Questionnaire (AAPPQ)

Although alcohol and alcohol problems may seem like a disparate choice for a questionnaire to be adapted and related to dementia, the inherent themes of role adequacy, role legitimacy and role support, were very applicable to nursing and furthermore, the tool has been successfully adapted, revalidated and used within other research studies unrelated to alcohol and alcohol problems, such as drugs, medication beliefs, mental health and co-morbidities (Lauder et al, 2000, Airey and Marriott, 2003, Watson et al, 2006). To understand the history of the AAPPQ and its derivatives, it is essential to gain an insight into its development.

The AAPPQ stemmed from the work of the 1973 Maudsley Alcohol Pilot Project (MAPP) (funded by the Department of Health and Social Security). The MAPP initially sought to explore the extent and nature of alcohol and alcohol problems and perceptions of such problems, ultimately aiming to make recommendations for health and healthcare improvement (Shaw et al, 1978). Building upon initial findings from the MAPP and as the MAPP director, the original AAPPQ formed part of Alan Cartwright's PhD (Cartwright, 1980b). Within his thesis, Cartwright (1980b) critiqued the AAPPQ's first use as a data collection tool in 1973. The AAPPQ's original aims were; "to enable scales to measure therapeutic commitment, experience, support and training to be

evolved and.....to examine the relationship between these variables” (Cartwright 1980b, p151). These initial aims and link to the evolvement of training, link well to the educational commitment to deliver dementia training to undergraduate student nurses. Indeed, many publications have since used the AAPPQ, however, it was initially useful to examine the key papers published by Cartwright that critique the fundamental founding elements of the tool and it’s testing.

A publication by Cartwright (1980a) critically discusses the first data collection using the AAPPQ (excluding extensive piloting of the tool which was already complete). ‘Trainees’ (n=109) (mostly trained professionals), attended a residential summer course, introducing alcohol and alcohol problems. Data was collected at 3 points using the AAPPQ; pre-course (1 week prior to attending the course), post course (on the day the course finished) and follow up (6 months after attending). Unfortunately, the response rate was only 37% from all data collections and thus due to non-response bias (Fincham, 2008), results could not be generalised to the whole cohort. However, the data collection did allow for further testing of the tool. Although the AAPPQ had been previously tested during piloting, this study facilitated further testing of each scale of the tool and the tool as a whole. Test/retest enhanced the reliability of the tool as a whole, with Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient readings confirming this reliability for the full tool and the subscales of support, self-esteem and therapeutic attitudes ($\alpha = 0.7 > 0.9$).

The AAPPQ was originally separated into 6 sections (A to F) (Cartwright, 1980b), however the refined version that was published had 3 sections; section A; seeking demographic data and information on experience, education and support, section B; the section that generates a score for therapeutic commitment and lastly section C; knowledge testing through a series of multiple-choice questions. The initial tool introduced the 5 therapeutic commitment scales; motivation to work with drinkers, work satisfaction, role adequacy, role legitimacy and task specific self-esteem (Cartwright, 1980a). In section B (therapeutic commitment) questions were scored using a 7-point Likert scale; strongly agree, quite strongly agree, agree, neither agree nor disagree, disagree, quite strongly disagree and strongly disagree. Overall, the findings of this first, initial data collection (Cartwright, 1980b) demonstrated that self-esteem influences therapeutic commitment, therapeutic commitment is influenced by support available and experience gained, thus self-esteem, experience and support are independent determinants of therapeutic commitment.

Accordingly, the tool's central themes were inherent from the beginning; role adequacy (adequately prepared and knowing enough to carry out one's role), role legitimacy (having the legitimate knowledge and skills and being placed in the correct position to carry out one's role) and lastly role support (being given adequate support to help carry out one's role effectively). These components were sought to give an indication of overall therapeutic commitment and questions also distinguished the participant's experience, training and clinical knowledge and understanding (as perceived by the person completing the questionnaire). Originally the therapeutic commitment scored via section B (Cartwright, 1980b) had a series of 46 questions which was refined to 41 questions, however there is a disparity in the literature over how many questions make up the original rating scale of the AAPPQ, with several versions of the questionnaire in use.

Indeed, in a further publication by Cartwright and Gorman (1993), it discusses the 32 statement AAPPQ as a scale that measures 'intensity of attitude'. It does not provide information on the specifics of the 32-scale questionnaire, however, does postulate commitment to the original MAPP hypothesis, stating that therapeutic commitment tests the motivation to work with those who are drinkers, expectations of satisfaction of working with those who drink alcohol and also task specific self-esteem. It states that education leads to changes in role requirements, thus increasing role security and in turn increasing therapeutic commitment.

Despite such disparity around the explicit features of the initial AAPPQ, it is recognised by Terrhorst, Gotham, Puskar et al (2013) that the reliability of the AAPPQ has remained constant despite various versions being used. In their study, Terrhorst et al (2013) sought to confirm the factor structure of the AAPPQ using a 30-item version of the original questionnaire. Baccalaureate (BSc) nursing students enrolled in a School of Nursing in the USA were sampled pre and post training (sample size; n=299). However, as the focus of this study was on exploring the factor structure of the AAPPQ, only the first set of data was analysed. This is because a large sample size is required to confirm the psychometric properties of a tool (Watson, McLaren, Shaw et al, 2003) and therefore subsequent data collections may not have been large enough, thus were discarded for the purposes of testing (Terrhorst et al, 2013). Interestingly, Terrhorst et al (2013) asked research participants to score the questionnaire using a 5-point Likert scale

(strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, strongly disagree) as opposed to the original 7-point scale as mentioned previously. Using a combination of exploratory factor analysis and principal components analysis, the results indicated that a 7 item components structure of subscales proved best for interrater reliability. The 7 subscales were; role adequacy, role legitimacy, role support, motivation, lack of confidence, task specific self-esteem and work satisfaction which drew parallels with the questionnaire configuration as per the shortened version of the AAPPQ (SAAPPQ) introduced by Anderson and Clement (1987).

Anderson and Clement (1987) carried out a study using a shortened version of the AAPPQ (SAAPPQ). The sample population this time was General Practitioner's (n=467) with a 67% response rate (n=312 for further analysis). The benefits of the original AAPPQ were again recognised in terms of evaluating impact of interventions (training/education) and facilitating dialogue on the structure of such training (again demonstrating direct relevance to planning educational curricula to reflect dementia care priorities and thus correlation to its use in this study). Indeed, Anderson and Clement recognised that various versions of the AAPPQ were in use, which can be demonstrated even with the key papers relating to the tool (Cartwright, 1980a, Gorman and Cartwright, 1991, Cartwright and Gorman, 1993). Acknowledging the use of a 30-item version of the original tool, the main focus of the paper by Anderson and Clement (1987) was on using data reduction techniques to test a short form of the tool. Their main argument for production of the SAPPQ was that poor response rates in survey questionnaire type studies (involving GP's) could be resolved (in part) by reducing the workload associated with questionnaire completion. This they postulated, could be achieved by producing a shorter, more user-friendly version of the AAPPQ (SAAPPQ). Factor analysis demonstrated comparability to the original AAPPQ but it was recognised that whilst the study seemed to show good correlation to the full AAPPQ, the SAAPPQ required further testing both longitudinally and in relation to pre/post educational interventions.

Indeed, Gorman and Cartwright (1991) further tested the implications of using long and short versions of the AAPPQ. In a small-scale study (n=33) a 29-item version of the questionnaire was tested. 1 group received educational interventions and a non-equivalent control group were also surveyed for comparison. At baseline, no significant differences were found (suggesting comparability of groups despite non-equivalency), however at follow up, 1 month and 6 monthly respectively, it was suggested that the summary scales optimistically demonstrate change

where change may not have occurred. The study reported that summary scales can mislead researchers and thus may produce findings that are not generalisable, especially if looking to evaluate educational effectiveness. However, it must be recognised that this study in itself is very small (n=33) and thus would not be generalisable.

To summarise the differences in the key AAPPQ papers and to make an explicit decision-making trajectory regarding the version of the AAPPQ to be adapted for use as the DDPCQ, it is useful to tabulate the findings;

Title of Research	Author and Publication Date	Number of Items	Scoring Matrix	Factor Structure	Other
The Effect of Role Insecurity on the Therapeutic Commitment of Alcoholism Counsellors. PhD Thesis.	Cartwright (1980b)	46 items, shortened to 41.	7-point Likert scale	5 factor structure (p191)	Includes 3 measures of self-esteem. Discusses 1 st and 2 nd version of AAPPQ (Pilot studies) but gives example of 3 rd version.
The Attitudes of Helping Agents Towards the Alcoholic Client; The Influence of Experience, Training, Support and Self Esteem.	Cartwright (1980a)	35 items	7-point Likert scale	5 factor structure	Also, attitude, support and self-esteem scoring scales. No version number explicitly stated.

Implications of Using the Composite and Short Versions of the Alcohol and Alcohol Problems Perceptions Questionnaire (AAPPQ).	Gorman and Cartwright (1991)	29 items	No mention of scoring scale	5 factor structure	No version number.
Processes Involved in Changing the Therapeutic Attitudes of Clinicians Towards Working with Drinking Clients.	Cartwright and Gorman (1993)	32 items	7-point Likert scale	No mention of factor structure	No mention of version number but refers to Cartwright (1980) and Gorman and Cartwright (1991) as reference but they used different versions.
The AAPPQ Revisited: the Measurement of General Practitioners' Attitudes to Alcohol Problems.	Anderson and Clement (1987)	30 items	7-point Likert scale	6 factor structure	Although not by the original authors, included because the 1991 study by Gorman and Cartwright (as seen above)

					refers to the importance of this study. Version 4.
Confirming the Factor Structure of the Alcohol and Alcohol Problems Questionnaire (AAPPQ) in a Sample of Baccalaureate Nursing Students.	Terrhorst et al (2013)	30 items	5-point Likert scale	7 factor structure	Again, whilst not by any of the original authors, this was the first study to verify the factor structure of the AAPPQ in a sample of nursing students so directly relevant to research study. No version number.

Table 5.1.3: AAPPQ Key Papers

When considering the inconsistency of the application of the AAPPQ (as represented above), it was decided that a shortened version of the questionnaire may not be appropriate for this research study at data collection and indeed it would be better to use the original version and adapt it where necessary.

Therefore, in keeping with research protocol, permission had to be sought to use the AAPPQ. The original author Alan Cartwright had retired, however, was able to be contacted via email and permission was given to use the original version of the tool and to adapt it to measure dementia care perceptions (see appendix 7). Thus, the original 41 item version of the AAPPQ (Cartwright, 1980b) was used as a template (see appendix 8) and adapted to become the Dementia and Dementia Care Perceptions Questionnaire (DDCPQ).

5.1.4: Dementia and Dementia Care Perceptions Questionnaire (DDCPQ)

When an existing instrument is modified in any way, it can negatively affected its validity and reliability (Cresswell, 2016), thus the validity and reliability of the DDCPQ had to be re-established.

When seeking to modify the tool, it was essential to revisit the research aim that was specific to the DDCPQ;

- evaluate the psychometric properties of a self-efficacy tool designed to measure attitudes, experiences and perceptions of dementia care in undergraduate student nurses

Thereafter, it was useful to consider how the AAPPQ had previously been adapted and tested. Whilst the AAPPQ has been extensively used in various versions to measure perceptions towards alcohol, it has also been adapted and used in many different ways.

The following table illustrates how the AAPPQ has been modified;

Name of Tool	Publication	Author	Similarities to AAPPQ	Reliability and Validity	Further Analysis Warranted?
Role Perception Questionnaire	Development of a Questionnaire to examine the Role of Counsellors Working with School Students and their Families with Alcohol or Other Drug-Related Problems	Grove and Bush (1998)	Adapted AAPPQ to form RPQ Fundamental components of AAPPQ retained	Clear explanation of testing for reliability and validity	Yes
Mental Health Problems Perception Questionnaire (MHPPQ)	Two papers; The Development and Testing of the Mental Health Problems Perception Questionnaire Further Testing of the Mental Health Problems Perception Questionnaire	Lauder, Reynolds, Reilly et al (2000) Angus, Lauder and Reynolds (2001)	Adapted AAPPQ to form MHPPQ Fundamental components of AAPPQ retained.	Clear explanation of testing for reliability and validity	Yes
Drug and Drug Problems Perceptions Questionnaire	Staff Attitudes Towards Working with Drug Users: Development of the Drug	Watson, Maclaren and Kerr (2006)	Adapted AAPPQ to form DDPQ	Clear explanation of testing for reliability and validity	Yes

	Problems Perceptions Questionnaire		Fundamental components of AAPPQ retained		
Prison Attitudes to Drugs Scale (PAD)	Measuring Therapeutic Attitudes in the Prison Environment: Development of the Prison Attitude to Drugs Scale.	Airey and Marriott (2003)	Adapted AAPPQ to form PAD Fundamental components of AAPPQ retained.	Clear explanation of testing for reliability and validity	Yes
No name for tool	Changing Staff Attitudes and Empathy for Working with People with Psychosis.	MacLeod, Deane and Hogbin (2002)	Adapted AAPPQ to form new unnamed tool Some fundamental components of AAPPQ retained.	Does not include full explanation of testing for reliability and validity Uses elements from another study	No
The Medication Alliance Beliefs Questionnaire (MABQ)	Training Inpatient Mental Health Staff How to Enhance Patient Engagement with Medications: Medication Alliance Training and	Byrne, Willis, Deane et al (2010)	Adapted AAPPQ to form MABQ Some fundamental components of AAPPQ retained	Does not include full explanation of testing for reliability and validity Uses another data collection tool alongside the MABQ	No

	Dissemination Outcomes in a Large US Mental Health Hospital.				
Co-Morbidity Problems Perceptions Questionnaire (CMPPQ)	Assessing the Impact of Training on Mental Health Nurses Therapeutic Attitudes and Knowledge about Co-Morbidity: A Randomised Control Trial.	Munro, Watson and McFadyen (2007)	Uses previously adapted AAPPQ as CMPPQ Some fundamental components of AAPPQ retained	Does not include full explanation of testing for reliability and validity Refers to previous study by author but this does not provide testing information either	No

Table 5.1.4: AAPPQ Modifications

As can be seen from the above table, from initial review, (n=5) studies prompted further analysis of their validity and reliability testing measures (Grove and Bush, 1998, Lauder et al, 2000, Angus et al, 2001, Airey and Marriott, 2003 and Watson et al, 2006);

Indeed, the most common adaptation of the AAPPQ is in relation to attitudes towards drugs. One of the first studies using the AAPPQ as a basis of a questionnaire relating to drugs perceptions is the Role Perceptions Questionnaire (RPQ) (Grove and Bush, 1998). The RPQ aimed to identify counsellor’s perceptions of their role relating to interventions in drug and/or alcohol problems amongst school students and their families. Using the AAPPQ (no version number included) as a baseline structure, the RPQ extended the questions to include alcohol, tobacco and other drugs. Section A was in keeping with the AAPPQ and collected demographic data and background information on education and experience, section B consisted of similar statements as per the AAPPQ but extended these questions to include other substance misuse and section C (knowledge testing) was not included as knowledge about alcohol/substance misuse was not required as part of this study. The fundamental constructs of role adequacy, legitimacy and support were maintained but questions were rewritten to include other substances (not just

perceptions relating to alcohol). This resulted in 47 statements whereby respondents were asked to indicate their feelings towards such statements using a 7-point Likert scale (again as per the original AAPPQ). Initial drafts of the RPQ were reviewed for face and content validity and then further piloting of the RPQ saw the need for some changes prior to implementation of the revised tool prior to study data collection. The research study was carried out in South Australia and sampled school counsellors (n=176). Despite a limited response rate of 49% (n=86), factor analysis was carried out to further test the RPQ. After an initial principal axis factor analysis using varimax rotation produced 9 factors that were not easily interpretable, a further analysis revealed a four-factor structure which draws some parallels with the original constructs of the AAPPQ (Grove and Bush, 1998). The four factors of role adequacy, role support, role permission and role definition were then tested for reliability using Cronbach's alpha coefficient. Following initial testing and then removal of low loading items, acceptable alpha readings were found for role adequacy ($\alpha=0.90$), role support ($\alpha=0.95$), and role permission ($\alpha=0.89$). However, the reliability of role definition was questionable ($\alpha=0.52$). This limitation in reliability was recognised by Grove and Bush (1998) and it is suggested that further testing would be required to enhance the reliability of the tool as a whole.

Whilst acknowledging the RPQ as an early adaptation of the AAPPQ, a study by Airey and Marriott (2003) developed a further drug related adaptation of the AAPPQ; the Prison Attitude to Drugs Scale (PAD). Whilst this study is specific to those working with drug abuse within the prison sector, the validity testing of another adaptation of the AAPPQ merited further critique. A convenience sample of staff working within the prison environment in the UK were sampled (n=357), with a respectable overall response rate of 70% (n=252) which facilitated a large enough sample to allow for psychometric testing. Test/Retest reliability was confirmed using Spearman's correlation co-efficient ($r \geq 0.7$). Principal components analysis was then applied using varimax rotation which resulted in a 3-factor structure which were renamed "confidence in skills", "personal rewards" and "job satisfaction" (Airey and Marriott, 2003, p183). The 3 factors were then tested for reliability using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, with factors scoring acceptable alpha ratings ($\alpha=0.87$, 0.79 and 0.71 respectively). The resulting PAD was a short 9-item questionnaire which is quite different from the original AAPPQ, however was justified by the authors due to high standards of acceptability in validity testing which reduced the number of questions and also the very specific setting in which the research took place and thus where the questionnaire would be applicable for use.

A more widely used tool to measure perceptions towards drugs and drug problems is the Drugs Problems Perceptions Questionnaire (DDPPQ) (Watson et al, 2003, Watson et al, 2006). In a study commissioned by the Scottish Government, the aim of the study was to evaluate the psychometric properties of an adapted version of the AAPPQ to measure attitudes of those working with drug users in a healthcare setting. The PAD (Airey and Marriott, 2003) was acknowledged, however, its use in a prison specific environment was recognised as not being valid for use with health professionals without further testing, therefore Watson et al sought to adapt their own tool. The DDPPQ was adapted from the AAPPQ (Cartwright, 1980a) with simple wording changes of the original questions to reflect the change from alcohol to drugs. As per section B of the original AAPPQ, the DDPPQ seeks respondents to score statements using a 7-point Likert score. The study sampled NHS mental health workers (n=1073), administering questionnaires to a random sample (n=672). Response rates were 56% and 68% from time 1 and time 2 data collections respectively. Test/retest reliability was carried out, examining sign test results and kappa coefficient for each item in the tool. Following this, some items were deleted, because of inconsistent sign test results or $\kappa < 0.4$. Thereafter, principal component analysis was carried out after the first data collection, using varimax rotation for factor loading and thus resulting in a 5-factor structure. The 5 factors were similar to the original factor structure of the AAPPQ; role adequacy, role support, job satisfaction, role-related self-esteem and role legitimacy. Thereafter, internal consistency was further tested by confirming acceptable Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the full tool ($\alpha=0.87$), role adequacy components ($\alpha=0.94$), role support ($\alpha=0.78$), job satisfaction ($\alpha=0.80$), role-related self-esteem ($\alpha=0.69$) and role legitimacy ($\alpha=0.89$). Finally, content validity was established by considering the comments returned with the questionnaires regarding ease of completion and relevance of questioning. The resulting DDPPQ tool is a 20-item questionnaire and whilst a limitation is that it was specifically tested in qualified and unqualified health care workers and not student nurses, it was proven to be a reliable and valid tool and thus gave good indication of the reliability and validity testing that would be required for the AAPPQ to be successfully adapted.

The final adapted tool to be further analysed was the Mental Health Problems Perceptions Questionnaire (MHPPQ) (Lauder et al, 2000, Angus et al, 2001). The MHPPQ was a revised version of the AAPPQ (41 item tool). Similar to the revisions by Watson et al (2006), the initial tool wording was retained, with any reference to "alcohol problems", changed to "mental health

problems” (Lauder et al, 2000, p223). The initial study testing the MHPPQ sampled district nurses in Scotland (n=82), with no mention of response rates. Initial item analysis reduced the tool to 27 items after unsuitable items were deleted. Thereafter, validity was tested using Pearson’s correlation coefficients which demonstrated significant correlations between the therapeutic commitment and role support, therapeutic commitment and role competency and role support and role competency; ($r=0.27, p<0.05/r=0.53, p<0.01/r=0.49, p<0.01$ respectively). Construct validity was then tested using principal components analysis with varimax rotation which resulted in a 3-factor structure; therapeutic commitment, role competency (comprising role adequacy and role legitimacy) and lastly, role support. Reliability was successfully confirmed using Cronbach’s alpha, measuring the 3 factors; therapeutic commitment ($\alpha=0.91$), role competency ($\alpha=0.85$) and role support ($\alpha=0.83$). The study findings draw parallels with the original AAPPQ and underlying concepts, however the study recognises that further psychometric testing with a larger sample size would enhance the tools validity and reliability. Indeed, the further study by Angus et al (2001) was a 2-part design that further tested the MHPPQ. Similar to the testing in the earlier study by Lauder et al (2000), this latter study further confirmed validity and reliability of the tool. Sample size was small in part 1 of the study (n=46), response rate (n=36) and larger in part 2 (n=288), response rate (n=152). Test/retest reliability was again confirmed with Pearson’s correlation coefficients for each factor of the scale; therapeutic commitment ($r=0.88, p<0.01$), role competency ($r=0.69, p<0.01$) and role support ($r=0.70, p<0.01$). Construct validity was again confirmed using principal components analysis using varimax rotation and a 3-factor structure was maintained. Internal reliability was further confirmed with acceptable Cronbach’s alpha ratings for therapeutic commitment ($\alpha=0.84$), role support ($\alpha=0.89$) and role competency ($\alpha=0.87$). Thus, the MHPPQ was again proven to be valid and reliable and provided a useful framework to guide the testing of validity and reliability for the DDCPQ.

5.2: Validity and Reliability of the DDCPQ

Learning from the previous adaptations of the AAPPQ as critiqued above, a plan was made to test the psychometric properties of the DDCPQ. With various versions of the AAPPQ in use and after discussion and advice from the author, Alan Cartwright, it was decided to retain the format of the original instrument (Cartwright, 1980b). Section A sought demographic data and information on experience and education to date and Section B contained 41 self-scoring statements, relating to role adequacy, role legitimacy and role support. Additionally, in direct correlation with the original AAPPQ tool, respondents would be asked to score the statements on a 7-point Likert scale from strongly agree to strongly disagree. It was decided not to include section C (knowledge testing) as this was very specific to alcohol and therefore difficult to adapt. Furthermore, this study aims to discover if and when learning had taken place, not what the learning was as the student nurses' specific dementia knowledge would be reflected in modular and programme related learning outcomes and therefore was not required as part of this study.

In keeping with the revised wording of the tools by Lauder et al (2000) and Watson et al (2006) and to adapt the wording to reflect the dementia perspective, the wording of the original tool was altered, simply changing 'alcohol' to 'dementia'. For example, Question 1B in the AAPPQ read; "I feel I have a working knowledge of alcohol and alcohol related problems", whereas Question 1B in the DDCPQ reads; "I feel I have a working knowledge of dementia and dementia related problems". This simple alteration theme was continued throughout the tool and resulted in version 1 of the DDCPQ.

Thereafter, to establish content validity, as advocated by Watson et al (2006), it was essential to ensure the wording of the tool was comprehensive and understandable. Firstly, to confirm that the tool reflected current language used in dementia care and dementia policy, the tool was subject to expert review by dementia experts from Alzheimer Scotland. Following constructive feedback from the subject experts, very slight wording changes were carried out and resulted in version 2 of the DDCPQ. Thereafter, to further verify content validity, it essential to ensure the tool was relevant to student nurses and that questions were easy to understand and answer. This was established as part of the pilot study process.

5.2.1: Pilot Study

The pilot study was carried out in August 2014, prior to initial data collection with the September 2014 cohort of pre-registration student nurses. To ensure direct comparability and equivalency with the cohort selected as part of the research study, the pilot study sample were also pre-registration student nurses. The MSc Adult Nursing cohort class of February 2014 were invited to complete the DDCPQ as part of the pilot study (n=20). Following completion of the questionnaire, students were invited to provide free comments on the questionnaire, using a feedback template, a way of refining the questions and also commencing analysis, according to Thomas (2016). Comments were generally positive and a two minor wording changes helped enhance the readability of Section A of the questionnaire (demographic data). The DDCPQ (version 3 – see appendix 9) was then ready for first data collection and psychometric testing using SPSS version 25.

5.2.2: Psychometric Testing of the DDCPQ

Field (2014) provides a useful flow chart identifying the procedure for data screening via factor analysis or PCA. Using this exemplar as a guide, it was useful to tabulate a plan for the testing of the DDCPQ;

(Adapted from Field, 2014)

Figure 5.2.2: Psychometric Testing Process

Thus, systematically using the above chart as a guide, the DDCPQ was methodically tested.

Data collection specifics regarding response rates will be discussed in the subsequent results chapter, however for the purpose of the preliminary testing of the tool, it was firstly essential to gain an adequate sample size. The total population of the September 2014 pre-registration student nurses on 3 University campuses were invited to take the DDCPQ (n=455) and an excellent response rate of 92% ensured an adequate sample size (n=420). Sample size adequacy for statistical testing can be checked by the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy (KMO) and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity (Field, 2014). KMO should be >0.5 and Bartlett's test should be significant ($p < 0.05$). As can be seen from the table below, KMO was 0.916 and $p = 0.00$ and thus both tests confirmed an adequate sample size had been achieved at time 1.

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.916
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square 11372.385
	Df 820
	Sig. .000

Table 5.2.2: KMO and Bartlett's Test

The next stage of testing, according to Field (2014), was to examine the correlation between variables. In parallel to the approach used by Lauder et al (2000), Pearson's correlation coefficients of the components were calculated. Whilst the tabulated results according to SPSS version 25 are too large to be included, the process can be articulated thus; Pearson's correlation coefficients were calculated for every pair of questions and then significant correlations (one tailed) were computed. The tabulated results on the (R-matrix) (Pearson's correlation matrix) were scanned for correlations greater than 0.3 and then the correlation coefficients were scanned for any values greater than 0.9 (identified as potentially problematic due to possibility of multicollinearity according to Field, 2014). At this point, no questions were unduly problematic with large correlation coefficients thus, all questions in the DDCPQ correlated well with one another. Nonetheless to further provide reassurance, the determinant of the

correlation matrix was also checked and was well above the 0.0001 value recommended by Field (2014).

Thereafter, construct validity was tested using factor extraction via a principal components analysis (PCA). Field (2014) recommends that to facilitate a trustworthy PCA, a sample size of at least 10 participants per variable should be sought. As part B of the DDCPQ comprised 41 statements, the ideal sample size to facilitate PCA at data collection 1 would be $n=410$ responses. Time 1 response rate was adequate for this ($n=420$) therefore PCA could be carried out with confidence. Brown (2006) recognises PCA as a common method of factor extraction which can be used to explore the dimensions of the questionnaire and relationships between variables (Watson et al, 2006). Field (2014) acknowledges that whilst some researchers report that factor analysis is more robust than PCA, the commonality of both involves extraction of factors. Therefore, as PCA had been effectively demonstrated in previous adaptations of the AAPPQ (Watson et al, 2006, Lauder et al, 2000) PCA was commenced. As recommended by Field (2014), as part of PCA, a scree plot can be useful to demonstrate the plotting of associated factors. The scree plot below was produced from dimension reduction (factor extraction) of the DDCPQ;

Figure 5.2.3: Initial Scree Plot

The points of inflection on a scree plot are an indicator of the factors extracted (Greasley, 2008), however, as can be seen from the scree plot above, this scree plot was difficult to interpret as not all of the points were on the curve, leading to the suggestion of multiple points of inflexion. Therefore, as recommended by Kaiser (1960), it is useful to consider retaining all factors with an eigenvalue >1 . Using Kaiser's criteria, 8 factors were extracted in the initial PCA, accounting for 66.7% of the total variance.

The 8-factor extraction was further checked by considering the communalities of the extraction. Whilst initial Kaiser Measure of sampling adequacy had been confirmed, it was useful to check that the default for factor extraction in SPSS (Kaiser's measure) was suitable for the data yield in this study. Kaiser's criterion had extracted 8 factors, however, as stated by Field (2014), this criterion is only accurate if in a sample size >250 , the mean of the communalities post extraction are ($n > 0.6$). This study meets the criteria with an adequate sample size ($n=420$) and the mean of communalities post extraction ($n=0.67$).

A further check was subsequently carried out by running a reproduced correlation matrix using the 8-factor model as extracted by the initial PCA. Again, too large to include, however, the table was checked for residuals computed between observed and reproduced correlations. As acknowledged by Field (2014), the percentage of non-redundant residuals with absolute values >0.05 should be $<50\%$. For this dataset, there were 121 residuals, which equated to 14% and thus was well within acceptable parameters.

The last stage of the factor analysis was factor rotation. As the theory behind the questionnaire suggested that all the factors in the tool were somewhat related, the recommended rotation method of choice for related variables is an oblique rotation, therefore Promax with Kaiser Optimisation was selected (Terrhorst et al, 2013, Field, 2014). Again, an 8-factor structure was extracted, accounting for 65.24% of the total variance. At this stage, as the findings were consistent thus far, it was decided to go ahead with the final stage of testing before any decisions were made regarding removal of any questions.

Post PCA, the final test checked the reliability of the DDCPQ. Cronbach’s Alpha Co-efficient is well documented to be the most robust measure of consistency in the reliability of a data collection tool (Field, 2014, Watson et al, 2006, Argyrous, 2005, Lauder et al, 2000). Therefore, reliability was checked using Cronbach’s Alpha Co-efficient for the DDCPQ;

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	420	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	420	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Table 5.2.3: Included Cases

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.933	41

Table 5.2.4: Cronbach’s Alpha: Full DDCPQ

As can be seen from the table above $\alpha=0.93$. If $\alpha \geq 0.7$ this indicates good reliability (Greasley, 2008, Field, 2014, Terrhorst et al, 2013, Argyrous, 2005), therefore, reliability of the DDCPQ as a tool in its entirety is excellent. It was also important to consider if the reliability of the tool would be affected by the removal of any of the questions, therefore the alpha rating was also considered for each question, should it be removed. The only question that would potentially very slightly increase α to 0.94 would be the “I am of equal worth” question but as this stage, it was not deemed worthy to remove one question, as all alpha’s were well above the recommended criteria.

Following the reliability testing order as demonstrated by Lauder et al (2000) and Watson et al (2006), the subsequent stage of alpha testing was to consider the alpha coefficients of each factor's components in turn. If each factor's component questions demonstrated acceptable alpha ratings, the tool's reliability would be confirmed. However, when considering the 8 extracted factors, as factor loadings less than 0.4 had been discarded (recommended as good practice) (Lauder et al, 2000, Watson et al, 2006, Angus et al, 2001), the 7th and 8 factors had only 1 and 2 component questions respectively. Thus, alpha coefficients could not be tested with such small numbers. Furthermore, considering that factor analysis is not a definitive computerised decision-making tool but instead, a tool to guide the researcher as the definitive decision maker (Field, 2014), it was decided to try the approach used by Terrhorst, et al (2013). In an effort to gain a greater degree of correlation to the original AAPPQ tool, Terrhorst et al (2013) specified a 6-factor structure (appropriate to the 30 item AAPPQ) when attempting dimension reduction on SPSS. Using this approach, the DDCPQ was subject to dimension reduction, specifying a 7-factor structure (in keeping with the original 41 item AAPPQ used in this study). In keeping with Kaiser's criterion, the 7 factors extracted all demonstrated Eigenvalues >1 and individual item loadings were specified to be retained if ≥ 0.4 . The scree plot below demonstrates the specified 7 factor structure;

Figure 5.2.4: 7 Factor Retention Scree Plot

As can be seen from the scree plot, it looks like there are points of inflexion at 3 and 7. Although multiple points of inflexion can make factor extraction decisions more difficult (as demonstrated in the previously extracted 8 factor structure), the fact that inflexions are visible at points 3 and 7 correlates directly with the original themes (n=3) and subthemes (n=7) of the AAPPQ and thus are applicable to the DDCPQ. The 3 main themes of the AAPPQ were Therapeutic Commitment, Role Security and Basic Role Requirements, with 7 subthemes of Task Specific Self Esteem, Expectation of Satisfaction of Working with Drinkers, Motivation to Work with Drinkers, Role Adequacy, Role Legitimacy, Role Support and Self Esteem. These themes and subthemes are then easily replicated within the 7-factor structure and can be directly applied to dementia.

The diagram below denotes the themes and subthemes of the DDCPQ;

Figure 5.2.5: Themes and Sub-Themes of DDCPQ

Whilst the 7-factor structure correlates the DDCPQ extremely well with the original 41 item AAPPQ, as the factor loading had been altered, it was essential again to re-establish reliability using Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient (Terrorst, 2013, Field, 2014). Alpha readings were calculated for the tool as a whole, the 3 main themes and the 7 sub themes. The results are confirmed in the following table;

Theme	Sub Theme	Cronbach's Alpha (α)	Reliability Status ($\alpha \geq 0.7$)
Full Tool		0.93	Reliable
Therapeutic Commitment	All	0.88	Reliable
Therapeutic Commitment	Task Specific Self Esteem	0.77	Reliable
Therapeutic Commitment	Satisfaction Working with Dementia	0.83	Reliable
Therapeutic Commitment	Motivation to Work with Dementia	0.65	Reliable
Role Security	All	0.94	Reliable
Role Security	Role Adequacy	0.96	Reliable
Role Security	Role Legitimacy	0.83	Reliable
Basic Role Requirements	All	0.75	Reliable
Basic Role Requirements	Role Support	0.89	Reliable
Basic Role Requirements	Self Esteem	0.76	Reliable

Table 5.2.5: Reliability Status: DDCPQ Themes and Sub-Themes

As can be seen from the table, the tool is reliable in its entirety and in its 3 main themes. In the 7 sub themes, all scores are reliable using the standard level of acceptability for alpha ($\alpha \geq 0.7$) (Nunnally, 1978, Greasely, 2008, Field, 2014). Interestingly, the lowest alpha score (motivation to work with dementia), whilst acceptable, correlates with the findings of previous studies who identified that opportunity and experience were related to the motivation subscale and significantly related to therapeutic attitude (Lightfoot and Orford, 1986, Terrhorst, 2013). Indeed, the sample in this study had had little opportunity or experience of working in dementia care at time 1 data collection and this may have been reflected in the motivational scores. Such experience and the implications of increased experience will be further discussed in the next chapter.

To summarise the testing of the DDCPQ, it is useful to revisit the previously adapted structure from Field (2014) and consider each item in relation to the DDCPQ;

Type of Testing	Measure	Method	Relevance to Study	Result
Preliminary analysis	Sample size	KMO Test	Sample size greater than 300 so KMO must be >0.5	KMO =0.916
Preliminary analysis	Correlations between variables	Scan R-matrix	Multicollinearity determinant should be >0.0001	p=0.00
Main analysis	Factor extraction	Kaiser's criterion	Appropriate if sample size >250	n=420
Main analysis	Factor extraction	Kaiser's criterion	Mean of communalities n=>0.6	n=0.67
Main analysis	Factor extraction	Scree plot	n>300	n=420
Main analysis	Factor rotation	Oblique rotation	Promax with Kaiser normalisation as factors were correlated	Structure matrix maintained
Final analysis	Reliability	Cronbach's Alpha Co-efficient	Alpha co-efficients calculated for tool as a whole, considering each question removed, by each theme and by each sub theme.	α =>0.7 in all aspects

Table 5.2.6: Summary of Psychometric Testing of DDCPQ: Validity and Reliability Confirmation

As can be seen from the above tool, the DDCPQ has proven to be valid and reliable when used in its context for this study and the following study aim has been met;

- To evaluate the psychometric properties of a self-efficacy tool designed to measure attitudes, experiences and perceptions of dementia care in undergraduate student nurses.

However, in relation to the other study aims and the qualitative aspect of this study it is also important to consider the concurrent data collection.

5.3: Concurrent Data Collection

The quantitative data collected via the DDCPQ was collected at the same time as the qualitative data and analysed simultaneously to enhance the triangulation of data at each stage of the study. In keeping with the transparent decision-making trajectory throughout this thesis, decisions taken regarding the qualitative data will now be discussed.

5.4: Qualitative Data Collection: Focus Groups

As previously exemplified, the quantitative and qualitative data were collected concurrently, with the qualitative method of choice, the focus group. Focus groups are a commonly used method of data collection in qualitative research, particularly in health and social science research (Thomas, 2009, Bryman, 2016). The flexibility of case study research, lends itself not only to differing positionality regarding paradigms and methodological underpinning (Hyett, Kenny and Dickson-Swift, 2014) but also to differing data collection processes (Casey and Houghton, 2010), thus its applicability to this mixed methods study. However, as recognised by Thomas (2009), data collection techniques must be justified, whether in quantitative or qualitative research. Qualitative data collection is most often in the form of collecting the spoken word, seeking to gain depth, meaning and understanding rather than just facts (Griffiths, 2009). This is often in the form of interviews, whether individually or in groups. Thomas (2016) purports that the researcher must make the ultimate decision, on the type of interview to undertake and that that decision is underpinned by considering the research participants and their defining characteristics. In this instance, with student nurses who were novice research participants, whilst they may not feel confident in sharing feelings, it was felt that they would gain confidence from each other and may feel more comfortable in a group setting, rather than in a one to one with a lecturer (researcher). To make such a decision, the research aims were revisited (see table below) and each aim considered in relation to suitability of data collection method;

Research Aim	Data Collection Suitability
To understand undergraduate student nurse perceptions of dementia care and their role in care delivery.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will be met in part by DDCPQ. • Need for research participants to share perceptions. • Students may feel more likely to share feelings if others feel the same. • Mirrors group reflections in class. • Focus group can facilitate.
To examine the influence of theory, skills training and clinical experience on approach to dementia care delivery amongst undergraduate student nurses.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will be met in part by DDCPQ. • Need for participants to share greater detail to get in-depth, rich data. • Students may be prompted by other students to remember theory and skills training received. • Mirrors group reflections in class. • Focus group can facilitate.
To explore how dementia training policy directives for pre-registration nurse education are reflected in undergraduate student nurses' knowledge, skills and readiness for nursing practice.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Met in part by DDCPQ. • Students may be prompted by other students to share learned knowledge and skills and feelings. • Mirrors group reflection in class. • Focus group can facilitate.
To evaluate the psychometric properties of a self-efficacy tool designed to measure attitudes, experiences and perceptions of dementia care in undergraduate student nurses.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Met in full by DDCPQ

Table 5.4: Research Aims and Data Collection Suitability

As can be seen from the above table, whilst it could be argued that individual interviews can encourage sharing of thoughts and feelings, for the novice research participant and to mirror

reflection in class (as part of group tutorials and used throughout the undergraduate nursing programme) it was decided to use focus groups.

The aim of the focus group, as suggested by Thomas (2016), is for the researcher to gain a true understanding of the participant's feelings, beliefs, perceptions and experiences. Furthermore, as suggested by Walshaw (2012), the focus group can shift the power balance of research. The researcher acts firmly as a facilitator, seeking to elicit viewpoints but not as an interviewer who holds the power of questioning. Thus, for this study, it helps establish the researcher solely as an objective researcher, taking the focus away from the teacher/student relationship and perhaps perceived power imbalance. Nonetheless, although the focus group is more flexible, with the researcher acting as facilitator and with the participants having a more active role, it is still important to have a planned approach and structure to the focus group (Liampattong, 2009, Yin, 2018). Utilising the focus group guidelines as suggested by Liampattong (2009), it was essential to ensure that certain factors had been considered. In keeping with the transparency of decision making exemplified throughout this study, the decisions regarding focus group technique have been justified in the following table;

Focus group technique	Applicability to this study
Aiming to understand perceptions in an in-depth manner to gain rich data that is relevant to the study.	Focus group questions echo research aims.
Participants should be a homogenous group, sharing the same characteristic relevant to the study.	All students are pre-registration, undergraduate student nurses in the September 2014 cohort at UWS.
Focus group should contain a maximum of 12 people to facilitate easy discussion/data collection/data analysis	The maximum number of 12 students were in each T1 focus group (to allow for natural attrition in longitudinal study).
Researcher acts as facilitator.	Researcher unknown to students at T1 to ensure teacher/student power balance not an issue.
In a mixed method study, the qualitative data sought should be complimentary to the quantitative data.	Clear plan from the start of the research of concurrent data collection and simultaneous analysis.

Table 5.4.1: Focus Group Techniques

As can be seen from the above table, the researcher has systematically considered the justification for using focus groups as a qualitative data collection method in this mixed methods study. In keeping with the ‘Yinian’ approach to case study design, this pre-planning should help ascertain the goal to capture the views of all group members by importantly seeking the participants ‘sense of reality’ (Yin, 2018, p113).

Nonetheless, it was considered that the students were both new students at T1 and also novice research participants, therefore the notion that all participants should have their say, led to the decision to use nominal group technique within the focus groups.

5.5: Nominal Group Technique

Nominal group technique (NGT) was devised in the 1960's as part of a psychological research study and has been widely used since as a popular 'consensus' method in health and social care research (Harvey and Holmes, 2012, Cunningham, 2017). NGT is a data collection method that is used within small groups to establish discussion of thoughts, feeling and perceptions (McMillan, King and Tully, 2016). Using a structured approach and ensuring a balanced input from every participant, NGT gets participants to rate their assertions in order of priority to get a group 'consensus'. NGT is similar in its approach to the other commonly used consensus method, the Delphi technique, however, there are also some significant differences. NGT allows for participants to be novices (as opposed to experts' opinions in Delphi) and also, NGT facilitates discussion amongst participants (unlike Delphi's anonymous responses). Thus, NGT is more appropriate for this study. Foth, Efstathiou and Vanderspank-Wright et al (2016) carried out a review of the use of Delphi and NGT in nursing education. Looking at published studies (n=101), using the consensus technique, Foth et al, purported that NGT has been well proven within nursing education to help define competence and learning needs, to assist in curricular review and also to facilitate learning conversations around perceived academic prowess and its link to experiential learning (linking theory to practice).

Moreover, Harvey and Holmes (2012) suggest that NGT strengthens focus groups as a data collection technique as all participants are included, all views and experiences get the chance to be shared (even opposing views) and as such, participants gain a sense of purpose, inclusion and ownership of the research (Cunningham, 2017). Harvey and Holmes (2012) further suggest that this notion of a consensual group voice and shared ownership increases the power of research findings and thus can enhance the power of the findings to influence change in healthcare, education and policy.

Nonetheless, whilst NGT gives power and voice to the research participants, it must be planned and focused to meet the research aims (Yin, 2018, Foth et al, 2016). The research aims were thus revisited so that questions could be formulated for the NGT focus groups. This is detailed in the table below;

Research Aim	Focus Group Questions Relating to Aim	Research Theme being Explored in Focus Group Question
To understand undergraduate student nurse perceptions of dementia care and their role in care delivery.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What knowledge/skills/experiences/qualities do you already have that will help you care for people with dementia. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role adequacy; Perceptions of current abilities and knowledge. • Role legitimacy; Perceptions of whether best placed to meet patients care needs.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do you hope/need to learn/gain to help you care for patients with dementia? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role Support; Perceptions of learning needs and support required.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What challenges will be/have been your way? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role Support; Perceptions of learning needs and support required.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the solutions to these challenges and how can you move forward? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role legitimacy; Perceptions of whether best placed to provide solution to challenges. • Role Support; Perceptions of learning needs and support required to overcome challenges.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are your ultimate goals to help deliver excellent care to people with dementia? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role adequacy; Perceptions of current abilities and knowledge in facilitating change. • Role legitimacy; Perceptions of whether best placed to drive care excellence. • Role Support; Perceptions of learning needs and support required to facilitate ultimate care goals.
<p>To examine the influence of theory, skills training and clinical experience on approach to dementia care delivery amongst undergraduate student nurses.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What knowledge/skills/experiences/qualities do you already have that will help you care for patients with dementia? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role adequacy; Perceptions of current abilities and knowledge and the changes in these perceptions over time. • Role legitimacy; Perceptions of whether best placed to meet patients care needs and the changes in these perceptions over time.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do you hope/need to learn/gain to help you care for patients with dementia? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role Support; Perceptions of learning needs and support required and changes in these

		perceptions over time.
To explore how dementia training policy directives for pre-registration nurse education is reflected in undergraduate student nurses' knowledge, skills and readiness for nursing practice.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What knowledge/skills/experiences/qualities do you already have that will help you care for patients with dementia? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role adequacy; Perceptions of current abilities and knowledge, in relation to key policy drivers. • Role legitimacy; Perceptions of whether best placed to meet patients care needs as detailed in key policy documents.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do you hope/need to learn/gain to help you care for patients with dementia? 	Role Support; Perceptions of learning needs and support required to be ready to deliver evidence-based dementia care.

Table 5.5: Focus Group Questions in Relation to Research Aims and Themes of Study

Furthermore, whilst the focus group questions were linked to the overall research aims, it was also essential to plan the focus group from start to finish to ensure an effective and productive use of time. Thus, a focus group guide was devised (see appendix 10) and this assisted in the organisation of the focus group, as well as ensuring a parity of approach in each focus group.

Indeed, the use of NGT also assisted in the structure of the focus group. As acknowledged by Foth et al (2016), NGT reflects the structured approach of quantitative research but by adopting a qualitative technique, which correlates well with the mixed method approach to this study. Such mixed method ideology is apparent in the ranking of ideas in NGT and in the structured

approach to its implementation. To provide such structure, the staged approach, as exemplified by Cunningham (2017) was adopted;

Stage 1	Idea generation and personal note taking. Individuals silently write ideas.
Stage 2	Generated ideas shared one at a time. Everyone participates in turn and shares what they have written.
Stage 3	Clarification. Similar ideas are grouped together. Any duplicates are removed. Clarification of meanings if required is discussed by the participants.
Stage 4	Reflective discussion. Group perceptions and sharing of ideas/thoughts/feelings.
Stage 5	Statements are ranked in order of priority. Rankings are discussed and group consensus achieved.

Table 5.5.1: Stages of Nominal Group Technique

This first ranking of statements commences the first stage of data analysis in NGT, however, it is recognised that data must be analysed in context as group dynamics can change the meaning of assertions (Griffiths, 2009), therefore as recommended by Walshaw (2012), the focus groups were both audio and video recorded to capture the reconstruction of conversation in the full context in which it was said (see consent form, appendix 6).

To further enhance the NGT experience for the research participants and to provide an alternative to the use of 'coloured post-its' to write upon, as suggested by Cunningham (2017), the 'Ketso Kit' was considered. The Ketso kit had previously provided a visual learning stimulus and conversation starter within the University environment (in other research projects) and its applicability to this study was very apparent.

5.6: The Ketso Kit

The Ketso Kit is an interactive tool that takes inspiration from the mind map as devised by Buzan and Buzan (1993) and utilises the ethos of experiential learning (Kolb, 1984 – as discussed in Chapter Three). Recognised by Whitworth, iCalvo and Moss, et al (2015), the Ketso Kit is a visual learning tool that facilitates a fun way to concept map. It is a hands-on kit, whereby participants use colourful leaves to write ideas upon and the leaves are strategically placed on tree-like branches to provide an overall picture or map of the landscape of ideas. The kinetic notion of the leaves fits well with the flexible nature of qualitative research and the visual learning aspect helps participants envisage how their unique contribution fits into the wider perspective of ideas (Whitworth et al, 2015).

The Ketso kit was used at all focus groups and the stages of its use is exemplified in the following table, which again demonstrates a staged approach to NGT as advised by Cunningham (2017);

Stage 1	<p>Idea generation and personal note taking.</p> <p>Individuals silently write ideas on their coloured leaves.</p> <p>Each colour of leaf relates to a different question.</p>
Stage 2	<p>Generated ideas shared one at a time.</p> <p>Everyone participates in turn and shares what they have written, putting their leaf on the appropriate branch as they explain their idea.</p>
Stage 3	<p>Clarification. Similar leaves are grouped together on the same branch.</p> <p>Any duplicates are removed.</p> <p>Clarification of meanings if required is discussed by the participants.</p>
Stage 4	<p>Reflective discussion.</p> <p>Group perceptions and sharing of ideas/thoughts/feelings.</p> <p>Some leaves may be moved around at this time as meaning and perceptions are altered following discussion.</p>
Stage 5	<p>Statements are ranked in order of priority.</p> <p>Rankings are discussed and group consensus achieved.</p> <p>Participants can clearly see all leaves and get a visual clue to the main concepts generated.</p>

Table 5.6: Stages of Nominal Group Technique Using the Ketso Kit

As can be seen from the table above, NGT integrates extremely well with the Ketso Kit, however for further clarity, it is useful to get visual representation of the Ketso Kit in action. The following picture on the left is an example of the Ketso Kit and on the right, initial rankings using the Ketso;

Figure 5.6: The Ketso Kit in Action

Thus, the use of the Ketso kit, assisted the research participants to feel comfortable in participating in the research and to feel that their contribution was valued, as well as providing an innovative and visually interactive, fun way of integrating NGT into the research focus groups. However, it is important to acknowledge that the mere presence of the researcher can influence the research findings (Flick, 2018) and thus, the notion of reflexivity is useful to help to ensure a rigorous approach to qualitative data collection (Yin, 2018).

5.7: Reflexivity

One of the advantages of using focus groups is to let research participants control the flow of the conversation, which can naturally lead to more in-depth sharing of thoughts and feelings (Gray, 2014). However, it is recognised that the researcher can hinder discussion (Bryman, 2016, Maher, Hadfield, Hutchings et al, 2018) and can also introduce bias by imposing personal viewpoints (Thomas, 2009). This view is shared by Bowling (2009) who additionally feels that when health professionals are the researchers, research participants sometimes only give the ‘public’ view of their feelings and often hold back their true feelings, particularly if they are likely to offend (such as unhappiness with healthcare). This is very applicable in this study, not only because the students are being asked to discuss the emotive subject of dementia care, but also because the researcher is a nursing lecturer and students may feel they cannot share their true feelings. To try to avoid students feeling this way, data was only collected from students on the campuses where the researcher did not teach. Therefore, at time 1, the researcher was

completely unknown to the students. The students were also informed of the confidentiality of their participation and the lack of any repercussion of involvement or indeed withdrawal from the study in both the participant information sheet and consent forms.

Moreover, as the researcher is a nurse and nurse lecturer and thus has knowledge of and previous experience of delivering dementia care, it was also important that the researcher's personal knowledge and experience did not affect the researcher's interpretation of the participants' discussion during the focus groups. Therefore, the researcher practiced reflexivity by identifying her own preconceptions relating to the study and setting them aside. As advocated by Casey and Houghton (2010), to enhance reflexivity, the researcher kept a reflective diary, a technique adopted from the start of the PhD journey to encourage ongoing reflection and recognition of bias, thus helping the researcher become an independent, objective researcher (Walshaw, 2012). Indeed, taking such steps to minimise preconceptions, is acknowledged by O'Leary (2004) as a method to help stop the 'contamination' of results and thus ensure the credibility of the researcher and rigour of the research (Bowling, 2009, Bazeley, 2018).

5.7.1: Rigour

It is well recognised that qualitative research is not always generalisable (Grix, 2010, Bryman, 2016). The data collected in qualitative research is most often related to feelings and perceptions and thus is unique to the individual experiencing it and is context specific (Maher, et al, 2018). Whilst this uniqueness is exactly what qualitative research seeks to understand, this individualised experience and the fact that qualitative research is usually carried out in small scale studies, means that it cannot be said with any confidence (unlike quantitative research), that everyone else sharing the same characteristics feels the same way. Therefore, standard measures of reliability, replicability, and validity that seek to demonstrate rigour, are more appropriate for quantitative research, rather than qualitative research (Maher et al, 2018). However, Bryman (2016) suggests that qualitative research can be tested for validity, reliability and rigour by considering its trustworthiness. Such trustworthiness is made up of 4 criteria, namely; credibility, transferability, dependability and confirmability.

Whilst the validity and reliability of the quantitative aspect of this study has already been proven, as this is a mixed methods study, it was equally important to consider each aspect of trustworthiness and thus ensure rigour, for the qualitative aspect of this study.

5.7.2: Trustworthiness

Ensuring credibility involves the researcher carrying out the research with complete accuracy and in a thorough manner, recognised by Tight (2017) as demonstration that data collection and analysis is accurate and appropriate to the research study design. Transferability is the qualitative research equivalent to generalisability. If the research is in-depth and contextually rich, it is recognised by Bryman (2016), that the theory generated may be able to be transferred to another area or used in another context. Dependability is achieved by completing full and accurate records of the research process, from planning of research design to data analysis, in enough detail to facilitate replication of the study (Maher et al, 2018). Lastly, confirmability involves the researcher ensuring objectivity by minimising bias in the prior acknowledgement and setting aside of any preconceptions (Bryman, 2016).

As advised by Korstjens and Moser (2017), it is useful to plan and provide clarity on all aspects of trustworthiness, therefore, in keeping with the transparent processes exemplified throughout this study, the specifics of achieving trustworthiness are detailed in the following table;

Trustworthiness Characteristic	Method of Achievement in this Study
Credibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A theoretical framework (Social Learning Theory) underpinned this study. • As part of nominal group technique, the research participants rated their discussion and as such, data analysis is started by the research participants. • The focus groups transcripts were both video and audio recorded and transcribed by the researcher in a timely soon after the event, to ensure authenticity of the verbatim discussion.
Transferability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The findings of the study will be compared to the literature to draw comparisons to similar studies in other areas.
Dependability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As this study is being completed as part of a PhD, the research journey has been articulated in detail throughout, with each decision made justified and set in context by the critical analysis of relevant evidence.
Confirmability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The researcher only collected data from students that were not based at the researcher's base campus. • The researcher pre-acknowledged her knowledge and experience of delivering dementia care and set aside all pre-conceptions.

Table 5.7.2: Trustworthiness

As can be seen from the above table, the researcher has considered all aspects of trustworthiness for the qualitative data collection.

5.8: Summary

In summary, this chapter has critically examined the data collection methods for both the quantitative and qualitative aspects of the research study. The data collection timings were

articulated and the use of the survey questionnaire as a quantitative data collection tool was critiqued. The background to the DDCPQ, with its central themes of Role Adequacy, Role Legitimacy and Role Support were critiqued and the psychometric properties of the DDCPQ confirmed, proving it to be a valid and reliable tool. Thereafter, the qualitative data collection through the use of focus groups was critiqued, justifying the use of nominal group technique and the 'Ketso Kit' to assist data collection. Finally, reflexivity, rigour and trustworthiness within the qualitative data collection was confirmed.

Now that the methods of data collection have been clearly articulated and the study methods confirmed to be reliable, valid and trustworthy, the next chapter will present the quantitative study results.

Chapter Six: Quantitative Results

This chapter will present the quantitative data results and analysis. As identified in Chapter Four, this study is a prospective, longitudinal mixed methods case study, therefore, there were many ways to present the data (Bowling, 2014, Bazeley, 2018). Whilst it is essential to ensure the integration of quantitative and qualitative data through complementary analysis in a mixed methods study (Bazeley, 2018) it is also recognised that analysis of multiple variables and analysis over time can be complex and difficult to present in a complementary style (Yin, 2018). Although concurrent triangulation of the quantitative and qualitative data as advocated by O’Cathan et al (2010), was carried out throughout this longitudinal study, it is recognised by Bazeley (2018) that a sequential approach to presentation of data findings can make it easier to extract significant findings. Thus, a ‘layering’ approach to the presentation of results was adopted (Cresswell and Plano Clark, 2011). The results will be presented or layered individually by chapter (quantitative and then qualitative) and then enhanced analysis through triangulation of both data sets will set the study as a ‘unified whole’ (Bazely, 2018) in Chapter Eight.

For the purposes of this chapter of quantitative results, data collection timings, response rates and demographic data will be detailed to provide an overview of the population (case) studied. Thereafter, student’s perceptions and the changes over time will be detailed, in relation to the underpinning main themes of the survey questionnaire (Role Adequacy, Role Legitimacy and Role Support).

6.0: Data Collection Timings

As a reminder, the quantitative data was collected over the 3-year undergraduate program of the September 2014 cohort BSc Adult Nursing programme at UWS;

Figure 6.0: Data Collection Timings

All students at Paisley, Ayr and Dumfries campuses were invited to participate in the study and response rates were tracked from T1 to T4.

6.1: Response Rates

In longitudinal studies, response rates usually decline as the study continues (Walker and Almond, 2010, Field, 2014, Bazely, 2018). Whilst this was demonstrated within this study, response rates remained extremely favourable at 92% (T1), 83% (T2), 89% (T3) and 81% (T4) respectively. The issue of non-response bias was therefore not a concern as response rates were excellent by longitudinal context and thus help to enhance the validity and reliability of the representativeness of the study as a whole. By gaining over 80% response rate, it is suggested by Fincham (2008) that this helps to capture the true characteristics of the population under study and is only usually achieved through multiple contact with research participants (as was the case in this longitudinal study). However, it also must be acknowledged that repeated involvement with research or over familiarisation with data collection tools can affect students' responses due to remembered responses and thus skew results. Whilst this is a recognised potential occurrence in repeated measures studies such as this, it is unlikely to happen in a

longitudinal study where data collections are a year apart. Yin (2018) acknowledges that extended involvement with longitudinal research studies is more likely to result in positive personalisation of the research by the participants, with students feeling part of the research journey. Indeed, this personalisation not only increases the likelihood for continual engagement in the research but also assists in case study research where an in-depth awareness of the case under study is desirable.

Moreover, to further enhance this in-depth understanding of the students and to provide deeper analysis of the changes in responses over time, students were also individually tracked. Using unique identifiers, 52% of the cohort (n=192) were able to be tracked from T1 to T4. Total response rates are detailed in the table below as well as tracked response rates year by year;

	Questionnaires Issued	Questionnaires Completed	Overall Response Rate
Students Commencing Year 1 (Ayr, Paisley and Dumfries); Time 1	455	420	92%
Students Commencing Year 2 (Ayr, Paisley and Dumfries); Time 2	419	349	83%
Time 2 Tracked Returns	T1-T2 tracked	305	73%
Students Commencing Year 3 (Ayr, Paisley and Dumfries); Time 3	381	339	89%
Time 3 Tracked Returns	T1-T2-T3 tracked	249	65%
Students Finishing BSc Programme (Ayr, Paisley and Dumfries); Time 4	372	302	81%
Time 4 Tracked Returns	T1-T2-T3-T4 tracked	192	52%

Table 6.1: Total Response Rates: DDCPO

To examine whether the response rate, pattern of trackable returns and other non-useable returns were the same on each campus, responses were also broken-down campus by campus.

6.1.1: Ayr Campus Responses

	Questionnaires Issued	Questionnaires Completed	Overall Response Rate
Students Commencing Year 1 Ayr; Time 1	159	151	95%
Students Commencing Year 2 Ayr; Time 2	154	144	94%
Time 2 Tracked Returns	T1-T2 tracked	124	81%
Students Commencing Year 3 Ayr; Time 3	143	131	92%
Time 3 Tracked Returns	T1-T2-T3 tracked	104	73%
Students Finishing Programme; Time 4	140	98	70%
Time 4 Tracked Returns	T1-T2-T3-T4 tracked	69	49%

Table 6.1.1: Response Rates Ayr Campus: DDCPQ

Ayr Campus	T2	T3	T4
Other Total Returns	20	27	29
Joiners	10	2	0
No Banner (unable to track change)	3	0	0
No previous data (various possible causes)	7	25	29
No further data (IS, student withdrawn, chose not to participate further)	27	20	24

Table 6.1.1a: Other Returns: Ayr Campus

6.1.2: Paisley Campus Responses

	Questionnaires Issued	Questionnaires Completed	Overall Response Rate
Students Commencing Year 1 Paisley; Time 1	230	205	89%
Students Commencing Year 2 Paisley; Time 2	207	148	71%
Time 2 Tracked Returns	T1-T2 tracked	128	62%
Students Commencing Year 3 Paisley; Time 3	192	164	85%
Time 3 Tracked Returns	T1-T2-T3 tracked	104	54%
Students Finishing Programme; Time 4	186	168	90%
T4 Tracked Returns	T1-T2-T3-T4 tracked	88	47%

Table 6.1.2: Response Rates Paisley Campus: DDCPQ

Paisley Campus	T2	T3	T4
Other Total Returns	20	60	87
Joiners	7	0	0
No Banner (unable to track change)	4	2	0
No previous data (various possible causes)	9	58	87
No further data (IS, student withdrawn, chose not to participate further)	77	17	23

Table 6.1.2a: Other Returns Paisley Campus

6.1.3: Dumfries Campus Responses

	Questionnaires Issued	Questionnaires Completed	Overall Response Rate
Students Commencing Year 1 Dumfries; Time 1	66	64	97%
Students Commencing Year 2 Dumfries; Time 2	58	57	98%
Time 2 Tracked Returns	T1-T2 tracked	53	92%
Students Commencing Year 3 Dumfries; Time 3	46	44	96%
Time 3 Tracked Returns	T1-T2-T3 tracked	41	89%
Students Finishing Programme; Time 4	46	36	78%
Time 4 Tracked Returns	T1-T2-T3-T4 tracked	35	76%

Table 6.1.3: Response Rates Dumfries Campus: DDCPQ

Dumfries Campus	T2	T3	T4
Other Total Returns	4	3	1
T2 Joiners	2	0	0
No Banner (unable to track change)	2	0	0
No previous data (various possible causes)	0	3	1
No further data at T2 (IS, student withdrawn, chose not to participate further)	11	12	6

Table 6.1.3a: Other Returns Dumfries Campus

6.1.4: Response Rate Summary

As can be seen from the tables above, the response rates were the highest in Dumfries campus (the smallest of the campuses) and the lowest in Paisley campus (the largest of the campuses), however this difference in response was non-significant ($p=0.512$). As participation was entirely voluntary and consent to participate implied by completion of the questionnaire, there was no individually identifiable data collected on reasons for choice of non-completion. However, for students that were in this position and had no further data available, this would be due to; choice not to participate at next data collection, being unable to participate due to being on interrupted study (time out of the nursing programme) or being withdrawn from the nursing programme. Although there were only a few students that fell into this category, individual data was not collected on this as accessing individual student's records was outside of ethical approval for the study and indeed infringed the student's rights to confidentiality.

Despite this, it was apparent that the greatest attrition of student numbers was evident at T2 (the start of year 2, thus attrition during year 1 of the nursing programme), which correlates with the literature on student progression and attrition in nursing (Urwin, Stanley, Jones et al, 2010, Orton, 2011). Although total student numbers reflect this in the tables above, these are total numbers of students in each year and thus have joiners (new students) added. When broken down by questionnaire response, it was evident that at T2 there was no further data available for $n=115$ students (from T1 into T2), $n=49$ students (from T2 into T3) and $n=53$ students (from T3 into T4) respectively, further reflecting the increased attrition at the beginning of the nursing course. This is even more noteworthy when considering that T2 had the greatest number of joiners ($n=19$) to the programme and thus student progression figures were even higher than they could have been compared to joiners $n=2$ (T3) and $n=0$ (T4). These joiners were HNC students who can articulate into the second year of an undergraduate nursing programme, having completed the equivalent of year 1 at a further education college.

Indeed, this information and other such educational and demographic data can be set in context by examining the student demographic profile. All data set questions and intervals of response parameters (such as; age 26-30, education: basic/advanced) are directly comparable with the

layout of the original questionnaire as developed by Cartwright (1980b) and were not changed as part of this study.

6.2: The Student Profile

The student profile is best exemplified by considering the greatest number of responses (n=420) at T1 (induction week). Demographic data was collected from all participants as part of the survey questionnaire (see appendix 9, Section A). Firstly, participating student response rates per campus were collected.

Total student response was (n=420), between Paisley Campus (n=205), Ayr Campus (n=151) and Dumfries Campus (n=64);

Figure 6.2: DDCPQ: Student Response by Campus

Reflective of the nursing population as a whole, there were more female students (n=371), than male students (n=49);

Figure 6.2.1: DDCPQ: Student Response by Sex

The majority of students were under 25 years of age at course commencement. Age under 25 (n=230), age 26-30 (n=74), age 31-40 (n=86), age 41-50 (n=23) and age 51-60 (n=7);

Figure 6.2.2: DDCPQ: Student Response by Age

Reflective of government funded spaces for nursing per field of practice in Scotland, most students were studying adult nursing (n= 342) compared to mental health nursing (n=78);

Figure 6.2.3: DDCPQ: Student Response by Course

Most students, regardless of course (adult/mental health), had no experience of ever working in dementia care (n=295), with only some having limited experience (n=125);

Figure 6.2.4: DDCPQ: Experience in Working with Dementia

Of those with experience, not all still worked in dementia care (n=95), with most students not currently employed in dementia care (n=325);

Figure 6.2.5: DDCPQ: Currently Employed in Dementia Care

Of those with experience of caring for people with dementia, this experience was limited. The majority of students had never cared for anyone with dementia (n=182), some had cared for 1-10 people (n=97), 11-25 people (n=33), 26-50 people (n=56), 51 to 100 people (n=32) and greater than 100 people (n=20);

Figure 6.2.6: DDCPQ: How Many People with Dementia Have You Cared For?

More specifically, when asked about counselling people with dementia, nearly all of the students indicated that they had never counselled anyone with dementia (n=354), some had counselled 1-10 people (n=39), 11-25 people (n=9), 26-50 people (n=4), 51-100 people (n=7) and greater than 100 people (n=7);

Figure 6.2.7: DDCPQ: How Many People with Dementia Have You Counselling?

Whilst some students indicated experience in dementia care, this experience was not always associated with having had any education on dementia. Most students (n=199) indicated they had never received any form of dementia education, some had received basic education (n=118), advanced education (n=51) and other forms of education (n=52);

Figure 6.2.8: DDCPQ: Dementia Education

Even for those who had received some education, this was in the most part not followed up with any additional education (n=318), with less than a quarter of students receiving additional education (n=102);

Figure 6.2.9: DDCPQ: Additional Dementia Education

Breaking down the education into total hours equivalent in days, again the majority of students had received no education (n=197), some receiving 1 day or less (n=72), 2-4 days (n=35), 5-7 days (n=24), 8-14 days (n=16) and greater than 14 days (n=76);

Figure 6.2.10: DDCPQ: Hours of Education

Furthermore, despite the multifactorial effects of dementia on both the person and their family, the majority of students (n=379) had never attended any training courses on counselling people with dementia and their carers' with only a minority receiving training (n=41);

Figure 6.2.11: DDCPQ: Training Courses Attended

Moreover, although the majority of students had received very little dementia education, for those who had previously worked in dementia care or indeed were currently working in dementia care, this lack of education was compensated in part by greater levels of supervision in the care delivery role. Most students (in correspondence with their inexperience) had never received any supervision of care delivery (n=312) which seems a lot, however, of the (n=125) students that had worked in dementia care, (n=108, 86%) had received some supervision;

Figure 6.2.12: DDCPQ: Supervision Received

When probed for more detail on the type of supervision, (n=337) indicated that they had not received ongoing supervision, (again this included the students with no experience). Interestingly, this meant though that (n=83, 66% of those with caring experience) received ongoing supervision in dementia care delivery;

Figure 6.2.13: DDCPQ: Ongoing Supervision

Whilst the above figures give an overview of the student demographic at course inception, the Likert scale component of the survey questionnaire (see appendix 9, Section B), gave an overview of the students perceptions of their ability to deliver dementia care at this early stage in their nursing career.

6.3: Student's Perceptions of Role Adequacy, Role Legitimacy and Role Support at Course Commencement (T1)

Students were asked 41 questions in relation to the themes of the original MAPP hypothesis as discussed in Chapter Three. As a reminder, the components of the original MAPP hypothesis (Shaw et al, 1978, Cartwright, 1980b, Gorman and Cartwright 1991, Cartwright and Gorman, 1993), were;

- Training, experience and knowledge gain should have a positive effect on role adequacy and role legitimacy.
- Role support is influenced by role security.
- Role security influences levels of therapeutic commitment.

Using the original scoring system according to Cartwright (1980), a scoring syntax was added to SPSS (Version 25) (see appendix 11) to compute the student's scores on the following themes;

Figure 6.3: Themes of DDCPQ

Additionally, an Overall Attitude (OA) score was calculated using the standard scores for Therapeutic Commitment (TC) and Role Security (RS). Again, as per the original scoring system (Cartwright, 1980b), a mean of zero and a standard deviation of one was used.

Furthering the MAPP hypothesis and results of the original studies using the 41-item questionnaire (Shaw et al, 1978, Cartwright, 1980a, Gorman and Cartwright 1991, Cartwright and Gorman, 1993), low levels of TC were shown to be a result of role insecurity (low scores on RS). It was recognised that those who scored poorly on TC were not as successful working within their role. For this study, using the original scoring, all students who scored outside of the parameters (less than -1 or more than 1) were unlikely to be successful in working with dementia. Whilst the lack of experience of the students at T1 has already been acknowledged, all students (n=420) TC scores were then analysed to give a baseline TC at course commencement;

Figure 6.3.1: Overall Attitude Scores T1

As can be seen from the above chart, most student's scores for TC were within the acceptable threshold. Of the total student population at T1 (n=420), (n=77) were out-with the

recommended therapeutic range (18.3% of the students) and (n=343) (81.7% of the students) within the therapeutic range, thus suggesting that most students were likely to be successful working within dementia care, should they wish.

Whilst the original studies (Shaw et al, 1978, Cartwright, 1980a, Gorman and Cartwright 1991, Cartwright and Gorman, 1993) acknowledged that levels of experience can affect TC scores; education, knowledge and training were positively associated with therapeutic attitude if support for learning and experience was apparent.

To examine if this was evident within the student nurse population in this case study, repeated measures ANOVA, using a significance value of $p < 0.05$ (Walker and Almond, 2010, Field, 2014) was used to examine the dependent variable scores of Therapeutic Commitment, Role Security and Basic Role Requirements against the following independent variables;

- Campus
- Course
- Sex
- Age
- Dementia Education
- Additional Education
- Hours of Education
- Training Courses
- Number of People with Dementia that Student has Worked With
- Number of People with Dementia that Student has Counsellled
- Supervision in Dementia Care
- Ongoing Supervision
- Currently Employed in Dementia Care
- Previously Employed in Dementia Care

In accordance with time series analysis and the layering approach to data presentation (Cresswell and Plano Clark, 2011), findings will be presented for T1 to show baseline measures for all variables and then analysis of scores over time (T1 to T4) will be presented for each theme.

6.3.1: Therapeutic Commitment

Repeated measures ANOVA for Task Specific Self Esteem (TSSE) scores as a component of TC showed no significance when comparing campus, course, sex or age. However, highly significant findings were found when considering the independent variables of education, training, dealing with dementia, counselling people with dementia, receiving supervision and working in dementia care. The following table displays all independent variables in relation to the dependent variable of TSSE at T1 with (n=420 students). All statistically significant results include a statement of meaningfulness in relation to the study;

Independent Variable	ANOVA/Statistical Significance (n=420) (*statistically significant)	Meaningfulness
Campus	F=0.941, dF=2, p=0.391	
Course	F=0.065, dF=1, p=0.799	
Sex	F=3.274, dF=1, p=0.071	
Age	F=1.025, dF=4, p=0.394	
Education	F=29.928, dF=3, p=0.000*	Having received education on dementia was associated with higher scores of TSSE.
Additional Education	F=30.653, dF=1, p=0.000*	Having received additional education on dementia was associated with higher scores of TSSE.
Hours of Education Received	F=13.141, dF=5, p=0.000*	As the hours of education increased, scores for TSSE increased.
Training	F=20.898, dF=1, p=0.000*	Having received training on dementia care was associated with higher TSSE.
How Many People with Dementia Cared For	F=22.371, dF=5, p=0.000*	As numbers of people with dementia that students had cared for increased, TSSE scores decreased.
How Many People with Dementia Counselling	F=3.377, dF=5, p=0.005*	As numbers of people with dementia that students had counselled increased, TSSE scores decreased.
Supervision	F=26.767, dF=1, p=0.000*	Receiving supervision was associated with higher TSSE scores.

Ongoing Supervision	F=25.127, dF=1, p=0.000*	Having received ongoing supervision was associated with higher TSSE scores.
Currently Employed in Dementia Care	F=44.377, dF=1, p=0.000*	Being currently employed in dementia care reduced TSSE scores.
Previously Employed in Dementia Care	F=52.440, dF=1, p=0.000*	Being previously employed in dementia care reduced TSSE scores.

Table 6.3.1: TSSE Mean Scores and Significance at T1:

This supports previous findings and the hypothesis that education, knowledge and training positively affect task specific self-esteem. Also supporting this, when analysing Satisfaction Working with Dementia and Motivation to Work with Dementia as the another components of Therapeutic Commitment, satisfaction and motivation scores were significantly influenced by education, training, supervision and dementia care at T1 with (n=420 students);

Independent Variable	ANOVA/Statistical Significance (n=420) (*statistically significant)	Meaningfulness
Campus	F=0.984, dF=2, p=0.375	
Course	F=0.119, df=1, p=0.730	
Sex	F=0.935, dF=1, p=0.334	
Age	F=0.458, dF=4, p=0.766	
Education	F=10.290, dF=3, p=0.000*	Having received education on dementia was associated with higher scores of satisfaction.
Additional Education	F=18.752, dF=1, p=0.000*	Having received additional education on dementia was associated with higher scores of satisfaction.
Hours of Education Received	F=7.961, dF=5, p=0.000*	As the hours of education increased, scores for satisfaction increased.
Training	F=12.859, dF=1, p=0.000*	Having received training on dementia care was associated with higher scores of satisfaction.
How Many People with Dementia Cared For	F=13.221, dF=5, p=0.000*	As numbers of people with dementia that students had cared for increased, satisfaction scores decreased.
How Many People with Dementia Counselling	F=4.047, dF=5, p=0.001*	As numbers of people with dementia that students had counselled increased, satisfaction scores decreased.
Supervision	F=16.730, dF=1, p=0.000*	Receiving supervision was associated with higher satisfaction scores.
Ongoing Supervision	F=5.179, dF=1, p=0.023*	Having received ongoing supervision was associated with higher satisfaction scores.
Currently Employed in Dementia Care	F=41.760, dF=1, p=0.000*	Being currently employed in dementia care reduced satisfaction scores.
Previously Employed in Dementia Care	F=52.440, dF=1, p=0.000*	Being previously employed in dementia care reduced satisfaction scores.

Table 6.3.1a: Satisfaction in Working with Dementia: Mean Scores and Significance at T1

Independent Variable	ANOVA/Statistical Significance (n=420) (*statistically significant)	Meaningfulness
Campus	F=0.158, dF=2, p=0.854	
Course	F=0.430, df=1, p=0.513	
Sex	F=3.274, dF=1, p=0.0712	
Age	F=1.161, dF=4, p=0.327	
Education	F=8.019, dF=3, p=0.000*	Having received education on dementia was associated with higher scores of motivation.
Additional Education	F=10.245, dF=1, p=0.001*	Having received additional education on dementia was associated with higher scores of motivation.
Hours of Education Received	F=4.256, dF=5, p=0.001*	As the hours of education increased, scores for motivation increased.
Training	F=15.661, dF=1, p=0.000*	Having received training on dementia care was associated with higher motivation scores.
How Many People with Dementia Cared For	F=7.768, dF=5, p=0.000*	As numbers of people with dementia that students had cared for increased, motivation scores decreased.
How Many People with Dementia Counselling	F=5.065, dF=5, p=0.000*	As numbers of people with dementia that students had counselled increased, motivation scores decreased.
Supervision	F=7.020, dF=1, p=0.008*	Receiving supervision was associated with higher motivation scores.
Ongoing Supervision	F=5.190, dF=1, p=0.023*	Having received ongoing supervision was associated with higher motivation scores.
Currently Employed in Dementia Care	F=16.856, dF=1, p=0.000*	Being currently employed in dementia care reduced motivation scores.
Previously Employed in Dementia Care	F=23.980, dF=1, p=0.000*	Being previously employed in dementia care reduced motivation scores.

Table 6.3.1b: Motivation to Work with Dementia: Mean Scores and Significance at T1

To examine whether this significance was apparent in the other themes, Role Security was explored next.

6.3.2: Role Security

Again, ANOVA was used with the same dependent and independent variables, testing for scores of Role Adequacy (RA) as a component of Role Security (RS) with (n=420) students at T1. Similar to TC, there were no significant differences according to course, sex and age, however, there were significant findings in relation to campus location, education, training, supervision and experience in dementia care;

Independent Variable	ANOVA/Statistical Significance (n=420) (*statistically significant)	Meaningfulness
Campus	F=6.125, dF=2, p=0.002*	Dumfries campus scored more highly on RA but as per discussion below, reasons for this could not be accounted for and thus, whilst significant, was it not deemed as a meaningful finding at this time.
Course	F=0.284, df=1, p=0.595	
Sex	F=1.180, dF=1, p=0.278	
Age	F=0.876, dF=4, p=0.478	
Education	F=115.556, dF=3, p=0.000*	Having received education on dementia was associated with increased scores for RA.
Additional Education	F=105.383, dF=1, p=0.000*	Having received additional education on dementia was associated with higher scores for RA.
Hours of Education Received	F=58.911, dF=5, p=0.000*	As the hours of education increased, scores for RA increased.
Training	F=51.98, dF=1, p=0.000*	Having received training on dementia care was associated with higher scores for RA.
How Many People with Dementia Cared For	F=71.241, dF=5, p=0.000*	As numbers of people with dementia that students had cared for increased, RA scores decreased.
How Many People with Dementia Counselling	F=14.060, dF=5, p=0.000*	As numbers of people with dementia that students had counselled increased, RA scores decreased.

Supervision	F=86.533, dF=1, p=0.000*	Receiving supervision was associated with higher RA scores.
Ongoing Supervision	F=48.698, dF=1, p=0.000*	Having received ongoing supervision was associated with higher RA scores.
Currently Employed in Dementia Care	F=121.461, dF=1, p=0.000*	Being currently employed in dementia care reduced RA scores.
Previously Employed in Dementia Care	F=124.947, dF=1, p=0.000*	Being previously employed in dementia care reduced RA scores.

Table 6.3.2: Role Adequacy: Mean Scores and Significance at T1

When considering that education, training, supervision and experience could have positively influenced feelings of Role Adequacy, Dumfries responses were then analysed further to try to establish reasons for the increased feelings of RA. There were no significant differences per campus on levels of education, training, working with dementia or previous working with dementia that may have influenced RA scores. Thereafter, age was also analysed (considering increased potential exposure to people with dementia by age) but again this was not significant so thus the increased RA scores at Dumfries could not be accounted for with the quantitative statistics. However, RA will be further analysed by considering the changes in perception over time in both this chapter and the following qualitative chapter.

Thereafter, as the final component of Role Security, Role Legitimacy (RL) was analysed. Repeated measures ANOVA for RL as a component of RS showed no significant difference by campus, course or sex. However, there was a significant difference in score according to education, training, supervision and dementia care experience with (n=420) students at T1;

Independent Variable	ANOVA/Statistical Significance (n=420) (*statistically significant)	Meaningfulness
Campus	F=1.759, df=2, p=0.173	
Course	F=0.165, df=1, p=0.685	
Sex	F=0.554, df=1, p=0.457	
Age	F=2.650, df=4, p=0.033*	Increased age associated with increased feelings of RL.
Education	F=30.762, df=3, p=0.000*	Having received education on dementia was associated with higher scores of RL.
Additional Education	F=41.423, df=1, p=0.000*	Having received additional education on dementia was associated with higher scores of RL.
Hours of Education Received	F=15.110, df=5, p=0.000*	As the hours of education increased, scores for RL increased.
Training	F=24.846, df=1, p=0.000*	Having received training on dementia care was associated with higher scores for RL.
How Many People with Dementia Cared For	F=28.653, df=5, p=0.000*	As numbers of people with dementia that students had cared for increased, RL scores decreased.
How Many People with Dementia Counselling	F=8.152, df=5, p=0.000*	As numbers of people with dementia that students had counselled increased, RL scores decreased.
Supervision	F=44.916, df=1, p=0.000*	Receiving supervision was associated with higher RL scores.
Ongoing Supervision	F=22.533, df=1, p=0.000*	Having received ongoing supervision was associated with higher RL scores.
Currently Employed in Dementia Care	F=50.313, df=1, p=0.000*	Being currently employed in dementia care reduced RL scores.
Previously Employed in Dementia Care	F=46.749, df=1, p=0.000*	Being previously employed in dementia care reduced RL scores.

Table 6.3.2b: Role Legitimacy: Mean Scores and Significance at T1

Indeed, it has already been established that students on all campuses had similarly low levels of education and experience in dementia care at T1. Thus, this positive association between age

and feelings of RL could only be attributed to greater life experiences that bring with it the ability to communicate personal skills such as empathy (which will be further explored in the next chapter) and relates to basic role requirements.

6.3.3: Basic Role Requirements

Repeated measures ANOVA for Role Support scores as a component of Basic Role Requirements showed no significant difference by campus, course, sex or age. As per the other components of TC, there were highly significant differences with all independent variables related to education, training, supervision and dementia care experience for (n=420 students) at T1;

Independent Variable	ANOVA/Statistical Significance (n=420) (*statistically significant)	Meaningfulness
Campus	F=1.534, dF=2, p=0.217	
Course	F=0.143, df=1, p=0.705	
Sex	F=0.554, dF=1, p=0.457	
Age	F=1.492, dF=4, p=0.204	
Education	F=12.919, dF=3, p=0.000*	Having received education on dementia was associated with less requirement for support.
Additional Education	F=12.093, dF=1, p=0.001*	Having received additional education on dementia was associated with less requirement for support.
Hours of Education Received	F=6.651, dF=5, p=0.000*	As the hours of education increased, need for support decreased.
Training	F=11.656, dF=1, p=0.001*	Having received training on dementia care was associated with less need for support.
How Many People with Dementia Cared For	F=10.059, dF=5, p=0.000*	As numbers of people with dementia that students had cared for increased, need for support decreased.

How Many People with Dementia Counselling	F=4.446, dF=5, p=0.001*	As numbers of people with dementia that students had counselled increased, need for support decreased.
Supervision	F=20.805, dF=1, p=0.000*	Receiving supervision was associated with less requirement for support.
Ongoing Supervision	F=14.888, dF=1, p=0.000*	Having received ongoing supervision was associated with less requirement for support.
Currently Employed in Dementia Care	F=40.379, dF=1, p=0.000*	Being currently employed in dementia care reduced the need for support.
Previously Employed in Dementia Care	F=29.976, dF=1, p=0.000*	Being previously employed in dementia care reduced the need for support.

Table 6.3.3: Role Support: Mean Scores and Significance at T1

Lastly, Self Esteem as a component of Basic Role Requirements was analysed. Repeated measures ANOVA demonstrated no significant differences in relation to the demographics of campus, course, sex or age. However, when considering the other independent variables, the only significant finding was having received education (F=4.301, dF=3, p=0.005). Unlike the other aspects of TC, there were no other significant score effects from receiving ongoing education, training, supervision or having experience in dementia care with (n=420) students at T1;

Independent Variable	ANOVA/Statistical Significance (n=420) (*statistically significant)	Meaningfulness
Campus	F=0.128, dF=2, p=0.879	
Course	F=2.825, df=1, p=0.094	
Sex	F=0.286, dF=1, p=0.593	
Age	F=0.834, dF=4, p=0.504	
Education	F=4.308, dF=3, p=0.005*	Having received education on dementia was associated with higher scores of self-esteem.
Additional Education	F=1.893, dF=1, p=0.170	
Hours of Education Received	F=0.610, dF=5, p=0.692	
Training	F=0.021, dF=1, p=0.886	
How Many People with Dementia Cared For	F=0.668, dF=5, p=0.648	
How Many People with Dementia Counselling	F=0.646, dF=5, p=0.665	
Supervision	F=0.290, dF=1, p=0.590	
Ongoing Supervision	F=2.235, dF=1, p=0.136	
Currently Employed in Dementia Care	F=1.590, dF=1, p=0.208	
Previously Employed in Dementia Care	F=1.954, dF=1, p=0.163	

Table 6.3.3a: Self-Esteem: Mean Scores and Significance at T1

Lastly, overall attitude was analysed.

6.3.4: Overall Attitude Score

Analysing all components of Therapeutic Commitment and Role Security resulted in the overall attitude (OA) score. Repeated measures ANOVA for OA showed no significant difference by campus, course, sex or age. As per all the components in relation to the OA, there were highly significant differences in scores with all independent variables related to education, training, supervision and dementia care experience, with (n=420) students at T1;

Independent Variable	ANOVA/Statistical Significance (n=420) (*statistically significant)	Meaningfulness
Campus	F=2.557 dF=2, p=0.079	
Course	F=0.028, df=1, p=0.869	
Sex	F=2.504, dF=1, p=0.114	
Age	F=1.137, dF=4, p=0.339	
Education	F=57.122, dF=3, p=0.000*	Having received education on dementia was associated with higher OA scores.
Additional Education	F=67.136, dF=1, p=0.000*	Having received additional education on dementia was associated with higher OA scores.
Hours of Education Received	F=29.582, dF=5, p=0.000*	As the hours of education increased, OA scores increased.
Training	F=44.994, dF=1, p=0.000*	Having received training on dementia care was associated with higher OA scores.
How Many People with Dementia Cared For	F=50.679, dF=5, p=0.000*	As numbers of people with dementia that students had cared for increased, OA scores decreased.
How Many People with Dementia Counselling	F=11.127, dF=5, p=0.000*	As numbers of people with dementia that students had counselled increased, OA scores decreased.
Supervision	F=58.823, dF=1, p=0.000*	Receiving supervision was associated with higher OA scores.
Ongoing Supervision	F=33.779, dF=1, p=0.000*	Having received ongoing supervision was associated with higher OA scores.

Currently Employed in Dementia Care	F=98.414, dF=1, p=0.000*	Being currently employed in dementia care reduced OA scores.
Previously Employed in Dementia Care	F=104.092, dF=1, p=0.000*	Being previously employed in dementia care reduced OA scores.

Table 6.3.4: Overall Attitude: Mean Scores and Significance at T1

Thus, after establishing baseline scores for all components in relation to the major themes of the study, the hypothesis that knowledge and training increase Role Adequacy and Legitimacy as part of Therapeutic Commitment was supported at T1. It was then essential to consider the changes in these scores over time.

6.4: Changes in Perceptions over Time

Changes in the student's questionnaire scores over time were analysed and statistical tests analysed for significance and hypothesis confirmability. Scores for Therapeutic Commitment, Role Security and Basic Role Requirements were analysed, as well as overall attitude scores.

6.4.1: Therapeutic Commitment: Task Specific Self Esteem

Task Specific Self Esteem (TSSE) as the first component of TC was analysed. Repeated measures ANOVA was used to examine relationships between and within variables.

There was a significant difference between campus and TSSE at T2 (F=; 4.061, dF=2, p=0.018); students in Paisley scored the highest and Ayr campus the lowest. There were no significant demographic differences between campuses to suggest a reason for this and this was not apparent at any other data collection, however Paisley campus did have a slightly younger in age cohort than the others.

Furthermore, there was a significant difference between TSSE and sex at both T2 ($F=4.882$, $df=1$, $p=0.028$) and T3 ($F=5.865$, $df=1$, $p=0.016$). Males scored higher on TSSE compared to females, but only at these 2 data collections.

As per T1, there was also a significant association between TSSE and education at T2 ($F=6.965$, $df=3$, $p=0.019$) but not at T3 or T4, suggesting education was more influential at the beginning of the nursing programme.

Additionally, as seen at T1, looking after people with dementia was significantly related to TSSE at T2 ($F=6.965$, $df=5$, $p=0.000$) and T3 ($F=5.977$, $df=4$, $p=0.000$) but not at T4.

Lastly, similar to T1, at T2, there was a significant association between TSSE and employment in dementia care; currently employed ($F=7.579$, $df=1$, $p=0.006$) and previously employed ($F=9.779$, $df=1$, $p=0.002$). This was not significant though at T3 or T4.

The following table displays all the significant findings with TSSE and maps these over time;

Independent Variable	ANOVA/Statistical Significance (*statistically significant)				Meaningfulness
	T1 (n=420)	T2 (n=305)	T3 (n=249)	T4 (n=192)	
Campus	F=0.941, df=2, p=0.391	F=4.061, df=2, p=0.018*	F=1.989, df=2, p=0.139	F=0.177, df=2, p=0.838	Significant finding at T2 but reason for finding not confirmed. Not recognised as meaningful at this stage.
Course	F=0.065, df=1, p=0.799	F=1.632, df=1, p=0.202	F=0.111, df=1, p=0.740	F=0.215, df=1, p=0.644	

Age	F=1.025, df=4, p=0.394	F=1.015, dF=2, p=0.400	F=1.075, dF=4, p=0.369	F=1.290, dF=4, p=0.275	
Sex	F=3.274, dF=1, p=0.071	F=4.882, dF=1, p=0.028*	F=5.865, dF=1, p=0.016*	F=0.047, dF=1, p=0.828	Males scored higher than females at T2 and T3 but reason for finding not confirmed. Not recognised as meaningful at this stage.
Education	F=29.928, dF=3, p=0.000*	F=3.374, dF=3, p=0.019*	F=1.344, dF=3, p=0.261	F=0.298, dF=3, p=0.827	Influence of education significant at beginning of programme. Education had positive effect on TSSE scores.
Additional Education	F=30.653, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=0.055, dF=1, p=0.815	F=0.357, dF=1, p=0.551	F=0.843, dF=1, p=0.360	Additional education significant at T1 with positive effect on TSSE scores.
Hours of Education	F=13.141, dF=5, p=0.000*	F=1.488, dF=5, p=0.207	F=0.341, dF=5, p=0.888	F=0.243, dF=5, p=0.943	Hours of education significant at T1, as hours of education increased, TSSE scores increased.
Training Course (counselling)	F=20.898, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=1.960, dF=1, p=0.163	F=0.903, dF=1, p=0.343	F=0.623, dF=1, p=0.431	Having attended a training course on dementia counselling significantly increased TSSE scores at T1.
Number of people with dementia (cared for)	F=22.371, dF=5, p=0.000*	F=6.965, dF=5, p=0.000*	F=5.977, dF=4, p=0.000*	F=0.245, dF=5, p=0.942	Number of people with dementia cared for had significant impact on TSSE scores at T1-T3. As numbers of people cared for increased, TSSE scores reduced.
Number of people with dementia (counselled)	F=3.377, dF=5, p=0.005*	F=4.479, dF=5, p=0.001*	F=3.643, dF=5, p=0.003*	F=0.409, dF=5, p=0.842	Number of people with dementia counselled had significant impact on TSSE scores at T1-T3. As numbers of people counselled increased, TSSE scores reduced.
Supervision	F=26.767, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=8.755, dF=1, p=0.003*	F=0.991, dF=2, p=0.373	F=0.310, dF=1, p=0.578	Supervision had significant impact at the beginning of the programme. Having received supervision had positive effect on TSSE scores.

Ongoing Supervision	F=25.127, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=0.015, dF=1, p=0.902	F=0.047, dF=1, p=0.828	F=1.837, dF=1, p=0.177	Ongoing supervision significant at T1 with a positive effect on TSSE scores.
Currently Employed in Dementia Care	F=44.377, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=7.579, dF=1, p=0.006*	F=0.158, dF=1, p=0.691	F=0.002, dF=1, p=0.965	Being employed in dementia care significantly reduced TSSE scores at the beginning of the undergraduate programme.
Previously Employed in Dementia Care	F=52.440, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=9.779, dF=1, p=0.002*	F=0.185, dF=1, p=0.667	F=0.090, dF=1, p=0.765	Being previously employed in dementia care, significantly reduced TSSE scores at the beginning of the undergraduate programme.

Table 6.4.1: Task Specific Self Esteem Over Time

As can be seen, most significant findings in relation to TSSE were evident at the beginning of the nursing programme. At T4 there were no significant relationships between TSSE and any of the variables.

Whilst significant findings for TSSE against other independent variables reduced throughout the course, there were also total scores for TSSE. Mean scores were calculated using one-way ANOVA and significance levels over time tested using a paired samples T-Test. As recommended by Field (2014), a confidence interval of 95% was used. The table below demonstrates mean scores and significance over time;

Time	Mean Score for TSSE	Changes over Time	Significant	Meaningfulness (as a % of total scores)
T1	17.01			
T2	16.48	T1 to T2 ($p=0.000$)	Yes	3% reduction
T3	13.62	T2 to T3 ($p=0.000$)	Yes	17% reduction
T4	12.46	T3 to T4 ($p=0.000$)	Yes	9% reduction

Table 6.4.1a: Task Specific Self Esteem Mean Scores and Significance Over Time

As can be seen, scores for TSSE changed significantly from T1 to T4 and total mean TSSE scores reduced from T1 to T4;

Figure 6.4.1: Task Specific Self Esteem Mean Scores over Time

Thus, as a component of Therapeutic Commitment, Task Specific Self Esteem, significantly reduced as the students progressed through their nursing programme with a 27% overall

reduction in scores from T1 to T4. As the next measure of Therapeutic Commitment, Satisfaction in Working with Dementia was analysed.

6.4.2: Therapeutic Commitment: Satisfaction in Working with Dementia

Repeated measures ANOVA was used to examine relationships between and within variables. Satisfaction levels as per TSSE were more significant at the beginning of the course with few significant findings as the nursing programme continued.

At T2 there was a significant association between satisfaction scores and age ($F=4.366$, $dF=4$, $p=0.002$). As age increased, satisfaction scores increased, thus older students displayed greater levels of satisfaction in working with dementia. This relationship was not however apparent at any other data collection than T2.

Like T1, satisfaction and the variable of caring for people with dementia indicated statistically significant results at T2 ($F=3.834$, $dF=5$, $p=0.002$) and T3 ($F=3.998$, $dF=4$, $p=0.004$). Interestingly though, greater exposure of caring for people with dementia did not increase satisfaction scores, in fact it was the complete opposite. As cared for numbers increased, satisfaction levels reduced, indicating the more that students cared for people with dementia, the less satisfied they felt.

The following table displays all the significant findings in relation to Satisfaction in Working with Dementia and maps these over time;

Independent Variable	ANOVA/Statistical Significance (*statistically significant)				Meaningfulness
	T1 (n=420)	T2 (n=305)	T3 (n=249)	T4 (n=192)	
Campus	F=0.984, df=2, p=0.375	F=0.028, df=2, p=0.973	F=2.783, df=2, p=0.064	F=0.037, df=2, p=0.964	
Course	F=0.119, df=1, p=0.730	F=2.001, df=1, p=0.158	F=1.945, df=1, p=0.164	F=3.713, df=2, p=0.055	
Age	F=0.458, df=4, p=0.766	F=4.366, df=4, p=0.002*	F=1.958, df=4, p=0.102	F=2.341, df=4, p=0.057	Increased age at T2, significantly increased scores for SWD. As this was only apparent at T2, it could not be accounted for and was not considered meaningful at this stage.
Sex	F=0.935, df=1, p=0.334	F=0.030, df=1, p=0.862	F=0.229, df=1, p=0.633	F=0.474, df=1, p=0.492	
Education	F=10.290, df=3, p=0.000*	F=1.431, df=3, p=0.234	F=2.370, df=3, p=0.071	F=0.602, df=3, p=0.614	Influence of education on SWD only significant at beginning of programme. Education had positive effect on SWD scores.
Additional Education	F=18.752, df=1, p=0.000*	F=0.379, df=1, p=0.539	F=0.000, df=1, p=0.986	F=0.104, df=1, p=0.747	Additional education significant at T1 with positive effect on SWD scores.
Hours of Education	F=7.961, df=5, p=0.000*	F=1.564, df=5, p=0.170	F=0.754, df=5, p=0.584	F=0.344, df=5, p=0.886	Hours of education significant at T1, as hours of education increased, SWD scores increased.
Training Course (counselling)	F=12.859, df=1, p=0.000*	F=0.098, df=1, p=0.754	F=0.456, df=1, p=0.343	F=0.623, df=1, p=0.500	Having attended a training course on dementia counselling significantly increased SWD scores at T1.
Number of people with dementia (cared for)	F=13.221, df=5, p=0.000*	F=3.834, df=5, p=0.002*	F=3.998, df=4, p=0.004*	F=0.409, df=5, p=0.842	Number of people with dementia cared for had significant impact on SWD scores at T1-T3. As numbers of

					people cared for increased, SWD scores reduced.
Number of people with dementia (counselled)	F=4.047, dF=5, p=0.001*	F=3.267, dF=5, p=0.007*	F=1.237, dF=5, p=0.292	F=0.184, dF=5, p=0.968	Number of people with dementia counselled had significant impact on SWD scores at the beginning of the undergraduate programme. As numbers of people counselled increased, SWD scores reduced.
Supervision	F=16.730, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=0.710, dF=1, p=0.400	F=1.361, dF=2, p=0.258	F=2.600, dF=1, p=0.109	Supervision had significant impact at the very beginning of the programme. Having received supervision had positive effect on SWD scores at T1.
Ongoing Supervision	F=5.179, dF=1, p=0.023*	F=2.006, dF=1, p=0.158	F=0.544, dF=1, p=0.461	F=0.014, dF=1, p=0.906	Ongoing supervision significant at T1 with a positive effect on SWD scores at the very beginning of the undergraduate programme.
Currently Employed in Dementia Care	F=41.760, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=0.315, dF=1, p=0.575	F=0.081, dF=1, p=0.776	F=0.409, dF=5, p=0.842	Being employed in dementia care significantly reduced SWD scores at the very beginning of the undergraduate programme.
Previously Employed in Dementia Care	F=36.515, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=0.078, dF=1, p=0.781	F=0.344, dF=1, p=0.558	F=1.078, dF=1, p=0.300	Being previously employed in dementia care, significantly reduced SWD scores at the very beginning of the undergraduate programme.

Table 6.4.2: Satisfaction in Working with Dementia over Time

As apparent, the most significant findings in relation to satisfaction were evident at the beginning of the nursing programme. At T4 there were no significant relationships between satisfaction and any of the other variables.

Whilst significant findings for satisfaction against other independent variables reduced throughout the course, there were also total scores for Satisfaction in Working with Dementia. As per TSSE, mean scores were calculated using one-way ANOVA and significance levels over

time tested using a paired samples T-Test with a 95% confidence interval. The table below demonstrates mean scores and significance over time;

Time	Mean Score for SWD	Changes over Time	Significant	Meaningfulness (as a % of total scores)
T1	15.72			
T2	14.80	T1 to T2 ($p=0.028$)	Yes	6% reduction
T3	14.45	T2 to T3 ($p=0.000$)	Yes	2% reduction
T4	14.14	T3 to T4 ($p=0.000$)	Yes	2% reduction

Table 6.4.2a: Satisfaction in Working with Dementia: Mean Scores and Significance over Time

Thus, scores for SWD changed significantly from T1 to T4 and total mean SWD scores reduced from T1 to T4;

Figure 6.4.2: Satisfaction in Working with Dementia: Mean Scores over Time

As a component of Therapeutic Commitment, Satisfaction in Working with Dementia, significantly reduced as the students progressed through their nursing programme with a 10% overall reduction in scores from T1 to T4. As the last measure of Therapeutic Commitment, Motivation to Work with Dementia was analysed.

6.4.3: Therapeutic Commitment: Motivation to Work with Dementia

Repeated measures ANOVA was again used to examine relationships between and within variables. Similar to the findings of TSSE and SWD, motivation findings were more significant at the beginning of the course with less significant findings as the nursing programme continued.

In concurrence with T1, training was significantly associated with increasing motivation at T2 ($F=7.052$, $df=1$, $p=0.008$), however there was no associations between education or training and motivation at any subsequent data collections.

Demographically, campus location was associated with significantly higher motivational levels at T2 ($F=3.770$, $df=2$, $p=0.024$). Specifically, Dumfries campus had the highest scores for motivation. The only difference between campuses was that Dumfries were a slightly older cohort of students. As it has already been demonstrated that there was a relationship between age and SWD at T2 and age and RL at T1, it may be that age is the only variable to account for the higher satisfaction scores at Dumfries campus. However, this increase was only evident at T3 and not at any other data collections.

Similar to TSSE, the demographic of sex was significantly related to satisfaction at T2 ($F=3.847$, $df=1$, $p=0.051$) and T3 ($F=4.273$, $df=1$, $p=0.040$). Males had higher scores for satisfaction than females. Again, as per TSSE, this was not evident at all other data collections.

In terms of delivering dementia care, motivational scores were comparable to satisfaction scores. As demonstrated at T1, there was also a significant association between the number of people with dementia students had cared for and the level of motivation to work with dementia students felt at T2 ($F=3.757$, $dF=5$, $p=0.003$) and T3 ($F=5.201$, $Df=1$, $p=0.040$). Exactly as per satisfaction; as the numbers cared for increased, the motivation scores decreased. Thus, caring for people with dementia actually reduced the motivation to work in dementia care.

Moreover, when staying on variables in relation to working in dementia care, being previously employed in dementia care was significantly associated with motivational scores at T2 ($F=3.999$, $dF=1$, $p=0.043$) (as also demonstrated at T1 but not after T2). Scores showed that previous dementia care experience lowered motivation scores and in fact those who had never worked in dementia care at all scored more highly in their motivation to work in dementia care than those who had care experience.

Lastly, there was a significant finding at T4 between nursing course and MWD ($F=4.736$, $dF=1$, $p=0.031$). Those students who were studying adult nursing were more motivated to work in dementia care than those students studying mental health nursing. Indeed, it is interesting as although there was a negative relationship between numbers of dementia patients cared for and motivational scores, when considering the adult/mental health divide, adult students had cared for far more people with dementia but demonstrated more motivation. This will be further explored later in the thesis.

The subsequent table displays all the significant findings in relation to Motivation to Work with Dementia and maps these over time;

Independent Variable	ANOVA/Statistical Significance (*statistically significant)				Meaningfulness
	T1 (n=420)	T2 (n=305)	T3 (n=249)	T4 (n=192)	
Campus	F=0.158, df=2, p=0.854	F=0.535, df=2, p=0.586	F=3.770, df=2, p=0.024*	F=0.132, df=2, p=0.877	Dumfries campus had higher MWD scores at T3 only. This significance could not be accounted for and thus was not deemed a meaningful finding at this stage.
Course	F=0.430, df=1, p=0.513	F=3.111, df=1, p=0.079	F=0.182, df=1, p=0.670	F=4.736, df=1, p=0.031*	Adult students had significantly higher scores for MWD at T4 than mental health students. This is a potentially meaningful finding in relation to nursing practice and will be further explored when triangulating these findings with the qualitative results in chapter 8.
Age	F=1.161, df=4, p=0.327	F=0.338, df=4, p=0.853	F=1.112, df=4, p=0.351	F=0.584, df=4, p=0.676	
Sex	F=0.935, df=1, p=0.334	F=3.847, df=1, p=0.051*	F=4.273, df=1, p=0.040*	F=0.284, df=1, p=0.595	Males scored higher than females at T2 and T3 but reason for finding not confirmed. Not recognised as meaningful at this stage.
Education	F=8.019, df=3, p=0.000*	F=1.543, df=3, p=0.203	F=0.399, df=3, p=0.754	F=0.604, df=3, p=0.613	Influence of education on MWD only significant at beginning of programme. Education had positive effect on MWD scores.
Additional Education	F=10.245, df=1, p=0.001*	F=1.764, df=1, p=0.185	F=0.087, df=1, p=0.768	F=0.017, df=1, p=0.898	Additional education significant at T1 with positive effect on MWD scores.
Hours of Education	F=4.256, df=5, p=0.001*	F=0.425, df=5, p=0.831	F=0.202, df=5, p=0.962	F=0.108, df=5, p=0.990	Hours of education significant at T1, as hours of education increased, MWD scores increased.

Training Course (counselling)	F=15.661, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=7.052, dF=1, p=0.008*	F=3.004, dF=1, p=0.084	F=2.568, dF=1, p=0.111	Having attended a training course on dementia counselling significantly increased MWD scores at the beginning of the undergraduate programme.
Number of people with dementia (cared for)	F=7.768, dF=5, p=0.000*	F=3.757, dF=5, p=0.003*	F=5.201, dF=4, p=0.000*	F=0.286, dF=5, p=0.920	Number of people with dementia cared for had significant impact on MWD scores from T1-T3. As numbers of people cared for increased, MWD scores reduced.
Number of people with dementia (counselled)	F=5.065, dF=5, p=0.000*	F=5.518, dF=5, p=0.000*	F=2.490, dF=5, p=0.032*	F=0.411, dF=5, p=0.841	Number of people with dementia counselled had significant impact on MWD scores from T1-T3. As numbers of people counselled increased, MWD scores reduced.
Supervision	F=7.020, dF=1, p=0.008*	F=11.644, dF=1, p=0.001*	F=1.615, dF=2, p=0.201	F=2.497, dF=1, p=0.116	Supervision had significant impact at the beginning of the programme. Having received supervision had a positive effect on MWD scores at T1.
Ongoing Supervision	F=5.190, dF=1, p=0.023*	F=0.035, dF=1, p=0.851	F=0.090, dF=1, p=0.765	F=0.355, dF=1, p=0.552	Ongoing supervision significant at T1 with a positive effect on MWD scores at the very beginning of the undergraduate programme.
Currently Employed in Dementia Care	F=16.856, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=1.934, dF=1, p=0.165	F=0.499, dF=1, p=0.480	F=0.022, dF=1, p=0.884	Being employed in dementia care significantly reduced MWD scores at the very beginning of the undergraduate programme.
Previously Employed in Dementia Care	F=23.980, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=3.999, dF=1, p=0.046*	F=1.077, dF=1, p=0.300	F=1.254, dF=1, p=0.264	Being previously employed in dementia care, significantly reduced MWD scores at the very beginning of the undergraduate programme.

Table 6.4.3: Motivation to Work with Dementia over Time

Again, although significant findings for motivation against other independent variables reduced throughout the course, there were also total scores for Motivation to Work with Dementia. As per SWD, mean scores were calculated using one-way ANOVA and significance levels over time

tested using a paired samples T-Test with a 95% confidence interval. The table below demonstrates mean scores and significance over time;

Time	Mean Score for MWD	Changes over Time	Significant	Meaningfulness (as a % of total score)
T1	12.92			
T2	13.19	T1 to T2 (p=0.006)	Yes	2% increase
T3	11.61	T2 to T3 (p=0.000)	Yes	12% decrease
T4	10.88	T3 to T4 (p=0.000)	Yes	6% decrease

Table 6.4.3a: Motivation to Work with Dementia: Mean Scores and Significance over Time

As demonstrated in the above table, scores for MWD changed significantly from T1 to T4 and total mean SWD scores were variable from T1 to T4;

Figure 6.4.3: Motivation to Work with Dementia: Mean Scores over Time

As a component of Therapeutic Commitment, Motivation to Work with Dementia, was variable as the students progressed through their nursing programme but had a 16% overall decrease in scores from T1 to T4. The next measure to be analysed was Role Security.

6.4.4: Role Security: Role Adequacy

Using repeated measures ANOVA to examine relationships between and within variables, Role Adequacy demonstrated a similar pattern to the other statistical results presented thus far, in that there were more significant findings at the beginning of the course with less significant findings as the nursing programme continued.

For Role Adequacy, a significant relationship with age was found at T2 ($F=4.770$, $dF=4$, $p=0.001$), but only at T2. As age increased, RA scores increased accordingly. Indeed, the significance of this is interesting when considering that Dumfries campus had higher rates of RA at T1 and they are the oldest students demographically. However, this significance was not apparent at any other data collections.

As per the other datasets, education was significantly related to RA ($F=8.955$, $dF=3$, $p=0.000$), as was training ($F=7.648$, $dF=5$, $p=0.006$), but only up to T2. Thereafter, education demonstrated no significance to adequacy scores, suggesting educational intervention was more impactful at the beginning of the nursing programme.

Furthermore, caring for people with dementia was significantly related to RA at T2 ($F=9.15$, $dF=5$, $p=0.000$) and T3 ($F=6.190$, $dF=4$, $p=0.000$). Indeed, as was the pattern with satisfaction and motivation, as numbers of people with dementia cared for increased, feelings of Role Adequacy decreased.

In conjunction with this negative experiential association, being currently employed in dementia care was significantly related to RA scores at T2 ($F=16.315$, $dF=1$, $p=0.000$) and T3 respectively ($F=6.190$, $dF=4$, $p=0.000$). Those who had no experience of working in dementia care perceived

that they were more adequately prepared for the role than those with experience; as experience increased, RA scores decreased.

Lastly, at T4, there was a significant difference between courses. In parallel with motivation scores, the student's course (field of nursing) demonstrated significant difference between RA scores. Students in the adult field demonstrated significantly higher scores of role adequacy ($F=4.103$, $df=1$, $p=0.044$) than students studying in the mental health field.

The table below displays all the significant findings in relation to Role Adequacy and maps these over time;

Independent Variable	ANOVA/Statistical Significance (*statistically significant)				Meaningfulness
	T1 (n=420)	T2 (n=305)	T3 (n=249)	T4 (n=192)	
Campus	F=6.125, df=2, p=0.002*	F=0.100, df=2, p=0.905	F=0.226, df=2, p=0.798	F=0.624, df=2, p=0.537	Dumfries campus had higher RA scores at T1 only. This significance could not be accounted for and thus was not deemed a meaningful finding at this stage.
Course	F=0.284, df=1, p=0.595	F=0.458, df=1, p=0.499	F=1.172, df=1, p=0.192	F=4.013, df=1, p=0.047*	Adult students had significantly higher scores for RA than mental health students at T4. This is a potentially meaningful finding in relation to nursing practice and will be further explored when triangulating these findings with the qualitative results in chapter 8.
Age	F=0.876, df=4, p=0.478	F=4.770, df=4, p=0.515	F=0.638, df=4, p=0.636	F=1.003, df=4, p=0.407	

Sex	F=1.180, dF=1, p=0.278	F=0.424, dF=1, p=0.515	F=2.122, dF=1, p=0.146	F=0.012 dF=1, p=0.912	
Education	F=115.556, dF=3, p=0.000*	F=8.955, dF=3, p=0.000*	F=1.114, dF=3, p=0.344	F=1.010, dF=3, p=0.389	Influence of education on RA only significant at beginning of undergraduate programme. Education had positive effect on RA scores.
Additional Education	F=105.383, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=4.914, dF=1, p=0.027*	F=0.254 dF=1, p=0.615	F=0.927, dF=1, p=0.337	Additional education significant at beginning of undergraduate programme with positive effect on RA scores.
Hours of Education	F=58.911, dF=5, p=0.000*	F=3.368, dF=5, p=0.006*	F=0.591, dF=5, p=0.707	F=0.307, dF=5, p=0.908	Hours of education significant at beginning of undergraduate programme, as hours of education increased, RA scores increased.
Training Course (counselling)	F=51.890, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=7.648, dF=1, p=0.006*	F=0.630, dF=1, p=0.428	F=1.665, dF=1, p=0.198	Having attended a training course on dementia counselling significantly increased RA scores at the beginning of the undergraduate programme.
Number of people with dementia (cared for)	F=71.241, dF=5, p=0.000*	F=9.150, dF=5, p=0.000*	F=6.190, dF=4, p=0.000*	F=0.582, dF=5, p=0.714	Number of people with dementia cared for had significant impact on RA scores from T1-T3. As numbers of people cared for increased, RA scores reduced.
Number of people with dementia (counselled)	F=14.060, dF=5, p=0.000*	F=7.707, dF=5, p=0.000*	F=5.336, dF=5, p=0.000*	F=0.906, dF=5, p=0.478	Number of people with dementia counselled had significant impact on RA scores from T1-T3. As numbers of people counselled increased, RA scores reduced.
Supervision	F=86.533, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=16.710, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=2.045, dF=2, p=0.132	F=1.753, dF=1, p=0.187	Supervision had a significant impact at the beginning of the programme. Having received supervision had a positive effect on RA scores.
Ongoing Supervision	F=48.698, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=6.876, dF=1, p=0.009*	F=2.625, dF=1, p=0.106	F=0.355, dF=1, p=0.552	Ongoing supervision significant at the beginning of the undergraduate

					programme with a positive effect on RA scores.
Currently Employed in Dementia Care	F=121.947, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=16.315, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=1.982, dF=1, p=0.160	F=0.972, dF=1, p=0.326	Being employed in dementia care significantly reduced RA scores at the beginning of the undergraduate programme.
Previously Employed in Dementia Care	F=124.947, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=21.812, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=0.371, dF=1, p=0.543	F=1.991, dF=1, p=0.160	Being previously employed in dementia care, significantly reduced RA scores at the beginning of the undergraduate programme.

Table 6.4.4: Role Adequacy over Time

In keeping with previous patterns, significant findings for Role Adequacy against other independent variables reduced throughout the course. To examine total scores for RA, mean scores were calculated using one-way ANOVA and significance levels over time tested using a paired samples T-Test with a 95% confidence interval. The table below demonstrates mean scores and significance over time;

Time	Mean Score for RA	Changes over Time	Significant	Meaningfulness (as a % of total scores)
T1	32.26			
T2	24.14	T1 to T2 (p=0.000)	Yes	25% reduction
T3	18.27	T2 to T3 (p=0.000)	Yes	24% reduction
T4	15.86	T3 to T4 (p=0.000)	Yes	13% reduction

Table 6.4.4a: Role Adequacy: Mean Scores and Significance over Time

Thus, scores for RA changed significantly from T1 to T4 and total mean scores decreased from T1 to T4;

Figure 6.4.4: Role Adequacy: Mean Scores over Time

As a component of Role Security, perceptions of Role Adequacy reduced throughout the undergraduate nursing programme with a significant 51% overall reduction in scores from T1 to T4. The second component of Role Security is Role Legitimacy.

6.4.5: Role Security: Role Legitimacy

Keeping the same measures of statistical analysis, repeated measures ANOVA was used to examine relationships between and within variables for Role Legitimacy. Findings for RL were more significant at the beginning of the course with less significant findings as the nursing programme continued.

Experience of caring for people with dementia was again significant. At T2 there was a relationship between the number of people with dementia that students had cared for, and feelings of RL ($F=5.515$, $dF=5$, $p=0.000$). Furthermore, working with dementia was also related to feelings of RL. There was a significant relationship at T2 between RL and being currently employed in dementia care ($F=4.480$, $dF=1$, $p=0.035$) and at T3 for those who had previously

been employed in dementia care ($F=5.538$, $df=1$, $p=0.019$). However, this relationship was negative again. The more experienced the student was, the lower the scores of RL.

Additionally, there was also a relationship between campus location and RL scores. At T2 and T3, there was a significant association between campus location and RL ($F=5.128$, $df=2$, $p=0.007$) and ($F=6.360$, $df=2$, $p=0.002$) respectively. This time, Ayr campus had higher levels of RL.

Finally, similar to RA, there was a significant relationship between RL and the student field of practice ($F=4.588$, $df=1$, $p=0.033$). Adult students scored higher on RL than their mental health colleagues.

All the significant findings in relation to Role Legitimacy and the changes over time are mapped in the table below;

Independent Variable	ANOVA/Statistical Significance (*statistically significant)				Meaningfulness
	T1 (n=420)	T2 (n=305)	T3 (n=249)	T4 (n=192)	
Campus	F=1.759, df=2, p=0.173	F=0.682, df=2, p=0.506	F=5.128, df=2, p=0.007*	F=6.360, df=2, p=0.002*	Ayr campus had higher RA scores at T3 and T4. This significance could not be accounted for and thus was not deemed a meaningful finding at this stage.
Course	F=0.165, df=1, p=0.685	F=0.206, df=1, p=0.650	F=0.612, df=1, p=0.435	F=4.588, df=1, p=0.033*	Adult students had significantly higher scores for RL than mental health students at T4. This is a potentially meaningful finding in relation to nursing practice and will be further explored when triangulating these findings with the qualitative results in chapter 8.

Age	F=2.650, df=4, p=0.033*	F=1.910, dF=4, p=0.109	F=1.425 dF=4, p=0.226	F=1.673, dF=4, p=0.158	Increased age was associated with higher RL scores at T1 only. This significance could not be accounted for and thus was not deemed a meaningful finding at this stage.
Sex	F=0.554, dF=1, p=0.457	F=0.093, dF=1, p=0.760	F=0.338, dF=1, p=0.561	F=0.323 dF=1, p=0.571	
Education	F=30.762, dF=3, p=0.000*	F=1.551, dF=3, p=0.201	F=0.824, dF=3, p=0.482	F=0.937, dF=3, p=0.424	Influence of education on RL only significant at very beginning of undergraduate programme. Education had positive effect on RL scores.
Additional Education	F=41.423, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=1.211, dF=1, p=0.272	F=3.629, dF=1, p=0.058	F=0.002, dF=1, p=0.969	Additional education significant at very beginning of undergraduate programme with positive effect on RL scores.
Hours of Education	F=15.110, dF=5, p=0.000*	F=0.953, dF=5, p=0.447	F=0.871, dF=5, p=0.501	F=1.744, dF=5, p=0.127	Hours of education significant at very beginning of undergraduate programme, as hours of education increased, RL scores increased.
Training Course (counselling)	F=24.846, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=1.215, dF=1, p=0.271	F=1.157, dF=1, p=0.283	F=0.006, dF=1, p=0.938	Having attended a training course on dementia counselling significantly increased RL scores at the very beginning of the undergraduate programme.
Number of people with dementia (cared for)	F=28.653, dF=5, p=0.000*	F=5.515, dF=5, p=0.000*	F=1.480, dF=4, p=0.209	F=1.735, dF=5, p=0.129	Number of people with dementia cared for had significant impact on RL scores at beginning of undergraduate programme. As numbers of people cared for increased, RL scores reduced.
Number of people with dementia (counselled)	F=8,152, dF=5, p=0.000*	F=4.298, dF=5, p=0.001*	F=2.834, dF=5, p=0.017*	F=0.458, dF=5, p=0.807	Number of people with dementia counselled had significant impact on RL scores from T1-T3. As numbers of people counselled increased, RL scores reduced.

Supervision	F=44.916, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=6.526, dF=1, p=0.011*	F=1.108, dF=2, p=0.332	F=0.104, dF=1, p=0.748	Supervision had a significant impact at the beginning of the programme. Having received supervision had a positive effect on RL scores.
Ongoing Supervision	F=22.533, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=0.318, dF=1, p=0.573	F=0.086, dF=1, p=0.770	F=0.070, dF=1, p=0.791	Ongoing supervision significant at the very beginning of the undergraduate programme with a positive effect on RL scores.
Currently Employed in Dementia Care	F=50.313, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=4.480, dF=1, p=0.035*	F=1.378, dF=1, p=0.242	F=3.647, dF=1, p=0.058	Being employed in dementia care significantly reduced RL scores at the beginning of the undergraduate programme.
Previously Employed in Dementia Care	F=46.749, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=3.004, dF=1, p=0.084	F=5.538, dF=1, p=0.019*	F=2.651, dF=1, p=0.105	Being previously employed in dementia care, significantly reduced RL scores.

Table 6.4.5: Role Legitimacy over Time

As per RA, significant findings for Role Legitimacy against other independent variables reduced throughout the course. To examine total scores for RL, mean scores were calculated using one-way ANOVA and significance levels over time tested using a paired samples T-Test with a 95% confidence interval. The table below demonstrates mean scores and significance over time;

Time	Mean Score for RL	Changes over Time	Significant	Meaningfulness (as a % of total scores)
T1	17.29			
T2	13.08	T1 to T2 (p=0.001)	Yes	24% reduction
T3	10.98	T2 to T3 (p=0.000)	Yes	16% reduction
T4	10.36	T3 to T4 (p=0.000)	Yes	6% reduction

Table 6.4.5a: Role Legitimacy Mean Scores and Significance over Time

As can be seen, scores for RL changed significantly from T1 to T4 and total mean scores decreased from T1 to T4;

Figure 6.4.5: Role Legitimacy: Mean Scores over Time

As the final component of Role Security, perceptions of Role Legitimacy reduced throughout the undergraduate nursing programme with a significant 40% overall reduction in scores from T1 to T4. Next, Basic Role Requirements were analysed.

6.4.6: Basic Role Requirements: Role Support

Once again, repeated measures ANOVA was used to examine relationships between and within variables. Similar to previous findings, Role Support findings were more significant at the beginning of the undergraduate nursing programme.

Interestingly, one of the first significant findings was between age and Role Support ($F=5.157$, $df=4$, $p=0.000$) at T2. As age increased, support scores increased, meaning that there was a perception of less support available to older students at this time.

Education was again significant at the earlier stages of the course. Education was significantly associated with support up to T2 ($F=3.355$, $dF=3$, $p=0.019$), with additional education also significant at T2 ($F=4.803$, $dF=1$, $p=0.029$).

In terms of Role Support, supervision was more significant here than at other variables. Supervision was significant throughout the undergraduate programme. Thus, although supervision requirements reduced, students' still perceived they required some supervision and would have benefit from supervision, even at T4 when nearing course completion and registration.

Indeed, in terms of experience, again there was a significant relationship between support and currently working in dementia care ($F=9.582$, $dF=1$, $p=0.002$) and previously working in dementia care ($F=7.130$, $dF=1$, $p=0.008$), up to T2. Those who had never been employed in dementia care and those who were not currently employed had increased scores for Role Support, meaning these students perceived a greater need for support and also perceived a lack of support to be available.

Finally, for Role Support, there was again a significant relationship between field of practice and support scores ($F=6.241$, $dF=1$, $p=0.013$). In correlation with previous findings, adult nursing students had higher scores than mental health nursing students.

All RS significances and changes over time are detailed in the table below;

Independent Variable	ANOVA/Statistical Significance (*statistically significant)				Meaningfulness
	T1 (n=420)	T2 (n=305)	T3 (n=249)	T4 (n=192)	
Campus	F=1.534, df=2, p=0.217	F=2.155, df=2, p=0.118	F=4.809, df=2, p=0.009*	F=0.379, df=2, p=0.685	Dumfries campus had higher RS scores at T3. This significance could not be accounted for and thus was not deemed a meaningful finding at this stage.
Course	F=0.143, df=1, p=0.705	F=0.784, df=1, p=0.377	F=1.409, df=1, p=0.236	F=6.241, df=1, p=0.013*	Adult students had significantly higher scores for RS than mental health students at T4. This is a potentially meaningful finding in relation to nursing practice and will be further explored when triangulating these findings with the qualitative results in chapter 8.
Age	F=1.492, df=4, p=0.204	F=5.157, df=4, p=0.000*	F=1.701, df=4, p=0.150	F=1.808, df=4, p=0.129	Increased age was associated with higher RS scores at T2 only. This significance could not be accounted for and thus was not deemed a meaningful finding at this stage.
Sex	F=0.554, df=1, p=0.457	F=0.014, df=1, p=0.907	F=0.097, df=1, p=0.561	F=0.323, df=1, p=0.756	
Education	F=12.919, df=3, p=0.000*	F=3.355, df=3, p=0.019*	F=0.215, df=3, p=0.886	F=1.478, df=3, p=0.223	Influence of education on RS only significant at beginning of undergraduate programme. Students who had received education perceived themselves to have less requirement for support.
Additional Education	F=12.093, df=1, p=0.001*	F=4.803, df=1, p=0.029*	F=1.097, df=1, p=0.296	F=1.341, df=1, p=0.248	Additional education significant at beginning of undergraduate programme. Students who had received additional education perceived themselves to have less requirement for support.

Hours of Education	F=6.651, dF=5, p=0.000*	F=1.760, dF=5, p=0.121	F=0.297, dF=5, p=0.914	F=0.717, dF=5, p=0.611	Hours of education significant at very beginning of undergraduate programme, as hours of education increased, need for support decreased.
Training Course (counselling)	F=11.656, dF=1, p=0.001*	F=2.121, dF=1, p=0.146	F=0.099, dF=1, p=0.753	F=0.245, dF=1, p=0.621	Having attended a training course on dementia counselling significantly reduced need for support at the very beginning of the undergraduate programme.
Number of people with dementia (cared for)	F=10.059, dF=5, p=0.000*	F=1.657, dF=5, p=0.145	F=0.429, dF=4, p=0.787	F=1.642, dF=5, p=0.151	Number of people with dementia cared for had a significant impact on RS scores at the very beginning of undergraduate programme. Students who had no or very little experience reported a greater need for support.
Number of people with dementia (counselled)	F=4.446, dF=5, p=0.001*	F=3.211, dF=5, p=0.008*	F=1.119, dF=5, p=0.351	F=0.907, dF=5, p=0.477	Number of people with dementia counselled had significant impact on RL scores at the beginning of the undergraduate programme. Students who had limited experience reported a greater need for support.
Supervision	F=20.805, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=11.718, dF=1, p=0.001*	F=3.014, dF=2, p=0.051*	F=4.884, dF=1, p=0.028*	Supervision had a significant impact throughout the programme. Whilst supervision scores reduced in association with greater knowledge and experience, the desire for supervision continued.
Ongoing Supervision	F=14.888, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=0.394, dF=1, p=0.531	F=0.431, dF=1, p=0.512	F=0.921, dF=1, p=0.339	Ongoing supervision was significant at the very beginning of the undergraduate programme.
Currently Employed in Dementia Care	F=40.379, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=9.582, dF=1, p=0.002*	F=0.578, dF=1, p=0.448	F=1.138, dF=1, p=0.288	Being employed in dementia care significantly influenced the need for support at the beginning of the undergraduate programme. Students with work experience perceived they required less support.

Previously Employed in Dementia Care	F=29.976, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=7.130, dF=1, p=0.008*	F=0.585, dF=1, p=0.445	F=0.019, dF=1, p=0.890	Being previously employed in dementia care, significantly reduced the perceived need for support at the beginning of the undergraduate programme.
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Table 6.4.6: Role Support over Time

Indeed, significant findings for Role Support against other independent variables reduced as the undergraduate programme continued. One-way ANOVA was used to calculate mean scores and to test significance levels over time; a paired samples T-Test with a 95% confidence interval was used. The table below demonstrates mean scores and significance over time;

Time	Mean Score for RS	Changes over Time	Significant	Meaningfulness (as a % of total scores)
T1	9.97			
T2	8.16	T1 to T2 (p=0.000)	Yes	18% reduction
T3	6.76	T2 to T3 (p=0.000)	Yes	17% reduction
T4	6.61	T3 to T4 (p=0.000)	Yes	2% reduction

Table 6.4.6a: Role Support: Mean Scores and Significance over Time

As can be seen, scores for Role Support changed significantly from T1 to T4 and total mean scores decreased from T1 to T4;

Figure 6.4.6: Role Support: Mean Scores over Time

Thus, as a component of Basic Role Requirements, perceptions of Role Support available reduced throughout the undergraduate nursing programme. With a significant 34% overall reduction in scores from T1 to T4, students required less support as they became more knowledgeable and experienced. The second component of Basic Role Requirements is Self-Esteem.

6.4.7: Basic Role Requirements: Self-Esteem

Using repeated measures ANOVA to examine relationships between and within variables, Self-Esteem showed few significant findings or changes from T1 to T4.

Self-esteem was significantly related to education at either end of the nurse training curriculum; T1 ($F=4.301$, $df=3$, $p=0.005$) and T4 ($F=2.2786$, $df=3$, $p=0.042$). Self-esteem scores also increased as hours of education experienced increased.

In terms of caring for people with dementia, there was only a significant finding at T2 ($F=6.509$, $df=1$, $p=0.001$). As the number of people cared for increased, feelings of self-esteem amongst students decreased (in correlation with findings for satisfaction, motivation, RA and RL).

Lastly, supervision was significantly correlated with SE at T2 ($F=6.509$, $df=1$, $p=0.011$) but not at any other data collection.

The limited SE significant findings are detailed below;

Independent Variable	ANOVA/Statistical Significance (*statistically significant)				Meaningfulness
	T1 (n=420)	T2 (n=305)	T3 (n=249)	T4 (n=192)	
Campus	F=0.128, df=2, p=0.879	F=1.820, df=2, p=0.164	F=2.089, df=2, p=0.126	F=0.724, df=2, p=0.486	
Course	F=2.825, df=1, p=0.094	F=0.009, df=1, p=0.926	F=0.440, df=1, p=0.508	F=0.051, df=1, p=0.821	
Age	F=0.834, df=4, p=0.504	F=1.032, df=4, p=0.391	F=0.490, df=4, p=0.743	F=1.117, df=4, p=0.350	
Sex	F=0.286, df=1, p=0.593	F=0.340, df=1, p=0.560	F=2.158, df=1, p=0.143	F=0.771, df=1, p=0.381	
Education	F=4.308, df=3, p=0.005*	F=2.441, df=3, p=0.064	F=0.930, df=3, p=0.427	F=2.786, df=3, p=0.042*	Influence of education on SE significant at very beginning and end of undergraduate programme. Education had a positive effect on SE scores.

Additional Education	F=1.893, dF=1, p=0.170	F=0.000, dF=1, p=0.988	F=1.613, dF=1, p=0.205	F=2.017, dF=1, p=0.157	
Hours of Education	F=0.610, dF=5, p=0.692	F=1.209, dF=5, p=0.305	F=0.341, dF=5, p=0.888	F=0.930, dF=5, p=0.463	
Training Course (counselling)	F=0.021, dF=1, p=0.886	F=0.250, dF=1, p=0.618	F=2.584, dF=1, p=0.109	F=0.474, dF=1, p=0.492	
Number of people with dementia (cared for)	F=0.668, dF=5, p=0.648	F=3.234, dF=5, p=0.007*	F=1.610, dF=4, p=0.172	F=0.265, dF=5, p=0.932	Number of people with dementia cared for had significant impact on SE scores T2 only. As numbers of people cared for increased, SE scores reduced. This was not deemed as meaningful at this time.
Number of people with dementia (counselled)	F=0.646, dF=5, p=0.665	F=1.961, dF=5, p=0.084	F=1.249, dF=5, p=0.287	F=0.996, dF=5, p=0.422	
Supervision	F=0.290, dF=1, p=0.590	F=6.509, dF=1, p=0.011*	F=1.104, dF=2, p=0.333	F=0.024, dF=1, p=0.876	Supervision had a significant impact on SE at T2 only. This was not deemed as a significant finding at this time.
Ongoing Supervision	F=2.235, dF=1, p=0.136	F=0.002, dF=1, p=0.966	F=0.050, dF=1, p=0.823	F=1.081, dF=1, p=0.300	
Currently Employed in Dementia Care	F=1.590, dF=1, p=0.208	F=0.303, dF=1, p=0.582	F=0.736, dF=1, p=0.392	F=0.405, dF=1, p=0.525	
Previously Employed in Dementia Care	F=1.954, dF=1, p=0.163	F=0.734, dF=1, p=0.392	F=0.307, dF=1, p=0.580	F=0.109, dF=1, p=0.741	

Table 6.4.7: Self-Esteem Over Time

Indeed, such limited findings in relation to Self-Esteem suggest that it is largely unrelated to the variables in question and this lack of significance was mostly unaffected by time. Nonetheless, it was still useful to explore total scores for SE.

One-way ANOVA was used to calculate mean scores and to test if there were significant changes in scores over time; a paired samples T-Test with a 95% confidence interval was used. The table below demonstrates mean scores and significance changes in perceptions over time;

Time	Mean Score for SE	Changes over Time	Significant	Meaningfulness (as a % of total scores)
T1	15.13			
T2	16.12	T1 to T2 ($p=0.001$)	Yes	7% increase
T3	14.32	T2 to T3 ($p=0.000$)	Yes	11% decrease
T4	13.05	T3 to T4 ($p=0.000$)	Yes	9% decrease

Table 6.4.7a: Self-Esteem Mean Scores and Significance over Time

As can be seen, scores for SE changed significantly from T1 to T4 and total mean scores were variable from T1 to T4;

Figure 6.4.7: Self-Esteem: Mean Scores over Time

Thus, as the final component of Basic Role Requirements, Self Esteem reduced throughout the undergraduate nursing programme, with a 14% overall reduction in scores from T1 to T4. The final aspect for analysis was the overall attitude score.

6.5: Overall Attitude

Keeping the same measures of statistical analysis for the final tests, repeated measures ANOVA was used to examine relationships between and within variables in relation to Overall Attitude Scores. In correspondence with all findings to date, results for attitude were more significant at the beginning of the nursing course with less significant findings as the nursing programme continued.

The first significant finding in relation to OA was age ($F=3.310$, $dF=4$, $p=0.011$). As the students age increased, overall attitude score increased. This was only noted at T2 and was insignificant at all other data collections.

Again, similar to previous findings, education and training had a significant impact on attitude until T2; ($F=4.156$, $df=3$, $p=0.007$) and ($F=4.906$, $df=1$, $p=0.028$) respectively. Education increased overall attitude scores. In terms of dementia experience, caring for people with dementia was significantly related to attitude at T2 ($F=10.052$, $df=5$, $p=0.000$) and T3 ($F=7.608$, $df=4$, $p=0.000$). Similar to previous findings with this variable, the more people with dementia that the students had cared for, the lower the attitude score, thus again, dementia care experience had a negative effect on attitude. Also, in terms of dementia care, currently working with dementia was significantly related to attitude ($F=8.498$, $df=1$, $p=0.004$) as was previously having worked in dementia care ($F=10.028$, $df=1$, $p=0.002$). However, these findings were only apparent until T2 and again, the greater the level of experience, the more negatively affected attitude score. Lastly, similar to the findings of RA and RL, there was a significant relationship between attitude and course ($F=5.085$, $df=1$, $p=0.025$). Adult field students scored higher on overall attitude than mental health field student nurses.

The overall significant findings in relation to OA and the changes over time are detailed in the table below;

Independent Variable	ANOVA/Statistical Significance (*statistically significant)				Meaningfulness
	T1 (n=420)	T2 (n=305)	T3 (n=249)	T4 (n=192)	
Campus	F=2.557, df=2, p=0.079	F=0.464, df=2, p=0.629	F=1.426, df=2, p=0.242	F=1.040, df=2, p=0.356	
Course	F=0.028, df=1, p=0.867	F=1.582, df=1, p=0.210	F=0.298, df=1, p=0.586	F=5.085, df=1, p=0.025*	Adult students had significantly more positive scores for OA than mental health students at T4. This is a potentially meaningful finding in relation to nursing practice and will be further explored when triangulating these findings with the qualitative results in chapter 8.

Age	F=1.137, df=4, p=0.339	F=3.310, df=4, p=0.011*	F=1.750, df=4, p=0.140	F=1.651, df=4, p=0.163	Increased age was associated with more positive OA scores at T2 only. This significance could not be accounted for and thus was not deemed a meaningful finding at this stage.
Sex	F=2.504, df=1, p=0.114	F=1.581, df=1, p=0.210	F=3.577, df=1, p=0.060	F=0.064, df=1, p=0.800	
Education	F=57.122, df=3, p=0.000*	F=4.156, df=3, p=0.007*	F=0.744, df=3, p=0.527	F=0.270, df=3, p=0.847	Influence of education on OA scores significant at beginning of undergraduate programme. Students who had received education had more positive OA scores.
Additional Education	F=67.136, df=1, p=0.000*	F=1.823, df=1, p=0.178	F=0.210, df=1, p=0.648	F=0.014, df=1, p=0.906	Additional education significant at very beginning of undergraduate programme. Students who had received additional education had more positive OA scores at course commencement.
Hours of Education	F=29.582, df=5, p=0.000*	F=1.476, df=5, p=0.197	F=0.068, df=5, p=0.997	F=0.097, df=5, p=0.993	Hours of education significant at very beginning of undergraduate programme, as hours of education increased, OA scores were more positive.
Training Course (counselling)	F=44.994, df=1, p=0.000*	F=4.906, df=1, p=0.028*	F=0.693, df=1, p=0.406	F=1.196, df=1, p=0.276	Having attended a training course on dementia counselling was associated with significantly more positive OA scores at beginning of the undergraduate programme.
Number of people with dementia (cared for)	F=50.679, df=5, p=0.000*	F=10.052, df=5, p=0.000*	F=7.608, df=4, p=0.000*	F=0.213, df=5, p=0.957	Number of people with dementia cared for had a significant impact on OA scores from T1 to T3. As numbers of people cared for increased, OA scores became less positive.
Number of people with	F=11.127, df=5, p=0.000*	F=7.684, df=5, p=0.000*	F=4.867, df=5, p=0.000*	F=0.124, df=5, p=0.987	Number of people with dementia counselled had significant impact on OA scores from T1 to T3. As numbers

dementia (counselled)					of people counselled increased, OA scores became less positive.
Supervision	F=58.823, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=14.042, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=2.465, dF=2, p=0.087	F=1.499, dF=1, p=0.222	Supervision had a significant impact at the beginning of the undergraduate programme. Supervision was associated with a more positive OA score.
Ongoing Supervision	F=33.779, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=0.205, dF=1, p=0.651	F=0.737, dF=1, p=0.391	F=0.142, dF=1, p=0.707	Ongoing supervision was significant at the very beginning of the undergraduate programme an associated with a more positive OA score.
Currently Employed in Dementia Care	F=98.414, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=8.498, dF=1, p=0.004*	F=0.012, dF=1, p=0.913	F=0.027, dF=1, p=0.869	Being employed in dementia care significantly influenced OA scores at the beginning of the undergraduate programme. Students with work experience had less positive OA scores.
Previously Employed in Dementia Care	F=104.092, dF=1, p=0.000*	F=10.028, dF=1, p=0.002*	F=0.006, dF=1, p=0.937	F=0.334, dF=1, p=0.564	Being previously employed in dementia care, significantly influenced OA scores at the beginning of the undergraduate programme. Students with previous work experience had less positive OA scores.

Table 6.5: Overall Attitude over Time

Indeed, Overall Attitude scores are the same as has been demonstrated throughout this analysis; significant findings against other independent variables reduced as the undergraduate programme continued.

One-way ANOVA was again used to calculate mean scores and to test significance levels over time; a paired samples T-Test with a 95% confidence interval was used. The table below demonstrates mean scores and significance over time;

Time	Mean Score for OA	Changes over Time	Significant	Meaningfulness (as a % of total scores)
T1	0.0000			
T2	0.0001	T1 to T2 (p=0.000)	Yes	Cannot be calculated as original number 0
T3	0.0002	T2 to T3 (p=0.000)	Yes	100% increase
T4	0.0005	T3 to T4 (p=0.000)	Yes	150% increase

Table 6.5a: Overall Attitude Mean Scores and Significance over Time

As can be seen, scores for Overall Attitude changed significantly from T1 to T4. A percentage change cannot be computed for T1 to T4 as the original mean was 0 but the total mean scores can be seen to increase significantly from T1 to T4;

Figure 6.5: Overall Attitude Mean Scores over Time

The OA score was calculated using the standard scores for Therapeutic Commitment (TC) and Role Security (RS). Again, as per the original scoring system (Cartwright, 1980b), a mean of zero and a standard deviation of one was used.

As previously stated, according to previous studies, low levels of TC were shown to be a result of role insecurity (low scores on Role Security) (Shaw et al, 1978, Cartwright, 1980a, Gorman and Cartwright 1991, Cartwright and Gorman, 1993). Indeed, those who score poorly on TC were identified as unlikely to be as successful working within their role. Again, for this study, using the original scoring (mean= 0 and SD=1), all students who scored outside of these parameters (-1 to 1) were unlikely to be as successful in working with dementia. Thus, although most students fell within the therapeutic level for Overall Attitude at T1 (n=343, 81.7%), considering the OA scores changed significantly over time, it was useful to map the students attitude scores at course completion T4;

Figure 6.5.1: Overall Attitude Mean Scores T4

As can be seen from the T4 Overall Attitude chart, most student's scores for TC were still within the acceptable threshold, although this was at a lesser extent than at T1 course commencement (a reduction of 4.1% in the therapeutic range). From the total participating population at T4

(n=192), (n=43, 22.4%) students were outside of the therapeutic range, with (n=149, 77.6%) within the therapeutic range, thus indicating that although there was a reduction in overall attitude scores, most students were still likely to be successful working within dementia care, should they wish.

6.6: Summary

To revisit the components of the original MAPP hypothesis (Shaw et al, 1978, Cartwright, 1980a, Gorman and Cartwright 1991, Cartwright and Gorman, 1993);

- Training, experience and knowledge gain should have a positive effect on role adequacy and role legitimacy – **Supported; but learning was only significant at the beginning of the undergraduate nursing programme.**
- Role support is influenced by role security – **Supported; but significance varied and the influence was not always in a positive manner.**
- Role security influences levels of therapeutic commitment – **Supported; but significance varied and this was not always a positive influence.**

Thus, the original hypotheses were supported, however, it was apparent that significant changes to students' perceptions were more apparent towards the beginning of their undergraduate nursing programme. In particular, the positive benefits of education and training were demonstrated in the highly significant association between therapeutic attitude and knowledge and learning, however, this was also in the most part only at the beginning of the students nursing journey. Furthermore, the significantly negative relationship between dementia care giving/care experience and levels of satisfaction, motivation, role adequacy and role legitimacy were an unexpected finding and will be further discussed later in the thesis.

In this chapter of quantitative results, data collection timings were detailed. Data was collected from the undergraduate students, from course induction (T1), then yearly at commencement of year 2 (T2), year 3 (T3) until course completion (T4). Response rates from the DDCPQ were excellent considering the longitudinal nature of the study, with response rates of 92%, 83%, 89%

and 81% respectively. Demographic data was detailed to provide an overview of the nursing student population studied. The demographic identified most students to be female, aged 25 or under with little or no experience of receiving any dementia education or delivering any dementia care.

Thereafter, students' perceptions were scored by the DDCPQ and the changes over time were detailed, in relation to the main underpinning themes of the survey questionnaire; Therapeutic Commitment (Task Specific Self Esteem, Satisfaction Working with Dementia and Motivation to Work with Dementia), Role Security (Role Adequacy and Role Legitimacy) and Basic Role Requirements (Role Support). The DDCPQ then scored the students Overall Attitude.

Task Specific Self Esteem reduced 27% overall between T1 and T4 and there was a significant positive association between Task Specific Self Esteem and education. The more education reduced, the more positive feelings of self-esteem were perceived to be, particularly towards the beginning of the undergraduate programme. Conversely, there was a negative association between Task Specific Self Esteem and caring for people with dementia. The more experienced the students were, the lower they perceived their Task Specific Self Esteem.

This was echoed in the measurements for perceived Satisfaction in Working with Dementia whereby scores reduced by 10% over the duration of the undergraduate programme and again there was a positive association between education and satisfaction scores and a negative association between experience and satisfaction scores. Similar to satisfaction, Motivation to Work with Dementia scores reduced by 16% over the nursing programme, with the same positive association with education and negative association with experience.

In terms of Role Security, Role Adequacy scores significantly reduced by 51% over the undergraduate programme. Further demonstrating the same trend with the positive influence of education and the negative influence of experience. Also, in parallel, Role Legitimacy scores reduced by 40% over the programme, again demonstrating the positive influence of education and the negative impact of experience.

However, despite these reductions in feelings of adequacy and legitimacy, student's requirements for Role Support reduced over the programme (meaning they required less support as they became more knowledgeable and experienced). Furthermore, Overall Attitude scores did become less positive over the undergraduate programme but by the end of their nursing programme 77.6% of students remained in the 'therapeutic range' of attitude, indicating that they were likely to be successful in working with dementia should they wish.

These findings are extremely interesting and indicate a negative shift in perceptions over the student nursing journey. To gain a deeper understanding of these results and to provide context and meaning to the scores, it is essential to triangulate these findings with the qualitative data. Using the layered approach to the presentation of data findings (Cresswell and Plano-Clark, 2011), the next chapter will detail the qualitative study results, allowing for subsequent triangulation of the data.

Chapter Seven: Qualitative Results

This chapter will present the results of the qualitative component of this study. Firstly, the demographics of the qualitative focus group participants will be detailed and the changes in the focus groups tracked from baseline (T1) to point of registration (T4). Furthermore, changes in the student's engagement with nominal group technique over time will be critiqued, as well as changes to group dynamics, researcher observations and engagement in nominal group technique and the Ketso Kit. The NGT rankings will be detailed and the changes in responses and rankings over time tabulated using time series analysis. Lastly, a conceptual framework of emergent themes will be generated to allow for conceptual analysis of the qualitative findings overall.

7.0: Focus Group Demographics

As previously identified in Chapter Four, all students in Ayr, Paisley and Dumfries campuses were invited to express an interest in focus group participation. The response rate of expressions of interest exceeded the capacity of the focus groups so interested students were randomly selected and articulated into an appropriate focus group. As per Chapter Five focus group plan, 12 participants were selected at each campus (n=36 in total), to allow for natural attrition due to the longitudinal nature of the study. As the participants were randomly selected, the participant's demographics were random and variable overall at T1;

Reflective of the nursing population there were more female participants (n=32), compared to males (n=4);

Figure 7.0: Focus Groups: Participant Breakdown by Sex

As per the total available population of the September 2014 nursing cohort (as exemplified in Chapter Six), the majority of participants were under 30 years of age. Figures showed; age under 25 (n=13), age 26-30 (n=9), age 31-40 (n=11) and 41-50 (n=3);

Figure 7.0.1: Focus Group: Participant Breakdown by Age

Most students were studying adult nursing (n=28), compared to mental health (n=8);

Figure 7.0.2: Focus Groups: Participant Breakdown by Course

Most students had no experience of delivering dementia care (n=23), with only some having limited care experience (n=13);

Figure 7.0.3: Focus Groups: Dementia Care Experience

Furthermore, most students had received no dementia education (n=23), compared to a few who had received “basic training” (n=13);

Figure 7.0.4: Dementia Education

Interestingly, whilst numbers of those having experience of dementia care (n=13) is the same figure as those who had received basic dementia training (n=13), there was no exacting relationship between clinical experience and having received education. Of the 13 who had received education, only 9 of these were in a work context, with 4 students having received the education in a non-working context, with no dementia care experience at T1.

Although the demographics of a small number of participants for the qualitative aspect of the study were simple to extract and indeed provide some further insight into the student profile, the dynamics of managing 12 participants in each focus group were initially challenging at T1. However, as anticipated, there was attrition of focus group participants over the 3-year data collection;

Campus	T1 Participant Numbers	T2 Participant Numbers	T3 Participant Numbers	T4 Participant Numbers
Paisley	12	7	7	5
Ayr	12	8	6	4
Dumfries	12	9	7	4

Table 7.0: Focus Group Attrition

As participation in the focus groups was entirely voluntary, aside from an email confirming dates and times, participants were not followed up post group if they chose not to attend, however, they did have the option to attend again at the next data collection to give them the option of participating as much as they could manage. Data was not collected regarding why students may have chosen not to attend focus groups, again in keeping with the voluntary nature of participation, however anecdotally, some students provided feedback regarding their inability to attend. Following such feedback, it was ensured that all subsequent focus groups were during lunch times in University as opposed to the end of the day (when some students had to go home promptly for childcare reasons) and also it was recognised that a Friday was not a good day for data collection, with students preferring the beginning of the week. Furthermore, as the undergraduate programme progressed, timings for data collection at T4 became challenging as students spent more time in clinical practice than in University, compared to the start of the programme, however with some negotiation timing and date wise, focus groups enabled all students who wanted to participate to have the opportunity.

The focus group analysis was commenced after each group and then further analysed after all the data was collected, using a systematic process.

7.1: Focus Group Analysis Process

Whilst ranking of priorities in keeping with NGT started the analysis process, the actual process of qualitative data analysis was much more in depth. Miles et al (2014) provide a useful guide to the processing part of data analysis and this was used to provide a structure for commencing analysis;

- Initial rating of assertions by participants as part of focus group
- Audio recorded narratives transcribed verbatim
- Video recordings reviewed and context statements added to narratives
- Narratives reviewed again and field notes correlated to data collection timings to give context to assertions and to provide a holistic picture of each focus group
- Conclusions drawn

(Adapted from Miles et al, 2014)

Using this structure as a guide, the holistic picture of the focus groups, commenced with the observed interactions and non-verbal behaviours of the students.

7.1.1: Researcher Observations

Whilst the audio-visual recordings and verbatim transcriptions provided the raw data for qualitative analysis, it was also important for the researcher to capture some field notes during the data collection. Observed behaviours as well as capturing the context of discussions, body language, expressions and gestures all help capture the true meanings of the data collected and thus add greater authenticity to the research findings (Miles et al, 2014, Bryman, 2016, Yin, 2018). As this study was longitudinal in nature, the data was collected over 3 years, which allowed the researcher a prolonged time with the research participants and thus greater insight than would have been achieved in a single data collection study. At T1 data collection, during induction week to the nursing programme, the students were relatively unknown to each other

and to the researcher. The students initially required a lot of support to understand the research process and nominal group technique.

7.1.2: Nominal Group Technique using the Ketso Kit: Changes over Time

At T1, as discussed in Chapter 5, the students were inducted to nominal group technique and their role in the process. On revising the field notes taken at the time of T1 data collection, this unfamiliarity in the NGT process was apparent;

“Some students, particularly the younger, inexperienced ones, are a little reticent to share their thoughts and ideas”.

Field Notes T1

As often observed within a group setting, some students tried to take the lead, with the more clinically experienced students keen to share their knowledge and skills;

“The focus group guide is proving invaluable as a structured approach to the group, it is ensuring everyone gets the chance to speak and nobody can overpower the conversation for any length of time”

Field Notes T1

Furthermore, the structured approach of NGT was soon mastered by all the participants with even the quieter students happily sharing their input once they had understood the process of NGT;

“Really nice to see the anticipation on the face of the youngest, most inexperienced members of the group as they wait their turn to provide their thoughts.....they’ve

realised that they are in a safe environment, have gradually started sharing openly and actually look like they are enjoying themselves now!"

Field Notes T1

Nonetheless, although the students relaxed and seemed to enjoy the focus group once they got used to the approach, it was also important to debrief the students on the NGT experience. Whilst working as a group to rate the findings in order of importance as part of NGT helps to sum up the salient points of the research findings and thus provides a debrief and a start to the thematic analysis process, it was important, especially at T1 to fully debrief the students on the whole experience;

"Once the rating of NGT was over, the students sat quietly looking around the room expectantly and the sense of uncertainty, palpable at the beginning of the focus group entered the room again"

Field Notes T1

The students were then debriefed on the NGT process by revisiting the focus group plan (see appendix 10). The process of considering what the focus group aimed to do, what had been achieved and then the consensus results were revisited. The students were thanked for their participation and then asked to share any reflections on the process and for many their first participatory experience in research. One of the students who had initially been very quiet and reserved was the first to share a reflection;

"I had no idea what to expect from today. I wanted to come along as I have an interest in dementia care but I was worried because I have no care experience and I've never even met anyone with dementia except my gran. I was a bit scared at first to say what I thought because I didn't want to feel stupid but then I realised that there were other people who were thinking the same as me and everyone was really kind to me and didn't laugh at my ideas"

Student A2, T1

Such anticipated reticence and anxiety at participating in the focus group, common in new research participants (Thomas, 2009, Bryman, 2016) was one of the initial reasons for using the Ketso Kit as both a visual aid and also a fun way to provide feedback.

A student, new to research and to nursing was intrigued by the Ketso Kit. The Ketso Kit was set up in the room ready for the focus group;

“The first student to arrive looks absolutely perplexed and apprehensive by the strange set up in front of her but she cannot resist having a feel at the leaves and the tactile branches of the kit when she thinks nobody is looking”

Field Notes T1

Indeed, even one of the more experienced and vocal students was a bit unsure initially;

“I was wondering what on earth was happening.....I thought, my wean (child) used to have fuzzy felt when she was wee, what on earth have we got it for?”

Student P4, T1

However, by the end of T1 data collection, students were feeling positive about both research participation and the Ketso Kit;

“I really enjoyed that, that was fun. I feel raring to go and make a difference now. It doesn't matter that I've not got any experience, we've all got something to offer”

Student P2, T1

“That wee kit was great fun, lovely and colourful, you should use that in classes. It really helps me to see things visually like that”

Student D10, T1

Such positive energy and desire to ‘make a difference’ continued throughout all the data collections with the student’s confidence to speak and engage in the research process growing at each data collection;

“Lovely to see the students growing in their relationships and friendships with each other as well as in their confidence to speak and share their thoughts and feelings”

Field Notes T2

The importance of communication in nursing and key focus of communication skills in pre-registration courses (QAA 2009, NMC, 2010a, NHS Education Scotland, 2016) was apparent in the communicative interactions between the students. The difference in body language between data collections was an unexpected finding;

Some of the students body language is closed (arms crossed, sitting on hands) and many are showing expressions of anxiety when sharing their assertions (blushing, pulling at sleeves, fiddling with the Ketso leaves).....heads are being nodded at times to agree with their peers.....eye contact is being made with me rather than each other”

Field Notes T1

However, as time moved on;

“There’s an ease now in their ability to use the Ketso Kit and in their comfort in engaging with the NGT process”

Field Notes T3

“Students body language is open with posture leaning forward to engage. Hands are being used to express themselves and they are displaying active listening to encourage ongoing conversation with each other.....they have almost forgotten I am even here”

Field Notes T4

This increased competence in communication was not only evident from the researcher’s field notes, but also recognised by the students. There was recognition that a nursing course can put students out of their comfort zone, but in doing so increases their confidence;

“I was so shy when I started this course and then when the lecturers make you role play and speak out in class you cringe and die inside but then you think, wait a minute it wasn’t that bad after all, everybody has to do it. My mum says I don’t shut up now so I must’ve changed”

Student D5, T3

Such changes over time were not only exemplified in the student’s communication skills and engagement with the research process but also in their articulation of their assertions during the NGT process.

7.2: NGT Ratings and Changes over Time

The students were asked the same questions at each data collection and in keeping with NGT, were asked to rate their findings in order of importance. There are many ways to manage NGT findings and to interpret and analyse the results (Foth et al, 2016, Cunningham, 2017), however, it is recognised that focus group data (particularly multiple focus groups) is often harder to interpret than other forms of qualitative data such as individual interviews (McMillan, Kelly, Sav et al, 2014). With that in mind it was decided to use a straightforward method of analysis that also correlated well with the quantitative aspect of the research study. McMillan et al (2017)

suggests focusing on ideas, priorities and then themes which draws parallels with the well-known method of data analysis by Miles and Huberman (Miles et al, 2014). Miles et al (2014) focuses on the framework of condense, display and conclude. This simplistic plan fits well with NGT and was used to provide a structure for the qualitative data analysis. The method is exemplified below;

Figure 7.2: Data Analysis Plan

(Adapted from Miles et al, 2014)

Using the concepts of condense and display, condensed findings are then presented as advised by Miles et al (2014) to visually display the data collections. The following tables illustrate the focus group questions and the student's ratings as they condensed their findings into an order of priority. All data collections (T1-T4) on all 3 campuses are displayed;

Table 7.2: Focus Group Question 1 and Ratings

Data Collection Timing	Question 1 - What knowledge/skills/experiences/qualities do you already have that will help you care for patients with dementia?		
	Ayr	Paisley	Dumfries
T1	1: Communication 2: Patience 3: Empathy 4: Sense of Humour	1: Patience 2: Empathy 3: Communication 4: Understanding	1: Patience, compassion and empathy 2: Knowledge 3: Evidence based practice
T2	1: Compassion and empathy 2: Understanding physiology behind behaviours 3: Techniques	1: Patience 2: Understanding 3: Knowledge	1: Communication 2: Awareness 3: Knowledge and understanding 4: Experience
T3	1: Patience, empathy and understanding 2: Knowledge	1: Empathy 2: Understanding of personhood 3: Understanding of disease progression	1: Knowledge and understanding 2: Desire to get to know the person 3: Experience
T4	1: Communication skills 2: Knowledge	1: Empathy 2: Knowledge 3: Understanding of effects of dementia	1: Experience

Data Collection Timing	Question 2 - What do you hope/need to learn/gain to help you care for patients with dementia?		
	Ayr	Paisley	Dumfries
T1	1: Knowledge 2: Experience (simulation and practice) 3: Learn how to care for patients at different stages of journey	1: Knowledge 2: Practical experience 3: How to care for patients in practice 4: Current guidelines	1: Knowledge 2: Skills 3: How to support patients and families
T2	1: Knowledge and understanding 2: Seeing things from the family's perspective	1: Knowledge 2: Patient experience 3: Clinical experience	1: Dementia journey from patient perspective 2: Awareness of patient's rights 3: Risk factors
T3	1: Knowledge 2: More ways to deliver person centred care 3: Experience of dementia in different care areas	1: Knowledge 2: More experience	1: Ability to change the culture 2: Knowledge
T4	1: Knowledge 2: Experience	1: Knowledge 2: Practical experience at all aspects of dementia journey	1: Learning how to care for older people with multiple comorbidities, including dementia 2: Learning that is ongoing in response to change in policy or new research

Table 7.2.1: Focus Group Question 2 and Ratings

Data Collection Timing	Question 3 - What challenges will be/have been in your way?		
	Ayr	Paisley	Dumfries
T1	1: Families (of patients) 2: Knowledge and understanding 3: Time	1: The person-centred care (being able to give the care you want) 2: Challenging behaviour 3: Resources (time, staff, funding)	1: Getting support (for patients and families) from health and social care teams 2: Patients families 3: Challenging behaviour
T2	1: Emotionally challenging 2: Keeping the individual safe 3: Environment	1: Staff attitudes 2: Time 3: Environment	1: Staff attitudes 2: Time 3: Environment
T3	1: Other staff 2: Time	1: Staff attitudes 2: Lack of dementia diagnosis 3: Recognition of ultimate outcome for patients	1: Staff attitudes 2: Environment
T4	1: Staff communication skills 2: Families	1: Other staff 2: Staff burnout – mental and physical exhaustion 3: Time	1: Staff attitudes 2: Lack of policy implementation

Table 7.2.3: Focus Group Question 3 and Ratings

Data Collection Timing	Question 4 - What are the solutions to these challenges and how can you move forward?		
	Ayr	Paisley	Dumfries
T1	1: Training and increased knowledge for staff and families 2: More time to care	1: Training 2: Funding 3: Support 4: MDT Communication 5: Gaining confidence	1: Communication 2: Increased awareness of dementia 3: More funding
T2	1: Training 2: Learning through role play	1: Staff training 2: Role modelling 3: More staff	1: Education for staff 2: Awareness of patient need by staff 3: Better time management by staff
T3	1: Training 2: Time 3: More staff	1: Staff training 2: Role modelling 3: Challenging negative staff behaviours	1: Staff training 2: Increased awareness of patient's rights 3: Better environments
T4	1: Training for staff 2: Study time for staff 3: Research	1: Staff training 2: Engagement with new knowledge and policies 3: More staff	1: Staff learning 2: Awareness of patients abilities

Table 7.2.4: Focus Group Question 4 and Ratings

Data Collection Timing	Question 5 – What are your ultimate goals to help deliver excellent care to patients with dementia?		
	Ayr	Paisley	Dumfries
T1	1: Funding for training, staff, research, advertising, resources 2: Increased knowledge	1: Excellent standard of care (achieved by training, funding and up to date practice) 2: Happy contented staff 3: Positive well-designed care environment	1: Happy, content patients 2: More funding for treatment, care and research 3: Effective teamwork 4: Increased awareness
T2	1: More time to care 2: Happy patients	1: Dementia trained staff 2: Better environments to care 3: Greater family involvement	1: Compulsory, dementia specific training for staff 2: More funding for social care packages 3: Role modelling 4: Rotational teams
T3	1: Dementia trained staff 2: Time to care 3: More staff	1: Standard of care that maintains personhood 2: More funding for staff and training	1: Role modelling 2: Quality improvement
T4	1: Increased knowledge of staff to improve care	1: Knowledgeable staff that understand challenging behaviours 2: More staff so more time to care	1: Person centred care for all 2: Holistic care

Table 7.2.5: Focus Group Question 5 and Ratings

The details from the tables then facilitated the ability to build an initial conceptual framework. As advocated by Miles et al (2014), conceptual frameworks can provide a useful representation of the researcher’s investigations. An initial framework (see below) provided a useful foundation of the variables where further understanding was sought and provided a practical link to the fundamental concepts underpinning the study;

Figure 7.2.1: Initial Conceptual Framework

As can be seen from the cyclical framework, the concepts are evolving and will change as the student progresses throughout their undergraduate programme. To further analyse the changing variables as exemplified in the tables and framework above, it was essential to revisit the initial rankings. According to Miles et al (2014), data condensing is a continuous process in a research study and condensation occurs throughout the process of analysis as an integral part of robust analysis. Such compilation, reduction and deduction is postulated by Yin (2018) as inherent to the construct of providing meaning and explanation in case study research. The ability to trace changes over time and draw together key themes in chronological sequence is

recognised as a method of time series analysis (Yin, 2018). Time series analysis is a major strength of the longitudinal case study.

To facilitate time series analysis and to further analyse the perceived importance of the concepts that the students ranked in the focus groups, the ratings for each question were further examined. In keeping with the mixed method design, Davis (2007) suggests counting qualitative data responses can provide a direct link to the positivist component of a successful mixed method study and assists with integration of analysis. Indeed, Miles et al (2014) concur and suggest that 'quantitizing' can provide a useful method of scoring that thus facilitates deeper understanding of the magnitude of feelings as reported by research participants. Such scoring of the qualitative data linked well not only with the mixed methods approach but also with the scoring in nominal group technique.

7.3: Scoring, Condensing and Further Analysing the Qualitative Data Using Time Series Analysis

Whilst scoring qualitative data is not a new concept (Liamputtong, 2009, Creswell, 2015, Bazeley, 2018), it can be scored in many formats. The simplest format is to tally how many times a concept is mentioned (for example; how many times communication was mentioned in the focus group). Whilst this is a valid measure of quantifying qualitative data, this study had to be scored slightly differently. As the students had already ranked their contributions in order of importance during the NGT, it was important not only to score each contribution but to also not lose this sense of perceived importance of the contribution.

Thus, the contributions and rankings were revisited and displayed again, this time in a tabulated form to demonstrate the scoring of each component according to the rating of the component by the nursing students. For example, for question 1;

What knowledge/skills/experiences/qualities do you already have that will help you care for patients with dementia?

The Ayr campus students scored the answers in the following order of priority at T1;

1: Communication

2: Patience

3: Empathy

4: Sense of Humour

Using the 'quantitizing' scoring system as exemplified by Miles et al (2014), the components would be scored 5 for communication (as it was perceived as most important), 4 for patience, 3 for empathy and 2 for sense of humour. Therefore, the greater the score, the greater the perceived importance according to the students. Using the initial answers from the students as the first point of analysis, the scores were firstly plotted on the tables as exemplified below;

7.3.1: What the Student Has: Role Adequacy and Role Legitimacy

Data Collection Timing	Question 1 - What knowledge/skills/experiences/qualities do you already have that will help you care for patients with dementia?		
	Ayr	Paisley	Dumfries
T1	1: Communication 5 2: Patience 4 3: Empathy 3 4: Sense of Humour 2	1: Patience 5 2: Empathy 4 3: Communication 3 4: Understanding 2	1: Patience, compassion and empathy 5 2: Knowledge 4 3: Evidence based practice 3
T2	1: Compassion and empathy 5 2: Understanding physiology behind behaviours 4 3: Techniques 3	1: Patience 5 2: Understanding 4 3: Knowledge 3	1: Communication 5 2: Awareness 4 3: Knowledge and understanding 3 4: Experience 2
T3	1: Patience, empathy and understanding 5 2: Knowledge 4	1: Empathy 5 2: Understanding of personhood 4 3: Understanding of disease progression 3	1: Knowledge and understanding 5 2: Desire to get to know the person 4 3: Experience 3
T4	1: Communication skills 5 2: Knowledge 4	1: Empathy 5 2: Knowledge 4 3: Understanding of effects of dementia 3	1: Experience 5

Table 7.3.1: Focus Group Question 1 with Scores

These themes were then totalled to give an understanding of both theme and order of overall priority;

Theme	Ratings	Total	Order of Importance
Communication	5,3,5,5	18	4 th
Patience	4,5,5,5,5	24	3 rd
Empathy and Compassion	3,4,5,5,5,5,5	32	2 nd
Sense of Humour	2	2	7 th
Knowledge and Understanding	2,4,4,4,3,3,5,4,4,4,5,4,4,4	49	1 st
Evidence Based Practice/Practical Experience	3,3,4,2,3,3	16	5 th
Other	4	4	6 th

Table 7.3.1a: Focus Groups: Question 1: Ratings in Order of Priority

Thereafter using the concept of time series analysis (Yin, 2018), the themes were broken into order of priority by data collection timings to explore and analyse the variable of time;

Theme	Ratings			
	Total T1	Total T2	Total T3	Total T4
Communication	8	10	5	5
Patience	14 (1 st)	5	5	0
Empathy and Compassion	12	5	10	5
Sense of Humour	2	0	0	0
Knowledge and Understanding	6	14 (1 st)	16 (1 st)	11 (1 st)
Evidence Based Practice/Practical Experience	3	5	3	5
Other	0	4	4	0

Table 7.3.1b: Focus Groups: Question 1: Ratings over Time

The variable of time can be easier to conceptualise when presented in graph format;

Figure 7.3.1: Focus Groups: Question 1: Themes and Changes over Time

As can be seen, at T1, patience was perceived as the most important quality that students already had, to help them care for people with dementia;

This perceived importance of patience was exemplified in the student's discussions, with some students acknowledging that their personal skills were all they had to offer at such an early stage in their nursing career;

"I have no experience so I put down that I am patient and have empathy"

Student P1, T1

"I have no experience of nursing but I know people with dementia have trouble eating and speaking so looking after them is similar to being a good parent I suppose; being patient"

Student D4, T1

"you need a lot of patience and empathy because one day it could be you"

Student D2, T1

Whilst patience was suggested by most at T1 as an inherent quality, rather than something that was learned, one student with dementia experience asserted that she was patient because she understood what was happening;

"you are patient because you understand why they are asking you things over and over again"

Student D1, T1

Furthermore, understanding challenges to patience were also recognised;

“with the repetitive nature of dementia, you need to be patient as you need to repeat the same thing over and over again”

Student D12, T1

“a lot of the times, whether you were there in the morning or the night before, they don’t know who you are, you need to remind them, again and again”

Student A3, T1

This recognised challenge and the ability to demonstrate patience (1st ranking at T1) and compassion and empathy (2nd ranking at T1) were linked to the skill of communication (3rd ranking at T1);

“you’ve got to communicate with them. I think the cornerstone to nursing is communication”

Student D1, T1

“you’ve got to continually tell them who you are and what you are doing”

Student P4, T1

“you need to be really aware of your non-verbal communication.....not let them think.....they are just a nuisance”

Student A11, T1

“you’ve got to show you are approachable.....you can’t be sulky or crabbit (grumpy).....you don’t want to scare them”

Student A1, T1

However, for most students that had little or no experience, there was the notion that you can have inherent skills such as patience but be unable to action them if you don’t have the knowledge base;

“It’s alright being a patient person, but if you don’t understand why you are being patient, it kind of defeats the purpose”

Student D6, T1

“you can be patient but absolutely rubbish at communicating”

Student P4, T1

Thus, the need for knowledge and understanding, as identified as 1st priority at T2, T3 and T4 was identified and could be explored in time series analysis, as advocated by Yin (2018);

Knowledge and understanding increased as students moved into year 2 (T2);

“I feel I had patience and empathy before, but now I have the actual knowledge to back it up.....now I’ve got the skills”

Student A7, T2

“I’ve learned people’s condition can change in different environments”

Student A5, T2

“I can understand some of the physical and emotional effects”

Student A8, T2

By year 3 (T3), students were appreciating disease progression and the implications of differing styles of caring behaviours;

“I have an understanding of disease progression”

Student P7, T3

“you can understand why they are behaving the way they are behaving”

Student A8, T3

“having knowledge means you can deal with things in a better way”

Student P2, T3

“I’ve learned that my actions determine my patients reactions.....it’s fascinating”

Student D6, T3

Lastly, by the end of the undergraduate programme (T4), students were appreciating the uniqueness of the dementia journey and the importance of individualised care;

“Dementia is different for everyone, that’s why maintaining personhood is so important”

Student P1, T4

This process of ‘quaitizing’ to condense, displaying in chart format and then using time series analysis to explore the variable of time was then completed with the other focus group questions;

7.3.2: What the Student Needs: Role Support Required

Order of Importance	Question 2 - What do you hope/need to learn/gain to help you care for patients with dementia?		
	Ayr	Paisley	Dumfries
T1	1: Knowledge 5 2: Experience (simulation and practice) 4 3: Learn how to care for patients at different stages of journey 3	1: Knowledge 5 2: Practical experience 4 3: How to care for patients in practice 3 4: Current guidelines 2	1: Knowledge 5 2: Skills 4 3: How to support patients and families 3
T2	1: Knowledge and understanding 5 2: Seeing things from the family's perspective 4	1: Knowledge 5 2: Patient experience 4 3: Clinical experience 3	1: Dementia journey from patient perspective 5 2: Awareness of patient's rights 4 3: Risk factors 3
T3	1: Knowledge 5 2: More ways to deliver person centred care 4 3: Experience of dementia in different care areas 3	1: Knowledge 5 2: More experience 4	1: Ability to change the culture 5 2: Knowledge 4
T4	1: Knowledge 5 2: Experience 4	1: Knowledge 5 2: Practical experience at all aspects of dementia journey 4	1: Learning how to care for older people with multiple comorbidities, including dementia 5 2: Learning that is ongoing in response to change in policy or new research 4

Table 7.3.2: Focus Groups: Question 2 with Scores

Theme	Ratings	Total	Order of Importance
Knowledge and Understanding	5,5,5,5,5,5,4,5,5	49	1 st
Practical experience	4,4,4,3,3,4,4,4	30	3 rd
Specifically Identified Learning Need	3,3,3,4,4,5,4,3,4,5,5	43	2 nd
Guidelines/Research	2,4	6	4 th

Table 7.3.2a: Focus Groups: Question 2: Ratings in Order of Priority

Theme	Ratings Total	Ratings Total	Ratings Total	Ratings Total
	T1	T2	T3	T4
Knowledge and Understanding	18 (1 ST)	10	14 (1 ST)	10 (1 ST)
Practical Experience	12	0	7	8
Specifically Identified Learning Need	6	19 (1 ST)	9	9
Guidelines/Research	2	4	0	0

Table 7.3.2b: Focus Groups: Question 2: Ratings over Time

Figure 7.3.2: Question 2: Themes and Changes over Time

As displayed above, for question 2, all students prioritised learning at all data collections. Knowledge and understanding were perceived as most important at T1, T3 and T4, with T2 identifying areas of specific learning need.

This thirst for knowledge and understanding even from programme induction week (T1) was apparent from all students, at all campuses, with students wanting to know everything they possibly could about dementia;

“I want knowledge and skills and techniques”

Student, D11, T1

“I don’t have a lot of nursing, health and medical knowledge and that’s what I need”

Student, D9, T1

“I want an understanding of the progression in dementia”

Student, A9, T1

"I want knowledge about dementia, how to support patients, facts, figures, legislations, what guidelines are there to help us"

Student, A12, T1

However, at T1, there were also some misconceptions in knowledge;

"I read a book about 8-10 years ago and it said that most people with dementia get it from CJD as they used to feed animals their own flesh and stuff like that; is that factually correct?"

Student, D8, T1

With some students even recognising they needed a 'how to' instruction book

"I need a 'how to care for patients in practice' book"

Student P6, T1

"I want the tools to help me deal with it, the tools of the trade"

Student A2, T1

Indeed, despite such naivety at T1, all students, even by T2 had cared for at least one person with dementia and were able to recognise that learning had taken place;

"I've come across people with dementia in every clinical area"

Student A1, T2

"I'm now aware of my responsibility to my patients"

Student D7, T2

“I was in a nursing home and 90% of the residents had dementia. It was fantastic to put into practice what we had learned”

Student D2, T2

Such recognition that their learning was transferable to practice was acknowledged, with the theory/practice link evident;

“I put theory into practice. The Domus stuff that we did.....like how the person feels and stuff like that.....I’ve been able to relate that out in practice with people I’m working with.....I could see first-hand the physical and emotional effects”

Student A9, T2

“I put theory into practice, it’s just an increased knowledge and understanding”

Student A12, T3

Indeed, the practical, experiential learning was very apparent in their assertions;

“you learn as you go along, I think, when you are working with people with dementia”

Student P3, T2

“you see how other staff deal with the patient and family, its learning”

Student P5, T2

“learning in practice is in a way I couldn’t imagine in any other situation in life”

Student D3, T4

With many students also recognising the unique importance of the patient experience in their learning journey;

“actually hearing from someone who is living through dementia taught me so much I didn’t know”

Student P5, T2

“it’s about living with dementia, having a life, having some sort of control”

Student A3, T4

“enabling people to take risks, learn new skills.....you don’t just let people stagnate”

Student D9, T4

As time moved on, the recognition of the holistic impact of dementia was apparent;

“it’s finding out what works for that individual person, what works for them, not forgetting it’s person centred”

Student A4, T3

“I used to think it was just a memory thing, I didn’t realise it affects your sight and sense of touch”

Student D2, T3

Furthermore, students also recognised the complexities of caring for older people with multiple comorbidities;

“the patient had type 1 diabetes (that they’d had for many years) and they had dementia. Staff presumed that because the patient had dementia, they were not able to manage their diabetes. Quite the opposite! You should never just assume”

Student D3, T4

“I’ve completely altered my perceptions of dementia and the physical and mental issues that go with it, I never realised it could affect so much”

Student D5, T4

This appreciation of the complexity of caring for older people with multiple needs was evident in the students need for ongoing learning, even at the end of their programme (T4);

“I need more placement exposure to people with dementia”

Student A4, T4

“I need more older adult experience and dementia education; I need to be prepared to continually learn”

Student P3, T4

“I need more experience of managing patient care and I need to broaden my knowledge to help me be able to keep giving the best care”

Student P2, T4

In recognition of the need for ongoing learning, an interesting finding was apparent from the mental health students. Whilst dementia is often grouped in healthcare under mental health as opposed to physical health, the students who were mental health field, were not as experienced in delivering dementia care as the adult students;

“most of my placements have been community mental health”

Student P11, T4

“my only inpatient experience in mental health was in acute admissions where I saw more psychosis and stuff.....my adult placement was out-patients, I’ve never seen someone with dementia in a hospital at all”

Student P12, T4

In particular, when they did come across people with dementia, it was at an earlier stage of the dementia journey and those students had quite specific learning needs in relation to caring for people with dementia;

“I have only come across dementia in memory clinics, pre and post diagnosis. Patients were quite well. I believe I really need experience of dementia in a ward setting”

Student P12, T4

“I need experience of delivering personal care, assisting with eating and drinking, the basics”

Student P11, T4

As well as recognising such learning needs, the students recognised the challenges to delivering dementia care that they perceived they would come across (T1) and the challenges they had actually come across (T2-T4).

7.3.3: Challenges to Achieving Role Adequacy and Role Legitimacy

Data Collection Timings	Question 3 - What challenges will be/have been in your way?		
	Ayr	Paisley	Dumfries
T1	1: Families (of patients) 5 2: Knowledge and understanding 4 3: Time 3	1: The person-centred care (being able to give the care you want) 5 2: Challenging behaviour 4 3: Resources (time, staff, funding) 3	1: Getting support (for patients and families) from health and social care teams 5 2: Patients families 4 3: Challenging behaviour 3
T2	1: Emotionally challenging 5 2: Keeping the individual safe 4 3: Environment 3	1: Staff attitudes 5 2: Time 4 3: Environment 3	1: Staff attitudes 5 2: Time 4 3: Environment 3
T3	1: Other staff 5 2: Time 4	1: Staff attitudes 5 2: Lack of dementia diagnosis 4 3: Recognition of ultimate outcome for patients 3	1: Staff attitudes 5 2: Environment 4
T4	1: Staff communication skills 5 2: Families 4	1: Other staff 5 2: Staff burnout – mental and physical exhaustion 4 3: Time 3	1: Staff attitudes 5 2: Lack of policy implementation 4

Table 7.3.3: Focus Groups: Question 3 with Scores

Theme	Ratings	Total	Order of Importance
Patient Challenge	4,3,4	11	6 th
Family Challenge	5,4,4	13	4 th
Knowledge Deficit challenge	4	4	7 th
Attitudinal Challenge	5,5,5,5,5,5,5	40	1 st
Care Related Challenge	5,5,4,4	18	3 rd
Resource Related Challenge	3,3,4,4,4,3	21	2 nd
Environmental Challenge	3,3,3,4	13	4 th
Emotional Challenge	5,3,4	12	5 th

Table 7.3.3a: Focus Groups: Question 3: Ratings in Order of Priority

Theme	Ratings T1	Ratings T2	Ratings T3	Ratings T4
Patient Challenge	7	4	0	0
Family Challenge	9	0	0	4
Knowledge Deficit Challenge	4	0	0	0
Attitudinal Challenge	0	10 (1 st)	15 (1 st)	15 (1 st)
Care Related Challenge	10 (1 st)	0	4	4
Resource Related Challenge	6	8	4	3
Environmental Challenge	0	9	4	0
Emotional Challenge	0	5	3	4

Table 7.3.3b: Focus Groups: Question 3: Ratings over Time

Figure 7.3.3: Focus Groups: Question 3: Themes and Changes over Time

As displayed above, the students perceived care related issues to be the biggest challenge at T1. Students initially worried about having the resilience to deal with the challenging behaviour that dementia can bring;

“I feel intimidated when people are aggressive”

Student P9, T1

“The emotional behaviour can be challenging and difficult”

Student P7, T1

“They don’t understand what’s happening to them so they lash out in another way”

Student A11, T1

Students also worried about the emotional aspect of delivering dementia care;

“Even with any amount of training, it must be difficult, you can still get attached to patients”

Student P12, T1

“you know the progressive and terminal nature of the condition”

Student D11, T1

Moreover, those with personal experience of dementia, recognised the emotional challenge that dementia can have on families;

“you can end up in an argument with families over care”

Student P1, T1

Families feel guilty so they lash out at the people who are helping because they feel guilty they cannot provide the care by themselves”

Student A1, T1

“Some people (families) will not let you help; they are in denial at the diagnosis but this can stop you progressing with treatment”

Student D7, T1

Additionally, at T1, the complexity of managing care for people with dementia was also a perceived challenge to the students;

“putting in place the right care.....getting a social worker.....getting a care package takes so long”

Student D11, T1

“time is a massive thing, people with dementia do need extra time”

Student, P4, T1

“patient safety.....ensuring they aren’t wandering off and falling all the time but also making sure that they can choose to go for a walk or make a choice to do something to pass the time”

Student A3, T1

As time moved on (T2-T4) and the students became more experienced, they became aware of competing priorities and the challenge of managing dementia, particularly in acute care settings;

“you can only do what you can do”

Student A6, T2

“I’d love to spend all the time in the world with someone because they’re confused or disorientated but when I have 20 or 30 others demanding my attention at the same time it’s so hard”

Student A4, T3

“you have one sick patient and one patient with dementia, the sick patient takes priority, physical needs are prioritised first”

Student A1, T4

“getting obs done every 15 minutes post op takes priority over the wee lady with dementia”

Student D4, T3

“hospitals can be quite horrific for people with dementia as staff just don’t have the time”

Student D1, T4

“lack of beds means people with dementia are stuck in wards where they shouldn’t be”

Student A3, T4

However, by far the most discussed challenge and rated as 1st priority at T2-T4 was the challenge of other staff (nursing staff; both trained and untrained);

“the biggest challenge is other people, not the person with dementia, but other people, other staff”

Student A10, T3

In particular, staff attitude was highlighted;

“other staff’s attitude, there was not a lot of support there”

Student P9, T2

“there was huffing and puffing and sighing and oh, here he goes again; they got the same level of care but prior to them getting to the patient, it felt as though it was a bother”

Student P1, T3

“they say why are they doing that, they’re doing that on purpose”

Student A3, T3

"I came across some really bad attitudes.....if you think the person isn't worth your time.....it shows in your behaviour"

Student D5, T4

"poor attitudes and power differentials when people have a lot of clinical experience"

Student P7, T3

Indeed, clinical experience was not always related to the ability to deliver better care, in fact sometimes the opposite;

"the people that understood more were the more newly qualified nurses, rather than the ones who had been maybe doing the job for years"

Student A12, T4

Such disparity of knowledge was demonstrated in the acknowledgement that challenging attitudes may be down to a lack of dementia knowledge and awareness, even in clinically experienced staff;

"maybe a lot of the time it's not deliberate to deliver bad care"

Student D9, T4

"you are dealing with staff who have no clue"

Student D1, T4

“negative attitudes from staff who had been in their job a long time. I don’t think its newly qualified staff. People who have been in the job for 20 years and just don’t have the knowledge”

Student A6, T4

“it would be good to video them to see if they are aware of what they are doing, I think they probably don’t even know any better”

Student P1, T4

Whilst the identified challenges seemed unsurmountable for some, the forward-thinking students then naturally moved forward towards finding solutions to the challenges that they had acknowledged;

7.3.4: Solutions to Overcome Challenges

Data Collection Timing	Question 4 - What are the solutions to these challenges and how can you move forward?		
	Ayr	Paisley	Dumfries
T1	1: Training and increased knowledge for staff and families 5 2: More time to care 4	1: Training 5 2: Funding 4 3: Support 3 4: MDT Communication 2 5: Gaining confidence 1	1: Communication 5 2: Increased awareness of dementia 4 3: More funding 3
T2	1: Training 5 2: Learning through role play 4	1: Staff training 5 2: Role modelling 4 3: More staff 3	1: Education for staff 5 2: Awareness of patient need by staff 4 3: Better time management by staff 3
T3	1: Training 5 2: Time 4 3: More staff 3	1: Staff training 5 2: Role modelling 4 3: Challenging negative staff behaviours 3	1: Staff training 5 2: Increased awareness of patient's rights 4 3: Better environments 3
T4	1: Training for staff 5 2: Study time for staff 4 3: Research 3	1: Staff training 5 2: Engagement with new knowledge and policies 4 3: More staff 3	1: Staff learning 5 2: Awareness of patients abilities 4

Table 7.3.4: Focus Groups: Question 4 with Scores

Theme	Ratings	Total	Order of Importance
Training/Learning/Research	5,5,5,5,5,5,5,5,5,3,5,4,5	64	1 st
Funding	4,3	7	5 th
Resources (staff/time/environment)	4,3,3,4,3,3,4,3	27	2 nd
Support/confidence	3,1,	4	6 th
Role modelling	4,4	8	4 th
Awareness/Better communication	2,5,4,4,3,4,4	26	3 rd

Table 7.3.4a: Focus Groups: Question 4: Ratings in Order of Priority

Theme	Ratings T1	Ratings T2	Ratings T3	Ratings T4
Training/Learning/Research	10	19 (1 st)	15 (1 st)	26 (1 st)
Funding	7	0	0	0
Resources (staff/time/environment)	4	6	10	3
Support/confidence	4	0	0	0
Role Modelling	0	4	4	0
Awareness/Better Communication	11 (1 st)	4	7	4

Table 7.3.4b: Focus Groups: Question 4: Ratings over Time

Figure 7.3.4: Focus Groups: Question 4: Themes and Changes over Time

As illustrated, at T1, awareness and better communication were highlighted as the top priority solution;

“having a wide range of info and support available would be great”

Student, P2, T1

“there’s a lot of things out just now about mental health, it would be good if increased awareness of dementia continued”

Student D2, T1

However, communication between health and social care teams in particular was highlighted as potentially challenging to solve;

“teamwork is essential.....it needs to start early. If we’re not at the stage to talk to each other, even in student life, bumping alongside social services then they might have a completely different picture of what we should do.....you’re just going to bump heads”

Student A5, T1

Indeed, whilst awareness and communication were not cited as top priority in T2-T4, such lack of understanding was further exemplified by the prioritisation of teaching, learning and research as a solution to challenges, at all further data collections (T2-T4);

“when people (including some nurses) hear dementia, they just think memory loss, there needs to be greater knowledge and insight”

Student P12, T3

“there needs to be extra training courses for staff to attend to keep them up to date”

Student D7, T2

This need for ongoing learning throughout a nursing career was obvious from the student’s assertions. Furthermore, (as previously suggested when the students considered challenges in question 3), more experienced practitioners were not always correlated with the ability to deliver the best, up to date, evidence-based care;

“I’ve tried challenging practice but I don’t have the authority to challenge. On the other hand, some say ‘well you’re the student, you’ll be more up to date than me’. With revalidation maybe that will change? Although nurses should’ve been up to date, the fact that revalidation is being brought in makes you think that maybe they weren’t?”

Student P11, T4

Interestingly, when considering this need for continued learning, the students reflected upon how they had learned and the transferability of that style of learning to experienced nurses in practice;

“we were prepared because of role play and scenarios, trial and error if you like, but safely”

Student A12, T4

“I think it would be great to give staff a wee reminder.....some role play.....just going back and considering what it’s like for the patient who can’t see, who’s confused and who’s getting their teeth brushed by someone they don’t know.....it’s a reminder of the basics, a reality check to bring the empathy back”

Student A6, T4

Nonetheless, whilst students acknowledged that greater experience was not always associated with up to date knowledge and evidence-based nursing care, the fact that they were still learners themselves was apparent, as they sought someone to aspire to, even when nearing the point of registration at T4;

“it would be great to have a role model”

Student D5, T4

“role modelling in dementia care would be excellent. Someone who knows their stuff, who can lead by example”

Student P12, T4

Although student’s mentors can often be role models, the impression given was that role models specifically for dementia care would be beneficial. Whilst the role model aspiration of dementia champions were acknowledged;

“dementia champions are great”

Student A4, T3

Students purported that it had to be the right people in the role to fulfil such aspirational status;

“If people are forced to be a champion and they don’t have the right attitude it doesn’t make any difference to care”

Student D9, T4

“If it’s not the right people, it’s not going to help”

Student D3, T4

Additionally, suggesting that paying lip service to a role, can make the situation even more unfortunate;

“if people take on the role of dementia champion just for the sake of it, it makes it worse”

Student P11, T4

Indeed, as well as advocating for aspiration role models, who are motivated to make positive changes to dementia care delivery, the students were ambitious in their ideas to help deliver excellent dementia care;

7.3.5: Ultimate Goals

Data Collection Timing	Question 5 – What are your ultimate goals to help deliver excellent care to patients with dementia?		
	Ayr	Paisley	Dumfries
T1	1: Funding for training, staff, research, advertising, resources 5 2: Increased knowledge 4	1: Excellent standard of care (achieved by training, funding and up to date practice) 5 2: Happy contented staff 4 3: Positive well-designed care environment 3	1: Happy, content patients 5 2: More funding for treatment, care and research 4 3: Effective teamwork 3 4: Increased awareness 2
T2	1: More time to care 5 2: Happy patients 4	1: Dementia trained staff 5 2: Better environments to care 4 3: Greater family involvement 3	1: Compulsory, dementia specific training for staff 5 2: More funding for social care packages 4 3: Role modelling 3 4: Rotational teams 2
T3	1: Dementia trained staff 5 2: Time to care 4 3: More staff 3	1: Standard of care that maintains personhood 5 2: More funding for staff and training 4	1: Role modelling 5 2: Quality improvement 4
T4	1: Increased knowledge of staff to improve care 5	1: Knowledgeable staff that understand challenging behaviours 5 2: More staff so more time to care 4	1: Person centred care for all 5 2: Holistic care 4

Table 7.3.5: Focus Groups: Question 5 with Scores

Theme	Ratings	Total	Order of Importance
Knowledge/learning/training Goal	4,2,5,5,5,5,5	31	2 nd
Resource Goal (staff/time/environment)	4,3,5,4,4,3,4	31	2 nd
Funding Goal	5,4,4,4	17	3 rd
Patient/Family Care Goal	5,5,4,3,5,4,5,4	35	1 st
Staff/Team Goal	3,3,2,5	13	4 th

Table 7.3.5a: Focus Groups: Question 5: Ratings in Order of Priority

Theme	Ratings T1	Ratings T2	Ratings T3	Ratings T4
Knowledge/Learning/Training Goal	6	10	5	10
Resource Goal (staff/time/environment)	3	4	3	0
Funding Goal	9	4	4	0
Patient/Family Care Goal	10 (1 st)	12 (1 st)	13 (1 st)	13 (1 st)
Staff/Team Goal	7	5	5	0

Table 7.3.5b: Focus Groups: Question 5: Ratings Over Time

Figure 7.3.5: Focus Groups: Question 5: Themes and Changes over Time

As can be seen from the graph above, students’ aspirational goals for the delivery of excellent dementia care were all prioritised on one significant goal from T1 to T4 inclusive; the patient and their family.

Whilst the need for knowledge was again recognised;

“we need teams of excellence, highly trained teams of staff”

Student D10, T1

“you need better awareness, knowledge and understanding of dementia”

Student D6, T2

And the benefits of greater funding and resources undeniable;

“we need more care, more support, more funding and more research”

Student D8, T2

“there needs to be increased funding to increase access to social activities for older people in the community with dementia”

Student P11, T4

“they need to keep the funds in dementia, I know there’s a lot of money being spent just now but that’s not always going to be the case”

Student P8, T1

Even with the threat of no funding, aspirations still continued;

“even if we could never raise the funds, we would still care, we want them (the patients) to be happy”

Student D2, T2

This desire to care was exemplified by the fact that the students prioritised the patient and family’s needs before they had any knowledge input or care experience. From induction week (T1), students knew how they wanted their patients to feel;

“I want patients to be happy and content”

Student D1, T1

“the goal is for calm, happy, settled patients”

Student P5, T1

“you and the people you work with can give people the best quality of life for the time that they’ve got left”

Student A11, T1

Moreover, even when more experienced and faced with the many challenges that have already been identified, the students still remained focused on the patient and family, driven by the motivation to put the patient first at all times;

“you don’t treat them as an illness but as a person, putting their dementia aside and getting to know them”

Student A3, T4

“take time to engage with patients.....quality time.....not just during interventions.....show an interest in something they enjoy”

Student A12, T4

“I treat them the way I treat my own mother, how I’d want her to be treated”

Student D9, T4

“you must maintain personhood, choice, control and dignity”

Student P12, T4

Finally, such desire to show caring and aspiration to make a difference was exemplified by a student who spoke emotionally about a particular patient she had cared for;

“I do believe I can make their lives better because I have learned some of the ways to do that. So, I don’t feel helpless or hopeless, even if the person can’t respond, even if they can’t smile, to say you’ve made a difference. I know I’ve made a difference. One day I was talking to her about some of the things her son said she was involved in and there was one moment.....she looked at me, literally looked right at me.....and I said, can

you understand?.....it was really emotional.....then she drifted again but in that moment I thought.....connection is everything”

Student D1, T4

This clear connection to learning that this student made and the assertions and aspirations of all the students in the focus groups were then linked back to the initial conceptual framework underpinning the research.

7.4: Conceptual Framework

As a reminder of the initial conceptual framework, it can be seen that the concepts were evolving and were anticipated to change over time;

Figure 7.4: Initial Conceptual Framework

Following time series analysis of the qualitative focus group findings, it was clear that the patient and family were at the centre of all aspects of the students' thoughts and affected every component of the conceptual framework. The 2-way arrows, in the following diagram depict the reciprocal relationship between the student and their patient;

Figure 7.4.1: Conceptual Framework with the Patient and their Family

Moreover, when the findings of the focus groups are then added to the framework, it gives greater context to the evolving concepts and the mutually effective relationships. However, it is also important to link the conceptual framework back to the underpinning theoretical

framework of this study; Social Learning Theory and the concept of Self-Efficacy (Bandura, 1997a, Bandura 1997b, Hayden, 2014).

Social Learning Theory is observable as the student firstly considers what they already know (learned knowledge and skills) and what they already have (inherent knowledge and skills). These are depicted as per Social Learning Theory, by considering Attention, Retention, Motivation and Reproduction. These aspects were observable at T1 through to T4 and are evolving and ongoing as the student's learning journey continues. The conceptual framework demonstrates flow through the diagrammatic arrows and it was apparent that the students progressed around the cycle more than once and would indeed continue to cyclically progress at nursing registration and beyond, demonstrating the lifelong commitment to learning in nursing.

Using the learning components of Social Learning Theory; through Attention, the student is influenced by the patient's needs, emotionally aroused by the effects of dementia and has expectations of their own ability to deliver dementia care. By Retention, the student remembers learning via coding and the symbolic influence of the learning environment (both simulated and clinical). Motivation sees the student demonstrate the desire to learn, care and enhance quality of life. Thereafter, Reproduction is where the student reproduces what they have learned (both in class and in practice).

Furthermore, the overarching and ongoing theme of the conceptual framework is Self-Efficacy. Again, the evolving and ongoing nature of self-efficacy is demonstrated by the progressive arrows and every aspect of the framework is influenced by the concept of self-efficacy. Using the components of self-efficacy as purported by Bandura (1997a, 1997b), the student is firstly influenced by Vicarious Experience (how they have been modelled by others), thus the impact of the attitudinal challenges reported by the students and the perceived importance of the need for role modelling. The student is also influenced in terms of Psychological and Emotional Status and indeed the psychological and emotional impact of nursing people with dementia was apparent in the student's assertions from T1 to T4. Students are also affected by Social Persuasion, through coaching, feedback and ultimately self-assessment. Lastly, students perceive their accomplishment of care delivery through Mastery Experience, reflecting on their

inherent and learned knowledge and skills and the impact this had on care delivery. This naturally leads to progression around the framework and the reconsideration of needs and wants and thus the cycle continues.

This progressive cycle, the students' feedback from their focus groups and the underpinning theoretical framework of Social Learning Theory and concept of Self Efficacy are depicted in the conceptual framework below. Using the format of structured qualitative data analysis by Miles et al (2014), this framework visually displays the final component of qualitative data analysis;

Figure 7.4.2 Overall Conceptual Framework

7.5: Summary

This chapter has presented the qualitative results of this study. The demographics of the qualitative focus group participants were detailed and were reflective of the overall cohort; most students being female, under 30 years of age, studying adult nursing and with little or dementia education or experience. Changes in the focus groups were then tracked from baseline (T1) to point of registration (T4) and although there was attrition due to the longitudinal nature of the study, the focus group status was maintained and all student students who wanted to participate were able.

Thereafter, changes in the students' engagement with nominal group technique over time was critiqued, including changes to group dynamics, researcher observations and engagement in nominal group technique and the Ketso Kit. The focus groups went well and provided interesting group dynamics, from unsure novice first years to confident and competent third years, both the process and the discussion developed positively over time. Also, the Ketso kit was popular with the students and provided a novel way of eliciting focus group discussion.

The NGT process worked extremely well as a structured method of feeding back when the students were both nursing and research novices, as well as when they were more experienced and had more to offer. The NGT rankings were summarised at each data collection and the changes in responses and rankings over time tabulated using time series analysis.

Initially, students recognised their lack of knowledge and understanding but similar to the quantitative scoring, acknowledged themselves to have inherent qualities to offer, such as patience and empathy. Through time series analysis, the students became more aware of the need for knowledge of the dementia journey and developed an appreciation of the disease process and challenges of caring for such a complex an unpredictable journey. Certainly, with this appreciation, came a thirst for even more learning and specific learning needs were identified by many.

As well as identifying such learning needs, students perceived challenges to dementia care delivery. These challenges moved from initially worrying about the dynamics of delivering dementia care and dealing with the emotive side of care delivery to dealing with challenging care environments, limited resources and overwhelmingly poor attitudes from staff in clinical areas.

Nonetheless, despite these challenges, students were able to suggest solutions to the problems encountered. An overall focus on increasing understanding of dementia was emphasised, namely identifying ongoing teaching, learning and research as a means of care improvement. Lastly, overall, from all students, on all campuses, their ultimate focus was the patient and their family and this was exemplified by the student's aspirations for patient centered care across the board.

These aspirations helped formulate a conceptual framework, which was refined to put the patient and the family at the centre of all care and care decisions and then finally, a conceptual framework of emergent themes was generated, demonstrating conceptual analysis of the qualitative findings overall.

The next chapter of this thesis will triangulate the quantitative and qualitative findings in keeping with the mixed methods approach.

Chapter Eight: Triangulation of Quantitative and Qualitative Results

Concurrent triangulation of the quantitative and qualitative data was carried out throughout this longitudinal study. However, as analysis of multiple variables and analysis over time is complex (O’Cathan et al, 2010, Yin, 2018), a sequential approach to the presentation of data findings and analysis using ‘layering’ was adopted (Cresswell and Plano Clark, 2011, Bazeley, 2018). The previous two chapters detailed the quantitative and qualitative data results, and now, in keeping with the layering approach, the next stage is to set the analysis in context as a ‘unified whole’ mixed methods study (Bazely, 2018). Indeed, such cohesive analysis in a research study assists in the interpretation of theory and in establishing achievement of the research aims; professed as one of the most essential components of a doctoral thesis according to Murray (2011). An integrated approach to achievement of research aims is essential in mixed methods case studies (Yin, 2018).

This chapter will critically triangulate the research findings to allow for such integrated achievement of the research aims. This will focus around the original themes of the research; namely; Therapeutic Commitment, Role Security and Role Support and the changes in these over time.

8.0: Students Perceptions of Role and Influences over Time

Aim 1 of the study was; To explore undergraduate student nurse perceptions of dementia care and their role in care delivery. According to social learning theory, perceptions are influenced by the environment around oneself and are shaped by learned knowledge and experiences (Bandura, 2006, Hayden, 2014), thus it is logical to triangulate the results relating to Aim 2 of the study in parallel to Aim 1. Aim 2 was; To examine the influence of theory, skills training and clinical experience on approach to dementia care delivery amongst undergraduate student nurses. The first aspect of students perceptions, considered their therapeutic commitment to dementia care.

8.1: Therapeutic Commitment

Therapeutic Commitment was measured by the Dementia and Dementia Care Perceptions Questionnaire (DDCPQ) and total scores calculated by measuring scores for the students Task Specific Self-Esteem (TSSE) as well as Satisfaction Working with Dementia (SWD) and the Motivation to Work with Dementia (MWD).

In terms of this study, the majority of the students were novices at course commencement. Of the (n=420) students in the study, most started with no experience of dementia care whatsoever (n=295) and the majority had never received any form of dementia education (n=199). This lack of experience was consistent across all student groups, from all campuses. Indeed, qualitative data from the focus groups supported this lack of experience, with students articulating their feelings of insecurity and uncertainty at their lack of knowledge and experience and also their desire to learn the skills and knowledge that they perceived to be required of them. Such inexperience and lack of confidence at course commencement is consistent with the literature, reporting that most students entering undergraduate nursing programmes are beginners (Brown, et al, 2008, Stevens, 2011, Baillie et al, 2015).

Indeed, although most students initially had a novice status, therapeutic commitment scores were positive at course commencement. The students' therapeutic commitment scores were calculated at course commencement (T1) and then changes over time measured each academic year (T2 and T3) and lastly at the end of course, when the students were ready for registration (T4). However, mean scores for Task Specific Self Esteem significantly reduced from T1 to T2 ($p=0.000$), from T2 to T3 ($p=0.000$) and from T3-T4 ($p=0.000$). To put this in meaningful context, this was a 3%, 17% and 9% reduction respectively and a 27% overall reduction in scores during the undergraduate nursing programme. Similar findings were also found for Satisfaction in Working with Dementia ($p=0.000$; 6% reduction T1 to T2, $p=0.002$; 2% reduction T2 to T3, $p=0.004$; 2% reduction T3 to T4), resulting in a 10% reduction overall in satisfaction scores from T1 to T4. Furthermore, although Motivation to Work with Dementia increased significantly from T1 to T2 ($p=0.000$, an increase of 2%) this was followed by a similar decline to satisfaction scores with a reduction at T2 to T3 ($p=0.003$, 12%) and again at T3 to T4 ($p=0.000$, 6%), making an overall reduction in motivation of 16%. Thus, as the students continued through their nursing

programme, their therapeutic commitment reduced. Specifically, as the number of people with dementia that they cared for increased, their levels of motivation and satisfaction reduced. Furthermore, there was a significant relationship between lower commitment scores and students who worked in dementia care ($p=0.000$) or previously worked in dementia care ($p=0.000$). This challenge to motivation and reduced feelings of satisfaction drawn from the DDCPQ were evident in the students' assertions during the focus groups. Students initially were both motivated to work in dementia care and perceived that they would achieve satisfaction working in dementia care. Nevertheless, as the students became more experienced (particularly from T3 onwards), they became acutely aware of attitudinal conflict in clinical practice when it came to delivering dementia care. These attitudinal challenges were also associated with poor levels of knowledge, understanding and awareness amongst clinical colleagues, especially the more experienced ones (both trained nurses and healthcare support assistants). This off-putting environment negatively affected the student's attitude scores but was also evident from the focus group feedback, in that the students perceived this negativity to affect their feelings of worth and their ability to impact positive change.

Such challenges with staff attitude correlates with the findings of a report by the Care Quality Commission (2011) who acknowledge that staff attitude can have a detrimental effect on both dementia care and the caring experience of those in the care giving team. Indeed, the challenges of providing dementia care are well acknowledged in national dementia policy (Scottish Government 2010, Scottish Government, 2013, Scottish Government, 2017) and will be further discussed in the next chapter. Interestingly, when considering student commitment to provide dementia care and their high motivational levels as well as perceived satisfaction at course commencement, the fact that levels of motivation and satisfaction reduced when clinical placement exposure increased, suggests that the clinical environment was the most influential factor. These findings draw parallels with the longitudinal study by Brown et al (2008) who suggest that students do not commence nursing programmes with negative preconceptions of elderly care but indeed, contributing factors to negative connotations of elderly care can be related to poor care standards and unhelpful staff attitudes directly observed in the elderly care environment during clinical placements, a view concurred by Baillie et al (2015).

Nonetheless, although the students reported some negative aspects from their clinical learning environments, the students remained positive overall to caring for people with dementia, with

adult nursing students in particular motivated to work with people with dementia. From the DDCPQ, it was clear that a significant motivator and positive influence towards therapeutic commitment and perceived satisfaction was education. Education in dementia care demonstrated a significant positive relationship with task specific self-esteem ($p=0.000$), satisfaction ($p=0.000$) and motivation to work with dementia ($p=0.000$). These findings support the work by Liu, Norman and While (2013) and Scerri and Scerri (2013), that education has a positive influence on students perceptions of caring for the older adult. Nonetheless, it must be acknowledged though that in this study, the positive impact of education was most significant at the beginning of the undergraduate programme and not nearer the end. This impact of timing of educational intervention is notable and will be further discussed when considering recommendations for practice.

Moving on from motivation and satisfaction and the positive influence of education on these variables, the next aspect of student perception explored was Role Security.

8.1.1: Role Security

Role Security was measured by the DDCPQ by scoring the students perceptions of Role Adequacy and Role Legitimacy. Baseline scores for Role Adequacy and Role Legitimacy were taken at course commencement (T1) and throughout the course (T2 and T3), as well as at the end of the undergraduate programme when ready for registration (T4).

Similar to Therapeutic Commitment, mean scores for Role Adequacy reduced significantly over the duration of the undergraduate programme. From T1 to T2 ($p=0.000$; 25% reduction), T2 to T3 ($p=0.000$; 24% reduction) and T3 to T4 ($p=0.000$; 13% reduction), resulting in a 51% reduction in total Role Adequacy scores between T1 and T4. This pattern was also repeated in scores of Role Legitimacy, with significantly reduced scores from T1 to T2 ($p=0.001$; 24% reduction), T2 to T3 ($p=0.000$; 16% reduction) and T3-T4 ($p=0.000$; 6%) respectively, with a 40% overall Role Legitimacy score reduction between T1 and T4. Therefore, as the students progressed throughout their undergraduate nursing programme, students felt less adequately prepared to deliver dementia care and less legitimately placed to deliver such care. Again, in direct

correspondence with therapeutic commitment, as the number of people with dementia that they cared for increased, the lower the feelings of Role Adequacy and Role Legitimacy were. Furthermore, being previously or currently employed in dementia care was also significantly associated with lower scores of adequacy and legitimacy at T1 (RA; $p=0.000$, RL; $p=0.000$) and T2 (RA; $p=0.000$, RL; $p=0.035$). Again, emphasising the impact of clinical care experiences in feelings of readiness for care delivery.

Indeed, in the focus groups, students purported such feelings of lack of readiness. Whilst at the beginning of the nursing programme, RA and RL scores were higher, students recognised that they didn't have the clinical knowledge and skills to deliver dementia care but perceived themselves to have the emotional skills such as patience and empathy. Undeniably, as time moved on, students recognised that they had learned new clinical skills and knowledge to help deliver dementia care but also acknowledged that they now realised the complexities of the reality of delivering such care, especially in acute care settings. This recognition of the impact of learning is evident in the positive relationship between education and feelings of RA ($p=0.000$) and RL ($p=0.000$), particularly at the beginning of the undergraduate programme (T1 and T2) where theory is more intensive. Certainly, the educational influence on perceptions of care delivery in elderly care is well documented (Scerri and Scerri, 2013, Baillie et al, 2015), however, the fact that the students found care delivery to be challenging and thus felt less adequately prepared as they progressed throughout their learning programme, has to be acknowledged.

Students resoundly reported the benefit of education, viewing it as complementary to the inherent qualities that they already perceived they had, such as empathy and patience. The students also spoke of their ability to apply theory to practice and as time went on they felt that they truly understood the unique and complex journey that each person with dementia experiences. Nonetheless, the students spoke emotively about being unable to always deliver person-centred care to people with dementia. This was in part recognised by the fact that, at the earlier stages of their nurse training, the students did not realise the complexities of caring for elderly people with multiple comorbidities, such as the multifaceted manifestations of dementia, in terms of both physical and emotional patient need. Indeed, such lack of recognition is acknowledged by Lovell (2006), who suggests that health professional's perceptions of elderly people and conditions associated with advancing age (such as dementia) are often not much different to that of the general public. Considering that most of the students commenced the

undergraduate nursing programme with no knowledge or experience, it is feasible that their perceptions would be no different to the general public and thus perhaps feelings of Role Adequacy and Role Legitimacy were not informed perceptions at course commencement (T1). When indeed, the students gained knowledge and experience, whilst they recognised that they had learned knowledge and had new skills to offer, they also realised the complexities of care planning and care management required by them and thus felt less prepared to deliver the reality of such complex nursing care.

The challenge of dealing with dementia that comes with complex physical and mental health needs was also evidenced by the fact that adult nursing students demonstrated higher scores for Role Adequacy and Role Legitimacy than their mental health colleagues. Certainly, it was evident from the DDCPQ that adult students had greater experience of delivering dementia care, however, the qualitative feedback from mental health students gave a greater insight into understanding this perceived difference in perception. The mental health students articulated their lack of experience of delivering care for the physical health needs of the patient with dementia, in particular, citing a lack of experience of caring for people with dementia towards the end of their dementia journey, when their care needs were more palliative and holistic in nature. This complexity of disease progression in dementia and complexity in care management of elderly patients, was recognised by the Care Inquiry Francis Report (Francis, 2013) who further called for specific elderly care training to meet these complex patient needs, such as evident in people living with dementia. Indeed, although many improvements have since been made, it is well recognised that care enhancement is an ongoing process and there is still a lot of support required to enable trained and untrained health professionals to deliver optimal dementia care in all clinical care environments (Scottish Government, 2013, Scottish Government, 2017).

8.1.2: Role Support

Role Support was measured by the DDCPQ by scoring the student's perceptions of their need for support and how readily available that support was. Baseline scores for Role Support were taken at course commencement (T1) and throughout the course (T2 and T3), as well as at the end of the undergraduate programme when ready for registration (T4).

Similar to Therapeutic Commitment and Role Security scores, mean scores for Role Support reduced significantly over the duration of the undergraduate programme. From T1 to T2 ($p=0.000$; 18% reduction), T2 to T3 ($p=0.000$; 17% reduction) and T3 to T4 ($p=0.000$; 2% reduction) respectively, resulting in a 34% reduction in Role Support scores from T1 to T4. In relevance to Role Support, this suggests that overall, students required less support as the nursing programme progressed and also students perceived that should support be required, they were able to get the necessary support from an available resource. This is reflective of the notion of students in their journey from novice to expert as discussed in Chapter Three (Benner, 1984) and indeed the changing requirement of supervision as the student becomes more experienced and thus requires less direct supervision (NMC, 2018c).

As would perhaps be expected, those students who had no experience of working in dementia care and had never been employed in dementia care had higher RS scores and perceived a significantly greater need for support, especially at the beginning of the nursing programme, when their clinical placement experience was more limited (T1; $p=0.000$, $p=0.000$, T2; $p=0.002$, $p=0.008$). Also, older students scored more highly and perceived that they needed a greater level of support, with advancing student age significantly impacting on increased support needs ($p=0.000$). Whether this relationship with age is due to an increased understanding of dementia due to life experience or indeed an incidental finding is unknown and indeed the limited literature available reports inconsistent findings when considering the variable of age and student nurse perceptions (Liu et al, 2013).

Furthermore, adult nursing students had significantly higher support scores than that of their mental health colleagues ($p=0.013$). Again, whilst adult students were more experienced in delivering dementia care and it might be assumed that support needs would thus be less, this is reflective of when and where adult students experienced dementia care. As discussed during focus groups, it was evident, that whilst mental health students were involved in post diagnostic dementia support and advance care planning at earlier stages of patient's dementia journey, adult students were delivering complex dementia care at the latter end of the dementia journey, at a stage where patients had complex physical and mental health needs. Thus, the desire for extra support in care delivery is clearly justifiable and again the impact of clinical experience on student perception is evident.

Lastly, in terms of Role Support, there was a significant association between supervision and support scores throughout the nursing programme (T1; $p=0.000$, T2; $p=0.001$, T3; $p=0.051$ and T4; $p=0.028$). This fits with the findings that students perceived a desirability for support and supervision at the beginning of the course when their experience was less, but also at the end of their course, when they were delivering more complex care and when expectations of their abilities in clinical practice were much greater (NMC, 2018b). Ridgeway et al (2018) acknowledges that clinical practice can influence such changeable perceptions in student nurse learners and notes that even more experienced learners often seek support. Certainly, as well as the influence of clinical experience on support requirements, perceived support needs also are influenced by attitudes and self-esteem (Liu et al, 2013).

8.2: Attitudes

Overall Attitude was measured by the DDCPQ by computing the student's scores for Task Specific Self-Esteem, Satisfaction in Working with Dementia, Motivation to Work with Dementia, Role Adequacy and Role Legitimacy. Baseline scores for Overall Attitude were taken at course commencement (T1) and throughout the course (T2 and T3), as well as at the end of the undergraduate programme when students were ready for registration (T4).

Mean scores for Overall Attitude increased throughout the undergraduate nursing programme, with significant increases between T1 - T2 ($p=0.000$), T2 - T3 ($p=0.000$) and T3 - T4 ($p=0.000$). Whilst the increased scores would seem to represent a more positive attitude as time progressed, for the DDCPQ (as per the original AAPPQ) (Cartwright, 1980b), the further the attitude scores deviate from 0, the less positive the attitude score. However, as discussed in Chapter Six, although the scores increased and thus attitudes were less positive, the scores remained between 0 and 1, indicating overall positive attitudes towards dementia and the likelihood of success working in dementia care should the students choose to pursue careers in this area.

Interestingly, when considering the specifics regarding influences towards attitude, once more the impact of clinical environments were evident. As the number of patients with dementia

cared for increased, attitudinal scores were significantly reduced at T1 ($p=0.000$), T2 ($p=0.000$) and T3 ($p=0.000$). Moreover, being previously employed in dementia care reduced attitude scores significantly at T1 ($p=0.000$) and T2 ($p=0.002$) and being currently employed in dementia care also significantly reduced scores at T1 ($p=0.000$) and T2 ($p=0.004$). These findings are similar to the Role Support findings and illustrate the impact of clinical care experiences, especially for the more inexperienced student, nearer the beginning of the undergraduate programme. Such negatively impacting clinical experiences are discussed by Brown et al (2008), who purport that during placements and also during paid, untrained healthcare assistant roles, student nurses are exposed to non-ideal or 'impoverished' environments of elderly care, where care standards can be low due to seemingly unsurmountable challenges to care provision such as lack of staff, lack of knowledge and inappropriate care environments. Conversely, Brown et al (2008) suggests that students need to be embraced in an 'enriched' care environment, which is a care environment where students feel belonging, purposeful and valued, with opportunity to meet personal goals in a safe learning environment.

Indeed, further considering such learning, from a positive perspective, education had again, a significant association with having a more positive attitude. Yet again, this was particularly at early stages of the undergraduate programme; T1 ($p=0.000$) and T2 ($p=0.007$). Thus, further demonstrating the impact of learning but also once more illustrating that the timing of any educational intervention must be carefully considered for the learning experience to be meaningful. This will be further discussed when considering implications for practice.

Lastly, looking at the latter end of the undergraduate programme, at T4, there was a significant relationship between course and attitude ($p=0.025$), with adult students scoring more positively than their mental health colleagues. This is in contrast to findings at the start of the nursing programme (the more patients cared for, the lower the attitude scores) as indeed adult students had all cared for many more people with dementia than mental health students by T4. However, this significant distinction between the nursing fields, reflects the basic physicality of patient need when adult students care for people with dementia nearer the end of the dementia journey. Adult students recognised that small care interventions as simple as the use of touch can make a great difference to the patient experience. Undeniably, this effect of the clinical environment and the fundamental needs of the person with more advanced dementia was apparent in the student's focus group assertions. Students spoke emotively of challenging

attitudes and behaviours of clinical staff and at times the feelings of helplessness that they perceived in terms of inciting positive behaviour change to deliver a high standard of dementia care. However, when it came to their own personal care delivery, there was (particularly towards the latter data collections and specifically from adult students), a real sense of pride at making a difference to the patients in their care. Students spoke of taking the time to provide holistic, person-centred care and a real desire to provide the best care possible, even with limited resources and funding, and within (at times) challenging environments. This positivity and importance of putting the patient first at all times was demonstrated when the students considered their ultimate goals for dementia care. From T1 course inception through to T4 course completion, every student, in every focus group, came to the consensus that their patient's needs and a positive care experience for the patient and their family were the most ultimate priority and goal. Such aspirational thinking and positive student ethos as found in this study is not always demonstrated in the literature though (Lambinov, 2009, Stevens, 2011, Liu et al, 2013).

Although some studies such as that carried out by Ridgeway et al (2018) indicated an increase in positive attitudes towards the elderly as nursing courses progress, other studies have demonstrated reduction in attitude scores over time (Lambinov, 2009) and most have demonstrated inconsistent findings (Stevens, 2011, Liu et al, 2013). It must be recognised though that these studies were only in relation to elderly care and not specifically dementia and indeed it is recognised that there are very few studies examining students exclusively and in particular, a lack of longitudinal studies (Liu et al, 2013, Ridgeway et al, 2018). Hence, the originality of this study which will be further discussed in the next chapter.

8.3: Summary

In summary, using a layering approach, this chapter has triangulated the data to integrate the findings and provide meaningful context to quantitative scores and qualitative statements.

Student's scores for the Therapeutic Commitment components of Task Specific Self Esteem, Satisfaction Working with Dementia and Motivation to Work with Dementia were critiqued and

triangulated with their qualitative perceptions of Therapeutic Commitment and the changes in these perceptions over time.

Thereafter, Role Security was critiqued and the underpinning concepts of Role Adequacy and Role Legitimacy considered in relation to student self-scoring and perceptive feelings of adequacy and legitimacy. These scores were directly related to the feelings of Role Support required and the changes in student self-perceived support requirements over time.

Lastly, the students Overall Attitude scores were assessed and contextually related to the students nursing care aspirations.

The following last and final chapter of this thesis will aggregate these study findings and evidence achievement of the overall research aims.

Chapter Nine: Discussion, Recommendations and Overall Conclusions

The purpose of a doctoral research study is to fulfil the research aims through a thorough, in-depth investigation, demonstrating transparency of evidence-based decision making to result in an original, credible, reliable and valid thesis (Thomas, 2009, Murray, 2011, Bryman, 2016). To continue the trajectory of such transparency as has been demonstrated throughout this thesis, and to demonstrate originality of knowledge contribution, it is essential to revisit the study research aims;

- To explore undergraduate student nurse perceptions of dementia care and their role in care delivery.
- To examine the influence of theory, skills training and clinical experience on approach to dementia care delivery amongst undergraduate student nurses.
- To appraise how dementia training policy directives for pre-registration nurse education are reflected in undergraduate student nurse's knowledge, skills and readiness for nursing practice.
- To evaluate the psychometric properties of a self-efficacy tool designed to measure attitudes, experiences and perceptions of dementia care in undergraduate student nurses.

To demonstrate achievement of these research aims, this final chapter will justify the background for the research study, aggregate the study results and set the results in context of the implications for nursing practice and the implications for dementia policy and practice. Furthermore, study limitations will be acknowledged and recommendations for practice suggested. Lastly, conclusions will be drawn, reaffirming the originality of this thesis and its contribution to both nursing practice and nurse education.

9.0: Justification for Research Study

The research aims were generated after an in-depth literature review in Chapter Three. It was recognised that like registered nurses, student nurses care for people with dementia in a variety of care settings and are likely to care for many more people with dementia as projected prevalence increases (WHO, 2015, Scottish Government, 2017). There is a plethora of research examining dementia care from nursing and social care perspectives but a dearth of research examining ability to deliver dementia care exclusively from the student nurse perspective (Suhonen, Gustafsson, Katajiso et al, 2010, Clissett et al, 2013). Thus, there was a need to explore student nurses perceptions of delivering dementia care, their role in care giving and importantly, their ability to deliver such care, as soon to be accountable, autonomous practitioners (Koh, 2012, Spector et al, 2012, Koskinen, Hupli, Katajisto et al, 2015). Nurses must determine themselves competent and up to date in both knowledge and skills when seeking initial nurse registration and also when renewing their annual registration (Spector et al (2012), Eccleston et al, 2015, Nursing and Midwifery Council, 2015). Therefore, nurse educators must ensure that nursing students' learning needs are being met to enable students to be ready to deliver safe, effective care to people with dementia (Alushi et al, 2015, Eccleston et al, 2015). To examine such perceptions of ability, this study used the concept of Self-Efficacy, underpinned by Social Learning Theory and took the original approach to explore such perceptions using a prospective, longitudinal mixed methods case study.

The dearth of similar studies has been acknowledged, and, to date, this research study is original in that, no other studies examining perceptions (not just attitudinal) towards dementia care in a longitudinal mixed method case study context have been carried out, exclusively with student nurses. In this study, undergraduate student nurses perceptions of dementia care and their role in care delivery has been explored and the influence of theory, skills training and clinical experience on approach to care delivery examined. Insight into these student perceptions and gaining an understanding of the influence of learning in both theory and practice, helps to inform workforce planning and indeed assist in the guidance of curricular content to ensure that student nurses are ready for professional registration and their role as a staff nurse (Liu et al, 2013, Ridgeway, 2018).

9.1: Insight Gained: Aggregation of Study Findings

Student's perceptions of dementia and their role in dementia care delivery were measured using the newly validated Dementia and Dementia Care Perceptions Questionnaire (DDCPQ). Using the concept of self-efficacy (perception of own ability of knowledge and skills) the DDCPQ sought to measure nursing student's self-perceived "Therapeutic Commitment" by establishing scores for Task Specific Self Esteem, Satisfaction Working with Dementia and Motivation to Work with Dementia. Furthermore, the DDCPQ measured "Role Security" through Role Adequacy (having the adequate knowledge and skills to care for people with dementia) and Role Legitimacy (being appropriately placed to deliver this care). Students were also scored on their perceived need for "Role Support" (the support required to deliver dementia care). These combined scores resulted in an "Overall Attitude" Score and the themes reflected the adapted questions from the original Alcohol and Alcohol Problems Perceptions Questionnaire AAPPQ (Shaw et al, 1978, Cartwright, 1980b, Gorman and Cartwright 1991, Cartwright and Gorman, 1993) from which the DDCPQ originated. These scores were then triangulated with the qualitative data generated from the focus groups to give context and deeper meaning to understand the student's perceptions and the changes in these perceptions over time.

At course commencement, the majority of the (n=420) students in the study were novices with no experience of dementia care (n=295). Most had never received any form of dementia education (n=199) and this was consistent across all student groups, from all three campuses. The qualitative data from the focus groups supported this lack of experience, with students articulating feelings of insecurity and uncertainty at their lack of knowledge and experience. However, whilst students recognised their limited knowledge and skill set, the students verbalised their perceived inherent qualities such as empathy and patience which they deemed as fundamental for dementia care delivery. Indeed, these inherent qualities were reflected in the scores of the DDCPQ at Time 1 (T1; course commencement). Despite lacking knowledge and experience, students scored positively in Role Adequacy and Role Legitimacy. The students did recognise their need for Role Support in their novice status but felt that they could deliver a good standard of dementia care without anything other than inherent personal qualities and attributes. Furthermore, the novice students perceived high levels of Satisfaction Working with Dementia and were highly Motivated to Work with Dementia, demonstrating positive Overall Attitude scores.

However, over time these scores changed. As the students moved through their undergraduate programme, scores for Therapeutic Commitment reduced (Task Specific Self Esteem; 27% reduction, Satisfaction; 10% reduction and Motivation; 16% reduction overall). Moreover, scores for Role Security reduced as well (Role Adequacy; 51% reduction and Role Legitimacy; 40% reduction overall). Initially these quantitative scores seemed alarming, essentially highlighting that the more learning and experience gained by the students, the less prepared they felt they were for delivering dementia care. Moreover, the more experience that they gained, the less motivated they were to work in dementia care and the less satisfaction they perceived from delivering said care. Thus, it was essential to triangulate these scores with the qualitative transcriptions to help understand this reduction in feelings of self-esteem, adequacy, legitimacy, motivation and satisfaction.

In the focus groups, students vocalised their experiences of challenging practical environments, whereby, not only were the physical environments challenging (particularly in acute care) but indeed lack of resources, staff and time, made dementia care delivery extremely difficult. Additionally, negative staff attitudes were overwhelmingly noted on all campuses, by all student groups to be detrimental to both student's motivation and ability to influence care delivery. The influence of the practical learning environment was greater than anticipated and certainly had more impact than the University learning environment, as placement hours increased over the duration of the undergraduate programme. Indeed, students spoke of feeling disempowered to make positive changes and unable at their novice stage, to share learning and good practice (despite the students perceiving themselves as more knowledgeable in dementia than some qualified staff).

In terms of learning, whilst scores reduced as learning increased, this was not due to the quality or the content of the theoretical learning. Interestingly, educational input and learning had a significantly positive influence on scores of self-esteem, satisfaction, motivation, adequacy and legitimacy, particularly nearer the beginning of the student's nursing journey. Furthermore, students perceived themselves to have gained a great deal of knowledge, skills and care delivery strategies by the end of their undergraduate programme. However, scores reduced rather than increased in correspondence to the increased learning. Due to the understanding gained from the qualitative data, it was apparent that this was in fact due to unrealistic expectations at course commencement. The novice student nurses recognised themselves to have inherent

qualities, helpful in dementia care delivery such as patience and empathy, however, the students initially perceived this to be enough to be able to deliver a good standard of dementia care. Indeed, once they had learned more about the nuances of the dementia journey and once they understood how complex the person with dementia's needs were and how challenging it was to deliver such complex care, the students perceived themselves as less able than previously recognised. Therefore, it wasn't that they had not learned or that the education offered was not enough, it was the fact that they did not initially have any understanding of the complexities of delivering holistic dementia care. This reflects the students' lack of education and experience at course commencement.

Indeed, although the students felt less adequately prepared to deliver dementia care, as their learning and experience increased, their scores for role support reduced, meaning that they perceived themselves to require less support, as they progressed through their undergraduate programme. This may seem conflicting with reduced feelings of role adequacy and legitimacy but it is reflective of the student's ability to work increasingly independently. Students articulated that whilst they felt it was at times difficult to fully meet the care needs of the person with dementia, they did not feel that anyone else could have done any better.

This positivity and self-belief is reflected again in the students Overall Attitude scores. Although attitudes were less positive as students progressed through their nursing journey, this was due to the challenges of dementia care delivery and indeed the majority of students remained positive in attitude score overall, with every single student, on every campus agreeing that the patient and their family were at the heart of everything they did as a student nurse.

These insightful findings, found through the concept of self-efficacy (asking the students their own perceptions of their knowledge and skill) have implications for both nursing education and dementia policy and practice.

9.2: Implications for Nursing Education

An explicit aim of this research study was directly related to the impact of policy and professional regulation on nursing education, namely seeking; To explore how dementia training policy directives for pre-registration nurse education is reflected in undergraduate student nurse's knowledge, skills and readiness for nursing practice. Although knowledge, skill acquisition and readiness for practice is assessable and demonstrable through the student nurses learning achievements in both University and in clinical practice, it is acknowledged that self-efficacy can be a more effective method to ascertain a person's perceptions of their own ability to attain, deliver or succeed (Zimmerman, 2000, Bandura, 1997a, Bandura, 1997b, Hayden, 2014). Certainly, nursing has long been associated with the concept of self-efficacy, in that nursing is a self-regulating profession in many ways.

9.2.1 Self-Regulation through Self-Efficacy

As a nurse, the ability to evaluate one's knowledge and skill base is an essential aspect of professional self-regulation and patient safety protocol. Recognition of areas of personal developmental requirement and limitations of personal and professional knowledge and skills are key elements of self-regulation in nursing (Boud, 2007, NMC, 2010b, NMC, 2015c, NMC, 2015d). In reality, nurses and student nurses must affirm both their good health and good character, on a yearly basis, confirming that they are fit for their practice and verifying that their mandatory knowledge and skills base is up to date and research based to fulfil patient need within their field of practice.

For registered nurses, this self-regulation occurs at the point of registration (NMC, 2010c, QAA, 2011) and thereafter throughout their career to meet the requisite revalidation criteria as set by the Nursing and Midwifery Council (NMC, 2017). Furthermore, nurses are often asked to use aspects of self-efficacy as part of clinical supervision and for evidencing knowledge and skills framework indicators at personal development reviews.

However, for student nurses, self-regulation is not as often utilised. Although the students should consider learning needs and abilities as well as knowledge limitations as part of personal reflection, this is often in an informal manner, such as in a reflective diary (Lew, Alwis and Schmidt, 2010, Adamson and Dewar, 2015). Student nurses can also sometimes be asked to self-assess or peer review their fellow students as part of skills sessions in University but again, these are always for informal, formative feedback. However, self-assessment through self-efficacy is an essential element of quality assurance in healthcare (NMC, 2010c) and thus using self-efficacy as a measure of knowledge change or skill acquisition in an undergraduate nursing programme demonstrates concordance with professional practice and has been exemplified in a few studies relating to elderly care (O'Connor and McFadden, 2010, Baillie et al, 2015, Ridgeway et al, 2018).

Indeed, a systematic literature review by Evripidou, Charalambous, Middleton et al (2018) critiqued (n=16) studies and found that nurses lack knowledge and confidence in dementia care but that improvement was noted after educational intervention, findings similar to other studies who also measure pre and post educational interventional improvement (Annear et al, 2016). However, these studies are not specific to dementia care from a student nurse perspective, thus again demonstrating the originality of this research study that seeks to measure change in perspectives over the duration of a full undergraduate nursing degree. Such measure of change and capture of perceptions of ability have positive implications for the student nurse's accountability for their own learning and professional development. Indeed, nursing students, whilst not fully accountable to the Nursing and Midwifery Council, must still uphold the standards of quality assurance and professionalism as would be expected of a registered nurse (Liu et al, 2013, NMC, 2015a).

9.2.2 Professional Regulation and Standards

The Nursing and Midwifery Council as the regulatory body for all registered nurses, midwives and nursing associates has a duty to ensure that the workforce are bound by professional standards. These professional standards are open to the public and ascertain what the public should expect from the healthcare professional caring for them and also set a precedence for the standard of professionalism expected of every registrant nurse, midwife and nursing associate (NMC, 2018a, NMC, 2018e, NMC, 2018f). The professional regulatory standards most

relevant to pre-registration nursing education will be critiqued and related to achievement of aim 3 of the research study as the professional regulations in nursing are highly reflected in all aspects of nurse education and preparation for clinical practice.

The Standards of Competence for Registered Nurses (NMC, 2010) set out a criteria to ensure public protection and safeguarding through the publication of set standards of nursing practice namely addressing; responsibility, accountability, self-awareness, teamwork, knowledge and dealing with complex patient care needs. Indeed, these standards as well as the Standards to Support Learning and Assessment in Practice (NMC, 2008), the Standards for Pre-Registration Nursing Education (NMC, 2010a) and the Standards for Competence for Registered Nurses (NMC, 2010b) were critiqued in Chapter Three as at the time of writing the literature review, these were the NMC standards in use. However, the NMC published new standards in 2018, therefore, throughout 2019 and beyond, these new standards are in the process of being gradually implemented by educational providers of nursing education as existing pre-registration nursing programmes are updated and revalidated to reflect the new standard frameworks.

Although the revalidated standards and Code of Conduct have been reviewed to reflect current contemporary healthcare and new roles within healthcare such as the nursing associate, the ethos of the underpinning concepts of excellence in patient care being delivered by a highly professional workforce remain fundamentally unchanged (NMC, 2018a, NMC 2018b, NMC 2018c, NMC, 2018d, NMC, 2018e, NMC, 2018f).

Part 1 of the Standards is concerned with nursing and midwifery education. The Standards Framework for Nursing and Midwifery Education (NMC, 2018b) is still in continued adherence with the Nursing and Midwifery Order 2001 (NMC, 2010a, 2015a) but has been updated to provide guidance in the contemporary nursing education context. Focusing on five particular areas of importance, the new framework sets expectational guidance. Focus one centres upon the learning environment, expecting all clinical areas to be safe and effective with a culture of student support through reflective learning. When considering the importance of this first area of the standard for education, certainly the importance of both the University and clinical learning environments were inherently obvious when considering part one of the policy's

relevance to this research study. From the DDCPQ, the positive influence of learning and an environment conducive to learning was apparent in the significant relationship between learning and perceptions of ability, particularly nearer the beginning of the undergraduate nursing programme. Furthermore, the influence of the clinical learning environment was inherent throughout all focus group transcriptions. There was no doubt that students recognised the importance of experiential learning and recognised that they could transfer theory to practice, however, the implications of a non-ideal learning environment were also apparent.

The second component of the Standards Framework for Nursing and Midwifery Education (NMC, 2018b) focused upon governance and quality, namely aspiring for clinical partners to have an equal role in theory and practical assessment which echoes the ethos of the previous standards. Nonetheless, there is a key message from the new standards regarding recognition of areas where improvement is required. Such recognition mirrors the fundamentals of self-efficacy as apparent throughout this study. Recognition of areas of requirement for self-improvement is inherently related to improving the quality of care overall in nursing (NMC, 2018b).

Indeed, recognition and reflection on areas for improvement inspires student empowerment, which is the third focus of the educational framework. Students are expected to have resilience skills and to be self-empowered to learn in a reflective manner and embrace constructive feedback to facilitate a cycle of self-improvement. The recognition of continual self-improvement and lifelong learning in nursing was acknowledged by many students in the study and the introduction of revalidation requirements cited in support of ongoing engagement in learning. However, as claimed by the students and indeed reflected in the standards, educators and practice assessors are intrinsically connected to the learning journey.

This in-depth connection is acknowledged in focus four of the standards framework which clearly denotes the influence of others in the learning experience, drawing parallels with this study's underpinning philosophy of social learning theory and reciprocal determinism (Bandura, 1997a, Bandura, 1997b, Hayden, 2014). Aspiring for positive connotations of what would be representative of reciprocal determinism, the new standards specifically recognise the need and benefit of role modelling in clinical practice. Again, in direct correlation with this suggestion, the

student nurses actively cited their need for role-modelling, but were also acutely aware of the importance of the qualities of a role model, and not just paying lip service to the title of role model.

Lastly in terms of the educational standards, was the relevance of the curriculum. All nursing curricula should be reflective of contemporary health care and current health priority areas. As previously cited in Chapter Three, not all nursing undergraduate curricula have been cognisant of the growing complexity of elderly care and in particular the burgeoning dementia statistics (Alushi et al, 2015, Collier et al, 2015, Eccleston et al, 2015). However, at the University of the West of Scotland (as detailed in Chapter Three), dementia education was included within every year of the nursing curriculum, increasing in complexity as the student became more experienced. As previously stated in Chapter Six, this positive relationship with education was reflected in the student nurses' assertions, particularly at data collections towards the beginning of this study. However, an important consideration was also apparent from the student's feedback in Chapter Seven; there was a distinct incongruence between the student nurses' level of dementia knowledge and skill and that of many registered nurses (particularly those who had trained some time ago). Indeed, it must then be considered that whilst reflecting current healthcare trends in an undergraduate nursing curriculum is advised, when these health trends then change, nurses already qualified and working in practice may not be equipped to deal with the newly evolved trends in healthcare and thus change in patient need. Therefore, the importance of ongoing learning in nursing is even more apparent and indeed, this ongoing learning from nurses in practice should be reflected when assessing students in clinical practice.

Part 2 of the new standards reflect the expected situation in clinical practice. Part 2: Standards for Student Supervision and Assessment is made up of 3 component parts (NMC, 2018c). Component one relates to the student learning journey, aspiring that students are in charge of their own learning and are empowered to embrace learning that is effectively tailored to their own specific level of need. Like part one of the standards, this notion of empowerment and taking charge of one's own learning goals requires a level of self-awareness such as is required in self-efficacy (Bandura, 1997b). Thus, the more that students are exposed to self-efficacy and its expectant perceptual awareness, then the more empowered the students are to take charge of their learning needs as required by the standards.

Interestingly, the second component part of the student supervision standards is concerned with effective role modelling and leading by example. The standard specifically asserts that supervisors must be knowledgeable and experienced in the area that they are supporting the student in. Furthermore, component part 3 additionally states that supervisors must maintain this knowledge and experience to be able to effectively support learning in practice through evidence-based assessment. Findings of this research study suggest that for some mentors or practice assessors this may be problematic as whilst many are very experienced practitioners, the currency of an up to date evidence-base to base that practice upon, is not always evident. Notably, some students even suggested that a refresher programme using simulation and role play techniques such as was used with the students as part of their undergraduate skills classes would prove insightful. Furthermore, it was suggested that there was a lack of awareness that practice could be improved, in other words, the practitioners didn't know what they didn't know, they did not realise what they were missing educationally and thus, again, the importance of ongoing education is undeniable.

Such ethos of ongoing learning is inherent in all undergraduate, pre-registration nursing courses. Part 3; Standards for Pre-registration Nursing Programmes (NMC, 2018d) asserts that on course commencement, individuals should have character values reflective of the attributes as defined in The Code (NMC, 2018f). However, new students do not need to have any prerequisite nursing skills or knowledge as achievement of the requisite knowledge and skill for nursing registration will be taught throughout the course and beyond. Whilst certain professional competencies and proficiencies are inherent throughout all pre-registration nursing courses, higher education providers have the flexibility to design curricula innovatively and uniquely to meet such requirements. Thus, despite the need for curriculums to reflect current healthcare priorities there can be quite differing levels of focus on priority areas and certainly dementia care is recognised as lacking in some undergraduate nursing courses, where the focus is often on acute conditions (Alushi et al, 2015, Eccleston et al, 2015). Nonetheless, higher education providers of nursing are essentially all professionally required to ensure that student nurses are fit for practice and purpose at the point of registration.

This fitness for purpose and practice is demonstrable by considering the standards of practice that are set for registered nurses. The updated expected role specific standards for registered nurses are detailed by the Standards of Proficiency for Registered Nurses (NMC, 2018a). The

constructs of nurses accountability as autonomous care providing practitioners remains unchanged from the previous standards, however, the notion of nurses being more equitable to other healthcare professionals and indeed having their own personal resilience to deal with the complexity of modern healthcare is now overtly mentioned, as well as having the requisite skills and knowledge to care for those living with dementia. Specifically, the standards of proficiency focus around the seven 'platforms' of; accountability, health promotion and prevention, care planning, care evaluation, leadership and teamwork, safety and coordination of care.

The first platform concept of accountability has always been inherent in nursing standards and nurses are also bound by the professional duty of candour (NMC, 2018a), thus having to take accountability even when things go wrong. However, the notion that nurses are also accountable for their own physical and mental health and wellbeing to enable them to be fit enough to care for others is now recognised. This platform emphasises the need for nurses to be self-aware and indeed fits with this study's underpinning concept of self-efficacy. Having a perceptive awareness of one's own fundamental skills (even emotional skills) are essential to meet this component of proficiency.

Secondly, in terms of the health and ill health continuum in platform two, the new standards recognise the changing demographics of health and this is also reflected in platform three where a distinct mention of patient's complex needs are addressed, including older people living longer with multiple comorbidities and dementia in itself being mentioned as a common condition experienced when caring for elderly patients. Students taking part in this study recognised such changing demographics when acknowledging the complexity of care needs of the person living with dementia and the multifaceted presentations of dementia care needs, amongst other comorbidities.

Platform four of the standards keeps the concept of care evaluation, with patients and families as partners in care decision making but also focuses not just on physical care but also mental and emotional care, even for adult field nurses. Specifically, people with confusion are mentioned and the need for proactively responding to patient need, working as a 'role model' for other healthcare professionals. This need for role modelling was articulated by the students

in the focus groups and suggested as a way to inspire others to provide excellent, holistic and person-centred dementia care.

Providing person centred care requires working with other professionals as part of a team and is essential when considering changing roles and role boundaries, as apparent in platform five of the standards. This teamwork and the challenges of working as part of a multidisciplinary team with at times conflicting demands was recognised as part of this research study and indeed students suggested the need for a joint approach to learning to ensure parity of principles and greater respect for the roles and responsibilities of other healthcare professionals. Furthermore, the ability to be motivational in care delivery is also aspired to, which also draws parallels with the findings from this study. Students recognised the need to stay motivated in dementia care for the patients benefit but also accepted the challenges to motivation when resources such as staffing are scarce and care environments are not ideally suited to care need.

Indeed, unsuitable environments were recognised to be a challenge to patient safety and lead onto platform six which focuses on patient safety. Similar to the safety ethos of the previous standards, patient safety is paramount but again the notion of personal safety through resilience is much more apparent. Such resilience in the face of adversity was very apparent again in this study. Students recognised that there were many challenges in the clinical environment, specifically attitudinal challenges from other staff. However, the students remained resolutely resilient and this was exemplified by their prioritisation of the patient and their family from the beginning of their nursing programme, right up until the end and point of registration.

Lastly, coordination of care and the implications of changing ways of working to provide complex care is recognised in platform seven of the standards. In relevance to this study, the students recognised the limitations of their own role boundaries and also the potentially positive influence of health and social care integration. Nevertheless, they also recognised the complexity of care delivery when professional role boundaries were uncertain in times of change. In terms of dementia care, when complexity of care is commonplace and patient care need demands input from differing healthcare professionals at one time, dementia policy and research can be useful to direct care decisions.

9.3: Implications for Dementia Policy and Practice

As an international public health priority (WHO, 2012, WHO, 2015), the amount of dementia policy and dementia research has increased greatly over recent years. The influence of dementia policy directives and findings from dementia research is apparent not only in healthcare but also in the public domain as the drive to increase awareness is ongoing. Indeed, the increasing global prevalence of dementia is highly visible when considering the ageing population. The World Health Organisation (WHO, 2017) advise that in 2015, 47 million people were living with dementia worldwide, with figures anticipated to increase to 75 million by 2030 and 132 million by 2050 respectively.

The Department of Health first published the Prime Minister's challenge on dementia in 2012 (Department of Health, 2012) aspiring for early diagnosis and high quality of care and support for those living with dementia and their families. The updated 2020 challenge acknowledges the improvements made but also acknowledges the need for further progress. Indeed, the refreshed edition of the Making a Difference in Dementia; Nursing Vision and Strategy (Department of Health, 2016) calls for the need for dementia care to be meaningfully delivered by responsive and knowledgeable nursing staff and cites the tiered training required for those professionally caring for people living with dementia.

Certainly nationally, dementia care has long since been policy driven. The first Dementia Strategy (Scottish Government, 2010) cited dementia as a national public health area of priority and devised a post diagnostic support plan to tackle recognised challenges in dementia practice. The initial strategy also pledged to improve dementia care by directly calling for improvement in caring and nursing staffs' knowledge and skills. Thus, the Standards of Care for Dementia in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2011a) were published as well as Promoting Excellence: A Framework for all Health and Social Services Staff Working with People with Dementia, their Families and Carers (Scottish Government, 2011b). The Standards of Care set a precedence for access to diagnosis, treatment and care whilst maintaining dignity, respect and independence for the person with dementia. As discussed in Chapter Three, the Promoting Excellence Framework set standards of expected education for all those working with dementia (informed,

skilled, enhanced and expert). It pledged that every single member of staff working in health and social care should at least be at the informed level of the framework.

Revising the progress of the Standards of Care for Dementia in Scotland as well as Promoting Excellence (Scottish Government, 2011a, Scottish Government, 2011b), the second Dementia Strategy (Scottish Government, 2013) recognised the improvements in diagnostic rates and the commitment of staff to improve knowledge and skills. Nonetheless, it was acknowledged that further improvement was still very much required. The second strategy thus made a commitment to at least one year post diagnostic support for all those diagnosed with dementia and also sought to improve acute care in particular, introducing dementia nurse consultants across all health boards to lead and incite positive change. Furthermore, a commitment to integrated care through the 8 pillars (see Chapter Three) was also instigated. Such commitment to integrated care was still recognised by the third and most recent Dementia Strategy (Scottish Government, 2017) and whilst the improvements and achievements of previous strategies were acknowledged, the recognition of the need for further improvement was still apparent. These improvements were particularly sought in care integration, post diagnostic support and at the palliative and end of life stage of the dementia journey.

The ongoing complexities of providing care, especially in acute settings is recognised by Transforming Specialist Dementia Hospital Care (Alzheimer Scotland, 2018). The report acknowledges that even with policy and care guidelines, staff still require support for continual learning and development opportunities. The report is very much cogniscent of progress made to date but still asserts that optimal care remains lacking in many areas. This view is concurred by the Leadership and Innovation in Hospital Care: Alzheimer Scotland Dementia Nurse Consultants Report 2015-2020 (Alzheimer Scotland, 2019). It purports that previous nurse education, training and workforce planning did not anticipate the changing demographics resulting in the majority of patients requiring nursing care being over 65 with multiple comorbidities including dementia. The report acknowledges the progress made to date in 'shifting the paradigm' of knowledge, skills and attitudes (Alzheimer Scotland, 2019, p10) but also recognises the need to have the right workforce of motivated nurses and other healthcare professionals working collaboratively and willingly, whilst engaged in a positive career trajectory of caring for older adults.

Certainly, the results of this research study confirm the demographic breakdown of most patients being older adults with multiple needs. All students, in all areas, from all fields of nursing had cared for people with dementia in a variety of care settings. There was some recognition of a paradigm shift and the positive impact noted of dementia nurse consultants and dementia champions (as discussed in Chapter Seven). However, the benefit of learning and the utmost need for ongoing learning, development and research was overwhelmingly apparent from both the DDCPQ and the student focus group feedback.

The impact of Nursing and Midwifery Council professional standards (NMC, 2018a) and upholding of The Code (NMC, 2018f) was very clear in the student nurses assertions when they discussed their person-centred care delivery. Their self reported components of professionalism, respect for patients and desire to provide optimal care to patients and their families reflected their own core values and that of the nursing profession. Dementia policy directives and research informed the students' dementia care delivery and students demonstrated awareness of patients' rights, required standards of care and evidence-based care delivery. The students were well aware of the multifaceted care needs of the person living with dementia and developed their own way of providing effective care by converting theory to practice, thus perceiving themselves to demonstrate a higher standard of nursing knowledge and skill in dementia care than their experienced colleagues in practice. Whilst the students recognised the challenges of delivering complex care, their attitudes remained positive and thus through their own self efficacy, reflected a readiness for successful dementia care practice.

These self-perceptions evident from the aggregated data as well as the important implications the study has for both nurse education and dementia policy and practice help demonstrate the achievement of the overall research aims.

9.4: Achievement of Research Aims

At this point in the thesis, it is useful to return to all of the research study's aims to confirm their achievement;

- To explore undergraduate student nurse perceptions of dementia care and their role in care delivery **(Achieved)**
- To examine the influence of theory, skills training and clinical experience on approach to dementia care delivery amongst undergraduate student nurses **(Achieved)**
- To appraise how dementia training policy directives for pre-registration nurse education are reflected in undergraduate student nurse's knowledge, skills and readiness for nursing practice **(Achieved)**
- To evaluate the psychometric properties of a self-efficacy tool designed to measure attitudes, experiences and perceptions of dementia care in undergraduate student nurses **(Achieved)**

Now that the research aims have been proven to be achieved through this unique, mixed methods, prospective, longitudinal case study, it is essential to recognise the limitations of the research study and recommendations arising from the study findings.

9.5: Limitations and Recommendations

As purported by Murray (2011), all research has limitations in terms of funding, time, availability of results or sometimes due to constraints of research design. These limitations must be acknowledged to demonstrate researcher awareness and an open and honest thesis.

9.5.1: Study Limitations

According to Walshaw (2012) research limitations are related to the sample, methodology, generalisability, reliability and validity and application to practice. These areas of potential limitation were therefore critiqued and applied to this research study;

- Sample size and attrition

The total population of students commencing the BSc Adult/Mental Health Nursing programme at UWS in September 2014 at Paisley, Ayr and Dumfries campuses were invited to take part in the research study (n=455). Hamilton campus students were not invited to take part in the research as Hamilton was the base campus of the researcher (as BSc programme lecturer) and thus many students had already met the researcher during the application and interview process. It was decided that to avoid any conflict of interest and role confusion and also to enable students to share perceptions freely during the research process, it was best to exclude Hamilton based students (n=182). Whilst this could be recognised as a limitation of the study as a whole campus was excluded, the overall participants (n=455) at initial data collection (T1) represented 71% of the total BSc Adult/Mental Health Nursing population at UWS (n=637). Furthermore, whilst Hamilton base campus had students attend the campus for theory, the students were based across Scotland for placement location as per the other campuses and thus did not represent any distinct demographics that would not be captured in the data from the other campuses. The included sample was therefore representative of the population as a whole. Furthermore, in terms of sample attrition (as common in longitudinal research studies), this was not an issue, with excellent response rates across the duration of the study; 92% T1, 83% T2, 89% T3 and 81% T4.

- Self-Selection of Research Participants

Although the total population of September 2014 nursing students on three campuses were invited to take part in the study, it is important to note that the students were asked to self-select to take part. According to Grix (2010) self-selection of research participants can result in self-selection bias, a view concurred by Bryman (2016). For example, only those who want to share good practice or who have experiences (either good or bad) may want to share them. Self-selection bias cannot be overcome but can

be reduced. For this study, those who self-selected to take part in the focus groups were then randomly selected to take part by the researcher, which reduces opportunity for bias. Furthermore, self-selection, can also result in non-response bias. Similar to previous, those who have had a bad experience or indeed no experience may choose not to participate. This study had extremely healthy response rates, especially for a longitudinal study, thus non-response bias was also limited.

- Methodology

This study was a prospective, longitudinal, mixed methods case study and justification for the selection of an appropriate methodology that suited the research aims was critiqued at length in Chapter Four. However, it must be acknowledged that methodological restrictions can limit research findings (Walshaw, 2012). A key strength of the case study design as advocated by Yin (2018) is the flexibility in design. Although most case studies are qualitative in nature (Thomas, 2016), the perception by Yin (2018) is that a case study can be designed to bespoke fit the subject under study. Thus, for this study, the 'case' under study (September 2014 cohort of student nurses at UWS) could be studied in a detail that would not have been possible using other methodological designs. The data was collected over the full duration of the undergraduate programme and included multiple survey questionnaire responses, researcher observations, field notes, Ketso Kit findings, focus group transcriptions and recorded visual focus groups. Therefore, there were no limitations directly resulting from the methodology.

- Generalisability

Generalisability considers whether the findings from a research study would be applicable to other similar people or groups (Vicsek, 2010). Generalisability of statistical data relies on the sample size being large enough to be representative of the population as a whole. As 71% of September 2014 undergraduate nursing students (n=455) at UWS participated in the research study, the findings can be said to be generalisable to the September 2014 cohort as a whole. Indeed, although UWS is the largest provider of undergraduate nursing provision in Scotland, it cannot be assumed that the findings of this study would be generalisable to every student nurse in Scotland or beyond as undergraduate courses vary and thus the student experience may not be comparable. In terms of the qualitative data, it can be harder to rationalise generalisability due to the

smaller participant numbers (Grix, 2010). However, the fact that this study is longitudinal in nature and thus the researcher had repeated interactions with the participants and also the fact that the students were asked the same questions at each data collection are recognised by Vicsek (2010) to increase the likelihood that experiences and perceptions shared are common to others in the same situation. Furthermore, as discussed in detail in Chapter Five, using the concept of trustworthiness, as advocated by Bryman (2016), this research study demonstrated credibility, transferability, dependability and confirmability.

- Reliability and validity

Reliability and validity were demonstrated by the thorough psychometric testing of the DDCPQ as discussed in Chapter Five of this study as well as in this chapter when justifying achievement of research aim 4; To evaluate the psychometric properties of a self-efficacy tool designed to measure attitudes, experiences and perceptions of dementia care in undergraduate student nurses. Furthermore, as mentioned above, the qualitative data was deemed to meet the criteria for trustworthiness, according to Bryman (2016).

- Application to practice

Limitations in terms of applicability to practice can be recognised as study limitations if the study involves a niche area of practice or was carried out in a geographical area that is demographically unique or has different characteristics to other areas. This study focus was on dementia care perceptions and thus would be applicable to all areas of nursing as changing demographics mean that there are many more people living with dementia than ever before (WHO, 2015, WHO, 2017). Thus, the majority of people that nurses care for are over 65 and often have multiple comorbidities and long-term conditions associated with advancing age, such as dementia. Geographically, this study was carried out in Scotland and although Scotland's health statistics are different to some countries in the world and thus could be recognised as a limitation, the global impact of dementia has been well identified (WHO, 2015, WHO, 2017) and thus this study is highly applicable to all nursing practice and can offer recommendations for practice improvement.

9.5.2: Recommendations for Future Practice

A key purpose of any doctoral research study is to generate new knowledge that can offer recommendations for improvement of future practice (Murray, 2011, Walshaw, 2012). As this study focuses on dementia care practice and nursing education, it can offer the following recommendations to both theory and practice;

- Consideration of the timing of educational interventions in undergraduate nursing programmes; this study has shown dementia education be significantly more meaningful nearer the beginning of the student's nursing journey. However, it has also recognised the importance for ongoing education and in particular, theoretical input around managing complex care for the more experienced student in preparation for nursing registration.
- Opportunity for undergraduate student nurses to engage in interprofessional learning at an early stage in their nursing journey. An appreciation of the core values and role specific responsibilities would enhance partnership working with allied health and social care professionals.
- Support for learning through the use of role modelling. Role models should be enthusiastic, knowledgeable and motivated to optimise inspirational effect. Role models could be students, lecturers, nurses and older people themselves.
- Elderly care and dementia care recognised as an exciting, worthwhile and rewarding career choice through greater opportunities for development and advancement in clinical, educational and research roles that are specifically aligned to the older adult.

9.5.3 Recommendations for Future Research

As recognised by the students as part of this study and considering the study findings, this thesis offers the following recommendations for future research;

- Replication of the study for another cohort of student nurses to see if dementia care improvements made to date have further influenced student perceptions and reduced the previously identified challenges in dementia care delivery.
- Testing of the DDCPQ with other dementia care providers such as nursing staff working in healthcare already, allied health professionals (students and experienced practitioners), social care workers (students and experienced practitioners).
- Psychometrically test a shortened version of the DDCPQ to establish a more user-friendly version of the questionnaire that can be quickly and easily used.

Following such recommendations for practice and for research, the thesis draws to a conclusion.

9.6: Conclusion

This doctoral thesis has examined the 'Preconceptions, Perceptions and Preparation for Contemporary Practice: Exploring Self Efficacy in Undergraduate Student Nurses Caring for Person's with Dementia'.

The background of dementia as a condition associated with older adulthood but not part of normal ageing was critiqued. The status of dementia as an international health priority was examined and the implications of the increasing dementia statistics from a nursing perspective explored. The literature review exposed the dearth of student perceptions of dementia care delivery as well as the professional implications of dementia care giving for nurses, thus resulting in the research aims.

Thereafter, the nursing education process was critiqued, learning theories considered in turn and justification provided for social learning theory and the concept of self-efficacy as the underpinning theoretical framework for this study.

Methodological designs were then critically analysed and justification provided for the use of a prospective, longitudinal, mixed method case study. Thereafter, the research data collection

methods of a survey questionnaire and Nominal Group Technique via focus groups were critiqued, with the questionnaire proven to be reliable and valid and the qualitative data proven to ensure rigour and trustworthiness.

Thereafter, the data findings were presented in a layered approach to help facilitate analysis of key findings and thus provide a logical flow to the presentation of the complex set of results, due to the mixed methods and longitudinal nature of the study. Subsequently, the findings were set in context, providing sound, evidence-based verification of achievement of the research aims, whilst also recognising the limitations of the study and recommendations for future practice and future research.

Lastly and most importantly, the unique knowledge contribution of this study was illustrated, namely;

- Conclusions drawn and new insight gained from measurement of the students 'role adequacy', role legitimacy' and the need for 'role support' in dementia care and the changes in these over the duration of an undergraduate nursing programme.
- Adaptation and psychometric testing of the Alcohol and Alcohol Perceptions Questionnaire to measure Dementia and Dementia Care Perceptions.
- Validation of a new tool; "The Dementia and Dementia Care Perceptions Questionnaire" – (DDCPQ).
- In depth understanding of 'the case'; student nurses' self-perceptions of their role in dementia care delivery using a self-efficacy approach, underpinned by social learning theory, in a longitudinal context.

Also, from a unique perspective, it is essential to consider the personal PhD journey of the researcher. From the commencement of the initial research idea, through the research process and to completion of this thesis, my personal and professional development has been astounding. I have honed my research skills and through greater conceptual awareness,

theoretical understanding of the research process as well as enhanced critical analysis skills, I feel that in some ways my research journey is just beginning. There is no doubt that this PhD has had a significant impact on my role as a nurse, as a lecturer and as a researcher. However, it has also inspired and humbled me, as an advocate of older people's nursing, to have had the privilege to truly understand the positive impact that student nurses can have on the lives of their patients, who are living a better life with dementia because the students are part of their journey.

References

Adamson, E. and Dewar, B. (2015) Compassionate Care: Student Nurses Learning Through Reflection and the Use of Story. *Nurse Education in Practice*. Vol 15 (3). pp155-161.

Airey, N. and Marriott, J. (2003) Measuring Therapeutic Attitudes in the Prison Environment: Development of the Prison Attitude to Drugs Scale. *Addiction*. Vol 98. pp179-184.

Alushi, L., Hammond, J.A. and Wood, J.H. (2015) Evaluation of Dementia Education Programmes for Pre-Registration Healthcare Students. A Review of the Literature. *Nurse Education Today*. Vol 35 (9). pp992-998.

Alzheimer Europe (2013) *The Ethical Issues Linked to the Perceptions and Portrayal of Dementia and People with Dementia*. Luxembourg: Alzheimer Europe.

Alzheimer's Disease International (2009) *World Alzheimer Report. Executive Summary*. London: Alzheimer's Disease International.

Alzheimer's Disease International (2012) *Policy Brief. Risk Factors for Dementia*. London: Alzheimer's Disease International.

Alzheimer's Disease International (2013) *Policy Brief for Heads of Government. The Global Impact of Dementia. 2013-2050*. London: Alzheimer's Disease International.

Alzheimer's Disease International (2014) *World Alzheimer Report 2014. Dementia and Risk Reduction. An Analysis of Protective and Modifiable Factors*. London: Alzheimer's Disease International.

Alzheimer Scotland (2009) Charter of Rights for People with Dementia and their Carers in Scotland. [Online] Available: www.alzscot.org/assets/0000/2678/Charter_of_Rights.pdf (Accessed 14 July 2015).

Alzheimer Scotland (2011) Getting Post Diagnostic Support Right for People with Dementia. [Online] Available: http://www.alzscot.org/assets/0001/1226/Getting_post_diagnostic_support_right.pdf (Accessed 14 July 2015).

Alzheimer Scotland (2012) Delivering Integrated Dementia Care: The 8 Pillars Model of Community Support. Edinburgh: Alzheimer's Scotland.

Alzheimer Scotland (2015) Advanced Dementia Practice Model: Understanding and Transforming Advanced Dementia and End of Life Care. Edinburgh: Alzheimer's Scotland.

Alzheimer Scotland (2015) Statistics: Number of People with Dementia in Scotland 2015. [Online] Available: http://www.alzscot.org/assets/0001/6171/2015_Stats.pdf (Accessed 14 July 2015).

Alzheimer Scotland (2019) Leadership and Innovation in Hospital Care: Alzheimer Scotland Dementia Nurse Consultants Report 2015-2020. Edinburgh: Alzheimer Scotland.

Alzheimer's Society (2014a) Dementia 2014: Opportunity for Change. London: Alzheimer's Society.

Alzheimer's Society (2014b) Dementia UK Update. 2nd Edn. London: Alzheimer's Society.

Anderson, P. and Clement, S. (1987) The AAPPQ Revisited: The Measurement of General Practitioner's Attitudes to Alcohol Problems. *British Journal of Addiction*. Vol 82. pp753-759.

Andrew, N. Lopes, A., Pereira, F. and Lima, I. (2013) Building Communities in Higher Education: The Case of Nursing. *Teaching in Higher Education*. Vol 19 (1). pp72-77.

Angus, N.J., Lauder, W. and Reynolds, W. (2001) Further Testing of the Mental Health Problems Perception Questionnaire. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*. Vol 33 (5). pp638-643.

Annear, M.J., Eccleston, C.E., McInerney, F., Elliot, K., Toye, C.M. Tranter, B.K. and Robinson, A.L. (2016) A New Standard in Dementia Knowledge Measurement: Comparative Validation of the Dementia Knowledge Assessment Scale and the Alzheimer's Disease Knowledge Scale. *Journal of American Geriatric Society*. Vol 64 (6) pp1329-1334.

Argyrous, G. (2005) *Statistics for Research with a Guide to SPSS*. 2nd Edn. London: Sage Publications.

Astrom, S., Nilsberg, M., Norberg, A., Sandman, P.O. and Winblad, B. (1991) Staff Burnout in Dementia Care – Relations to Empathy and Attitudes. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*. Vol 28 (1). pp65-75.

Baillie, L. (2015) Dementia Friends Sessions for Nursing Students. *Nursing Older People*. Vol 27 (9). pp34-38.

Baillie, L., Merrit, J., Cox, J. and Crichton, N. (2015) Confidence and Expectations About Caring for Older People with Dementia: A Cross Sectional Study of Nurses. *Educational Gerontology*. Vol 41. pp670-682.

Baldwin, C. and Capstick, A. (2007) Tom Kitwood on Dementia. A Reader and Critical Commentary. Berkshire: Open University Press.

Ballard, C., Gauthier, S., Corbett, A., Brayne, C., Aarsland, D. and Jones, E. (2011) Alzheimer's Disease. *The Lancet*. Vol 377 (9770). pp1019-1031.

Bandura, A. (1977) Self-Efficacy: Toward a Unifying Theory of Behavioural Change. *Psychological Review*. Vol 84. pp191-215.

Bandura, A. (1991) Social Cognitive Theory of Self-Regulation. *Organisational Behaviour and Human Decision Processes*. Vol 50. pp248-287.

Bandura, A. (1997) *Self-Efficacy. The Exercise of Control*. New York: WH Freeman and Company.

Bandura, A. (2006) Towards a Psychology of Human Agency. *Perspectives on Psychological Sciences*. Vol 1 (2). pp164-180.

Banerjee, S., Farina, N. Daley, S. Grovenor, W., Hughes, L. Hebditch, M., Mackrell, S., Nilforooshan, R., Wyatt, C. Vries, K., Haq, I. and Wright, J. (2016) How do we enhance undergraduate healthcare education in dementia? A review of the role of innovative approaches and development of the Time for Dementia Programme. *International Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry*. Vol 32. pp68-75.

Banks, P. Waugh, A., Henderson, J., Sharp, B., Brown, M., Oliver, J. and Marland, G. (2014) Enriching the Care of Patients with Dementia in Acute Settings? The Dementia Champions Programme in Scotland. *Dementia*. Vol 13 (6). pp717-736.

Barnes, D.E. and Yaffe, K. (2011) The Projected Effect of Risk Factor Reduction on Alzheimer's Disease Prevalence. *The Lancet Neurology*. Vol 10 (9). pp819-828.

Bazely, P (2018) *Integrating Analyses in Mixed Methods Research*. London; Sage Publications.

Bell, J. (2005) *Doing Your Research Project*. 4th Edn. Berkshire: Open University Press.

Benner, P. (1984) *From Novice to Expert. Excellence and Power in Clinical Nursing Practice*.

Berragan, L. (2011) Simulation: An Effective Pedagogical Approach for Nursing. *Nurse education Today*. Vol 31 (7). pp660-663.

Boud, D. (2007) Reframing Assessment as if it were Important. In Boud, D., & Falchikov, N. (eds.) *Rethinking Assessment in Higher Education: Learning for the Longer Term*. London: Routledge.

Bowling, A. (2009) *Research Methods in Health*. 3rd Edn. Berkshire: Open University Press.

Brooker, C. and Waugh, A. (2013) *Foundations of Nursing Practice. Fundamentals of Holistic Care*. 2nd Edn. China: Mosby Elsevier.

Brown, J., Collins, A. and Duguid, P. (1989) Situated Cognition and the Culture of Learning. *Educational Researcher*. Vol 18 (1). pp32–42.

Brown, J., Nolan, M., Davis, S., Nolan, J. and Keady, A. (2008) Transforming Student's Views of Gerontological Nursing: Realising the Potential of Enriched Environments of Learning and Care: A Multi Method Longitudinal Study. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*. Vol 45. pp1214-1232.

Brown, T.A. (2006) *Confirmatory Factor Analysis for Applied Research*. New York: The Guilford Press.

Bryman, A. (2016) *Social research Methods*. 5th Edn. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Bunn, F., Goodman, C., Sworn, K., Rait, G., Brayne, C., Robinson, L., McNeilly, E. and Iliffe, S. (2012) Psychological Factors that Shape Patient and Carer Experiences of Dementia Diagnosis and Treatment: A Systematic Review of Qualitative Studies. *PLOS Medicine*. e1001331.

Buzan, T and Buzan, B. (1993) *The Mind Map Book*. London: BBC Books.

Byrne, M.K., Willis, A., Deane, F.P., Hawkins, B. and Quinn, R. (2010) Training Inpatient Mental Health Staff How to Enhance Patient Engagement with Medications: Medication Alliance Training and Dissemination Outcomes in a Large US Mental Health Hospital. *Journal of Evaluation in Clinical Practice*. Vol 16. pp114-120.

Cardarelli, R. Kertesz, A. and Knebl, J.A. (2010) Frontotemporal Dementia: A Review for Primary Care Physicians. *American Family Physician*. Vol 82 (11). pp1372-1377.

Care Quality Commission (2011) *Dignity and Nutrition Inspection Programme: National Overview*. London: Care Quality Commission.

Carlisle, O., & Jordan, A. (2005). It Works in Practice but Will it Work in Theory? The Theoretical Underpinnings of Pedagogy. In O'Neill, G., Moore, S., & McMullin, B. (2005) (Editors) *Emerging Issues in the Practice of University Learning and Teaching*. Dublin: All Ireland Society for Higher Education (AISHE).

Carpenter, B., Balsis, S., Otilingham, P.G., Hanson, P.K. and Gatz, M. (2009) The Alzheimer's Disease Knowledge Scale: Development and Psychometric Properties. *The Gerontologist*. Vol. 49 (2). pp 236–247.

Cartwright, A., K., J. (1980a) The Attitudes of Helping Agents Towards the Alcoholic Client: The Influence of Experience, Support, Training and Self Esteem. *British Journal of Addiction*. Vol 75. pp413-431.

Cartwright. A.K.J. (1980b) The Effect of Role Insecurity on the Therapeutic Commitment of Alcoholism Counsellors. PhD Thesis. London: Institute of Psychiatry.

Cartwright, A.K.J. and Gorman, D.M. (1993) Processes Involved in Changing the Therapeutic Attitudes of Clinicians Towards Working with Drinking Clients. *Psychotherapy Research*. Vol 3 (2). pp95-104.

Casey, D. and Houghton, C. (2010) Clarifying Case Study Research: Examples from Practice. *Nurse Researcher*. Vol 17 (3). pp41-51.

Chan, K.Y., Wang, W., Wu, J.J., Liu, L., Theodoratou, E., Car, J., Middleton, L., Russ, T.C., Deary, I.J., Campbell, H., Wang, W. and Ruden, I. (2013) Epidemiology of Alzheimer's Disease and Other Forms of Dementia in China, 1990-2010: A Systematic Review and Analysis. *The Lancet*. Vol 381 (9882). P2016-2023.

Cherry, K.E. and Palmore, E. (2008) Relating to Older People Evaluation (ROPE): A Measure of Self-Reported Ageism. *Educational Gerontology*. Vol 34. pp849-861.

Clarke, C. and Reed, J. (2006) Case Study Research. In: Gerrish, K. and Lacey, A. (eds.) *The Research Process in Nursing*. 5th Edn. Oxford: Blackwell Publishing.

Clissett, P., Porock, D., Harwood, R.H. and Gladman, J.R.F. (2013) The Challenges of Achieving Person-Centred Care in Acute Hospitals: A Qualitative Study of People with Dementia and their Families. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*. Vol 50 (11). pp1495-1503.

Colby, A., Kohlberg, L., Gibbs, J., & Lieberman, M. (1983). A Longitudinal Study of Moral Judgement. *Monographs of the Society for Research in Child Development*. 48(1-2). pp124.

Collier, E., Knifton, C. and Surr, C. (2015) Dementia Education in Higher Education Institutions. *Nurse Education Today*. Vol 35 (6). pp731-732.

Collins, A., Brown, J.S and Holum (1991) Cognitive Apprenticeship: making Thinking Visible. *American Educator*. Vol 6 (11). pp38-46.

Cook, N., McNamee, D., McFetridge, B. and Deeny, P. (2010) Experiences of People with Parkinson's Disease and their Carers of a Specialist Nursing Service. *British Journal of Neuroscience Nursing*. Vol 6 (6). pp264-270.

Coyne, E. and Needham, J. (2012) Undergraduate Nursing Students Placement in Specialty Clinical Areas: Understanding the Concerns of the Student and the Registered Nurse. *Contemporary Nurse*. Vol 42 (1). pp97-104.

Creswell, J.W., Klassen, A.C., Plano Clark, V.L. and Smith, K.C. (2011) *Best Practices for Mixed Methods Research in the Health Sciences*. London: Office of Behavioural and Social Sciences Research.

Creswell, J.W. and Plano Clark, V.L. (2011) *Designing and Conducting Mixed Methods Research*. 2nd Edn. London: Sage Publications Ltd.

Creswell, J.W. (2016) *A Concise Introduction to Mixed Methods Research*. California: Sage Publications Inc.

Crinson, I. (2009) *Health Policy*. London: Sage Publications Ltd.

Cunningham, S. (2017) Evaluating a Nursing Erasmus Exchange Experience: Reflections on the Use and Value of the Nominal Group Technique for Evaluation. *Nurse Education in Practice*. Vol 26. pp68-73.

Davis, M.B. (2007) *Doing a Successful Research Project*. Houndmills: Palgrave MacMillan.

Department of Health (2009) *Living Well with Dementia: A National Dementia Strategy*. London: Department of Health.

Department of Health (2010) *Quality Outcomes for People with Dementia: Building on the Work of the National Dementia Strategy*. London: Department of Health.

Department of Health (2012) *Prime Minister's Challenge on Dementia. Delivering Major Improvements in Dementia Care and Research by 2015*. London: Department of Health.

Department of Health (2013a) *Dementia. A State of the Nation Report on Dementia Care and Support in England* [Online] Available URL: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/262139/Dementia.pdf

Department of Health (2013b) *G8 Dementia Summit Declaration*. [Online] Available URL: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/265869/2901668_G8_DementiaSummitDeclaration_acc.pdf (Accessed 14 July 2015).

Department of Health (2013c) NHS Outcomes Framework 2014-2015. London: Department of Health.

Department of Health (2013d) The Prime Minister's Challenge on Dementia. Delivering Major Improvements in Dementia Care and Research by 2015: Annual Report of Progress. London: Department of Health.

Department of Health (2015) Prime Minister's Challenge on Dementia 2020. London: Department of Health.

Der Vugt, M.E. and Verhey, F.R.J. (2013) The Impact of Early Dementia Diagnosis and Intervention on Informal Caregivers. *Progress in Neurobiology*. Vol 110 (2013). pp54-62.

Dewing, J. and Dijk, S. (2014) What is the Current State of Care for Older People with Dementia in General Hospitals? A Literature Review. *Dementia*, 1471301213520172.

Dingwall, L., Fenton, J., Kelly, T.B. and Lee, J. (2017) Sliding Doors: Did Drama Based Inter-Professional Education Improve the Tensions Round Person-Centred Nursing and Social Care Delivery for People with Dementia: A Mixed Methods Exploratory Study. *Nurse Education Today*. Vol 51. pp1-7.

Eccleston, C.E.A., Lea, E.J., McInerney, F., Crisp, E., Marlow, A. and Robinson, A.I. (2015) An Investigation of Nursing Students Knowledge of Dementia: A Questionnaire Study. *Nurse Education Today*. Vol 35 (6) pp800-805.

Ellis, G., Whitehead, M.A., Robinson, D., O'Neill, D. and Langhorne, P. (2011) Comprehensive Geriatric Assessment for Older Adults Admitted to Hospital: Meta-Analysis of Randomised Control Trials. *British Medical Journal*. BMJ 2011; 343 doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmj.d6553>.

Evripidou, M., Charalambous, A., Middleton, N. and Papastavrou, E. (2018) Nurses' Knowledge and Attitudes About Dementia Care: Systematic Literature Review. *Perspective in Psychiatric Care*. Vol 55. pp48-60.

Fawcett, J. (2015) Invisible Nursing Research: Thoughts about Mixed Methods Research and Nursing Practice. *Nursing Science Quarterly*. Vol 28 (2). pp167-168.

Field, A. (2014) *Discovering Statistics Using IBM SPSS Statistics*. 4th Edn. London: Sage Publications Ltd.

Fincham, J.E. (2008) Response rates and Responsiveness for Survey's, Standards and the Journal. *American Journal of Pharmacy Education*. Vol 72 (2). p43.

Flick, U. (2018) *An Introduction to Qualitative Research*. 6th Edn. London: Sage Publications Ltd.

Flyvbjerg, B. (2006) Five Misunderstandings About Case-Study Research. *Qualitative Inquiry*. Vol 12 (2). pp219-245.

Foth, T., Efstathiou, N., Vanderspank-Wright, B., Upholz, L., Dutthorn, N., Zimansky, M. and Humphrey-Murto, S. (2016) The Use of Delphi and Nominal Group Technique in Nursing Education: A Review. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*. Vol 60. pp112-120.

Fox, C., Lafortune, L., Boustani, M. and Brayne, C. (2013) The Pros and Cons of Early Diagnosis in Dementia. *British Journal of General Practice*. DOI: 10.3399/bjgp13X669374.

Francis, R. (2013) *Report of the Mid Staffordshire NHS Foundation Trust Public Inquiry*. London: The Stationery Office.

Gagne, R. M. and Driscoll, M.P. (1988) *Essentials of Learning for Instruction*. 2nd Edn. New Jersey: Prentice Hall.

Galvin, J.E., Duda, J.E., Kaufer, D.I., Lippa, C.F., Taylor, A. and Zarit, S.H. (2010) Lewy Body Dementia: Caregiver Burden and Unmet Needs. *Alzheimer Disease and Associated Disorders*. Vol 24 (2). pp177-181.

Gandesha, A., Souza, R., Chaplin, R., Hood, C. (2012) Adequacy of Training in Dementia Care for Acute Hospital Staff. *Nursing Older People*. Vol 24 (4). pp26–31.

Gardner, L. (2013) Benner Reflection and Expertise: Some Further Thoughts. *Nurse Education Today*. Vol 33 (3). pp183-184.

General Data Protection Regulation (2016) Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of The European Parliament and of the Council. EU: European Parliament.

George-Carey, R., Adeloje, D., Chan, K.Y., Paul, A., Kolcic, I., Campbell, H. and Rudan, I. (2012) An Estimate of the Prevalence of Dementia in Africa: A Systematic Analysis. *Journal of Global Health*. Vol 2 (2). pp1-13.

Glanz, K., Rimer, B.K. and Viswanath, K. (2008) *Health Behaviour and Health Education*. 4th Edn. San Francisco: Jossey Bass.

Goldman, J.G., Williams-Gray, C., Barker, R.A., Duda, J.E. and Galvin, J.E. (2014) The Spectrum of Cognitive Impairment in Lewy Body Diseases. *Movement Disorders*. Vol 29 (5). pp608-621.

Gorman, D.M. and Cartwright, A.K.J. (1991) Implications of Using the Composite and Short Versions of the Alcohol and Alcohol Problems Perception Questionnaire (AAPPQ). *British Journal of Addiction*. Vol 86. pp327-334.

Gray, D. (2014) *Doing Research in the Real World*. 3rd Edn. London: Sage Publications Ltd.

Greasley, P. (2008) *Quantitative Data Analysis Using SPSS. An Introduction for Health and Social Science*. Berkshire: Open University Press.

Griffiths, F. (2009) *Research Methods for Healthcare Practice*. London: Sage Publications Ltd.

Grix, J. (2010) *The Foundations of Research*. 2nd Edn. Hampshire: Palgrave MacMillan.

Grove, J.C. and Bush, R.A. (1998) Development of a Questionnaire to Examine the Role of Counsellors Working with School Students and their Families with Alcohol or Other Drug-Related Problems. *Drug and Alcohol Review*. Vol 17. pp77-86.

Harvey, N. and Holmes, C.A. (2012) Nominal Group Technique: An Effective Method for Obtaining Group Consensus. *International Journal of Nursing Practice*. Vol 18. pp188-194.

Hayden, J. (2014) *Health Behaviour Theory*. 2nd Edn. Burlington: Jones and Bartlett Learning.

Holloway, I. and Wheeler, S. (2010) *Qualitative Research in Nursing and Healthcare*. 3rd Edn. Oxford: Wiley Black.

Hvalic-Touzery, S., Skela-Savic, B., Macrae, R., Jack-Waugh, A., Tolson, D., Hellstrom, A., De Abreu, W. and Pesjak, K. (2018) The Provision of Accredited Higher Education on Dementia in Six European Countries: An Exploratory Study. *Nurse Education Today*. Vol 60. pp161-167.

Hyett, N., Kenny, A. and Dickson-Swift, V. (2014) Methodology or Method? A Critical Review of Qualitative Case Study Reports. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies on Health and Well-being*. *Int J Qualitative Stud Health Well-being* 2014, 9: 23606 doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3402/qhw.v9.23606>.

Illeris, K. (2007) What do we Mean by Experiential Learning? *Human Resources Development*. Vol 6 (1). pp84-95.

ISD Scotland (2014) Quality and Outcomes Framework. Prevalence, Achievement, Payment and Exceptions Data for Scotland 2013/2014. [Online] Available URL: <https://isdscotland.scot.nhs.uk/Health-Topics/General-Practice/Publications/2014-09-30/2014-09-30-QOF-Report.pdf?30019778014> (Accessed 3 August 2015).

James, B.D., Bennett, D., Boyle, P.A., Leurgans, S. and Schneider, J.A. (2012) Dementia from Alzheimer Disease and Mixed Pathologies in the Oldest Old. *Journal of the American Medical Association*. Vol 307 (17). pp1798-1800.

Jarvis, P. (2010) *Adult Education and Lifelong Learning. Theory and Practice*. 4th Edn. Oxon: Routledge.

Jiwa, N.S., Garrard, P. and Hainsworth, A.H. (2010) Experimental Models of Vascular Dementia and Vascular Cognitive Impairment: A Systematic Review. *Journal of Neurochemistry*. Vol 115 (4). pp814-828.

Johnson, B.M. and Webber, P.B. (2005) *An Introduction to Theory and Reasoning in Nursing*. 2nd Edn. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams and Wilkins.

Johnson, R.B., Onwuegbuzie, A.J. and Turner, L.A. (2007) Towards a Definition of Mixed Methods. *Journal of Mixed Method Research*. Vol 1 (2). pp112-133.

Jordan, K. and Church, T. (2013) A Clinical Learning Experience: Enhancing Baccalaureate Nursing Students' Self-Efficacy in Meeting the Psychosocial Needs of Clients with Dementia. *Journal of Nursing Education*. Vol 52 (3). pp171-174.

Jurgens, F.J., Clissett, P., Gladman, J.R.F. and Harwood, R.H. (2012) Why are Family Carers of People with Dementia Dissatisfied with General Hospital Care? A Qualitative Study. *BMC Geriatrics*. Vol 12 (57). pp1-10.

Kaiser, H.F. (1960) The Application of Electronic Computers to Factor Analysis. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*. Vol 20. pp141-151.

Kala, S., Isaramalai, S. and Pohthong, A. (2010) Electronic Learning and Constructivism: A Model for Nursing Education. *Nurse Education Today*. Vol 30. pp61-66.

Kimzey, M., Mastel-Smith, B. and Alfred, D. (2016) The Impact of Educational Experiences on Nursing Students' Knowledge and Attitudes Toward People With Alzheimer's Disease: A Mixed Method Study. *Nurse Education Today*. Vol 46. pp57-63.

Kitwood, T. (1997) *Dementia Reconsidered. The Person Comes First*. Berkshire: Open University Press.

Klassen, A.C., Creswell, J., Plano Clark, V.L., Clegg Smith, K. and Meissner, H.I. (2012) Best Practices in Mixed Methods for Quality of Life Research. *Qualitative Life Research*. Vol 21. pp377-380.

Knowles, M. (1980) *The Modern Practice of Adult Education: From Pedagogy to Andragogy*. Chicago: Follett.

Kogan, N. (1961) Attitudes Toward Old People: The Development of a Scale and an Examination of Correlates. *Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*. Vol 62. pp44–54.

Koh, L. C. (2012) Student Attitudes and Educational Support in Caring for Older People – A Review of Literature. *Nurse Education in Practice*. Vol 12. pp16-20.

Kolb, D.A. (1984) *Experiential Learning. Experience as the Source of Learning and Development*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall.

Korczyński, A.D., Vakhapova, V. and Grindberg, L.Y. (2012) Vascular Dementia. *Journal of the Neurological Sciences*. Vol 322 (1). pp2-10.

Korstjens, I. and Moser, A (2017) Series: Practical Guide to Qualitative Research. Part 4: Trustworthiness of Publishing. *European Journal of General Practice*. Vol 24. Pp120-124.

Koskinen, S., Hupli, M., Katajisto, J. and Salminen, L. (2012) Graduating Finnish Nurse Students Interest in Gerontological Nursing – A Survey Study. *Nurse Education Today*. Vol 32 (4). pp356-360.

Koskinen, S., Salminen, L., Stolt, L. and Leino-Kilpi, H. (2015) The Education Received by Nursing Students Regarding Nursing Older People: A Scoping Literature Review. *Scandinavian Journal of Caring Sciences*. Vol 29 (1). pp15-29.

Lambrinov, E., Sourtz, P., Kalokerinou, A. and Lemonidou, C. (2009) Attitudes and Knowledge of the Greek Nursing Students Attitudes Towards Older People. *Nurse Education*. Vol 29 (6). pp617-622.

Lauder, W., Reynolds, W., Reilly, V. and Angus, N. (2000) The Development and testing of the Mental Health Problems Perception Questionnaire. *Journal of Psychiatric and Mental Health Nursing*. Vol 7. pp221-226.

Lauder, W., Watson, R., Topping, K., Holland, K. , Johnson, M., Porter, M., Roxburgh, M. and Behr, A. (2008) An Evaluation of Fitness for Practice Curricula: Self-Efficacy, Support and Self-Reported Competence in Pre-Registration Student Nurses and Midwives. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*. Vol 17. pp1858-1867.

Lave, J. and Wenger, E. (1991) *Situated Learning: Legitimate Peripheral Participation*. Cambridge: University of Cambridge Press.

Lave, J. and Wenger, E. (1999) *Legitimate Peripheral Participation*. In: Murphy, P. (ed) *Learners. Learning and Assessment*. London: Open University Press.

LeCouteur, D.G., Doust, J., Creasey, H. and Brayne C. (2013) Political Drive to Screen for Pre-Dementia: Not Evidence Based and Ignores the Harms of Diagnosis. *British Medical Journal*. Vol 347. p1-6.

Levitt-Jones, T., Hoffman, K., Dempsey, J., Jeong, S.Y., Noble, D., Norton, C., Roche, J. and Hickey, N. (2010) The 'Five Rights' of Clinical Reasoning: An Educational Model to Enhance Nursing Students Ability to Identify and Manage Clinically 'At Risk' Patients. *Nurse Education Today*. Vol 30 (6). pp515-520.

Lew, M., Alwis, W., & Schmidt, H. (2010). Accuracy of Student's Self-assessment and their Beliefs About its Utility. *Assessment and Evaluation in Higher Education*, 35 (2), pp. 135-156.

Liamputtong, P. (2014) *Qualitative Research Methods*. 3rd Edn. Australia: Oxford University Press.

Lightfoot, P. J. and Orford, J. (1986) Helping Agents' Attitudes Towards Alcohol-Related Problems: Situations Vacant? A Test And Elaboration Of A Model. *British Journal of Addiction*. Vol 81. pp749–756.

Lintern, T. and Woods, R.T. (1996) The Dementia Care Practitioner Assessment (DCPA). *Journal of the British Association for Services to the Elderly*. Vol 63. pp12-18.

Livingston, G., Pitfield, C., Morris, J., Manela, M., Lewis-Holmes, E. and Jacobs, H. (2012) Care at the End of Life for People with Dementia Living in a Care Home: A Qualitative Study of Staff Experiences and Attitudes. *International Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry*. Vol 27 (6). pp643-650.

Liu, Y., Norman, I.J. and While, A. E (2013) Nurses' Attitudes Towards Older People: A Systematic Review. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*. Vol 50. pp 1271-1282.

Logan, P. and Angel, L. (2011) Nursing as a Scientific Undertaking and the Intersection with Science in Undergraduate Studies; Implications for Nursing Management. *Journal of Nursing Management*. Vol 19 (3). pp407-417.

Lovell, M. (2006) Caring for the Elderly: Changing Perceptions and Attitudes. *Journal of Vascular Nursing*. Vol 24 (1). pp22–26.

MacKenzie, C.S. and Peragine, G. (2003) Measuring and Enhancing Self-Efficacy Among Professional Caregivers of Individuals with Dementia. *American Journal of Alzheimer's Disease and Other Dementia's*. Vol 18. pp291-299.

Macnee, C.L. and McCabe, S. (2008) *Understanding Nursing Research*. 2nd Edn. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams and Wilkins.

Maher, C., Hadfield, M., Hutchings, M. and de Eyto, A. (2018) Ensuring Rigor in Qualitative Data Analysis: A Design Research Approach to Coding Combining Nvivo with Traditional Methods. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*. Vol 17 (1). pp1-13.

Mangialasche, F., Soloman, A., Winbald, B., Mecocci, P. and Kivipelto, M. (2010) Alzheimer's Disease: Clinical Trials and Drug Development. *The Lancet Neurology*. Vol 9 (7). pp702-716.

Manchailasche, F. Kivipelto, M., Soloman, A. and Fratiglioni, L. (2012) Dementia Prevention: Current Epidemiological Evidence and Future Perspective. *Alzheimer's Research and Therapy*. Vol 4 (6). pp1-8.

Marie Curie (2015) *Living and Dying with Dementia in Scotland. Barriers to Care*. Edinburgh: Marie Curie Cancer Care.

McKenzie, E.L. and Brown, P.M. (2014) Nursing Students' Intentions to Work in Dementia Care: Influence of Age, Ageism and Perceived Barriers. *Educational Gerontology*. Vol 40. pp619-633.

McKinney, A.A. and Page, K. (2009) Podcasts and Videostreaming: Useful Tools to Facilitate Learning of Pathophysiology in Undergraduate Nursing Education? *Nurse Education in Practice*. Vol 9 (6). pp372-376.

McMillan, S.S., Kelly, F., Sav, A., Kendall, E., King, M.A., Whitty, J.A. and Wheeler, A.J. (2014) Using the Nominal Group Technique: How to Analyse Across Multiple Groups. *Health Service Outcomes Research Method*. Vol 14. pp92-108.

McMillan, S., King, M. and Tully, M.P. (2016) How to use Nominal Group and Delphi Techniques. *International Journal of Clinical Pharmacy*. Vol 38 (3). pp655-662.

Merriam, S.B. (1998) *Qualitative Research and Case Study Applications in Education*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.

Merriam, S.B., Caffarella, R.S. and Baumgartner, L.M. (2007) *Learning in Adulthood. A Comprehensive Guide*. 3rd Edn. San Francisco: John Wiley and Sons Inc.

Merriam, S.B. and Tisdell, E.J. (2016) *Qualitative Research. A Guide to Design and Implementation*. 4th Edn. San Francisco: Jossey Bass.

Miles, M.B., Huberman, A.M. and Saldana, J. (2014) *Qualitative Data Analysis. A Methods Sourcebook*. 3rd Edn. California: Sage Publications Inc.

Morra, L.F. and Donovan, P.J. (2013) Clinical Presentation and Differential Diagnosis of Dementia with Lewy Bodies: A Review. *International Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry*. Vol 29 (6). pp569-576.

Morrell, N., Ridgway, V.J. (2014) Are we Preparing Student Nurses for Final Practice Placement. *British Journal of Nursing*, Vol 23(10). pp518-23.

Murphy, F., Rosser, M., Bevan, R., Warner, G. and Jordan, S. (2012) Nursing Students Experiences and Preferences Regarding Hospital and Community Placements. *Nurse Education in Practice*. Vol 12 (3). pp170-175.

Murray, R. (2011) *How to Write a Thesis*. Berkshire: Open University Press.

National Records of Scotland (2013) Age Standardised Death Rates Calculated Using the European Standard Population. [Online] Available URL: <http://www.nrscotland.gov.uk/statistics-and-data/statistics/statistics-by-theme/vital->

[events/death/age-standardised-death-rates-calculated-using-the-esp](#) (Accessed 11 January 2016).

Nelson, A., Dumville, J. and Torgerson, D. (2006) Experimental Research. In: Gerrish, K. and Lacey, A. (eds.) *The Research Process in Nursing*. 5th Edn. Oxford: Blackwell Publishing.

NHS Education Scotland (2008) *Nursing and Midwifery in Scotland: Being Fit for Practice*. Edinburgh: NES.

NHS Education Scotland (2008) *Quality Standards for Practice Placement*. 2nd Edn. Edinburgh: NES.

NHS Education Scotland (2012) *Acute Care Dementia Learning Resource*. [Online] Available URL: http://www.nes.scot.nhs.uk/media/1521260/acute_dementia_interactive_2012.pdf (Accessed 4 August 2015).

NHS Education Scotland (2013) *Dementia Skilled – Improving Practice Learning Resource*. [Online] Available URL: http://www.nes.scot.nhs.uk/media/857092/dementia_skilled_final.pdf (Accessed 4 August 2015).

NHS Education Scotland (2014) *Nursing and Midwifery Strategy 2014-2017*. Edinburgh: NES.

NHS Education Scotland (2014) *Promoting Excellence in Supporting People Through a Diagnosis of Dementia*. Enhanced Practice Resource. Edinburgh: NES.

NHS Education Scotland (2016) *Supporting Quality in Pre-registration Nursing and Midwifery Education*. Issue 4. Edinburgh: NES.

NHS Scotland (2013) Getting Knowledge into Action to Improve Healthcare Quality: Report of Strategic Review and Recommendations. Edinburgh: NHS Scotland.

Nunally, J.C. (1978) Psychometric Theory. New York: McGraw Hill.

Nursing and Midwifery Council (2008) Standards to Support Learning and Assessment in Practice; NMC Standards for Mentors, Practice Teachers and Teachers. London: NMC.

Nursing and Midwifery Council (2010a) Standards for Pre-Registration Nursing Education. London: NMC.

Nursing and Midwifery Council (2010b) Standards for Competence for Registered Nurses. London: NMC.

Nursing and Midwifery Council (2015a) Quality Assurance of Education and Local Supervising Authorities Annual Report 2014–2015. London: NMC.

Nursing and Midwifery Council (2015b) Strategy 2015-2020. London: NMC.

Nursing and Midwifery Council (2015c) The Code: Professional Standards of Practice and Behaviour for Nurses and Midwives. London: NMC.

Nursing and Midwifery Council (2015d) Openness and Honesty; When Things Go Wrong: The Professional Duty of Candour. London: NMC.

Nursing and Midwifery Council (2015e) Revalidation. London: NMC.

Nursing and Midwifery Council (2017) Revalidation. How to Revalidate with the NMC. Requirements for Renewing Your Registration. London: NMC.

Nursing and Midwifery Council (2018a) Standards of Proficiency for Registered Nurses. London: NMC.

Nursing and Midwifery Council (2018b) Standards Framework for Nursing and Midwifery Education. Part 1 of Realising Professionalism: Standards for Education and Training. London: NMC.

Nursing and Midwifery Council (2018c) Standards for Student Supervision and Assessment. Part 2 of Realising Professionalism: Standards for Education and Training. London: NMC.

Nursing and Midwifery Council (2018d) Standards for Pre-Registration Nursing Programmes. Part 3 of Realising Professionalism: Standards for Education and Training. London: NMC.

Nursing and Midwifery Council (2018e) Standards of Proficiency for Nursing Associates. London: NMC.

Nursing and Midwifery Council (2018f) The Code. Professional Standards of Practice and Behaviour for Nurses, Midwives and Nursing Associates. London: NMC.

Norton, S., Matthews, F.E., Barnes, D.E., Yaffe, K. and Brayne, C. (2014) Potential for Primary Prevention of Alzheimer's Disease: An Analysis of Population Based Data. *The Lancet Neurology*. Vol 13 (8). pp788-794.

O'Cathain, A., Murphy, E., & Nicholl, J. (2008) The Quality of Mixed Methods Studies in Health Services Research. *Journal of Health Services Research Policy*. Vol 13 (2). pp92-98.

O'Connor, M.L. and McFadden, S.H. (2010) Development and Psychometric Validation of the Dementia Attitudes Scale. *International Journal of Alzheimer's Disease*. [Online] Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.4061/2010/454218>

O'Driscoll, M., Allan, H. and Smith, P. (2010) Still Looking for Leadership – Who is Responsible for Student Nurses Learning in Practice? *Nurse Education Today*. Vol 30 (3). pp212-217.

O'Leary, Z. (2004) *The Essential Guide to Doing Research*. London: Sage Publications Ltd.

Oliver, P. (2010) *The Student's Guide to Research Ethics*. 2nd Edn. Berkshire: Open University Press.

Orton, S. (2011) Rethinking Attrition in Student Nurses. *Journal of Health and Social Care Improvement*. February Issue. pp1-7.

Ostlund, U., Kidd, L., Wengstrom, Y. and Rowa-Dewar, N. (2010) Combining Qualitative and Quantitative Research within Mixed Method Research Designs: A Methodological Review. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*. Vol 48. pp369-383.

Parahoo, K (2014) *Nursing Research: Principles, Process and Issues*. 3rd Edn. Hampshire: Palgrave MacMillan.

Pavlov, I.P. (1927) *Conditional Reflexes: An Investigation of the Physiological Activity of the Cerebral Cortex*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Piaget, J. and Inhelder, B. (1969) *The Psychology of the Child*. New York: Basic Books.

Piguet, O., Hornberger, M., Mioshi, E. and Hodges, J.R. (2011) Behavioural Variant Frontotemporal Dementia: Diagnosis, Clinical Staging and Management. *The Lancet Neurology*. Vol 10 (2). pp162-172.

Prince, M., Bryce, R. Albanese, E., Wimo, A., Ribeiro, W. and Ferri, C.P. (2013) The Global Prevalence of Dementia: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Alzheimer's and Dementia*. Vol 9 (1). pp63-75.

Proctor, S. and Allan, T. (2006) Sampling. In: Gerrish, K. and Lacey, A. (eds.) *The Research Process in Nursing*. 5th Edn. Oxford: Blackwell Publishing.

Pulsford, D., Hope, K. and Thompson, R. (2007) Provision for Professionals Working with People with Dementia: A Scoping Exercise. *Nurse Education Today*. Vol 27. pp5-13.

Quality Assurance Agency (2009) *Scottish Subject Benchmark Statement: Nursing*. Glasgow: QAA Scotland.

Quality Assurance Agency (2011) *Key Aspects of Practice-Based Learning in Teaching, Nursing and Social Work in Scotland*. Glasgow: QAA Scotland.

Quality Assurance Agency (2018) *The Revised UK Quality Code for Higher Education*. Glasgow: QAA Scotland.

Quinn, F.M. (2000) *The Principles and Practice of Nurse Education*. Cheltenham: Nelson Thornes.

Ridgeway, V., Mason-Whitehead, E. and McIntosh-Scott, A. (2018) Visual Perceptions of Ageing: A Longitudinal Mixed Methods Study of UK Undergraduate Student Nurses' Attitudes and Perceptions Towards Older People. *Nurse Education in Practice*. Vol 33. pp63-69.

Robinson, L., Dickinson, C., Bamford, C., Clark, A., Hughes, J. and Exley, C. (2013) A Qualitative Study: Professionals Experiences of Advance Care Planning in Dementia and Palliative Care, 'A Good Idea in Theory but' *Palliative Medicine*. Vol 27 (5). pp401-408.

Rockwood, K., Zeng, A., Leibman, C., Mucha, L. and Mitnitski, A. (2012) Validation of an Informant-Reported Web-Based Data Collection to Assess Dementia Symptoms. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*. Vol 14 (2) e42.

Rogers, C.R. (1983) *Freedom to Learn for the 80's*. New York: Merrill Publishing.

Rokstad, A.M.M., Halse, I., Tretteteig, S., Barca, M.L., Kirkevold, O., McCabe, L., Selbaek, G., Taranrod, L., Testad, I. Vatre, S., Vossius, C., Wimo, A. and Engedal, K. (2014) Effects and Costs of a Day Care Centre Program Designed for People with Dementia – a 24 Month Controlled Study. *Journal of Clinical Trials*. Vol 4 (4). pp1-5.

Roland, M. and Paddison, C. (2013) Better Management of Patients with Multimorbidity. *British Medical Journal*. BMJ 2013; 346:f2510 doi: 10.1136/bmj.f2510.

Royal College of Nursing (2012) *Quality with Compassion. The Future of Nursing Education*. Report of the Willis Commission. London: RCN.

Royal College of Nursing (2013) Dementia. Scoping the Role of the Dementia Nurse Specialist in Acute Care. London: RCN.

Ruey, S. (2010) A Case Study of Constructivist Instructional Strategies for Adult Online Learning. British Journal of Educational Technology. Vol 41 (5). pp706-720.

Scerri, A. and Scerri, C. (2013) Nursing Students Attitudes and Knowledge Towards Dementia – A Questionnaire Survey. Vol 33 (9). pp962-968.

Scottish Credit and Qualifications Framework (2012) Scottish Credit and Qualifications Framework Level Descriptors. Glasgow: SCQF.

Scottish Government (2008) Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) Act 2000. A Short Guide to the Act. [Online] Available URL: www.scot.gov/Resource/Doc/217194/0058194.pdf (Accessed 5 July 2015).

Scottish Government (2010a) Scotland's National Dementia Strategy. Edinburgh: Scottish Government.

Scottish Government (2010b) The Healthcare Quality Strategy for NHS Scotland. Edinburgh: The Scottish Government.

Scottish Government (2011a) Standards of Care for Dementia in Scotland. Edinburgh: Scottish Government.

Scottish Government (2011b) Promoting Excellence: A Framework for all Health and Social Services Staff Working with People with Dementia, their Families and Carers. Edinburgh: Scottish Government.

Scottish Government (2013) Scotland's National Dementia Strategy 2013-2016. Edinburgh: Scottish Government.

Scottish Government (2014) Public Bodies (Joint Working) (Scotland) Act 2014. [Online] Available URL: http://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2014/9/pdfs/asp_20140009_en.pdf (Accessed 25 June 2015).

Scottish Government (2015) Setting the Direction for Nursing and Midwifery Education. Delivery Plan 2015-16. Edinburgh: Scottish Government.

Scottish Government (2017) Scotland's National Dementia Strategy 2017-2020. Edinburgh: Scottish Government.

Scottish Public Health Network (2013) Health and social care needs of older people in Scotland: an epidemiological assessment. Glasgow: NHS Health Scotland.

Scriven, A. (2010) Promoting Health: A Practical Guide. London: Bailliere Tindall.

Selbaek, G., Engedal, K. and Bergh, S. (2013) The Prevalence and Course of Neuropsychiatric Symptoms in Nursing Home Patients with Dementia: A Systematic Review. Journal of the American Medical Directors Association. Vol 14 (3). pp161-169.

Sharp, S.I., Aarsland, D., Day, S., Sonnesyn, H., Alzheimer's Society Systematic review Group and Ballard, C. (2010) Hypertension is a Potential Risk Factor for Vascular Dementia: Systematic Review. International Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry. Vol 26 (7). pp661-669.

Shaw, S., Cartwright, A., Spratley, T. and Harwin, J. (1978) *Responding to Drinking Problems*. London: Crook Helm Ltd.

Shin, J.H., Seo, H. Kim, K.H., Kim, K.H. and Lee, Y. (2015) Knowledge about Dementia in South Korean Nursing Students: A Cross-Sectional Survey. *BMC Nursing*. Vol 14 (65). pp1-7.

Skinner, B.F. (1969) *Contingencies of Reinforcement: A Theoretical Analysis*. New York: Appleton Century Crofts.

Spector, A., Orrell, M., Schepers, A. and Shanahan, N. (2012) A Systematic Review of Knowledge of Dementia Outcome Measures. *Ageing Research Reviews*. Vol 11 (1). pp67-77.

Spouse (1998) Scaffolding Student Learning in Clinical Practice. *Nurse Education Today*. Vol 18 (5). pp345-351.

Stake, R.E. (1995) *The Art of Case Study Research*. California: Sage Publications Inc.

Stake, R.E. (2006) *Multiple Case Study Analysis*. New York: The Guilford Press.

Stevens, J. A. (2011) Student Nurses' Career Preferences for Working with Older People: A Replicated Longitudinal Study. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*. Vol 48 (8). pp944-951.

Strudsholm, T., Meadows, L.M., Robinson Vollman, A., Thurston, W. and Henderson, R. (2016) Using Mixed Methods to Facilitate Complex, Multiphased Health Research. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*. January - December. pp1–11.

Stump, G.S., Husman, J. and Brem, S.K. (2012) The Nursing Student Self-Efficacy Scale. *Nursing Research*. Vol 61 (3). pp149-153.

Suhonen, R., Gustafsson, M.L., Katajisto, J., Valimaki, M. and Leino-Kilpi, M. (2010) Nurses Perceptions of Individualised Care. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*. Vol 66 (5). pp1035-1046.

Surr, C., Baillie, L., Waugh, A. and Brown, M. (2017) Position Paper: The Importance of Including Dementia in Pre and Post Qualifying Curricula for Health and Social Care Professionals. *Higher Education for Dementia Network: UK*.

Surr, C.A., Gates, C. Irving, D., Oyeboode, J., Smith, S.J., Parveen, S., Drury, M. and Dennison, A. (2017) Effective Dementia Education and Training for the Health and Social Care Workforce: A Systematic Review of the Literature. *Review of Educational Research*. Vol 87 (5). pp966-1000.

Surr, C.A., Smith, S.J., Crossland, J. and Robins, J. (2016) Impact of a Person-Centred Dementia Care Training Programme on Hospital Staff Attitudes, Role Efficacy and Perceptions of Caring for People with Dementia: A Repeated measures Study. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*. Vol 53. pp144-151.

Survey Monkey (2018) Sample Size Calculator. [Internet] Available URL: <https://www.surveymonkey.com/mp/sample-size-calculator/> (Accessed 10 August 2019).

Survey Systems (2018) Power Formula. [Internet] Available URL: <https://www.surveysystem.com/sscalc.htm> (Accessed 10 August 2019).

Swanbourne, P.G. (2010) *Case Study Research*. London: Sage Publications Ltd.

Terrhorst, L., Gotham, H.J., Puskar, K.R., Mitchell, A.M., Talcott, K.S., Braxter, B., Hagle, H., Fioravanti, M. and Woomer, G.R. (2013) Confirming the Factor Structure of the Alcohol and Alcohol Problems Questionnaire (AAPPQ) in a Sample of Baccalaureate Students. *Research in Nursing and Health*. Vol 36. pp412-422.

Thomas, G. (2009) *How to do your Research Project*. London: Sage Publications Ltd.

Thomas, G. (2016) *How to do your Case Study*. 2nd Edn. London: Sage Publications Ltd.

Tight, M. (2017) *Understanding Case Study Research*. London: Sage Publications Ltd.

Tilley, D.S., Allen, P., Collins, C., Bridges, R.A., Francis, P. and Green, A. (2007) Promoting Clinical Competence: Using Scaffolded Instruction for Practice-Based Learning. *Journal of Professional Nursing*. Vol 23 (5). pp285-289.

Toot, S., Devine, M., Akporobaro, A. and Orrell, M. (2013) Causes of Hospital Admission for People with Dementia: A Systematic Review and Meta Analysis. *Journal of the American Medical Directors Association*. Vol 14 (7). pp463-470.

Topping, A. (2006) The Quantitative-Qualitative Continuum. In: Gerrish, K. and Lacey, A. (eds.) *The Research Process in Nursing*. 5th Edn. Oxford: Blackwell Publishing.

Traynor, V., Inove, K. and Crookes, P. (2011) Literature Review: Understanding Nursing Competence in Dementia Care. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*. Vol 20. pp1948-1960.

Tritter, J. (2007) Mixed Methods and Multidisciplinary Research in Healthcare. In: Saks, M. and Allsop, J. (eds.) *Researching Health. Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed Methods*. London: Sage Publications Ltd.

Twomey, A. (2004) Web Based Teaching in Nursing. Lessons from the Literature. Nurse Education Today. Vol 24 (6). pp452-458.

United Kingdom Central Council for Nursing, Midwifery and Health Visiting (1986). Project 2000: A New Preparation for Practice. London : UKCC.

United Kingdom Central Council for Nursing, Midwifery and Health Visiting (1999) Fitness for Practice. The UKCC Commission for Nursing and Midwifery Education. London: UKCC.

United Kingdom Central Council for Nursing, Midwifery and Health Visiting (2001) Fitness for Practice and Purpose. The Report of the UKCC's Post Commission Development Group. London: UKCC.

United Nations (2013) World Population Prospects. The 2012 Revision. Methodology of the United -Nations Population Estimates and Projections. New York: United Nations.

University of the West of Scotland (2018) Regulatory Framework 2018/2019. University of the West of Scotland: University Senate.

Urwin, S., Stanley, R., Jones, M., Gallagher, A., Wainwright, P. and Perkins, A. (2010) Understanding Student Nurse Attrition: Learning from the Literature. Nurse Education Today. Vol 30 (2). pp202-207.

Vicsek, L. (2010) Issues in the Analysis of Focus Groups: Generalisability, Quantifiability, treatment of Context and Quotations. The Qualitative Report. Vol 15 (1). pp122-141.

Vygotsky, L. (1978) *Mind in Society: The Development of Higher Psychological Processes*. In Cole, M., John-Steiner, V., Scribner, S., & Souberman, E. (1978). (eds). *L.S. Vygotsky: Mind in Society: The Development of Higher Psychological Processes*. London: Harvard University Press.

Walker, J. and Almond, P. (2010) *Interpreting Statistical Findings. A Guide for Health Professionals and Students*. Berkshire: Open University Press.

Walshaw, M. (2012) *Getting to Grips with Doctoral Research*. London: Palgrave MacMillan.

Watson, H., MacLaren, W. and Kerr, S. (2006) Staff Attitudes Towards Working with Drug Users: Development of the Drug Problems Perceptions Questionnaire. *Addiction*. Vol 102. pp206-215.

Watts, T.E. and Davis, R. (2014) Tensions and Ambiguities: A Qualitative Study of Final Year Adult Field Nursing Students' Experiences of Caring for People Affected by Advanced Dementia in Wales, UK. *Nurse Education Today*. Vol 34. pp1149-1154.

Whitworth, A., iCalvo, M.T., Moss, B., Kifle, N.A. and Blasternes, T. (2015) Mapping the Landscape of the Academic Library. *Qualitative and Quantitative Methods in Libraries*. Vol 4. pp843-853.

Wood, J.H, Alushi, L. and Hammond, J.A. (2017) Communication and Respect for People with Dementia: Student Learning – A Novel Practical Experience of Undergraduate Students Interacting with People with Dementia in Care Homes (Innovative Practice). *Dementia*. Vol 16 (2). pp243-248.

World Health Organisation (2009) *Global Standards for the Initial Education of Professional Nurses and Midwives*. Geneva: WHO.

World Health Organisation (2012) Dementia: A Public Health Priority. UK: World Health Organisation.

World Health Organisation (2013) WHO Methods and Data Sources for Global Burden of Disease Estimates 2000-2011. Geneva: World Health Organisation.

World Health Organisation (2014) Global Health Estimates for 2000-2012. [Online] Available URL: http://www.who.int/healthinfo/global_burden_disease/estimates/en/index2.html

World Health Organisation (2015) World Health Statistics 2015. Luxembourg: World Health Organisation.

Yazan, B. (2015) Three Approaches to Case Study Methods in Education: Yin, Merriam, and Stake. The Qualitative Report. Vol 20 (2). pp134-152.

Yin, R.K. (2018) Case Study Research and Applications. Design and Methods. 6th Edn. London: Sage Publications.

Yu-Tzu, W., Hsin-yi, L., Norton, S., Chen, C., Chen, H., Chenglin, H., Fleming, J., Matthews, F.E. and Brayne, C. (2013) Prevalence Studies of Dementia in Mainland China, Hong Kong and Taiwan: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. PLoS One 8 (6):e66252.

Zimmerman, B.J. (2000) Self efficacy: An Essential Motive to Learn. Contemporary Educational Psychology. Vol 25 (1). pp82-91.

Appendix 1

Modules

Independent Study

Research Evidence in Practice

Fitness for Practice

Holistic Skills

Applied Skills/Skills in Mental Health Nursing

Responding to Ill Health

Nursing for Recovery

Care of Vulnerable People

Fundamental Skills

Foundations of Life and Social Science

Foundations of Health

Introduction to Nursing

Dementia Care in Pre-Registration Nursing at UWS

Dementia Enhanced Practice Level – Year 3

- Safe, values based person centred care
- Holistic assessment with dementia specific tools and approaches
- Addressing complex and changing physical health care needs
- Medication concordance
- Psychosocial interventions; life story work, cognitive stimulation
- Theoretical models, frameworks and perspectives on care delivery
- Strengths based planning for current and future needs
- Advance planning, advance directives and care at end of life
- Critical understanding of policy and research developments

Dementia Skilled Practice Level – Year 2

- Lifespan approach examining social, emotional, physical and spiritual dimensions and how to meet needs
- The persons capacities, interpersonal support and opportunities
- Resilience
- Rights, dignity and compassion
- Recognising and challenging abuse and neglect
- Developing an understanding of the experience of dementia for the person and their supporters

Dementia Informed Practice Level – Year 1

- Communication skills and strategies
- Values based, person centred support and care
- Responding to stress and distress
- Impact of pathophysiology, medication, environment and caregivers
- Protective legislation, policy and protocols
- Social inclusion and the effects of stigma
- Spirituality, wellbeing and quality of life
- Relationships, partnership and kinship
- Citizenship and a rights based approach
- Maintaining health and promoting recovery

Appendix 2

Inclusion Criteria

- Student nurse enrolled on the 3 year undergraduate BSc Adult/Mental Health Nursing programme within the University of the West of Scotland
- Base campus Ayr, Paisley or Dumfries

Exclusion Criteria

- Student nurse based at Hamilton campus as chief investigator teaches at Hamilton campus

Appendix 3

Ref: AS/ESB

17th July, 2014

School of Health, Nursing and Midwifery
Hamilton Campus
Caird Building
HAMILTON
ML9 0QA

Hazel McWhinnie

Personal details withheld.

Dear Hazel

Outcome of School of Health Nursing and Midwifery Ethics Committee

Thank you for your recent submission to the above Committee.

I can confirm your submission was reviewed by the Committee, where the outcome has been:

- **APPROVED**

This outcome requires no further action.

Feedback from the Committee is attached for your information.

On behalf of the School Ethics Committee, I take this opportunity to wish you well with your study.

Yours sincerely

Personal details withheld.

Professor Austyn Snowden
Chair
School of Health Nursing & Midwifery Ethics Committee

cc Glenn Marland

Faculty of Education, Health & Social Sciences

Dr Jeanne Keay, Vice-Principal (International) and Executive Dean of Faculty of Education, Health & Social Sciences

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Appendix 4

Dear Student,

My name is Hazel McWhinnie and I am a nursing lecturer at the University of the West of Scotland, Hamilton campus.

I am conducting a research study and invite you to be involved. Your participation is entirely voluntary and you are free to withdraw from the study at any time.

If you wish to find out more about the research and are considering opting to take part in the research, please read the attached participant information sheet and it will help you make your decision.

I am happy to answer any questions you may have at this stage or at any time. My contact details are;

Hazel McWhinnie

Lecturer

Room C4.30 Hamilton Campus

Tel: [REDACTED]

Email: [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

Many thanks for reading this letter and I wish you every success in your nursing journey.

Appendix 5

Title of Project: Preconceptions, Perceptions and Preparation for Practice: A Longitudinal Study Exploring Self Efficacy in Undergraduate Student Nurses Caring for Person's with Dementia

Information sheet: Research participant/Student Nurse

I would like you to take part in a research study. To help decide if you should participate in the study, please consider the following information;

If you do take part, you will be kept fully informed during the study and you will be able to let me know if you have any concerns about your experience of the research. You can withdraw from the study at any time, without it having any impact on your role as a student nurse within the University of the West of Scotland. Even if you decide that you no longer wish to take part in the study once the study has started, you do not have to give a reason for your withdrawal.

This information sheet is intended to help you decide if you wish to be involved in this study. I will be available to go through this with you in order to discuss any issues or concerns and explain any aspect that is not clear.

If you decide that you would like to take part in the study, please sign the consent form. You will be given a copy of this to keep.

Who am I?

I am Hazel McWhinnie a nursing lecturer here at UWS, based at Hamilton campus. I am studying for my MPhil/PhD within the University and this is my research study.

What is the purpose of the research?

The research is intended to help me understand your perceptions of dementia care delivery and your role in dementia care delivery.

Why have you been invited to become involved?

You are a new nursing student at the University of the West of Scotland and over the next 3 years of your programme, you will be undertaking classes that will help you gain knowledge and skills in dementia care, as well as participating in practice learning environments to gain clinical experience of caring for people with dementia. I am interested in learning about the experiences that you have.

What information will be gathered if I take part?

The research involves gathering a variety of different information about your perceptions of dementia and your ability to provide care to people with dementia.

The study is called a longitudinal study, which means it takes place over a longer time than most other types of research. If you agree to take part in this study, I will ask you for information at various points throughout your 3 year undergraduate nursing programme (from your 1st week, right up to your point of registration).

Firstly, you will be asked to complete a survey questionnaire which will ask you questions about your experiences of dementia care (if any) and how you feel about dementia.

Thereafter, you will be invited to take part in a focus group discussion to provide more in depth information. The focus group discussion will be digitally recorded and then what has been said will be written down. This will allow me to study the information that has been given and to develop a more careful and detailed understanding of what has been discussed. After the focus group, I will send you a written note of the discussion for you to check for authenticity.

This process will be repeated at the end of year 1, year 2 and year 3 of your programme.

Are there any risks involved?

In the event that you become upset during the focus group, you can withdraw your involvement at any time. This will not affect your role as a student nurse within the University in any way. Regular discussion with myself will explore how you are feeling about your participation in the research and any questions that may arise. Your personal tutor and year lead will also be able to discuss any concerns you have.

Are there any benefits?

It is intended that this study will have a positive impact on nursing practice by helping to understand the student nurse experience of caring for people with dementia. This understanding will help nurse education be responsive to both patient need and student need, enhancing dementia care by preparing students to be skilled, knowledgeable practitioners who are readily prepared for nursing practice.

What if you have concerns about any aspect of the research?

If you have any issues or worries that arise in the course of the research, this can be addressed in the first instance by Hazel McWhinnie (chief investigator). There is also support in the University environment for students involved in the study by the chief investigator who is a registered nurse as well as pastoral support at all times from your personal tutor.

All personal tutors will be aware of the study and can be accessed for support or advice at any point during your undergraduate programme.

Alzheimer Scotland also provides support for anyone at any stages of the dementia/caring journey and contact details can be made available for students if they require additional support or information and have agreed to this course of action.

What will happen to the information collected?

The information will be used to gain understanding of your perceptions of dementia and your experience of caring for people with dementia. All personal information will be kept confidential. The people who take part in this study will not be identified by name on any of the material. All the research information will be kept in a secure, locked environment in the University of the West of Scotland. All recorded information from focus groups will be disposed of on study completion. No information regarding you will be removed from the University or copied.

What will happen to the results of the research?

The project will be presented initially as fulfilment of the requirements for my doctoral study. On completion of the study, further dissemination will include poster presentations and journal articles to publish the study results more widely but again there will be no personally identifiable data of research participants.

Who has given permission for this research?

The School of Health Ethics Committee has examined this proposal and given permission.

What if you need more information?

If you need any further information please contact Hazel McWhinnie,

University of the West of Scotland, Hamilton Campus, Tel: [REDACTED]

Email: [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

Thank you for taking the time to read this information sheet.

Appendix 6

Consent form

Title of Project: Preconceptions, Perceptions and Preparation for Practice: A Longitudinal Study Exploring Self Efficacy in Undergraduate Student Nurses Caring for Person's with Dementia

Name of Chief Investigator: Hazel McWhinnie

Please initial the box

1) I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet dated: 17/05/2014, version one, about the above study. I have been given the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these questions answered to my satisfaction.

2) I understand that I have agreed to my voluntary participation in the research and that I am free to withdraw my involvement from the study at any time. I do not need to give a reason for this

and there will be no consequence to my role as a student nurse at the University of the West of Scotland.

3) I understand that appropriate parts of the data collected for the research may be looked at by responsible individuals from the University of the West of Scotland and I give permission for these individuals to look at this material. The study will not include any personally identifiable data.

4) I agree to the audio and visual digital recording of the focus groups that I am participating in and I understand that I will be given a written transcription of the discussion for verification of its authenticity.

5) I agree to taking part in the study.

Name of participant Date Signature

Name of researcher taking consent Date Signature

One copy of this form will be retained by the research participant and one by the researcher.

Appendix 7

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 8

SECTION B

Below is a series of statements about working with drinkers. Please show how far you agree or disagree with each statement by circling the appropriate figure on each line.

In this section, the term “drinker” is used to refer to a person with alcohol related problems, and the term “client” is used to describe a person with whom you deal. If you are a doctor, please read “patient” in this context.

The term “profession” is used to refer to the main professional or voluntary groups of which you are a part. Please answer questions about your “profession” from your perspective as a G.P., voluntary counsellor, probation officer, care assistant or whatever.

		Strongly agree	Quite strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagreed	Disagree	Quite strongly disagree	Strongly disagree
1	I feel I have a working knowledge of alcohol and alcohol related problems	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
2	I feel I know enough about the causes of drinking problems to carry out my role when working with drinkers	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
3	I feel I know enough about the alcohol dependence syndrome to carry out my role when working with drinkers	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
4	I feel I know enough about the psychological effects of alcohol to carry out my role when working with drinkers	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
5	I feel I know enough about the factors which put people at risk of developing drinking problems to carry out my role when working with drinkers	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
6	I feel I know how to counsel drinkers over the long term	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
7	I feel I can appropriately advise my clients about drinking and its effects	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8	I feel I have a clear idea of my responsibilities in helping drinkers	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
9	I feel I have the right to ask clients questions about their drinking when necessary	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

10	I feel that my clients believe I have the right to ask them questions about drinking when necessary	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
11	I feel I have the right to ask a client for any information that is relevant to their drinking problem	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
12	If I felt the need when working with drinkers I could easily find someone with whom I could discuss any personal difficulties that I might encounter	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
13	If I felt the need when working with drinkers I could easily find someone who would help me clarify my professional responsibilities	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
14	If I felt the need I could easily find someone who would be able to help me formulate the best approach to a drinker	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
15	I am interested in the nature of alcohol-related problems and the responses that can be made to them	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
16	I feel I am able to work with drinkers as well as others	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
17	I want to work with drinkers	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
18	All in all I am inclined to feel I am a failure with drinkers	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
19	I wish I could have more respect for the way I work with drinkers	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
20	I feel that I have something to offer to drinkers	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
21	I feel that the best I personally can offer	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

	drinkers is referral to somebody else							
22	I feel I do not have much to be proud of when working with drinkers	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
23	I feel that there is little I can do to help drinkers	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
24	I often feel uncomfortable when working with drinkers	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
25	Pessimism is the most realistic attitude to take toward drinkers	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
26	I feel I have a number of good qualities for work with drinkers	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
27	A times I feel I am no good at all with drinkers	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
28	In general, one can get satisfaction from working with drinkers	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
29	In general, it is rewarding to work with drinkers	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
30	In general, I feel I can understand drinkers	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
31	In general, I like drinkers	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
32	On the whole, I am satisfied with the way I work with drinkers	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
33	On the whole, I am satisfied with myself	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
34	At times, I think I am no good at all	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
35	I feel I have a number of good qualities	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
36	I am able to do things as well as most other people	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
37	I feel I do not have much to be proud of	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
38	I certainly feel useless at times	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

39	I feel that I am a person of worth at least on an equal plane with others	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
40	I wish I could have more respect for myself	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
41	All in all I am inclined to feel that I am a failure	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Appendix 9

Dementia and Dementia Care Perceptions Questionnaire (DDCPQ)

This questionnaire has been devised to assess how education and training changes people's perception of dementia and dementia related problems. The questionnaire is designed to tell us what people know about dementia and dementia related problems, and what their opinions are about certain issues.

There are no correct answers to the questions and it is important that you try to answer as closely as possible to how you feel even although it is unlikely that you will be able to answer all the questions confidently. Even so it is important that you attempt every question.

Thank you for your kind co-operation.

SECTION A

Please tick the relevant box or answer when prompted

Campus Location Paisley Ayr Dumfries

1. Sex:

(a) Male

(b) Female

2. Age:

(a) Under 25

(d) 41 - 50

(b) 26 - 30

(e) 51 - 60

(c) 31 – 40

(f) 61 and over

3. If you are a member of any professional or voluntary group that brings you into contact with clients who have dementia

(Please specify group)

.....

4. How many years have you been part of a professional or voluntary group?

(a) No membership or < 1 year

(b) 1 - 5 years

(c) 6 - 10 years

(d) More than 10 years

5. Have you received any education in dementia or dementia related problems?

(a) No

(b) Yes, Basic Training (such as a study day)

(c) Yes, Advanced Training (such as dementia champions or a
Higher Education qualification with an older persons focus)

(d) Yes, other

(If (d) applies to you, please specify type of training/education below)

.....

.....

6. Have you received any other educational lectures, seminars, courses, etc. on dementia and dementia related problems?

(a) Yes

(b) No

(If (a) applies to you, please specify below)

.....

.....

7. In total, about how many hours of education on dementia and dementia related problems have you received?

(a) None

- (b) One day or less
- (c) Two to four days
- (d) Five to seven days
- (e) 8 to 14 days
- (f) More than 14 days

8. Have you ever attended any training courses to help you counsel people with dementia or their carers?

- (a) Yes
- (b) No

(If (a) applies to you, please specify course below)

.....

9. With approximately how many people with dementia have you worked?

- (a) None
- (b) 1 – 10
- (c) 11 - 25
- (d) 26 - 50
- (e) 51 – 100
- (f) More than 100

10. Approximately how many people with dementia related problems or their carers have you counselled?

- (a) None
- (b) 1 - 10
- (c) 11 - 25
- (d) 26 - 50
- (e) 51 - 100

(f) More than 100

11. When working with clients with dementia, do you presently receive supervision from a more experienced person?

(a) Yes

(b) No

(If (a) applies to you, please specify your supervisor below)

.....

.....

12. When working with people with dementia have you ever received any on-going supervision from a more experienced person?

a) Yes

(b) No

If (a) applies to you, please specify supervisor below)

.....

.....

13. Do you presently work for an employer, agency or group which specialises in working with people with dementia?

(a) Yes

(b) No

(If yes, (a) applies to you, which employer, agency or group?)

.....

.....

14. Have you ever worked for an employer, agency or group which specialises in working with people with dementia?

(a) Yes

(b) No

(If yes, (a) applies to you, which employer, agency or group?)

.....

Section B – Self-Efficacy

These statements are to help me get an idea of your feelings and experiences regarding dementia and dementia care. Please read the numbered statements on the left and circle your answer. For example in statement 1, if you have worked in a dementia care environment and have an excellent knowledge of dementia, you might strongly agree with the statement and circle number 1.

		Strongly agree	Quite strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagreed	Disagree	Quite strongly disagree	Strongly disagree
1	I feel I have a working knowledge of dementia and dementia related problems	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
2	I feel I know enough about the problems of dementia to carry out my role when caring for those with dementia	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
3	I feel I know enough about the clinical manifestations of dementia to carry out my role when working with those with dementia	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
4	I feel I know enough about the psychological effects of dementia to carry out my role when working with those with dementia	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
5	I feel I know enough about the factors which put people at risk of developing dementia to carry out my role when working with those with dementia	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
6	I feel I know how to counsel people diagnosed with dementia	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
7	I feel I can appropriately advise my clients about dementia and its effects	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

8	I feel I have a clear idea of my responsibilities in helping those with dementia	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
9	I feel I have the right to ask clients questions about their experience of dementia when necessary	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
10	I feel that my clients believe I have the right to ask them questions about their experience of dementia when necessary	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
11	I feel I have the right to ask a client for any information that is relevant to their diagnosis of dementia	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
12	If I felt the need when working with people with dementia I could easily find someone with whom I could discuss any personal difficulties that I might encounter	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
13	If I felt the need when working with people with dementia I could easily find someone who would help me clarify my professional responsibilities	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
14	If I felt the need I could easily find someone who would be able to help me formulate the best approach to caring for someone with dementia	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
15	I am interested in the nature of dementia problems and the responses that can be made to help	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
16	I feel I am able to work with those with dementia as well as others	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

17	I want to work with clients who have dementia	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
18	All in all I am inclined to feel I am a failure with clients who have dementia	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
19	I wish I could have more respect for the way I work with clients who have dementia	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
20	I feel that I have something to offer those with dementia	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
21	I feel that the best I personally can offer those with dementia is referral to somebody else	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
22	I feel I do not have much to be proud of when working with clients with dementia	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
23	I feel that there is little I can do to help those with dementia	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
24	I often feel uncomfortable when working with those with dementia	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
25	Pessimism is the most realistic attitude to take toward dementia	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
26	I feel I have a number of good qualities for work with people with dementia	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
27	At times I feel I am no good at all with clients with dementia	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
28	In general, one can get satisfaction from working with those with dementia	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

29	In general, it is rewarding to work with people with dementia	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
30	In general, I feel I can understand people with dementia	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
31	In general, I like clients with dementia	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
32	On the whole, I am satisfied with the way I work with those with dementia	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
33	On the whole, I am satisfied with myself	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
34	At times, I think I am no good at all	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
35	I feel I have a number of good qualities	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
36	I am able to do things as well as most other people	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
37	I feel I do not have much to be proud of	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
38	I certainly feel useless at times	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
39	I feel that I am a person of worth at least on an equal plane with others	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
40	I wish I could have more respect for myself	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
41	All in all I am inclined to feel that I am a failure	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Are you interested in participating further in this research?

If not, thank you kindly for your participation so far.

If you would like to be further involved, the next stage is a focus group discussion to provide more in depth information on the points on this questionnaire.

This will allow me to study the information that has been given and to develop a more careful and detailed understanding of what has been discussed. This process will be repeated at various points throughout your training. All information regarding the focus groups is on the participant information sheet for your perusal to allow you to make an informed choice about your involvement.

If you wish to be involved in the focus groups, please either leave your contact details below or email me at [REDACTED] stating your name, campus and Banner number and I will contact you.

.....
.....

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 10

Focus group Guide

- Reintroduce researcher and thank participants for involvement
- Advise on aims of study and reintroduce participant information sheet, reinforcing ability to ask questions at any time
- Explain to participants procedure during focus groups, explaining how nominal group technique is carried out
- Gain written consent for participation in focus groups and digital recording (audio/visual via SMOTS)
- Advise participants on freedom to withdraw from study at any time without any consequence to student nurse role and without having to give any reason for withdrawal
- Once participants and researcher comfortable and ready to commence start, commence focus group
- Carry out focus group using nominal group technique, digitally recording throughout
- Following focus group and debriefing as part of nominal group technique, make time to answer any queries or questions from participants
- Thank participants for involvement in study and advise re. sharing of transcriptions for participants to verify for authenticity of proceedings
- Advise participants re. dates/timings of next focus groups

Focus group questions

Focus Group questions centred on the themes of role advocacy, legitimacy and support, starting from present-day and looking to the future;

- What knowledge/skills/experiences/qualities do you already have that will help you care for patients with dementia?
- What do you hope/need to learn/gain to help you care for patients with dementia?
- What challenges will be/have been your way?
- What are the solutions to these challenges and how can you move forward?
- What are your ultimate goals to help deliver excellent care to patients with dementia?

Appendix 11

DATASET ACTIVATE DataSet1.

COMPUTE TC_TSSE=Q16b_WorkWell+Q32b_Satisfied+(8-Q18b_Failure)+(8-Q19b_Respect)+(8-Q22b_Proud)+(8-Q27b_NoGood).

VARIABLE LEVEL TC_TSSE(Scale).

FORMATS TC_TSSE(f8.0).

COMPUTE

TC_SWD=Q24b_Uncomfortable+Q28b_Satisfaction+Q29b_Rewarding+Q30b_Understand+Q31b_Like.

VARIABLE LEVEL TC_SWD(Scale).

FORMATS TC_SWD(f8.0).

COMPUTE

TC_MWD=Q15b_Problems+Q17b_Want+(8-Q21b_Referral)+(8-Q23b_Little)+(8-Q25b_Pessimism).

VARIABLE LEVEL TC_MWD(Scale).

FORMATS TC_MWD(f8.0).

COMPUTE

RS_RA=Q1b_Knowledge+Q2b_Problems+Q3b_Clinical+Q4b_Psychological+Q5b_Risk+Q6b_Counsel+Q7b_Advise.

VARIABLE LEVEL RS_RA(Scale).

FORMATS RS_RA(f8.0).

```
COMPUTE
RS_RL=Q8b_Responsibilities+Q9b_Questions+Q10b_Questions2+Q11b_Information.

VARIABLE LEVEL RS_RL(Scale).

FORMATS RS_RL(f8.0).
```

```
COMPUTE BR_RS=Q12b_Difficulties+Q13b_Responsibility+Q14b_Approach.

VARIABLE LEVEL BR_RS(Scale).

FORMATS BR_RS(f8.0).
```

```
COMPUTE BR_EX=Q10_Hours.

VARIABLE LEVEL BR_EX(Scale).

FORMATS BR_EX(f8.0).
```

```
COMPUTE

BR_SE=Q35b_Qualities+Q36b_Ability+Q39b_Worth+(8-Q34b_NoGood)+(8-Q37b_Pride)+(8-
Q41b_Failure).

VARIABLE LEVEL BR_SE(Scale).

FORMATS BR_SE(f8.0).
```

```
DESCRIPTIVES VARIABLES=TC_TSSE TC_SWD TC_MWD RS_RA RS_RL

/SAVE/STATISTICS=MEAN STDDEV.
```

```
COMPUTE OA_Score=MEAN(ZTC_TSSE,ZTC_SWD,ZTC_MWD,ZRS_RA,ZRS_RL).

EXECUTE.
```